

Cu suportul Programului Erasmus+ al Uniunii Europene

Studii Europene

nr. 5

Chişinău
2015

Studii Europene

nr. 5

Uniunea Europeană și Europa de Est (I)

Chișinău
2015

Această publicație este realizată cu suportul Uniunii Europene în cadrul Programului Erasmus+, acțiunea Jean Monnet 2014-1419 Fostering Information and Communication Capacity in Promoting European Studies.

Publicația de față reflectă numai punctul de vedere al autorilor și Comisia Europeană nu este responsabilă pentru eventuala utilizare a informațiilor pe care le conține.

Textele nu exprimă în mod necesar poziția ECSA-Moldova.

**Fondator:
ECSA-Moldova**

Indexare Gesis-SSOAR

**ISSN 2345-1041
ISSN-L 2345-1041**

Consiliul onorific

Președinte:

Prof. univ. dr. Dusan SIDJANSKI (Geneva, Elveția)

Vicepreședinte:

Prof. univ. dr. Ioan HORGHA (Oradea, România)

Membri:

Prof. univ. dr. Francisco ALDECOA LUZÁRRAGA (Madrid, Spania)

Prof. univ. dr. Carlos Eduardo PACHECO AMARAL (Ponta Delgada, Portugalia)

Prof. univ. dr. hab. Alexandru ARSENI (Chișinău, Moldova)

Prof. Dr. Dr. h. c. Enrique Lorenzo BANÚS IRUSTA (Barcelona, Spania)

Prof. univ. dr. Iordan Gheorghe BĂRBULESCU (București, România)

Prof. univ. dr. Georges CONTOGEOGIS (Atena, Grecia)

Prof. univ. dr. Ioan DERȘIDAN (Oradea, România)

Prof. univ. dr. Gaga GABRICHIDZE (Tbilisi, Georgia)

Prof. univ. dr. Nico GROENENDIJK (Enschede, Olanda)

Prof. univ. dr. hab. Victor JUC (Chișinău, Moldova)

Prof. Dr. Dr. h. c. mult. Wilfried HELLER (Potsdam, Germania)

Prof. univ. dr. Anatolii KRUGLASHOV (Cernăuți, Ucraina)

Prof. univ. dr. Ariane LANDUYT (Siena, Italia)

Prof. univ. dr. Ewa LATOSZEK (Varșovia, Polonia)

Prof. univ. dr. Ani MATEI (București, România)

Prof. univ. dr. hab. Elena PRUS (Chișinău, Moldova)

Prof. univ. dr. Maria Manuela TAVARES RIBEIRO (Coimbra, Portugalia)

Prof. univ. dr. Grigore SILAȘI (Timișoara, România)

Prof. univ. dr. István SÜLI-ZAKAR (Debrecen, Ungaria)

Prof. univ. dr. Mihai ȘLEAHTIȚCHI (Chișinău, Moldova)

Comitetul științific

Președinte:

Prof. univ. dr. Tudorel TOADER (Iași, România)

Vicepreședinte:

Conf. univ. dr. Marta PACHOCKA (Varșovia, Polonia)

Membri:

Conf. univ. dr. Mircea BRIE (Oradea, România)

Conf. univ. dr. Paulo Jorge TAVARES CANELAS DE CASTRO (Macau, China)

Conf. univ. dr. Georgeta CISLARU (Paris, Franța)

Conf. univ. dr. Simion COSTEA (Târgu-Mureș, România)

Lector univ. dr. Dorin DOLGHI (Oradea, România)

Conf. univ. dr. Sedef EYLEMER (Izmir, Turcia)

Conf. univ. dr. Aurelian LAVRIC (Chișinău, Moldova)

Conf. univ. dr. Cristina-Maria MATIUȚĂ (Oradea, România)

Lector univ. Giancarlo NICOLI (Roma, Italia)

Lector univ. dr. Mihaela Narcisa NIEMCZIK-ARAMBAȘA (Potsdam, Germania)

Conf. univ. dr. Danielle OMER (Le Mans, Franța)

Conf. univ. dr. Marco OROFINO (Milano, Italia)

Conf. univ. dr. Saverina PASHO (Tirana, Albania)

Conf. univ. dr. Snezana PETROVA (Skopje, Macedonia)

Lector univ. dr. Vadim PISTRINCIUC (Chișinău, Moldova)

Conf. univ. dr. Galina POGONEȚ (Chișinău, Moldova)

Lector univ. dr. István József POLGÁR (Oradea, România)

Lector univ. dr. Ada-Iuliana POPESCU (Iași, România)

Conf. univ. dr. Lehte ROOTS (Tallinn, Estonia)

Lector univ. dr. Alina STOICA (Oradea, România)

Conf. univ. dr. Aleksandra SZCZERBA-ZAWADA (Varșovia, Polonia)

Conf. univ. dr. hab. Zorina ȘIȘCAN (Chișinău, Moldova)

Lector univ. dr. Beatrice ȘTEFĂNESCU (Iași, România)

Conf. univ. dr. Alexis VAHLAS (Strasbourg, Franța)

Conf. univ. dr. Diego VARELA PEDREIRA (A Coruña, Spania)

Lector superior dr. Khaydarali YUNUSOV (Tașkent, Uzbekistan)

Colegiul redacțional

Editor:

Conf. univ. dr. Vasile CUCERESCU (Chișinău, Moldova)

Redactor-șef:

Conf. univ. dr. Carolina DODU-SAVCA (Chișinău, Moldova)

Redactor-șef adjunct:

Conf. univ. dr. Mihai HACHI (Chișinău, Moldova)

Membri:

Conf. univ. dr. Ion BURUIANĂ (Chișinău, Moldova)

Conf. univ. dr. Violeta MELNIC (Chișinău, Moldova)

Prof. univ. dr. hab. Ludmila ROȘCA (Chișinău, Moldova)

Conf. univ. dr. Alexandru ZNAGOVAN (Chișinău, Moldova)

Asistență IT:

Ing. Vitalie CORCODEL (Chișinău, Moldova)

Asist. Viorica MUNTEANU (Chișinău, Moldova)

Asist. Ala OLĂRESCU (Chișinău, Moldova)

Cuprins:

Drept:	10
Acordul de asociere între Moldova și Uniunea Europeană: o nouă generație de acorduri?	11
Victoria BERCU, Vasile CUCERESCU	
Aplicarea principiilor UNIDROIT de instanțele naționale și arbitrajul internațional	31
Irina BURUIANĂ	
Consacrarea constituțională și juridică a reglementărilor privind protecția mediului în Europa și utilizarea resurselor naturale	40
Natalia MINKO	
Fundamente juridice pentru Georgia – armonizarea europeană de la acordul de parteneriat și cooperare la acordul de asociere	50
Giorgi GETSADZE	
Cooperarea la frontiera externă a Uniunii Europene prin intermediul contractelor de muncă internaționale	70
Ion BURUIANĂ	
Economie:	80
Creșterea economică inteligentă a Uniunii Europene: realizări, provocări și perspective	81
Rodica CRUDU	
Dezvoltarea durabilă și sărăcia la periferiile Ungariei	102
István SÜLI-ZAKAR	
Dezvoltarea economică a statelor membre ale Uniunii Europene și perspectiva europeană a Republicii Moldova	117
Mihai HACHI, Corina CIUMAC	
Noi surse de resurse proprii ale Uniunii Europene	140
Agnieszka KŁOS	
Istorie politică:	161
Guvernarea de coaliție: posibilități de aplicare eficientă a resurselor puterii politice	162
Ludmila ROȘCA	
Rolul diasporelor privind căile de integrare: cazurile Armeniei și Moldovei	178
Tigran YEPREMYAN, Andrei ENACHI	
„Român și bulgar” – comunicare și stereotipuri despre integrarea	

europeană	203
Gabriela GOUDENHOOF	
Teoria integrării diferențiate în practică – de la Balcanii de Vest la Parteneriatul Estic	218
Mircea BRIE, Daniela BLAGA	
Interculturalitate:	238
Crearea unui spațiu intercultural autentic – o oportunitate pentru Republica Moldova	239
Tamara CRISTEI	
La République de Moldova entre passé et l'Union européenne. Confluences des valeurs	256
Carolina DODU-SAVCA	
Le Cosmopolitisme européen de Rousseau	276
Snezana PETROVA	
Who's Who	286

Contents:

Law:	10
Association Agreement between Moldova and the European Union: a New Generation of Agreements?	11
Victoria BERCU, Vasile CUCERESCU	
Application of UNIDROIT Principles by National Courts and International Arbitration	31
Irina BURUIANĂ	
Constitutional and Legal Fixing of Regulations on Environmental Protection in Europe and the Use of Natural Resources	40
Natalia MINKO	
Legal Grounds for Georgia – EU Approximation from Partnership and Cooperation Agreement to Association Agreement	50
Giorgi GETSADZE	
EU External Border Cooperation through International Work Contracts	70
Ion BURUIANĂ	
Economics:	80
EU Smart Growth: Achievements, Challenges and Perspectives	81
Rodica CRUDU	
Sustainable Development and Poverty in the Peripheries of Hungary	102
István SÜLI-ZAKAR	
Economic Development of EU Member States and European Perspective of the Republic of Moldova	117
Mihai HACHI, Corina CIUMAC	
New Sources of Own Resources of the European Union	140
Agnieszka KŁOS	
Political History:	161
Coalition Governance: Possibilities of Efficient Application of Political Power Resources	162
Ludmila ROȘCA	
Diasporas' Role in the Integration Paths: the Cases of Armenia and Moldova	178
Tigran YEPREMYAN, Andrei ENACHI	
“Romanian and Bulgarian” – Communication and Stereotypes about European Integration	203
Gabriela GOUDENHOOF	

Theory of Differentiated Integration in Practice – from the Western Balkans to the Eastern Partnership	218
Mircea BRIE, Daniela BLAGA	
Interculturality:	238
Creation of an Authentic Intercultural Area – an Opportunity for the Republic of Moldova	239
Tamara CRISTEI	
The Republic of Moldova between the Past and the European Union. Confluences of Values	256
Carolina DODU-SAVCA	
Rousseau’s European Cosmopolitanism	276
Snezana PETROVA	
Who’s Who	286

DREPT / LAW

Acordul de asociere între Moldova și Uniunea Europeană: o nouă generație de acorduri?

Drd. Victoria BERCU

dragomirvica@mail.ru

Colegiul Pedagogic „Alexei Mateevici” din Chișinău, Moldova

Conf. univ. dr. Vasile CUCERESCU

vasile.cucerescu@studii.eu.org

ECSA-Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: The Association Agreements between the European Union and the countries of the Eastern Partnership constitute a new type of agreements in comparison with the ones applied to current Member States for pre-accession. The European Union signed Association Agreements with three Eastern Partnership countries: Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. The article focuses on the Association Agreement between Moldova and the European Union, analyzing it together with other complementary acts in the process of initiation, initialing, signing and implementation of the agreement.

Key-words: European Union, Moldova, Association Agreement, Action Plan, Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement, Eastern Partnership, European Neighbourhood Policy, National Programme.

Introducere. Statele din Parteneriatul Estic sunt privilegiate în comparație cu celelalte țări care fac parte din Politica Europeană pentru Vecinătate în dezvoltarea relațiilor de parteneriat cu Uniunea Europeană. Mai exact, este vorba de trei state: Georgia, Moldova și Ucraina. Cadrul juridic favorabil ține de încheierea acordurilor de asociere între acestea și Uniunea Europeană, deși cu viteze diferite, individualizate fiecărui stat partener în parte. Moldova se află la etapa cea mai avansată în ceea ce privește implementarea Acordului de Asociere, cu toate că există o multitudine de factori care determină ritmul de realizare.

Ceea ce trebuie de menționat din start e că noile acorduri de asociere destinate statelor din Parteneriatul Estic diferă considerabil de cele anterioare care s-au aplicat statelor membre actuale la etapa de pre-aderare la Uniunea Europeană. Noile acorduri de asociere sunt mult mai elaborate și comprehensive, dar și mai solicitante pentru parteneri. În cele ce urmează, se face o analiză a Acordului de Asociere, care se referă la Moldova, inclusiv

celelalte acte premergătoare și complementare inițierii, parafării, semnării și implementării acestuia până în momentul de față.

O nouă generație de acorduri. Republica Moldova a semnat Acordul de Asociere cu Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora pe 27 iunie 2014, iar la 02 iulie 2014 a fost ratificat de Parlamentul Republicii Moldovei¹. Documentul în cauză este de o complexitate copleșitoare, practic neexistând domenii ale activității politice și social-economice la care să nu se refere. Aceasta înseamnă că Republica Moldova va trebui să-și modernizeze toate sferele vieții politice și social-economice, apropiindu-se de standardele Uniunii Europene în următorii ani. În acest proces, Republica Moldova va fi asistată de către Uniunea Europeană, inclusiv prin intermediul instrumentelor politice, tehnice și financiare.

Angajamentul dat va necesita un efort conjugat, devotament și dedicație, atât din partea clasei politice, cât și din partea cetățenilor Republicii Moldova. Anume necesitatea acestui efort a fost invocată de Președintele Comisiei Europene, Jose Manuel Barroso, care a vizitat Republica Moldova în ajunul semnării Acordului de Asociere, îndemnând clasa politică și cetățenii Republicii Moldova la coeziune națională în procesul de integrare europeană. Îndemnul respectiv nu poate avea însă rezonanță într-o societate divizată, mai cu seamă confruntarea directă a argumentelor dintre părțile angajate în promovarea proiectului de integrare europeană și a celui de alternativă – eurasiatic – a cedat terenul în favoarea circulației unor mituri legate de asocierea Republicii Moldova la Uniunea Europeană.

Relațiile Republicii Moldova cu Uniunea Europeană au deja o istorie etapizată cu o durată de peste 20 de ani. Etapele sunt caracterizate de nivelul de profunzime și complexitate al relațiilor bilaterale, fiind reflectate în acorduri și documente semnate. Primul document juridic complex a fost Acordul de Parteneriat și Cooperare (APC) dintre Comunitățile Europene și statele membre, pe de o parte, și Republica Moldova, pe de altă parte, încheiat la 28 noiembrie 1994, și ratificat de către Parlament un an mai

¹ Cf. *Acord de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte*

târziu, prin Hotărârea nr. 627-XIII din 03 noiembrie 1995, intrat în vigoare la 01 iulie 1998, pentru o perioadă de 10 ani cu posibilitatea prelungirii tacite¹.

La momentul semnării APC, contextul politic regional era marcat de semnarea Cartei de la Paris pentru o nouă Europă și de documentul „Sfidările schimbării” al Conferinței pentru Securitate și Cooperare în Europa (CSCE) de la Helsinki (1992). Documente de mare importanță, acestea aveau la bază o nouă doctrină politică, dedicată destinderii de după terminarea războiului rece. „Noua gândire politică” era orientată spre afirmarea supremației valorilor general-umane, spre o conviețuire pașnică a popoarelor și a cooperării între state, spre afirmarea transparenței, pluralismului și democrației.

Următorul document complex, semnat de Republica Moldova cu Uniunea Europeană, a fost Planul de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova, semnat pe 22 februarie 2005 în cadrul Politicii Europene de Vecinătate (PEV)². Lansarea Politicii Europene de Vecinătate, în 2004, de către Uniunea Europeană, a însemnat adaptarea relațiilor bilaterale dintre Uniunea Europeană și vecinii săi la o realitate nouă, marcată de extinderea Uniunii Europene în 2004, precum și de așteptarea extinderii în 2007 spre Estul și Sud-Estul Europei. Extinderea Uniunii Europene a necesitat stabilirea unor relații noi cu vecinii săi. În acest scop Uniunea Europeană a elaborat planuri de acțiuni tipizate pe care le-a negociat cu noii vecini. Așa a ajuns Republica Moldova să semneze Planul de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova, care a avut menirea să aducă valoarea adăugată APC-ului, precizând obiectivele acestuia și oferind un instrument nou, necesar pentru atingerea lor, inclusiv instrument financiar, pus la dispoziție de Uniunea Europeană.

Politica de integrare europeană a Republicii Moldova, după semnarea Planului de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova, s-a bazat pe doi piloni principali:

- realizarea prevederilor Planului de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova în perioada 2005-2008;
- valorificarea posibilităților ce derivau din participarea Republicii Moldova la inițiativele regionale din Europa de Sud-Est – Pactul de

¹ Cf. www.gov.md/europa/

² Cf. *Planul de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova*

Stabilitate, Procesul de Cooperare în Europa de Sud-Est și viitorul acord modificat privind comerțul liber cu Europa Centrală¹.

Aderarea Republicii Moldova în acest proces regional, remodelat de extinderea Uniunii Europene, a determinat desfășurarea unui șir de evenimente interne foarte importante, care reieșeau din Decretul prezidențial nr. 957, semnat încă pe data de 13 noiembrie 2002, cu privire la constituirea Comisiei Naționale pentru Integrare Europeană (CNIF). Decretul prevedea că o Comisie va elabora și prezenta Parlamentului Strategia de integrare europeană a Republicii Moldova și a Planului de Acțiuni pentru realizarea acestei Strategii și implementare a acesteia.

Abordarea respectivă a avut un impact pozitiv în atingerea unui consens politic național, care pe 24 martie 2005 s-a manifestat prin votarea unanimă a Declarației Parlamentului Republicii Moldova privind parteneriatul politic pentru realizarea obiectivelor integrării europene care prevedea „promovarea consecventă și ireversibilă a cursului strategic spre integrarea europeană”². În consecință, Parlamentul Republicii Moldova a adoptat un șir de acte legislative importante pentru consolidarea democrației și a statului de drept.

Pe 04 mai 2006 Republica Moldova a fost acceptată în calitate de membru cu drepturi depline în cadrul Procesului de Cooperare în Europa de Sud-Est, ceea ce a confirmat prin aceasta apartenența Republicii Moldova la spațiul sud-est european, atât în viziunea autorităților Republicii Moldova, cât și în viziunea Uniunii Europene.

În iunie 2008 a expirat termenul de zece ani prevăzut pentru APC, existând necesitatea substituirii acestui acord cu altul. Pentru Uniunea Europeană, această problemă era comună tuturor statelor ex-sovietice, care au semnat acorduri de parteneriat și cooperare. Astfel au fost propuse partenerilor din Europa de Est de către Uniunea Europeană o nouă generație de acorduri. În acest context, pe 12 ianuarie 2010, Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană s-au angajat în negocierea unui document ambițios, Acordul de Asociere, care să înlocuiască APC. În paralel a fost negociat și definitivat Planul de Acțiuni Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană privind liberalizarea regimului de vize, fiind prezentat Republicii

¹ I. Boțan, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, p. 21

² www.old.parlament.md/news/25.03.2005

Moldova la 24 ianuarie 2011¹, care conținea patru blocuri importante: securitatea documentelor; migrația ilegală; ordinea publică și securitatea; relațiile externe și drepturile fundamentale.

Dialogul Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană privind liberalizarea regimului de vize a fost lansat la 15 iunie 2010. În acest context, a fost creat Grupul de lucru privind coordonarea procesului de liberalizare a regimului de vize cu Uniunea Europeană și aprobat Programul național de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni privind liberalizarea regimului de vize (martie 2011) și Măsurile Adiționale ale Programului național de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni privind liberalizarea regimului de vize (februarie 2012)².

Dialogul Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană privind liberalizarea regimului de vize este structurat conform celor 4 blocuri în două etape: prima – viza consolidarea cadrului juridic, iar a doua – implementarea activităților formulate în Plan. La 23 mai 2011, Republica Moldova a prezentat Comisiei Europene primul Raport de Progres privind implementarea Planului de Acțiuni Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în domeniul liberalizării regimului de vize, care cuprinde măsurile realizate din momentul înmânării oficiale a Planului de Acțiuni la 24 ianuarie 2011, urmând cu strictețe structura și logica acestuia. Raportul se axează preponderent pe implementarea acțiunilor ce țin de realizarea primei etape de consolidare a cadrului legislativ în conformitate cu cele 4 blocuri tematice ale Dialogului Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană privind liberalizarea regimului de vize. Aici erau descrise un șir de măsuri deja întreprinse ce se referă la cea de-a doua etapă de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni.

La 14 noiembrie 2011, Republica Moldova a prezentat cel de-al doilea Raport de Progres privind implementarea Planului de Acțiuni Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în domeniul liberalizării regimului de vize. Totodată, Republica Moldova a salutat noua viziune a Uniunii Europene privind liberalizarea regimului de vize reflectată în cadrul Declarației finale a Summit-ului Parteneriatului Estic prin excluderea sintagmei de „perspectivă pe termen lung” în favoarea abordării diferențiate

¹ *Programul Național de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni în domeniul liberalizării regimului de vize*

² <http://www.polonia.mfa.md/relatiile-moldova-ue/>

a fiecărui partener estic în funcție de performanțele individuale „în timp potrivit”. În rezultatul acțiunilor întreprinse în cadrul fazei I, Republica Moldova a elaborat, modificat, ajustat și aprobat 42 acte legislative și normative în conformitate cu standardele și legislația Uniunii Europene.

Luând în considerație Decizia Consiliului Uniunii Europene din 19 noiembrie 2012 de a iniția procesul de evaluare a implementării condițiilor celei de-a II-a faze, Republica Moldova a prezentat Comisiei Europene primul raport privind realizarea condițiilor celei de-a II-a faze a PALV la 13 decembrie 2012. Ulterior, la 28 ianuarie 2013, la Bruxelles are loc reuniunea Înaltilor Oficiali Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană privind liberalizarea regimului de vize, în cadrul căreia au fost trecute în revistă ultimele evoluții ale dialogului Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană și menționate principalele recomandări ale celui de-al III-lea Raport al Comisiei Europene cu referire la implementarea Planului de Acțiuni.

În perioada 18 februarie – 15 martie 2013 a urmat evaluarea implementării fazei a II-a a Planului de Acțiuni, la care au participat experții din partea instituțiilor Uniunii Europene și a statelor membre. În cadrul acesteia au fost evaluate trei blocuri tematice, fiind apreciate pozitiv. La 25 iunie 2013 a fost publicat cel de-al patrulea Raport privind progresele realizate pentru punerea în aplicare de către Republica Moldova a planului de Acțiuni privind liberalizarea vizelor în care se stipula că Republica Moldova a atins progrese foarte bune privind implementarea eficientă și durabilă a valorilor de referință prevăzută pentru a II-a fază.

În rezultat, la 27 noiembrie 2013, Comisia Europeană a propus liberalizarea regimului de vize pentru cetățenii Republicii Moldova prin modificarea Regulamentului 539/2001 privind liberalizarea regimului de vize pentru călătoriile de scurtă durată în spațiul Schengen pentru cetățenii Republicii Moldova, posesori ai pașaportului biometric.

La 14 martie 2014 în cadrul Ședinței Consiliului Uniunii Europene, reunite în formatul miniștrilor pentru transport, statele membre au susținut propunerea Comisiei Europene de anulare a vizelor pentru călătoriile de scurtă durată (pentru o perioadă de ședere de până la 90 zile pe parcursul a 6 luni) în spațiul Schengen pentru cetățenii Republicii Moldova posesori ai pașaportului biometric. Președintele Parlamentului European, Martin Schulz, și reprezentantul Președinției Consiliului Uniunii Europene, ministrul adjunct de externe al Greciei, Dimitris Kourkoulas, au semnat la 03 aprilie

2014 modificarea Regulamentului 539/2001¹ pentru a permite transferul Republicii Moldova în lista țărilor terțe ai căror resortisanți sunt exonerati de obligativitatea vizei.

Această decizie a intrat în vigoare la 28 aprilie 2014, după publicarea ei în Jurnalul Oficial al Uniunii Europene la 08 aprilie 2014.

O parte a viitorului Acord de Asociere se referea la stabilizarea unei Zone de Liber Schimb Aprofundat și Cuprinzător, care urma să intre în vigoare conform formulării „atunci când vor fi întrunite condițiile relevante”. În ceea ce privește pregătirea Republicii Moldova pentru începerea negocierilor asupra ZLSAC, Uniunea Europeană a remis executivului moldovean un set de recomandări, transpuse în Hotărârea de Guvern nr. 1125 din 14 decembrie 2010 cu privire la aprobarea Planului de Acțiuni al Republicii Moldova privind implementarea recomandărilor Uniunii Europene pentru instituirea Zonei de Liber Schimb Aprofundat și Cuprinzător între Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană. Majoritatea recomandărilor Uniunii Europene reprezentau, de fapt, restanțele majore ale Republicii Moldova în implementarea părții economice a PAUERM².

Planul de Acțiuni privind implementarea Recomandărilor Uniunii Europene a fost structurat în 13 domenii, ultimele măsuri planificate pentru implementare fiind pentru anul 2015. Astfel, unele măsuri din aceste domenii aveau legătură cu accesul produselor moldovenești pe piețele europene. Prin alte măsuri, Republica Moldova se angaja să creeze o zonă de liber schimb aprofundată și comprehensivă. Aceasta înseamnă că părțile aspiră la o integrare economică care ar depăși domeniul comercial, Uniunea Europeană fiind interesată, prin companiile sale, să întâlnească în Republica Moldova un climat de afaceri clar și prietenos, asistat de o justiție independentă și competentă.

La Summit-ul Uniunii Europene de la Vilnius, desfășurat la 28-29 noiembrie 2013, Republica Moldova a fost invitată să parafeze Acordul de Asociere, semnat pe 27 iunie 2014 și ratificat câteva zile mai târziu, pe 02 iulie 2014³.

¹ www.infoeuropa.md/liberalizarea-regimului-de-vize/

² I. Boțan, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, p. 23

³ Cf. *Legea nr.112 din 02.07.2014 pentru ratificarea Acordului de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte*

Acordul de Asociere din cadrul Parteneriatului Estic prevede crearea unui nou cadru juridic pentru relațiile bilaterale, mult mai avansat decât era prevăzut în acordurile de parteneriat și cooperare. Acordurile cu statele Parteneriatului Estic, din care face parte și Republica Moldova, au un specific aparte ce ține de un context regional. Acestea au fost ghidate într-o perioadă în care euroscepticismul a atins cote însemnate în statele membre ale Uniunii Europene. În plus, Rusia, partener strategic al Uniunii Europene, s-a arătat deranjată de inițiativa Uniunii Europene în spațiul postsovietic, pe care îl consideră drept spațiu de interes exclusiv¹. Astfel, în cadrul lansării Parteneriatului Estic, pe 7 mai 2009, înalți funcționari europeni s-au văzut nevoiți să precizeze că inițiativa europeană nu atentează la interesele Rusiei și își dorește ca în statele Parteneriatului Estic, Uniunea Europeană și Rusia să promoveze o politică a responsabilității comune. Cu toate că aceste acorduri pentru statele Parteneriatului Estic nu pot prevedea drept rezultat final aderarea la Uniunea Europeană (deși nu îl exclud), ele pot contribui substanțial la modernizarea societății din țările respective. Nivelul de integrare economică cu Uniunea Europeană nu poate depăși cea de-a doua treaptă integraționistă – liberul schimb, chiar dacă acesta va fi aprofundat și cuprinzător.

Documentul a stabilit cadrul juridic al relațiilor dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană în domeniile politic, comercial, economic, juridic, cultural-științific și are ca obiectiv susținerea Republicii Moldova pentru:

- consolidarea democrației și a statului de drept și respectarea drepturilor omului și a minorităților naționale prin asigurarea cadrului corespunzător al dialogului politic;
- dezvoltarea durabilă a economiei și finalizarea procesului de tranziție spre o economie de piață, a investițiilor și relațiilor economice armonioase.

Prin Acordul de Asociere, Republica Moldova și-a asumat o serie de angajamente. Acest document conține 465 de articole, care odată puse în aplicare în legislația noastră, va face din Republica Moldova o țară cu un *acquis* comunitar integrat Uniunii Europene.

¹ I. Boțan, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, p. 15

Acordul de Asociere urmărește să contribuie la dezvoltarea politică și social-economică a Republicii Moldova prin cooperare cât mai amplă într-un șir vast de domenii de interes comun, inclusiv în domeniile de bună guvernare, justiție, libertate și securitate, integrare comercială și cooperare economică sporită, politică de încadrare în câmpul muncii și socială, management financiar, administrare publică și reforma serviciului public, participarea societății civile, dezvoltare instituțională, reducerea sărăciei și dezvoltare durabilă.

Prima rundă de negocieri privind Acordul de Asociere între Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană a avut loc la 12 ianuarie 2010, urmând alte 15. Negocierile date s-au finalizat la 15 martie 2013 la Bruxelles.

Rundele de negocieri, în baza cărora este conceput Acordul de Asociere, au luat sfârșit după parafarea lui la 29 noiembrie 2013 în cadrul celui de-al III-lea Summit al Parteneriatului Estic de la Vilnius. Pe document și-au pus semnătura primul-ministru al Republicii Moldova Iurie Leancă, Înalțul Reprezentant al Uniunii Europene pentru Afaceri Externe, Catherine Ashton, și Comisarul European al Comerțului, Karel De Gucht¹.

Scopul principal al Acordului de Asociere este asocierea politică și integrarea economică a Republicii Moldova în baza valorilor comune. Acordul recunoaște aspirațiile europene și alegerea europeană a Republicii Moldova, lăsând deschisă calea pentru viitoarele evoluții progresive în relațiile bilaterale. Acordul nu prevede expres obiectivul final aderarea la Uniunea Europeană, astfel conform articolului 49 din Tratatul privind Uniunea Europeană, Georgia, Moldova și Ucraina au perspective europene și pot cere să devină membre ale Uniunii Europene cu condiția să adere la principiile democrației, să respecte libertățile fundamentale, drepturile omului și drepturile minorităților și să garanteze statul de drept.

La baza Acordului de Asociere au stat următoarele valori comune: democrația, respectarea drepturilor omului și a libertăților fundamentale, supremația legii și economia de piață, valori care au fost puse în 1994 la baza Acordului de Parteneriat și Cooperare, fiind dezvoltate în cadrul Politicii Europene de Vecinătate prin PAUEM, semnat în 2005 și aprofundat în cadrul Parteneriatului Estic, lansat în 2009.

¹ www.infoeuropa.md/privind-acordul-de-asociere-republica-moldova-uniunea-europeana/

La 27 iunie 2014 liderii Uniunii Europene și Primul-ministru al Republicii Moldova Iurie Leancă au semnat la Bruxelles Acordul de Asociere între Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană. La eveniment au fost prezenți șefi de state și de guverne din cele 28 țări membre ale Uniunii Europene, care la fel și-au pus semnătura pe document. Semnarea acestui Acord este calificat drept o zi istorică pentru Republica Moldova, care s-a angajat pe calea reformelor democratice și a cooperării europene, iar liderii europeni și-au manifestat încrederea că dorința noastră pentru a respecta aceste angajamente este ireversibilă.

La 28 iunie 2014 Cabinetul de miniștri al Republicii Moldova a aprobat proiectul de lege pentru ratificarea Acordului de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Uniunea Europeană și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte. În data de 01 iulie 2014, la Bruxelles, Republica Moldova a semnat, concomitent cu statele din Balcanii de Vest (Macedonia, Muntenegru, Serbia, Albania, Bosnia și Herțegovina), Acordul de Asociere la Programul European pentru cercetare și inovare Orizont (H2020). H2020 devine primul program european la care se asociază Republica Moldova. În rezultatul semnării acestui Acord, entitățile fizice și juridice, reprezentând țara noastră obțin drepturi similare cu cele din statele membre ale Uniunii Europene în cadrul apelurilor programului H2020.

La 02 iulie 2014 a avut loc ratificarea Acordului de Asociere de către Parlamentul Republicii Moldova. Conform procedurilor legale, acesta urmează a fi ratificat de către legislativele celor 28 de state membre ale Uniunii Europene. Începând cu 01 septembrie 2014 intră în vigoare prevederile Acordului de Asociere între Uniunea Europeană și Republica Moldova. Aplicarea provizorie survine până la ratificarea de către statele membre ale Uniunii Europene a Acordului de Asociere.

Au urmat diferite acțiuni privind implementarea de mai departe a Acordului de Asociere Uniunea Europeană și Republica Moldova. Astfel la 29 septembrie 2014 urmează semnarea Acordului Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova privind participarea țării noastre la programul pentru Competitivitatea Întreprinderilor și a Întreprinderilor Mici și Mijlocii (COSME).

La 07 octombrie 2014 Guvernul Republicii Moldova a adoptat Hotărârea cu privire la aprobarea Planului de Acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în perioada

2014-2016¹. Conform Planului, Ministerul Afacerilor Externe și Integrării Europene va prezenta Guvernului raportul privind executarea Planului Național de acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană la data de 15 iulie și 15 decembrie a fiecărui an de raportare.

Planul include acțiunile necesare de a fi realizate de către instituțiile responsabile conform fiecărui articol, precum și Anexe ale Acordului de Asociere, în termenele indicate și cu specificarea resurselor financiare necesare. Acesta reprezintă prin sine instrumentul de bază pentru monitorizarea procesului de integrare europeană în următorii trei ani. Planul a fost elaborat în baza propunerilor autorităților publice vizate și a consultărilor publice organizate de către Ministerul Afacerilor Externe și Integrării Europene (în parteneriat cu Fundația Est Europeană) în perioada 16 – 19 iunie 2014 pentru fiecare domeniu separat².

Planul Național de acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în perioada 2014-2016 cuprinde titlurile: principii generale; dialogul politic și reformele, cooperarea în domeniul politicii externe și de securitate; justiție, libertate și securitate; cooperarea economică și alte tipuri de cooperare sectorială (compus din 28 de capitole pe diverse domenii); comerț și aspecte legate de comerț (11 capitole); asistență financiară și dispoziții antifraudă și de control³.

Nu putem trece cu vederea semnarea la 06 noiembrie 2014 a Memorandului de înțelegere privind suportul oferit Republicii Moldova pentru perioada 2014-2017 și a Acordului privind finanțarea Programului de susținere pentru crearea Zonei de Liber Schimb. Iar la 13 decembrie 2014, Parlamentul European în cadrul ședinței plenare a ratificat Acordul de Asociere Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova.

Acordul de Asociere va intra în vigoare după data depunerii tuturor instrumentelor de ratificare. Ratificarea va fi efectuată deopotrivă de Republica Moldova și de cele 28 de state membre ale Uniunii Europene în conformitate cu procedurile naționale. Până la moment, Acordul de

¹ Hotărâre cu privire la aprobarea Planului Național de acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în perioada 2014-2016

² <http://www.mfa.gov.md/implementarea-aa/>

³ Hotărâre cu privire la aprobarea Planului Național de acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în perioada 2014-2016

Asociere a fost ratificat de către 26 de state ale Uniunii Europene: România, Letonia, Estonia, Malta, Lituania, Bulgaria, Slovacia, Ungaria, Suedia, Polonia, Croația, Danemarca, Irlanda, Germania, Olanda, Cehia, Marea Britania, Franța, Portugalia, Slovenia, Finlanda, Belgia, Austria, Cipru, Spania. Au mai rămas să ratifice Acordul de Asociere Grecia și Italia.

Până la încheierea tuturor procedurilor de ratificare și intrare în vigoare a Acordului de Asociere, Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană au convenit să aplice prevederile acestuia cu titlu provizoriu, imediat după primirea de către Depozitar a notificării Uniunii Europene și a Republicii Moldova privind finalizarea procedurilor necesare în acest scop.

În esență, Acordul de Asociere însumează o serie de angajamente pe care Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană și statele membre și le-au asumat cu scopul de a aprofunda și întări legăturile existente. Astfel, pentru a asigura îndeplinirea acestor angajamente, părțile au consemnat prin Acord să stabilească un mecanism instituțional de monitorizare a implementării, dar și de luare a deciziilor asupra aspectelor ce cad sub incidența prevederilor Acordului.

La nivel instituțional, este creat Consiliul de Asociere cu rolul de monitorizare a punerii în aplicare a prevederilor, dar și de revizuire periodică a funcționării anumitor aranjamente. Consiliul este format din reprezentanți ai Consiliului Uniunii Europene, ai Comisiei Europene și ai Guvernului Republicii Moldova. Deciziile se iau de comun acord și sunt obligatorii pentru părți. Consiliul de Asociere se întrunește periodic, dar nu mai rar de o dată pe an la nivel ministerial.

În îndeplinirea funcțiilor sale, Consiliul este asistat de Comitetul de Asociere, care este format din reprezentanți ai părților la nivel de înalți funcționari. Comitetul de Asociere poate adopta decizii obligatorii în virtutea stipulărilor exprese din Acord sau a unei delegări din partea Consiliului de Asociere.

Atât Consiliul cât și Comitetul de Asociere sunt prezidate, alternativ, de un reprezentant al Uniunii Europene sau al Guvernului Republicii Moldova.

De asemenea, Acordul de Asociere stabilește crearea unui Comitet de Asociere Parlamentar care va reuni reprezentanți ai Parlamentului Republicii Moldova și ai Parlamentului European. Acest Comitet are dreptul de a cere informații de la Consiliul de Asociere, de a face recomandări

acestua și de a stabili subcomitete parlamentare. Acordul de Asociere presupune și inițierea unei Platforme a Societății Civile ca un for de discuții între reprezentanții societății civile din Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană.

Titlul II al Acordului de Asociere stipulează că dialogul politic va fi concentrat pe eficiența reformei interne și a cooperării din domeniul politicii externe și de securitate¹. Reforma internă țintește spre asigurarea unei bune guvernări prin: sporirea eficacității instituțiilor democratice și a statului de drept; respectarea drepturilor și libertăților fundamentale ale omului; continuarea reformelor în sistemul judecătoresc, asigurarea independenței sistemului judecătoresc, imparțialității și eficacității organelor de drept; continuarea reformelor în domeniul administrației publice și dezvoltarea unui serviciu public responsabil, eficient, transparent și profesionist; combaterea eficientă a corupției, inclusiv prin sporirea cooperării internaționale.

Justiția, libertatea și securitatea sunt subiectele Titlului III, care prevede că respectarea drepturilor omului și libertățile fundamentale va sta la baza cooperării în domeniile libertății, securității și justiției². Principiul supremației legii urmează să asigure independența sistemului judecătoresc, accesul cetățenilor la justiție și dreptul la un proces judiciar echitabil.

Recunoașterea progreselor obținute în domeniul de referință este că Republica Moldova a obținut regimul liberalizat de vize pentru călătorii și vizite pe termen scurt în 26 de țări ale Uniunii Europene și în spațiul Schengen. Evaluând progresele realizate de Republica Moldova, pe 14 martie 2014, Consiliul Uniunii Europene, reunit în formatul miniștrilor pentru Transport ai statelor membre ale Uniunii Europene, a susținut propunerea Comisiei Europene de anulare a vizelor de scurtă durată în spațiul Schengen pentru cetățenii Republicii Moldova³.

În acest context părțile vor asigura un nivel corespunzător în privința protecției datelor cu caracter personal, prelucrate în cadrul cooperării

¹ *Acord de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte*, p. 48-50

² *Ibidem*, p. 50-51

³ I. Boțan, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, p. 30

polițienești și judiciare în materie penală. Transferul de date între părți va avea loc doar dacă acesta este necesar conform acordurilor încheiate privind prevenirea și combaterea crimei organizate, corupției și a altor activități ilegale; combaterea contrabandei și a traficului cu ființe umane, cu arme și droguri; prevenirea falsificării documentelor; combaterea infracțiunilor cibernetice, spălării banilor, combaterea finanțării terorismului. De asemenea, este importantă cooperarea juridică în materie civilă, penală și comercială.

Unul dintre cele mai ample titluri, Titlul IV, se referă la cooperarea în sectorul economic și alte sectoare și care include 28 de capitole privitoare la diferite domenii: reforma administrației publice, dialogul în domeniul economic, dreptul societăților comerciale, evidența contabilă și auditul și guvernarea corporativă; ocuparea forței de muncă, politica socială și asigurarea oportunităților egale; protecția consumatorilor; statistică, managementul finanțelor publice; impozitarea; politica cu privire la industrie și întreprinderi; sectorul minier și al materiilor prime; agricultura și dezvoltarea rurală; cooperarea în domeniul energetic; transportul; mediul înconjurător și altele¹.

Titlul V² al Acordului de Asociere, cuprinzând 15 capitole, 20 de anexe și două protocoale, este dedicat comerțului și accesului reciproc al mărfurilor pe piețele Republicii Moldova și Uniunii Europene. Acesta stabilește constituirea zonei de comerț liber, adică a Zonei de Liber Schimb Aprofundat și Cuprinzător (ZLSAC), pe parcursul unei perioade de tranziție cu o durată de cel mult zece ani, începând cu data intrării în vigoare a Acordului de Asociere, în conformitate cu Articolul XXIV al Acordului General pentru Tarife și Comerț 1994 (GAAT 1994), care prevede dreptul statelor semnatare de a participa la instituirea zonelor de comerț liber, având în vedere următoarele: prin zona de comerț liber se înțelege un grup din două sau mai multe teritorii vamale, între care taxele vamale sau alte reglementări de comerț restrictive sunt eliminate pentru cea mai mare parte a comerțului cu produse originale din teritoriile constitutive ale zonei de comerț liber; și în cazul unei zone de comerț liber, taxele vamale sau alte

¹ *Acord de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte*, p. 51-62

² *Ibidem*, p. 62-115

reglementări comerciale, menținute în fiecare din teritoriile constitutive și aplicabile în comerțul părților contractante neincluse într-o astfel de zonă sau neparticipante la un astfel de acord, la formarea unei astfel de zone de comerț liber nu vor fi mai mari sau restrictive, decât taxele vamale sau alte reglementări de comerț corespunzătoare care au existat în aceste teritorii înainte de formare a zonei de comerț liber¹.

Zona de liber schimb aprofundat și cuprinzător (DCFTA)² este parte a Acordului de Asociere dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană, care va oferi Republicii Moldova un cadru necesar pentru modernizarea relațiilor comerciale și pentru dezvoltarea sa economică datorită deschiderii piețelor prin excluderea taxelor vamale (taxelor de import și export, după necesitate, pentru comerțul cu bunuri) și a cotelor, și printr-o armonizare cuprinzătoare a legislației, normelor și reglementărilor Republicii Moldova la legislația europeană din diferite sectoare ce țin de comerț. Aceste reforme sunt direcționate spre crearea unor condiții necesare pentru alinierea sectoarelor-cheie ale economiei Republicii Moldova la standardele europene.

Totodată, în cadrul Acordului de Asociere, Republica Moldova va beneficia de asistență financiară prin intermediul mecanismelor și instrumentelor de finanțare relevante ale Uniunii Europene, va putea beneficia de împrumuturi de la Banca Europeană de Investiții, Banca Europeană pentru Reconstrucții și Dezvoltare și alte instituții financiare internaționale. Domeniile prioritare și volumul asistenței financiare vor fi convenite prin programe de acțiuni anuale bazate pe cadre multianuale, care vor reflecta prioritățile de politici convenite. Curtea Europeană de Conturi va avea dreptul să examineze dacă toate cheltuielile legate de utilizarea fondurilor Uniunii Europene au fost efectuate în mod legal, cu respectarea procedurilor, și au fost administrate bine și corect. Comisia Europeană va putea impune măsuri și sancțiuni, iar autoritățile Republicii Moldova vor lua măsuri corespunzătoare în vederea recuperării fondurilor Uniunii Europene plătite în mod necuvenit dacă e cazul.

¹ I. Boțan, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, p. 57-58

² *Zona de liber schimb aprofundat și cuprinzător Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova*, p. 3, www.mfa.gov.md

Astfel Cadrul unic de asistență financiară pentru anii 2014-2017 pentru Republica Moldova de către Uniunea Europeană este destinat pentru a sprijini modernizarea instituțiilor publice cheie, care pun în aplicare Acordul de Asociere și a Zonei de Liber Schimb Aprofundat și Cuprinzător; îmbunătățirea politicilor finanțelor publice și de management, ale competitivității în afaceri și ale celei comerciale din mediul rural; oportunitățile comerțului cu Uniunea Europeană și protecția minorităților și a grupurilor vulnerabile. Programul va contribui la asocierea politică și integrarea economică în Uniunea Europeană.

Cadrul unic de asistență (CUA) al sprijinului Uniunii Europene pentru Republica Moldova, în 2014-2017, a fost adoptat la 11 iunie 2014. Acesta este un document de program care va consemna sprijinul Uniunii Europene pentru țară în următorii patru ani. Cadrul unic de asistență (CUA) a fost consultat cu autoritățile naționale, societatea civilă, instituțiile Uniunii Europene și statele membre. Este un prim pachet de asistență bilaterală acordată Republicii Moldova în conformitate cu Cadrul unic de asistență, care stabilește obiectivele și prioritățile strategice pentru viitoarea cooperare a Uniunii Europene – Republica Moldova în 2014-2017.

Pachetul Uniunii Europene de sprijin anual (Programul anual de acțiune 2014) a oferit suma de 101 milioane € drept alocare bilaterală pentru Republica Moldova. Finanțarea a fost acordată prin intermediul Instrumentului european de vecinătate (IEV) pentru două acțiuni:

1. Sprijin pentru Reformele politice ale Finanțelor Publice din Republica Moldova (37 de milioane €) pentru a ajuta Ministerul Finanțelor, Parlamentul și Instituția Supremă de Audit a Republicii Moldova în procesul de consolidare a bunei guvernări, politica fiscală eficientă, politica transparentă și responsabilă a finanțelor publice și consolidarea sistemelor de management financiar public;

2. Programul european de vecinătate pentru agricultură și dezvoltare rurală (ENPARD) pentru Republica Moldova, sprijin pentru agricultură și dezvoltare rurală (64 milioane €): destinat pentru sporirea dezvoltării rurale prin ameliorarea dialogului politic, guvernării și a serviciilor de livrare a suportului în conformitate cu necesitățile fermierilor privați în scopul creșterii competitivității în sectorul agricol. O parte din a doua acțiune va fi destinată intensificării în continuare a dialogului între autoritățile centrale și regionale.

La 02 mai 2014, Comisia Europeană a aprobat un program de sprijin pentru Republica Moldova în valoare de 30 milioane €, care vizează competitivitatea business-ului mic, dezvoltarea legislației naționale în conformitate cu standardele de calitate ale Uniunii Europene și promovării exporturilor și oportunităților de investiții, comunicare și campanii de informare cu privire la acordul comercial ZLSAC cu Uniunea Europeană. Acest sprijin suplimentar a fost acordat prin noul mecanism al instrumentului european de vecinătate „mai mult pentru mai mult”¹.

La 21-22 mai, la Riga, liderii Uniunii Europene s-au întâlnit cu reprezentanții țărilor din cadrul Parteneriatului Estic cu ocazia celui de-al patrulea summit pentru a reconfirma importanța pe care Uniunea Europeană o acordă acestuia. Participanții la summit au trecut în revistă progresele realizate de la Summit-ul de la Vilnius din 2013 și au trasat o agendă pozitivă pentru viitor²:

- Declarația comună a Summit-ului Parteneriatului Estic (Riga, 21-22 mai 2015);
- Declarația președintelui Donald Tusk la conferința de presă a Summit-ului Parteneriatului Estic de la Riga, 22 mai 2015.

Președintele Donald Tusk la conferința de presă a menționat: „Parteneriatul nostru, precum și summit-ul de la Riga în sine, nu vizează decizii dramatice sau a face pași uriași. Relația noastră are la bază libera voință, respectul și egalitatea. Parteneriatul nostru va avansa pas cu pas, așa cum a fost construită și Uniunea Europeană”³.

Summit-ul a reprezentat prilejul de a demonstra hotărârea Uniunii Europene de a cultiva relații mai strânse și în același timp diferențiate cu partenerii săi. Uniunea Europeană este puternic implicată în relația cu toți cei șase parteneri din Europa de Est și Caucazul de Sud: Armenia, Azerbaidjan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova și Ucraina, indiferent de nivelul lor individual de ambiție în ceea ce privește relațiile cu Uniunea Europeană. Sfera de aplicare și gradul de aprofundare a cooperării sunt determinate de aspirațiile și necesitățile Uniunii Europene și ale țărilor partenere și ritmul reformelor.

¹ <http://www.infoeuropa.md/vb-documente-oficiale/programul-anual-de-actiune-2014-pentru-republica-moldova/>

² <http://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/meetings/international-summit/2015/05/21-22/>

³ *Ibidem*

La Summit-ul de la Riga, liderii Uniunii Europene au reafirmat importanța agendei de reformă în țările din cadrul Parteneriatului Estic, precum și necesitatea de a construi instituții consolidate și mai transparente, neafectate de corupție.

Discuțiile s-au axat pe proiecte de cooperare multilaterală care vizează:

- consolidarea instituțiilor și a bunei guvernante: Uniunea Europeană și-a confirmat angajamentul privind sprijinirea țărilor partenere în direcția consolidării instituțiilor și a rezilienței lor la provocările externe;
- intensificarea mobilității și a contactelor interumane;
- dezvoltarea oportunităților de piață, prin îmbunătățirea mediului de afaceri și a securității juridice în țările partenere din Europa de Est, în beneficiul IMM-urilor și al altor întreprinderi și acordând o atenție specială domeniului economiei digitale;
- asigurarea securității energetice și îmbunătățirea interconexiunilor energetice, precum și a celor de transport.

Soluționarea conflictelor din regiune a fost de asemenea o prioritate pe ordinea de zi a summit-ului. Toți participanții la summit au convenit să continue toate eforturile vizând detensionarea situației și obținerea unei soluții politice pentru criza din Ucraina, precum și rezolvarea pașnică a altor conflicte încă nesoluționate din regiune.

Summit-ul de la Riga a fost însoțit de o serie de evenimente colaterale, menite să demonstreze că Parteneriatul Estic merge dincolo de relațiile interguvernamentale, implicând societatea civilă, mass-media, mediul de afaceri și alte părți interesate. În cadrul Forumului de afaceri al Parteneriatului Estic desfășurat la Riga la 21 mai 2015, Comisia Europeană a lansat facilitatea pentru întreprinderile mici și mijlocii (IMM-uri) aferentă zonei de liber schimb aprofundate și cuprinzătoare.

Facilitatea va oferi granturi în valoare de aproximativ 200 de milioane €, estimându-se că va stimula noi investiții de cel puțin 2 miliarde € pentru IMM-urile din cele trei țări participante în cadrul unei zone de liber schimb aprofundate și cuprinzătoare: Georgia, Moldova și Ucraina.

Acordul de Asociere este unul dintre cele mai importante documente internaționale de până acum pe care l-a semnat Republica Moldova. Miza este foarte mare – modernizarea rapidă a țării. Este vorba de un efort uriaș

pe care trebuie să-l facă societatea moldovenească, politicienii, deopotrivă cu cetățenii.

Concluzii. Acordul de Asociere între Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană face parte din noua generație de acorduri elaborate de Bruxelles pentru statele din Parteneriatul Estic. Prevederile Acordului de Asociere au un caracter sofisticat datorită realităților interne ale statelor partenere cât și conjuncturii geopolitice din regiune. Caracterul comprehensiv se explică prin problemele reale care urmează a fi rezolvate cu eforturi comune pentru a înregistra progrese în domeniile politic, juridic, economic și social. Astfel, Uniunea Europeană promovează dezvoltarea unor relații privilegiate cu vecinii săi în vederea constituirii unui spațiu comun de stabilitate, securitate și bunăstare.

Bibliografie:

1. *Acord de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte, din 27 iunie 2014, [în] Monitorul Oficial nr. 185-199/442 din 27 iunie 2014, p. 46-386*
2. Boțan Igor, *Prevederile Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană*, Ghid, Chișinău: Arc, 2014
3. *Ghidul Acordului de Asociere dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană*, Chișinău, 2014
4. *Hotărâre cu privire la aprobarea Planului Național de acțiuni pentru implementarea Acordului de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană în perioada 2014-2016, nr. 808, din 07.10.2014, [în] Monitorul Oficial nr. 293-296, 3 octombrie 2014*
5. *Legea nr.112 din 02.07.2014 pentru ratificarea Acordului de Asociere între Republica Moldova, pe de o parte, și Comunitatea Europeană a Energiei Atomice și statele membre ale acestora, pe de altă parte, [în] Monitorul Oficial nr. 185-199 din 18.07.2014*
6. *Planul de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova*, Ghid, Chișinău, 2006
7. *Programul Național de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni în domeniul liberalizării regimului de vize*, Hotărârea de Guvern nr. 122/04.03.2011

8. Tornea Ion, *Acordul de Liber schimb aprofundat și cuprinzător dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană*, Ghid informativ pentru producătorii agricoli, Idis Viitorul, www.viitorul.org
9. *Zona de liber schimb aprofundat și cuprinzător Uniunea Europeană – Republica Moldova*, Chișinău, 2014
10. www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/meetings/international-summit/2015/05/21-22/
11. www.gov.md/europa/
12. www.infoeuropa.md/liberalizarea-regimului-de-vize/
13. www.infoeuropa.md/privind-acordul-de-asociere-republica-moldova-uniunea-europeana/
14. www.infoeuropa.md/vb-documente-oficiale/programul-anual-de-actiune-2014-pentru-republica-moldova/
15. www.mfa.gov.md
16. www.mfa.gov.md/implementarea-aa/
17. www.old.parlament.md/news/25.03.2005
18. www.polonia.mfa.md/relatiile-moldova-ue/

Copyright©Victoria BERCU
Copyright©Vasile CUCERESCU

Application of UNIDROIT Principles by National Courts and International Arbitration

LL.M. student Irina BURUIANĂ

buruiana.irina@mail.ru

“Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Abstract: UNIDROIT Principles have a major role in harmonization of international commerce. One of the main purposes is to unify, finding a balance among existing differences regarding legal, social and economic systems of various countries. The principles' wide applicability offers enough reasons to innovate systematically this domain. The UNIDROIT Principles can be used both in connection with an arbitration clause and with a clause providing for jurisdiction of a national court, because the UNIDROIT Principles provide a common ground between different national legal orders, they provide a good reference point for dialogue between lawyers from different jurisdictions. Knowing the UNIDROIT Principles is like speaking an additional language when it comes to cross-cultural legal communication. Over the years, the UNIDROIT Principles have become a practical reality and a part of the international law practice.

Key-words: UNIDROIT principles, international arbitration, application, national courts, uniformity, globalization, rules of law.

Globalization and worldwide trade between market participants from over 200 nations and legal orders have caused international trade and investment to become highly complex. This includes the law as a service discipline to such trade and transactions.

The trend of closed economy, which became dominant after World War II, commenced changing in 1980s. Around fifty states were members of the United Nations in 1950s and by the 1990s this membership had increased to one hundred ninety two¹. Meanwhile, the restrictions on international trade started to loosen. As a result of the fall of the Berlin Wall and the collapse of the Eastern Block, the trade between East and West started to increase in volume. In addition, as a result of the improvement of industry and technology, international relations blossomed and along with

¹ Cf. <http://www.un.org/en/members>

that international trade evolved further. Both developed and developing economies cannot limit themselves any more within their own countries, local products or capital¹.

As a result of this process of trade liberalization, the significance of conflict of laws problems has increased in the resolution of disputes related to international commercial contracts. The expectation of businesses is that the law will, in the event of a dispute, be applied with certainty and predictability. Certainty of law avoids unexpected results and harmonizes dispute resolution outcomes. In order to meet the above expectations, international and professional institutions have conducted studies with the purpose of unifying the substantial law rules for international agreements². For example, along with international conventions such as the United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods³ (CISG), Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road⁴ (CMR), international institutions such as International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) and the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) have prepared model laws and model contracts, e.g. UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration, UNCITRAL Model Law on International Credit Transfers, UNCITRAL Model Law on Cross-Border Insolvency. These conventions and model laws have become an important source of international commercial and private international law. In addition to those instruments, the International Institute for the Unification of Private Law⁵ (UNIDROIT) prepared UNIDROIT Principles of International Commercial Contracts (UNIDROIT Principles).

By their nature, the UNIDROIT Principles are similar to most national laws. The reasons for these similarities are simple. First, the UNIDROIT Principles are the result of intensive comparative legal research and debate. Second, the UNIDROIT Principles have influenced many legislators over the years including, for example, the Chinese legislator and (with respect to some fundamental changes of the German contract law in 2002) the German legislator.

¹ Cf. M. Shapiro, *The Globalization of Law*

² K. P. Berger, *The Creeping Codification of the Lex Mercatoria*, p. 144

³ Cf. *Convention of International Sale of Goods*

⁴ Cf. *UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration*

⁵ Cf. *UNCITRAL Model Law on International Credit Transfers*

This structural similarity becomes evident whenever a practitioner examines it: all lawyers will find many familiar concepts when they study the UNIDROIT Principles. In view of the structural similarities between the UNIDROIT Principles and most national laws, the UNIDROIT Principles are often helpful in overcoming legal barriers in contract negotiations. They are truly neutral and give no advantage to either party. Their choice avoids often costly research of a State law which could be chosen as a neutral law.

Sometimes, the parties agree on the UNIDROIT Principles in their entirety and choose them to possible extent instead of national law. In this case the UNIDROIT Principles become, *de facto*, the *lex contractus* for all issues covered by the Principles. In addition, any mandatory law applicable under the circumstances and the law applicable to other issues not covered by the Principles, such as company law, would apply.

The purpose of UNIDROIT Principles is to provide a set of rules which can be applied to all types of international commercial contracts. These rules are intended to create an equal and fair situation for both parties and are suitable for the needs and fast progress of international commercial relations¹. The UNIDROIT Principles were prepared by a study group consisting of lawyers, judges and other officers who are experts in the fields of contract and international commercial law, and who represent different systems of law and socio-economy.

The UNIDROIT Principles include fair provisions which balance the rights and obligations of both parties to the contract since they were not prepared to protect the interests of a certain sector. The UNIDROIT Principles abstained from using terminology which is unique to a certain system of law and thus ensure that the parties are placed at an equal legal level. Similarly, the UNIDROIT Principles were not prepared only for a certain type of contract, but aim to regulate the law of contracts in general. Thus, the UNIDROIT Principles are flexible in nature and adaptable to the special circumstances of the contractual relationship and the various interests of the parties. This flexibility also ensures that the UNIDROIT Principles can be easily adapted to the constant and fast technical and economic changes that occur in the field of international commerce. The UNIDROIT Principles did not adopt the solutions accepted by most of the countries (*common core*

¹ Cf. *UNCITRAL Model Law on Cross-Border Insolvency*

approach); but adopted more suitable solutions for cross-border commercial relations (*better rule approach*). This is also in line with the constantly changing character of international commerce. It was thought by the drafters that it would be in the interests of international business that the UNIDROIT Principles would be applicable to agreements concerning commercial relations generally.

However, the incorporation of the UNIDROIT Principles into international commercial contracts or choice of them as the applicable law to a contract is not very widespread among the international business community. The reason for this is probably the skepticism concerning the application of the UNIDROIT Principles by national courts and even by the arbitral tribunals. In other words, as traditional judges refrain from respecting the choice of UNIDROIT Principles and rather apply a certain national law to the resolution of a dispute arising out of a contract, members of the business community are generally discouraged from selecting the UNIDROIT Principles as the applicable law for their agreement.

The UNIDROIT Principles can be used both in connection with an arbitration clause and with a clause providing for the jurisdiction of a national court.

The UNIDROIT Principles do not form a 'law' as they only partly codify the law of contracts and obligations and they do not exhaustively determine the content of *lex mercatoria*. The priority, given to the mandatory rules of the applicable national law in Art. 1.4 of the UNIDROIT Principles, demonstrates that the UNIDROIT Principles do not form a 'law' by themselves. In addition, as the UNIDROIT Principles are prepared by an international institution, the sovereign power of a state needed to introduce any set of rules as 'law' is lacking. Consequently, although the choice of national rules of law by the parties can be interpreted as an incorporation of such rules of law to the contract, they can be respected as contract terms but they will be binding only to the extent they do not contradict with the mandatory provisions of the applicable national law. In contrast, the contemporary view is that the UNIDROIT Principles should be applied by the national courts in the event that they are chosen as the applicable law to the contract by the parties. In arbitral proceedings, it is usually accepted that parties may choose national rules of law to be applicable to their contracts. The provisions of national arbitration laws and institutional

arbitration rules regarding the law applicable to the substance of the dispute usually authorize the parties to choose UNIDROIT Principles. In *ad hoc* arbitrations, the parties may select the law applicable to the *ad hoc* procedure. In such cases, the law applicable to the substance of the dispute must be determined according to the relevant provision of the arbitration rules chosen by the parties. If the parties have not chosen which law to apply to the *ad hoc* arbitration procedure, then the applicable law to the substance will be determined according to the law of the place of arbitration.

According to Art. 28 of the UNCITRAL Model Law, the arbitral tribunal shall decide the dispute in accordance with such 'rules of law' as they are chosen by the parties. Failing any designation by the parties, the arbitral tribunal shall apply the 'law' determined by the conflict of laws rules which it considers applicable. Due to this difference in the terminology, it is accepted that the parties may choose UNIDROIT Principles as applicable 'rules of law' and the UNIDROIT Principles can be applied independently from any national law.

Consequently, it may be concluded that provisions of arbitration laws and rules, which do not limit the choice of law of the parties with the term 'law', but rather use the term 'rules of law', permit the application of UNIDROIT Principles if chosen by the parties. The use of the term 'rules of law' aims to authorize the parties to choose national rules of law as well as national laws as applicable law to their contracts.

In institutional arbitration, the arbitration rules of the institution are the primary point of reference for the determination of the law applicable to the substance. The choice of the UNIDROIT Principles in the context of a combination with an *institutional* arbitration clause is easy, because international arbitration bodies will accept such a choice. Many rules of arbitration do not refer to "national law", but to "rules of law". Such provisions can be found in, for example, the rules of arbitration used by International Chamber of Commerce and by London Court of International Arbitration. By applying the chosen UNIDROIT Principles, the arbitration tribunal applies not only the chosen rules of the arbitration institution, but also gives effect to the contractual parties' will, derived from the respective agreement and independent of national law. Further, there is no risk that the application of the chosen UNIDROIT Principles prevents the recognition

and execution of an award because, at least under the *New York Convention on Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards*, the decision on the applicable substantive law cannot be a ground for the refusal of an enforcement of an award.

According to Art. 17(1) of the International Chamber of Commerce Arbitration Rules: *“The parties shall be free to agree upon the rules of law to be applied by the Arbitral Tribunal to the merits of the dispute”*.

According to paragraph 4 of the Preamble to the UNIDROIT Principles, when the parties have not made a choice of law in their contract, the UNIDROIT Principles may be applied. According to Art. 28 of the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration, the arbitral tribunal shall decide the dispute in accordance with such ‘rules of law’ as are chosen by the parties, failing any designation by the parties, the arbitral tribunal shall apply the ‘law’ determined by the conflict of laws rules which it considers applicable. According to the prevailing view in the doctrine, it is not fortuitous that the arbitrators shall decide according to the ‘law’ in the absence of choice of law by the parties. The purpose of this wording is to ensure the application of national laws by the arbitrators. Furthermore, the application of the UNIDROIT Principles will put the arbitrators with different legal and educational backgrounds on an equal footing. Otherwise, if the domestic law of the place of origin or training of one arbitrator is applied, that arbitrator will be more influential over the other arbitrators. The application of the UNIDROIT Principles would avoid such a possibility.

There are a number of arbitral awards based on the UNIDROIT Principles in circumstances where, although the Principles were not chosen by the parties, the arbitrators applied them as the applicable law. For instance, the arbitral tribunal formed under the auspices of Arbitration Institute of the Stockholm Chamber of Commerce, in its award numbered 117/1999, concluded that in deciding the dispute it would be guided primarily by the UNIDROIT Principles even though the agreement between the parties was silent as to the law of the contract. The arbitral tribunal stated that the UNIDROIT Principles have wide recognition and set out principles that offer protections for contracting parties that adequately reflect the basic principles of commercial relations in most if not all developed countries.

International commercial contracts should be governed by the most closely connected law; in other words, this ought to be the law that is accepted as the rules of law and principles which would lead to the most fair and most appropriate solution to the circumstances of the dispute and the expectations of the parties ('better law'). The better law for international commercial contracts is the body of general rules and principles upon which there is an international consensus. The localisation of complex international contractual relations by connection to a certain national law determined by reference to characteristic performance or other presumptions is artificial. The presumptions, which define the most closely connected law with the contract by geographical connections, restrict the application of national rules of law. The classical conflict of laws method depending on geographical connections should be left aside to provide space for resolutions depending on quantitative connections. The law whose content is appropriate to the needs of international commerce and which promotes the validity of the contract between the parties, and that recognises the legal concepts used by the parties in their contracts, instead of necessarily having a geographical connection to the dispute, should be the most closely connected law with the contract.

Application of the UNIDROIT Principles is generally accepted in arbitral proceedings either when the parties have chosen them as the applicable rules of law to the merits of their dispute or, in the absence of such choice of law, as the most appropriate law.

As the UNIDROIT Principles provide a common ground between different national legal orders, they provide a good reference point for dialogue between lawyers from different jurisdictions. The study of the UNIDROIT Principles opens the mind to comparative legal thinking. It trains structural thinking, because as a product of comparative research, the UNIDROIT Principles draw apparent structural similarities between the different legal orders of the world. From the national legal perspective of any lawyer from any jurisdiction in the world, a comparison between the UNIDROIT Principles and the lawyer's own national law will evidence to what extent that national law of contracts meets international standards and to what extent the Unidroit Principles are comparable to that national legal order.

It should not be forgotten that the courts are not only obliged to apply their own national laws, they are also expected to serve for the preservation of the integrity of international commerce. Although national judges are obliged to apply their own national laws, they are also expected to decide the international disputes with an international perspective. This is expressly accepted by Art. 7 of the CISG. It is acknowledged by the 74 contracting states that in the interpretation of CISG, “regard is to be had to its international character and to the need to promote uniformity in its application”. In other words, it is set forth that national judges applying the CISG to disputes arising out of international relations shall consider the international character.

Knowing the UNIDROIT Principles is like speaking an additional language when it comes to cross-cultural legal communication. Over the years, the Unidroit Principles have become a practical reality and a part of the international law practice. The UNIDROIT Principles are never the only tool to cope with or to shape a contractual bargaining situation. For example, often, it is possible to implement a specific national legal order of choice in any given circumstances. Yet, the Unidroit Principles often serve as a tool to bridge cultural differences. They can be used in their entirety, with specific amendments, or partly, for certain clauses. It is a matter of proficiency to know about them.

Bibliography:

1. Berger K. P., *The Creeping Codification of the Lex Mercatoria*, The Hague - London - Boston: Kluwer Law International, 1999
2. *Convention of International Sale of Goods*,
<http://www.uncitral.org/pdf/english/texts/sales/cisg/CISG.pdf>
3. <http://www.un.org/en/members>
4. Shapiro M., *The Globalization of Law*, In “Global Legal Studies Journal”, vol, 1, 1993
5. *UNCITRAL Model Law on Cross-Border Insolvency*,
http://www.uncitral.org/uncitral/en/uncitral_texts/insolvency.html
6. *UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration*,
http://www.uncitral.org/uncitral/en/uncitral_texts/arbitration/1985Model_arbitration.html
7. *UNCITRAL Model Law on International Credit Transfers*,

http://www.uncitral.org/uncitral/en/uncitral_texts/payments/1992Model_credit_transfers.html

Copyright©Irina BURUIANĂ

Constitutional and Legal Fixing of Regulations on Environmental Protection in Europe and the Use of Natural Resources

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Natalia MINKO

x_pro1@tut.by

International University MITSO, Belarus

Abstract: The article examines modern constitutional and legal models and approaches fixing bases of the environmental policy pursued by the states. It is noted that constitutions of a number of states are limited to a short mention of the right of citizens for favorable environment or efforts (obligations) of the state (government bodies) for protection and improvement of environment. In certain states the legislator is limited to a short mention of a constitutional right of citizens for favorable environment without raising questions of the use of natural resources, implementation of state control and supervision in this sphere. Attention is paid to constitutions of some states of Europe (Greece, Spain, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Switzerland), which contain groups of norms, articles and even sections devoted to environmental protection and rational environmental management, quality of life, sustainable development, competence of authorized bodies of the government; their contents is considered. Fixing of the principles of state regulation on environmental protection and environmental management is analyzed.

Key-words: constitutions, constitutional and legal regulation, environmental protection, environmental management, right of citizens for favorable environment, ecological rights, government bodies.

In the second half of the 20th century among global problems of the world community the environmental problem including requirements of environmental protection, ensuring ecological safety in the course of implementation of economic and other activity, and also rational use of natural resources, their restoration was accurately designated. Constitutional and legal fixing was received by special norms concerning the organization of an order of use of natural riches with determination of powers of the governments, central, regional bodies, and also local authorities and self-government.

With the advent of new constitutional and legal institutes there are modern constitutional models, which are characterized by a certain socio-

political approach to object, the contents and ways of the constitutional regulation of certain public relations, and also reflecting the level of legal consciousness in society¹.

In this respect in constitutions and special laws of the majority of states at different phases fixing was received by the catalogue of the interconnected nature protection and nature-resource norms, which defined the main ways of development of the state environmental policy taking into account the nation-wide level of social and economic development.

The stated circumstances caused interest in research, which propose to open an order and features of constitutional and legal fixing of nature-resource provisions of the world by modern states.

We carried out the comparative analysis of constitutional and legal fixing of norms on environmental protection and environmental management worldwide: Austria, Azerbaijan, Albania, Andorra, Armenia, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Vatican, Great Britain, Hungary, Germany, Greece, Georgia, Denmark, India, Ireland, Iceland, Spain, Italy, Kazakhstan, Cyprus, China, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Moldova, Monaco, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Romania, the USA, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Ukraine, Finland, France, the Czech Republic, Switzerland, Sweden, Estonia, Japan², and also Republic of Belarus³ that promoted formation of certain notions of establishment of constitutional and legal bases of functioning of the mechanism of nature protection and nature-resource regulation.

Constitutions (Basic Laws) of the majority of the specified states (Azerbaijan, Albania, Andorra, Armenia, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Hungary, Georgia, India, Kazakhstan, China, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Macedonia, Malta, the Netherlands, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Finland, the Czech Republic, Estonia) do not contain a detailed legal regulation of the relations arising in the sphere of environmental protection and environmental management, do not define limits of powers

¹ T. Ya. Habriyeva. *Theory of the Modern Constitution*, pp. 16-17

² Constitutions of the States of Europe

³ The Constitution of the Republic of Belarus of 1994

of government bodies in this sphere, only in a general view indicating the need for environmental protections, rational use of natural riches, importance of their reproduction, collecting and providing data in this sphere for the state and citizens.

In the constitutional acts of such states as Belgium (Art. 23), Bulgaria (Art. 55), India (Art. 48A), Latvia (Art. 115), the Netherlands (Art. 21), Tajikistan (Art. 44), the Russian Federation (Art. 4), Turkmenistan (Art. 10), Finland (Art. 20), Estonia (Art. 53) and some others, the legislator is limited to a short mention of the right of citizens for favorable environment or efforts (obligations) of the state (government bodies) for protection and improvement of environment without raising the questions of use of natural resources, implementation of the state control and supervision in this sphere.

So, Hungary recognizes and carries out the right of everyone for healthy environment (Art. 18); the Constitution of the Netherlands of February 17, 1983, provides that government bodies have to care of preservation of the population, protection and improvement of environment (Art. 21). A peculiar fixing of considered norms is in the Constitution of Turkey of November 7, 1982, with changes and additions on ecological rights are considered in a context and close interrelation with development of healthcare institutions and providing social help (Art. 56) by the state. Article 53 of the Constitution of Estonia of June 28, 1992, establishes a duty of everyone to make thrifty use of environment and to indemnify the damage caused by them to environment. The constitution of Albania of October 21, 1998, fixes situation that everyone has the right for information on environment and its protection (Art. 56). The Constitution of the Czech Republic of December 16, 1992 (Art. 35) contains a similar norm.

Meanwhile such countries as Armenia (Art. 10), Belarus (Art. 46), Georgia (Art. 37), Lithuania (Art. 54), China (Art. 9) went further, having constitutionally affirmed the right of citizens for healthy and favorable surrounding environment, and also an obligation of the state on control, ensuring effective, reasonable and rational environmental management. So, according to the constitutional establishments of Armenia the state provides protection and reproduction of environment, rational use of natural resources (Art. 10). The constitution of Lithuania of October 25, 1992, with changes and additions provides situation that the state shows care of

protection of natural environment, exercises supervision for careful use, and also restoration and enhancement of natural resources (Art. 54).

The constitutional and legal nature protection and nature-resource provisions as a rule are contained in sections devoted to the rights, freedoms and duties of citizens, considering that the state is represented by authorized government bodies as a bound party on ensuring these rights.

So, the right of each person for favorable environment and for indemnification caused by violation of this right is provided in Art. 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus, too. Also the obligation of the state (represented by the appropriate authorized government bodies and officials) on control of rational use of natural resources for protection and improvement of living conditions, and also protection and restoration of environment is constitutionally established. Regulations on sole state ownership on subsoil, waters, and the woods are fixed in Art. 13 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus; about state ownership on lands for agricultural purpose; guarantees of equal protection and a condition of development of all forms of ownership are established. Article 44 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus contains a number of norms fixing the state guarantees on protection of property right and assistance of its acquisition; thus, it is underlined that implementation of property right should not harm to public advantage and safety, and also surrounding environment¹.

The constitution of the Republic of Belarus guarantees also a right to health protection of citizens, including free treatment in State Healthcare Institutions, which is provided, including carrying out actions for improvement of environment, by rational use and restoration of natural resources².

It is important to note that there are reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus not only the ecological rights of citizens, but also a general obligation for protection of surrounding environment as a duty of everyone. Thus, in Belarus the following independent directions of interstate environmental policy are constitutionally established:

¹ The Constitution of the Republic of Belarus of 1994

² Ibidem, Art.45

environmental protection; effective and rational use of natural resources, their restoration, and also control of environmental management.

According to instructions of constitutional precepts of law and norms of international law, implementation of obligations in environmental protection and environmental management are assigned to the supreme government bodies (the President of the Republic of Belarus, National Assembly of the Republic of Belarus, Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Belarus and its territorial authorities, the State committee on property of the Republic of Belarus), and also local authorities.

At the same time a number of constitutions does not contain special norms on environmental protection and environmental management at all, there are only regulations on the property right (the right for property), health protection of the people, quality of life (Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Vatican, Great Britain, Germany, Denmark, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Cyprus, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Monaco, Romania, the USA, France, Sweden, Japan).

N. Robinson specifies in the research “Legal Regulation of Environmental Management and Environmental Protection in the USA” that the instruction about powers of the federal Government on regulation of use of lands for trade implementation is fixed in article 1 § the 8th paragraph of the Constitution of the United States of America of September 17, 1787, with changes and additions. In many states there are special provisions reflecting the significant and fundamental directions of nature-resource policy. A number of constitutions contain norms, which do not demand further actions of legislation and often limit further legislative activity in the considered sphere. Some provisions regulate use of natural resources by restriction of certain kinds of activity (for example, sales of this resources), except for especially provided freedoms of action of the legislator¹.

This approach is, as a rule, very characteristic for early and pre-war constitutions, which paid not enough attention to norms of social, economic and ecological orientation; therefore nature protection and nature-resource

¹ N. Robinson. *Legal Regulation of Environmental Management and Environmental Protection in the USA*, pp. 58-86

provisions found the direct reflection in their texts, and gained development in a special legislation.

At the same time constitutions of some states of Europe (Greece, Spain, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Switzerland) contain groups of norms, articles and even sections, which are especially devoted to environmental protection and rational environmental management, quality of life, sustainable development. They regulate questions of pollution in the course of environmental management, protection of territories of reserves and national parks, the right for ecological information and eco-legal education, an order of use of natural resources, determination of competences of local and other bodies of the state (public) power in the specified sphere, thus, in detail fixing constitutional and legal bases of the state environmental policy (including politicians in the sphere of environmental management).

So, according to Art. 18 and Art. 24 of the Constitution of the Hellenic Republic of June 11, 1975, the state undertakes to take special preventive or repressive measures for conservation. The special law regulates the questions concerning forest conservation and in general forest territories, special laws regulate questions of property and distribution of mines, pits, caves, archaeological zones and finds, mineral, flowing and underground waters, and also riches of subsoil in general, questions of property, operation and management of sea lagoons and large lakes, and also questions of territories resulting from their drying.

It should be noted that the Constitution of the Portuguese Republic of April 2, 1976, with changes and additions obliges the state to warn and control environmental pollution and its consequences through own bodies, to develop rational use of natural resources, keeping their ability to updating and ecological stability; respecting the principle of solidarity of generations to assist in cooperation with local authorities of goodness of an urban environment and city life, in particular, in the architectural plan and in respect of protection of historical zones to promote giving of the ecological orientation to various spheres of the policy developed and which is carried out at the branch level, etc. (Art. 66).

The Constitution of the Swiss Confederation of April 18, 1999, illustrates in this relation the greatest attention to the considered sphere. The special section IV of the considered Constitution provides a detailed

regulation of the obligation of the state represented by the Union and cantons on rational use and protection of natural resources. The Constitution was adopted on a referendum after very long and careful development that caused the accuracy, completeness, the present and relevance of the formulation of many provisions, a detailed regulation of major public relations.

Provisions of Art. 74 of the Constitution of Poland of April 2, 1997, in our opinion, also deserve a special assessment as it defines competences of government bodies on nature protection and nature-resource areas. So, “the public authorities pursue the policy ensuring to present and to future generations ecological safety. Environmental protection is an obligation of the public authorities”¹.

The above mentioned allows to draw a conclusion that in the majority of the states of the world, including Belarus, constitutional and legal establishments of a nature protection and nature-resource orientation have exclusively declarative character as for them lack of addressing and the indication of responsibility is characteristic. At the same time a considerable progressive step of the states is not only fixing of the right of everyone for favorable environment, but also allocation of independent activity of government bodies – effective, rational use of natural resources with establishment of an obligation of the states on control (supervision) of environmental management against the general rather high level of other state obligations to society and the citizen. In the constitutions adopted within the last ten-fifteen years, this tendency is mostly noticeable that it is the most important advanced step of the states on the way of sustainable development.

Further development of constitutional precepts of law regulating this sphere of the relations has to rely on strategy and model of a sustainable development, which will act as a core of the state environmental policy and ideology. This strategy gained recognition and fixing in the majority of the democratic states of the world.

A. D. Ursule in the work “A sustainable development: the conceptual model” defines the sustainable development as the operated system and balanced development expressing interrelation and balance of economy,

¹ Constitutions of the States of Europe

ecology and social-political (state) aspect, which is directed on the solution of major national objectives in combination with preservation of natural and resource potential¹. L.-K. Kaldvell leans on that the model of sustainable development is aimed at observance of interests of the person in the surrounding environment, maintenance of stability of ecosystems, coordination of activity of the government and international bodies and organizations².

It is obvious that commitment of this model demands its constitutional and legal fixing, and also reduction in compliance with the industry nature-resource and adjacent legal instructions.

Due to stated fixing of the principles of state regulation of environmental protection and environmental management in a separate article of the developed Ecological code of the Republic of Belarus, chapter 3 of the General part of the model Ecological code for the State Parties of the CIS in the following edition is offered:

“The state pursues the policy ensuring to present and to future generations ecological safety by means of environmental protection, rational use of natural resources.

Everyone has the right for favorable environment, ecological equilibrium.

The state is obliged to create conditions through the appropriate republican and local government bodies with the assistance of everyone for sustainable development to hold the following activities:

- 1) to control, warn and eliminate consequences of environmental pollution and to promote restoration of natural resources;
- 2) to develop competent and rational use of natural resources on the basis of conventional international and national principles, protecting their ability to updating;
- 3) to define competence of republican and local public authorities in the sphere of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources;

¹ A. D. Ursule. *Sustainable Development: Conceptual Model*

² L. K. Caldwell. *International Environmental Policy: Emergence and Dimensions*

4) to promote development of ecological education, eco-legal education of citizens, and also free realization of the right for ecological information;

5) to promote full realization of the right for indemnification in connection with violation of the right of citizens for favorable environment;

6) to provide a combination for development of environmental protection and rational environmental management to development of quality of life by carrying out the corresponding economic and financial policy;

7) to develop and deepen an ecological orientation of various spheres of the pursued state policy and ideology at the republican and local levels”.

In general it is possible to draw a conclusion that in the majority of modern states, including the Republic of Belarus, the importance of nature protection and nature-resource problems taking into account their increase, duration and long duration is realized. The solution of these problems in many respects is defined by policy of the state, ways of development and which order of realization determines activities of authorized government bodies. Therefore, modern constitutions, as a rule, contain the three-unit definition of ecological activity concerning interaction of the state, society and the nature, including environmental protection, ensuring ecological safety, competent, effective and rational environmental management.

However, legal fixing of nature protection and nature-resource requirements not always assure their execution. A lot of things depend on the level of social and economic development of the state, the policy pursued by the state and ideology, creation of the relevant system of government bodies effectively operating mechanisms of state regulation on environmental protection and use of natural resources.

Bibliography:

1. Caldwell L. K. *International Environmental Policy: Emergence and Dimensions*. 2nd ed. Durham: Duke University Press, 1990.
2. *Constitutions of the States of Europe*. Edited by of L. A. Okunkov. M.: Norm, 2001.
3. Habriyeva T. Ya. *Theory of the Modern Constitution* / T. Ya. Habriyeva, V. E. Chirkin. M.: Norm, 2005.

4. Robinson N. *Legal Regulation of Environmental Management and Environmental Protection in the USA*. M.: Progress, 1990.
5. The Constitution of the Republic of Belarus of 1994 (with the changes and additions accepted on republican referendum on November 24, 1996 and on October 17, 2004). 4 prod., stereotype. Minsk: National. Center legal inform. Republic of Belarus, 2009.
6. Ursule A. D. Sustainable Development: Conceptual Model / A. D. Ursule. National. Interests. 2005. No. 1. http://ni-journal.ru/archive/2005/n1_05/5324690e/d93f12df. Accessed on 10.01.2015.

Copyright©Natalia MINKO

Legal Grounds for Georgia – EU Approximation from Partnership and Cooperation Agreement to Association Agreement

Ph.D. candidate Giorgi GETSADZE

giorgi_getsadze@yahoo.com

New Vision University, Georgia

Abstract: Membership to the European family became Georgia’s main goal after gaining independence in 1991. The country started to work hard to reach its aim and in 2014 the Association Agreement between Georgia and the EU was signed. Georgia has done a lot to be closer to the EU and legislation approximation became the main means to reach its goal. The process started shortly after signing the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA), first legal ground for the approximation process. The present paper reviews the legislation frameworks and instruments used for legal approximation. The aim of this paper is to show how Georgian Parliament and Government construed all legal acts, primary and secondary, in compliance with EU law and how these mechanisms worked. It shows the steps taken on the ground of Georgian legislation in the legal approximation process for the last decades. As a result, we will have the picture of legislation approximation in Georgia with its benefits and drawbacks.

Key-words: European Union, Georgia, approximation, partnership and cooperation agreement, association agreement.

Legal bases from “soft” obligation to mandatory law

The cooperation between Georgia and the EU started in 1992 shortly after the European Community recognized the independence of Georgia. Active legal initiatives took place in 1994 and as a result ended up with signing of the PCA on 22 April 1996 with the European Communities, Member States, on the one part, and Georgia, on the other part¹. By signing this Agreement the parties expressed their hopes that full implementation of the Agreement will help Georgia to continue and finish legal reforms².

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement has an important place within Georgian legislation. According to the Constitution of Georgia, an

¹ Georgia-EU Cooperation, Office of the Minister of Georgia on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, <http://www.eu-nato.gov.ge/ge/eu/cooperation>, accessed on 06.03.2015.

² Preamble of the PCA.

international treaty or agreement of Georgia has superiority over domestic normative acts, if it does not contradict the Constitution¹. Consequently, the PCA, as an international agreement, is part of Georgian legal system and its place is below constitution and above all domestic legislation².

Before tackling Georgia-EU approximation process it should be noted that legal acts of Georgian Parliament or / and Georgian Government don't distinguish the terms of "approximation" and "harmonization"; there is no explanation given why to use one of those terms and it seems they have the same meaning. In order to describe the legal approximation process, both "approximation" and "harmonization" are used in official Georgian documents and the way how they are used leads to the conclusion that they are assumed as synonyms³.

The PCA established the partnership with the European Communities and Georgia and one of the most important objectives of these relations was the legal approximation that is prescribed by the 5th Chapter of the Agreement. The approximation of existing and future Georgian legislation to the requirements of the European Communities was an important precondition for strengthening economic cooperation that is why "Georgia shall endeavor to ensure that its legislation will be gradually made compatible with that of the Communities"⁴. This article is very similar to what is in the EU-Ukraine PCA and can't be understood as mandatory requirement for Legal Approximation. Wording makes general statement and gives a wide range of possibilities for Legal Approximation Programmer or Plan adaptation, without a concrete list of legal documents, which should be approximated⁵. According to this wording, Georgia has "soft" obligations in the legal approximation process without specific obligations⁶. The PCA gives a list of fields where legal approximation should take place: laws and regulations governing investment by companies, customs law, company law,

¹ Constitution of Georgia, Article 6, par. 2. 14.08.1995; Legislation Herald of Georgia; <https://matsne.gov.ge/en/document/view/30346>, accessed on 28.03.2015.

² Gaga Gabrichidze, "Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia", p.180.

³ Ibidem, p.183.

⁴ Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, Article 43 Par. 2.

⁵ Art. 51 EU-Ukraine PCA, emphasis added; Seen The EU-Ukraine Association Agreement: Assessment of an Innovative Legal Instrument, p.4.

⁶ Gaga Gabrichidze, Op. cit., pp.181-182.

banking law, company accounts and taxes, intellectual property, protection of workers at the workplace, financial services, rules on competition, public procurement, protection of health and life of humans, animals and plants, the environment, consumer protection, indirect taxation, technical rules and standards, nuclear laws and regulations and transport¹. Cooperation between parties covers mainly all fields that are related to formation and reinforcement of democratic institutions. The Agreement also includes technical assistance to adopt and implement appropriate primary and secondary legislation².

Partnership and Cooperation Agreement has a very important role in Georgia-EU Legal Approximation process, but it has its drawbacks: the PCA gives bases for legal approximation, but contains “soft” binding obligations; there are no concrete goal to achieve; there are no responsibilities defined for no fulfilment of approximation requirements; the PCA contains wide range of priorities, but there is no list of legislation that should be approximated; the objectives of the PCA are broad, but it does not provide specific means to achieve these objectives. In that way the PCA gives the first legal ground of legislation approximation. Despite the fact that the agreement gives “soft” and “flexible” obligations, it was accepted as mandatory and strict requirement and was used as legal ground for future legislative activities. Exactly to facilitate obligations under Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, to approximate existing and future legislation with EU requirements³, the Georgian Parliament issued Resolution №828⁴, according to which “all the laws and other normative acts adopted by the parliaments of Georgia starting from 1st September 1998 should be compatible with the standards and norms of the European Union”⁵. In order to ensure this obligation, requirements of all international norms and applicability in accordance with the draft law, should be included in

¹ PCA, Article 43, Par. 2.

² Ibidem, Article 71.

³ Ibidem, Article 43 Par. 1; translated by the author.

⁴ Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia “On the Harmonization of Georgian Legislation with that of the EU”, 02 September 1997, №828-Is; Legislation Herald of Georgia, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/38704>, accessed on 08.04.2015.

⁵ Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia №828-Is, Article 1.

explanatory note of the draft Law¹. Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia №828 was adopted after one year the PCA was signed on 02.09.1997. The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement came into force only on 01.07.1999². Accordingly, Georgia did not have obligation to start legal approximation process. Nevertheless, the Georgian Parliament made advanced step and the Georgian legislative expressed its aspiration and desire to approximate future legislation to EU requirements, even before the PCA came into force.

Wording of Resolution №828 of the Parliament of Georgia was an attempt of general subordination of domestic legislation to the EU law, “in fact, it has never been implemented and neither has played any role in the legislation process thereafter”³. Accordingly, it was just a requirement, which expressed good will of the Parliament of Georgia to start and accelerate legal approximation process; unfortunately, in practice it was never used in the way that could lead to an appropriate result.

In order to facilitate EU-Georgia legal approximation process, relevant records were made in “Georgian Law on Normative Acts”, which prescribes lists of documents that should be provided with draft law. Explanatory note of the draft law should include information regarding relevance with international acts and relation to EU directives⁴. Similar requirements are laid down in Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, according to which draft law should be prepared in accordance to the law of Georgia on normative acts; draft law should be supplemented by explanatory note indicating “compatibility of draft law to EU directives”⁵. This wording gives rise to question: why the reference is made to EU directives and not to the whole EU acquis?⁶ From word by word understanding it seems that Georgian legislation should be in compliance

¹ Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia №828-Is, Article 2.

² “The European Union and Georgia portrait of a partnership”, p.6. http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/brochures/eu_georgia_en.pdf.

³ Gaga Gabrichidze, “Legal Approximation to the EU Acquis – a Georgian Perspective, p.32.

⁴ Law of Georgia on Normative Acts, №1876–IIs; 22 October 2009, Article 17, Par.1(c)-(c.a); Legislation Herald of Georgia, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/90052>; accessed on 05.04.2015.

⁵ Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, №6533-Is, 22 June 2012, Article 145. <http://parliament.ge/ge/kanonmdebloba/parlamentis-reglamenti>; accessed on 13.04.2015.

⁶ Gaga Gabrichidze, Op. cit., p.32.

only with EU directives and it should not take into account EU legislation as a whole, but it was a result of wrong association of EU law to EU directives¹.

At first glance, it seems that requirements to fulfil legal approximation obligations are quite well laid down in Georgian legislation, but in-depth analysis makes it clear that these instruments were not enough to reach the goal. Unfortunately, there is no statistical data regarding compliance or non compliance of draft law with EU directives, but research conducted by Gaga Gabrichidze made it obvious that even those draft law that claim compatibility with EU directives are doubtful in compliance with EU directives².

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement did not lose its importance in the following years. The Decree of the President of Georgia №317 “On Promotion of the implementation of Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between Georgia and the EU”³ referred PCA as “The basic legal document of Georgia-EU relations and full and effective enforcement of this Agreement will speed up Georgia-EU approximation process”⁴. To ensure promotion of the implementation of the PCA, a Governmental Commission was set up with the main goal to facilitate Georgia-EU partnership and cooperation. The main task of the Governmental Commission was to coordinate implementation of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, in particular, to promote approximation of national law to EU legislation⁵. This fact once again underlines that Georgia has intention to facilitate the legal approximation process with the EU and control this process on Governmental level; this is proven by the fact that the Governmental Commission has power to request information from different agencies and ministries. It should be mentioned that this power was not just for revision of information; Governmental

¹ Gaga Gabrichidze, “Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia”, p.184.

² Idem, “Legal Approximation to the EU Acquis – a Georgian Perspective”, p.32.

³ Decree of the President of Georgia “On the Promotion of the Implementation of Partnership and Cooperation between Georgia and the EU”, 24 July 2000, №317, Legislation Herald of Georgia, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/1252267>, accessed on 08.04.2015.

⁴ Decree of the President of Georgia №317.

⁵ Ibidem, Georgia-EU Partnership and Cooperation Promotion Governmental Commission Charter, Article 2, Par.1.

Commission had power to evaluate working results and, if necessary, create separate working groups¹. One of the main tasks of the Governmental Commission was to prepare PCA implementation Action Plan and to present, before 1st November 2000, the draft strategy of accelerating EU integration process in order to discuss it in a Government session.

The steps for preparation PCA implementation Action Plan and Strategy for EU integration process lead to the decision to create a Unified Strategy, which should determine legal approximation priorities and its implementation stages². In order to achieve this goal all ministries had to prepare their own proposals for the creation of a Unified Strategy of Georgia-EU Legal Approximation³ and an important role was given to the "Recommendations for the Strategy of Approximation of Georgian Legislation to that of the EU", prepared by the Georgian-European Policy and Legal Advice Center (GEPLAC). The Governmental Commission had the obligation to prepare the draft of the Unified Strategy and to discuss it, before the 1st of April 2001 in the Governmental session⁴. The involvement of the ministries in the preparation process had a positive impact on the priorities and principles from all fields that should be presented in the Unified Strategy.

Thus, by two normative acts, the Decree of the President of Georgia №317 and the Order of the President of Georgia №1422, the development of Georgia-EU Legal Approximation Strategy was delegated to the Governmental Commission for the Promotion and Implementation of the PCA. This fact should be considered as an important step forward, because only the Governmental Commission had obligation and responsibility in the creation of the Strategy, that made it easier to control and hasten the process; as a result, there was no delay in this process; the strategy was approved by the Order of the President of Georgia №613 and the

¹ Decree of the President of Georgia №317; Georgia-EU Partnership and Cooperation promotion Governmental Commission Charter, Article 3.

² Edict of the President of Georgia "On Development of the Strategy on Approximation of Georgian Legislation to that of EU" №1422, 31 December 2000.

³ Decree of the President of Georgia №317.

⁴ Edict of the President of Georgia №1422.

preparation of the National Plan of Harmonization was scheduled by the end of 2003¹.

The Strategy of harmonization determines the “Essential requirement and the important aspect for further development of the country”². The Strategy refers to the main fields of legal approximation of priorities and describes the core directions and tasks, which should be taken into account in the legal approximation process: corporate law; customs law; financial services; tax legislation; intellectual property; protection of workers at the workplace; competition law; public procurement; agriculture (veterinary and phytosanitary); environment; consumers’ rights; technical rules and standards; transport³.

It should be mentioned that the last chapter of the Strategy is dedicated to the “legislation approximation procedures”, but there are no procedural rules prescribed; only the indication to prepare the National Program of Approximation of Georgian legislation to EU legislation, which will determine the main stages of legal approximation and will define the responsibilities of the State Agencies⁴. Accordingly and despite the fact that the Strategy determines priorities of legal approximations, it doesn’t prescribe the approximation process stages. It underlines that only the National Program of Approximation of the Georgian legislation to EU legislation will give the possibility to determine the responsibilities of different state agencies.

As Georgia has not had any experience in legal approximation process, there was an expressed desire to share the European experience in the legislative approximation methodology. It concerned EU Member States as well, those states that have already passed all the association stages and have already conducted the approximation of the national legal system to the EU’s legislation. It was considered that sharing the experience of EU Member States could give Georgia the possibility to follow their steps and avoid the mistakes of the others. From the Georgian perspective, the EU methodology included: economic analysis and the impact on further

¹ Edict of the President of Georgia “On the Strategy of Harmonization of Georgian Legislation with that of the EU” №613, 14 June 2001.

² Ibidem, Chapter 4.

³ Ibidem, Chapter 6.

⁴ Ibidem, Chapter 7, legislation approximation procedure.

development of the economic sectors of new legislative initiative; involvement of active businesses and companies, which are active in the filed regulated by the new legislation; discussions with workers, trade unions, associations and non-governmental organizations; active debates in national press¹. This determination was essential for further processes. It excluded from the very beginning the “copy-paste” methodology and focused on the economic analysis and business involvement in the approximation process. This methodology is central in the approximation process. It makes it easier to understand the level of economic impact on particular legal acts; it involves impact on business and economy. It is vital to avoid bankruptcy and disappearance of small and medium business, because mostly they will “feel pressure” of strict requirements. In order to avoid this drawback, approximation should be done gradually, step by step, analyzing and evaluating the existing situation.

Soon the approximation process went beyond the general strategy and important steps were taken when every ministry had to establish Eurointegration Departments and the deputy minister had to coordinate the functionality of these departments². It was obvious that Georgia was involved in the European integration and the legislation approximation moved to a more intensive phase, as at the ministerial level became possible to implement the approximation policy. The creation of Eurointegration Departments made it possible to conduct approximation process with intensive involvement of specialists in particular fields. In general, a ministry doesn't have the capacity and enough knowledge in the field of another ministry so that the approximation of particular fields should be done by appropriate professionals. The fact that the coordination of the Eurointegration Departments was entrusted to the Deputy Minister once again underlined that the approximation was a very important process for the Georgian Government.

Institutional framework

In parallel with the legislation approximation process, the European integration was supported by institutional frameworks. Coherent and coordinated actions of state Agencies were crucial for the approximation

¹ Edict of the President of Georgia, №613, Chapter 7. legislation approximation procedure.

² Edict of the Government of Georgia №22.

process; the “EU Cooperation Coordination Council” (Coordination Council) was introduced. The decisions and recommendations of the Coordination Council were mandatory for all the Agencies involved in the approximation process¹. One of the main tasks of the Coordination Council was to “support further process of harmonization of Georgian legislation to European legislation”². Work sessions and activities of the Coordination Council were conducted by the President of Georgia, who was the Chairman at the same time. Consequently, the president of Georgia had the powerful tool to participate and support the approximation process.

The importance of the role of the Parliament of Georgia in the legal approximation process was underlined in 2003 when the Parliament received the power to conduct negotiations with relevant bodies of the EU regarding the acceleration of Georgia’s integration into the EU. Also, there was made a clear demand for presenting reports to the Parliament about the performance of the obligations taken in front of the EU³. As the approximation was the main tool to perform obligations in front of the EU, the Georgian Parliament was aware about every step taken in this field. This process was reinforced by the Georgian Parliamentary Committee of European Integration, which monitored implementation of Georgia-EU PCA⁴. The Committee has the power to review draft laws in compliance with EU legislation⁵. At first sight, it seems that the Parliament of Georgia was fully involved in the EU-Georgia approximation process and influenced this process, but opinions of the Committee were not legally binding and there is only a potential possibility to have influence on the political processes in Georgia”⁶. Despite the fact that the Committee of the European Integration did not have direct impact on the approximation process, the possibility to

¹ Decree of the President of Georgia “On Setting up the EU Cooperation Coordination Council” №150, 23 April 2001.

² Decree of the President of Georgia №150, Article 3, Par. f.

³ Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia “On Acceleration of the full integration of Georgian to the EU” №2026–lis, 28 March 2003.

⁴ Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, №3353, 25 March 2004, Legislation Herald of Georgia, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/13528>, Article 30, par.f.

⁵ Charter of the Parliamentary Committee of European Integration, Article 2, Par. C, <http://parliament.ge/ge/saparlamento-saqmianoba/komitetebi/evropastan-integraciis-komiteti-143/debuleba1910>, accessed on 15.04.2015.

⁶ Gaga Gabrichidze, “Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia”, p.188.

influence political processes could be considered as an important and indirect power.

The role of the Prime-minister was increased in 2004 when the President of Georgia issued the Decree №278. The Decree of the President of Georgia №317 "On Promotion of the implementation of Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between Georgia and the EU" and the Decree of the President of Georgia "On Setting up EU Cooperation Coordination Council" №150 were invalidated. Consequently, EU Cooperation Council and the Governmental Commission were abolished. In the same year, EU Integration Commission was presented to support and coordinate the integration process¹. One of the main tasks of the Commission was to support approximation of Georgian legislation to EU legislation². EU Integration Commission replaced EU Cooperation Council and the Governmental Commission, and it was chaired by the Prime-minister of Georgia³. Here we see how the power is transferred from the president to the Prime-minister. As the Cooperation Coordination Council was abolished, the President of the Georgia lost the possibility to participate directly in the approximation process; and by establishing EU Integration Commission, the Prime-minister received the tool to support the approximation of the Georgian legislation to EU legislation.

The Office of the State Minister of Georgia on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration was established⁴ for the coordination of EU-Georgia political, economic and legal approximation. The main tasks of the Office were to coordinate the process of planning, implementing and monitoring EU assistance programmers in Georgia⁵.

Consequently, all the main actors of the Georgian legislative and executive authorities, like President, Parliament and Prime-minister, were

¹ Edict of the Government of Georgia "On Setting up the EU Integration Commission" №76, 10 July 2004.

² Ibidem.

³ Gaga Gabrichidze, "Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia, p.187.

⁴ Decree of the President of Georgia "On the Introduction of the Office of the State Minister in the Government of Georgia" №61, 14 February 2004, Legislation Herald of Georgia, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/34990>; accessed on 01.04.2015.

⁵ Office of the State Minister of Georgia on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, <http://www.eu-nato.gov.ge/en>.

involved in the approximation process. They have different tools and different level of power that changed over time.

European Neighborhood Policy. In 2004, shortly after the inauguration of the President of Georgia, Mikheil Saakashvili, the Council agreed that there was a need for early action in support of Georgia. The Commission was invited to bring forward a recommendation on the relationship with Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan to the European Neighborhood Policy (ENP)¹.

Georgia's involvement in ENP was important as well as for the EU, too. From the European Security Strategy perspective, the South Caucasus was identified as a region where the EU should take "stronger and more active interest"². In addition, as the Council had confirmed, sharing benefits of an enlarged EU was the main objective of the European Neighbourhood Policy; the aim was to increase stability, security and prosperity of the European Union and its neighbours³. From the Georgian perspective, the involvement in the ENP was the possibility to gain better access to the EU internal market and to deepen the political, economic and legal cooperation. This opportunity depended on Georgia's contribution in implementing political, economic and institutional reforms and on the legal approximation process⁴.

On 12 May 2004 the Council recalled its interest in promoting stability, democracy and prosperity in the Southern Caucasus and decided to include Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan in the ENP⁵.

After the adoption of the EU–Georgia ENP Action Plan on 14 November 2006, it became the basic tool for implementation of the ENP's objectives⁶ and the Commission noted that ENP Action Plan could be used for strengthening EU-Georgia relations and further implementation of the

¹ General Affairs and External Relations Council, Conclusions; Brussels, 26 January 2004, p.11.

² European Security Strategy; Brussels, 12 December 2003, p.9.

³ General Affairs and External Relations; Press Release, Council of the European Union, Provisional Version, Luxembourg, 14 June 2004, p.11.

⁴ Gaga Gabrichidze, "Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia", p.180.

⁵ General Affairs and External Relations, Press Release, Council of the European Union, Provisional Version, Luxembourg, 14 June 2004, p.13.

⁶ Gaga Gabrichidze, Op. cit., p.180.

PCA¹. But in relation to legal approximation issues EU-Georgia, ENP Action Plan is more progressive than the PCA: it expands scope of the fields covered by legal approximation; it has time limits for implementation of the planned measures; the approximation provisions are directly related to the Action Plan priorities²; the scope of the fields are expanded and the progress reports by the European Commission had impact on the legal approximation process in Georgia and the need to ensure achievement of the objectives made some kind of “pressure” on Georgian legislator to improve legislation approximation process³.

The European Neighborhood Policy involved financial support from the EU, including technical assistance and twinning to meet EU norms and standards, and targeted advice and support for legislation approximation through such mechanism as TAIEX⁴. Georgia received step by step assistance from the EU and as the next step to the ENP Action Plan country Strategy Paper (CSP) was introduced, it covered EU financial assistance to Georgia for the period 2007-2013, and it made Georgia eligible for the new European Neighborhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI)⁵. The assistance included support for legal approximation in a broader range of areas⁶.

The most important part of the ENP was the possibility for Georgia to implement the Action Plan; there was a possibility of new enhanced agreement to replace the PCA upon its expiry⁷. This statement proved that the ENP gave possibilities to go forward and deepen political, economic and legal relations with the EU; everything that was needed was to fulfill the Action Plan requirements.

Eastern Partnership

In May 2009 high representatives of Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine, the representatives of the European Union

¹ Communication from the Commission to the Council; European Neighborhood Policy; Recommendations for Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and for Egypt and Lebanon, pp.5-6.

² Gaga Gabrichidze, “Legal approximation to the EU acquis – a Georgian perspective”, p.30.

³ Idem, “Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia, p.184

⁴ European Neighborhood Policy; European Union-Georgia Action Plan, p.6.

⁵ European Neighborhood and Partnership Instrument Georgia; Country Strategy Paper 2007-2013, p.5.

⁶ Ibidem, pp.21-22.

⁷ Communication from the Commission to the Council; European Neighborhood Policy; Recommendations for Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and for Egypt and Lebanon, p.6.

and high representatives of its Member States met in Prague for establishing the Eastern Partnership to bring their relationship to a new level and adopted Joint Declaration¹.

In order to achieve the main goal, accelerate political association and further economic integration, the Eastern Partnership aimed at supporting political and socio-economic reforms of the partner countries, facilitating approximation towards the European Union².

Prague Summit took view that agreed Eastern Partnership umbrella should provide “the foundation” for Association Agreements (AA) between the EU and the partner countries, and it should be directly related to compliance with the resulting commitments³. The Eastern Partnership, leading to Association Agreement, was very important for Georgia, because it opened new perspectives for more comprehensive relations with the EU. Establishing Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Areas as part of the Association Agreement depended on the regulatory approximation with the EU laws and standards⁴. In this case, Georgia had to comply with from the beginning as the aims of the EaP was conclusion of a new generation of Association Agreements; Georgia was given the chance to switch on a new type of agreement, giving the possibility to create the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area and asses the EU market. It was possible only by approximating the Georgian legal system and standards to the EU requirements.

EU-Georgia Association Agreement

On 27 June 2014 the Association Agreement between the EU and the Member States and Georgia was signed. It was the result of all that Georgia has done during past years in the EU-Georgia approximation process. The Association Agreement is a unique Agreement that might be considered as integration without membership⁵, aiming to deepen political and economic

¹ Joint Declaration of the Prague Eastern partnership Summit, p.5.

² Ibidem, p.6.

³ Ibidem, p.7.

⁴ Ibidem.

⁵ Cf. Adam Lazowski, “Enhanced Multilateralism and Enhanced Bilateralism: Integration without Membership in the European Union”, pp.1433-1458; Guillame Van der Loo, “The EU-Ukraine Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area: a coherent mechanism for legislative approximation?”, pp.63-88. Seen Guillaume Van der Loo, Peter Van Elsuwege and

relations between the EU and Georgia, by approximation of standards, and gradual development of different fields¹. The Association Agreement refers to the integration-oriented agreements, meaning that the agreement includes principles and provisions of the EU law that should be transposed into the legal system of the third country, like it is in the case of EU Member States². Consequently, signing the agreement posed on Georgia more responsibility in legal approximation process as it undertook the obligation to transpose EU norms and standards taking into account the social, economic and political situation in the country. An “Association Agenda” including the plan for three years (2014-2016) was adopted to facilitate the approximation process. It highlights the priority areas determined by the Association Agreement and provides measures to be implemented for legal and practical approximation in different fields³.

EU-Georgia Association Agreement is part of a new generation of Association Agreements with the Eastern Partnership countries providing a long-term foundation for future EU-Georgia relations. The Agreement took an ambitious and innovative approach, going qualitatively beyond the PCA⁴.

The legislation approximation is the main foundation for the integration in European economy, because approximation of the legal basis with EU requirements is a prerequisite for the accession to European market. In addition, the Association Agreement is the legal tool that will replace the PCA as a basic bilateral agreement with the EU and Georgia.

One of the most important parts of EU-Georgia Association Agreement is the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA). The enforcement of the DCFTA will make possible for Georgian products to have access to European market. The DCFTA includes the mechanisms for

Roman Petrov (Eds.), *The EU-Ukraine Association Agreement: Assessment of an Innovative Legal Instrument*, p.2.

¹ http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/news/2014/20140325_01_ka.pdf; accessed on 17.02.2015.

² Cf. Guillaume Van der Loo, Peter Van Elsuwege and Roman Petrov (Eds.), *The EU-Ukraine Association Agreement: Assessment of an Innovative Legal Instrument*, Abstract.

³ http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/eap_aa/associationagenda_2014_ka.pdf; accessed on 2.15.2015.

⁴ EU-Georgia Association Agreement, “what does the Agreement offer?”, p.1, http://eeas.europa.eu/georgia/pdf/quick_guide_eu_ge_aa_en.pdf; accessed on 07.05.2015.

European integration and opens the door to EU internal market¹. As a part of the DCFTA Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures, the Association Agreement contains indications on gradual approximation². This approximation should be done by the approximation list that should contain a list of EU legislation in accordance with Georgia's priorities³.

The Association Agreement introduces two types of approximation: gradual and dynamic. As it is indicated in Article 417, the approximation of the Georgian law to that of the EU should be done gradually in accordance to the Annexes of the agreement. In parallel to gradual approximation, the dynamic approximation should follow the Annexes of the AA that should be periodically revised in order to reflect the evaluation of EU law⁴. As Georgia has a list of legislation and a timetable for approximation, the changes of EU law will be taken into account. The Association Agreement includes monitoring of the approximation process including implementation and enforcement aspects. In order to facilitate this process, Georgia has to report to the EU on the progress of approximation⁵. One of the ways of the report is the table of correspondence that should be used to evaluate the compliance of the Georgian particular legal act with EU law. It has four fields for: EU Act, national legislation, remarks (from Georgia), reviewer's comments⁶. Annex 11 of the AA provides two ways of legal approximation: adopt new rules and procedures; change existing rules and procedures.

The implementation process of the Association Agreement is supervised by the Association Council consisting of members of the Council of the European Union and members of the European Commission, on the one hand, and members of the Government of Georgia, on the other hand⁷. In order to assist the Association Council in performance of its duties and functions an Association Committee was established. The Association Committee shall be composed of representatives of the Parties, in principle

¹ <http://www.economy.ge/ge/dcfta>, accessed on 01.05.2015.

² AA, Art.55.

³ Ibidem, Art.55 and Annex 11.

⁴ Ibidem, Article 418.

⁵ Ibidem, Art.419, par. 2.

⁶ Ibidem, Annex XI-A, Part II, 2.2.

⁷ Ibidem, Art.404-405.

senior civil servant level¹. The Association Council has power to take binding decisions and also make recommendations².

The most important innovations offered by the Association Agreement: it replaced the PCA as basic bilateral agreement with the EU; it provides step by step action in different fields regarding legal approximation; it includes time tables; spatial approximation list should be agreed between the EU and Georgia; tables of correspondence should be made in order to see the approximation of particular Georgian legal acts with EU requirements; Georgia's priority areas should be taken into account while making the Approximation List; the Approximation List is subject of revision if required (it's flexible); the approximation process should be conducted gradually giving Georgia the possibility to make comprehensive analysis of each legal act and only after that it should be approximated with EU requirements; the Approximation List will be made for 10-15 years and it will make it easier to plan the approximation process in advance.

Discussions on the approximation issue of EU-Georgia Association Agreement will keep us in long debates, underlying that after the 27th of June 2014 Georgia moved to a new dimension of legal approximation.

Conclusion

We have a clear picture of the main steps that Georgia has performed in Georgia-EU legal approximation process; starting from the PCA to recently signed Association Agreement. During the last decades the system of Georgian legislation transformed from "soft" obligation to mandatory law and the main actors of the Georgian legislative and executive authorities, like the President, the Parliament and the Prime-minister, were involved in the approximation process; they have different tools and different levels of powers that change over time. Through the Agreement Georgia commits a gradual approximation with economic analysis avoiding the "copy-paste" methodology.

Supporting legal approximation by institutional frameworks and the support from EU (by including Georgia in the ENP and the EaP), it made possible signing of the Association Agreement that replaced the PCA as a basic bilateral agreement with the EU; signing Association Agreement is a big

¹ AA, Art.407-408.

² Ibidem, Art. 406 par.1.

step forward for Georgia as the AA may be considered as an integration-oriented agreement, meaning that the agreement includes principles and provisions of EU law that should be transposed in the legal system of the third country, like it is in the case of EU Member State; it means that Georgia will have more responsibilities and hopefully it will lead Georgia to the desired result. From achievements and mistakes made by Georgia it may be concluded that the legal approximation process in Georgia is successful, but there is a lot to be done in this field.

Bibliography:

Articles

1. Gabrichidze Gaga, "Legal Approximation and Application of EU Law in Georgia"; in: Roman Petrov, Peter Van Elsuwege (eds.), *The Application of EU Law in the Eastern Neighbourhood of the European Union – Towards a Common Regulatory Space?*, London: Routledge, 2014.
2. Gabrichidze Gaga, "Legal Approximation to the EU Acquis – a Georgian Perspective"; in: Andreas Kellerhals, Tobias Baumgartner (eds.), *EU Neighbourhood Policy – Survey and Perspectives*, Zürich, 2014.
3. Lazowski Adam, "Enhanced Multilateralism and Enhanced Bilateralism: Integration without Membership in the European Union", 45 (2) *Common Market Law Review* (2008), 1433-1458.
4. Van der Loo Guillaume, Van Elsuwege Peter and Petrov Roman, *The EU-Ukraine Association Agreement: Assessment of an Innovative Legal Instrument*; European University Institute, Department of Law; 2014/09; European University Institute, Badia Fiesolana, I – 50014 San Domenico di Fiesole (FI).
5. Van der Loo Guillame, "The EU-Ukraine Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area: a coherent mechanism for legislative approximation?", in Peter Van Elsuwege, Roman Petrov (Eds.) *Legislative Approximation and Application of EU Law in the Eastern Neighbourhood of the European Union. Towards a Common Regulatory Space?*, London: Routledge, 2014, pp.63-88.

International Agreements

1. Partnership and Cooperation Agreement.
2. EU-Georgia Association Agreement.

Legal Acts of Georgia

1. Charter of the Parliamentary Committee of European Integration N13/16, 10 December 2012.
2. Constitution of Georgia.
3. Decree of the President of Georgia "On Setting up the EU Cooperation Coordination Council" №150; 23 April 2001.
4. Decree of the President of Georgia "On the Introduction of the Office of the State Minister in the Government of Georgia" №61; 14 February 2004.
5. Decree of the President of Georgia "On the Promotion of the Implementation of Partnership and Cooperation between Georgia and the EU", 24 July 2000, №317.
6. Edict of the Government of Georgia "On Setting up the EU Integration Commission" №76, 10 July 2004.
7. Edict of the President of Georgia "On Development of the Strategy on Approximation of Georgian Legislation to that of EU" №1422; 31 December 2000.
8. Edict of the President of Georgia "On the Strategy of Harmonization of Georgian Legislation with that of the EU" №613; 14 June 2001.
9. Law of Georgia on Normative Acts, №1876–IIs; 22 October 2009.
10. Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia "On Acceleration of the full integration of Georgian to the EU" №2026–IIs; 28 March 2003.
11. Resolution of the Parliament of Georgia "On the Harmonization of Georgian Legislation with that of the EU", 02 September 1997, №828-Is.
12. Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, №3353, 25 March 2004.
13. Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, №6533-Is, 22 June 2012.

Online resources

1. A Security Europe in a Better World; European Security Strategy; Brussels, 12 December 2003.
<http://www.google.ge/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CBwQFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.consilium.europa.eu%2Fen%2Fdocuments-publications%2Fpublications%2F2009%2Fpdf%2F-european-security-strategy-secure-europe-better->

world%2F&ei=daVZVef0DIroywPA2YCAAQ&usg=AFQjCNGrbG73NuMaCslVWb4TJ-bZEPBdHg&bvm=bv.93564037,d.bGQ

2. Communication from the Commission to the Council; European Neighborhood Policy; Recommendations for Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and for Egypt and Lebanon; Brussels, 2.03.2005.
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/external_relations/relations_with_third_countries/eastern_europe_and_central_asia/r14103_en.htm

3. Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area.
<http://www.economy.ge/ge/dcfta>

4. EU-Georgia Association Agenda.
http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/eap_aa/association_agenda_2014_ka.pdf

5. European Neighborhood and Partnership Instrument Georgia; Country Strategy Paper 2007-2013. <http://www.enpi-info.eu/library/content/georgia-country-strategy-paper-2007-2013>

6. General Affairs and External Relations Council, Conclusions; Brussels, 26 January 2004.
http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/eu_georgia/council_recommended_to_ec_on_the_relationship_of_georgia_am_azer_to_enp.pdf

7. General Affairs and External Relations; Press Release; Council of the European Union; Provisional Version; Luxembourg, 14 June 2004.
http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/eu_georgia/council_decision_on_the_inclusion_of_georgia_armenia_and_azerbaijan_in_the_enp.pdf

8. Georgia-EU Cooperation; Office of the Minister of Georgia on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration. <http://www.eu-nato.gov.ge/ge/eu/cooperation>

9. Joint Declaration of the Prague Eastern partnership Summit; Brussels, 7 May 2009.
http://www.consilium.europa.eu/uedocs/cms_data/docs/pressdata/en/er/107589.pdf

10. Office of the State Minister of Georgia on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, <http://www.eu-nato.gov.ge/en>

11. Questions and answers regarding Association Agreement/DCFTA
http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/news/2014/20140325_01_ka.pdf

12. "The European Union and Georgia portrait of a partnership".
http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/georgia/documents/brochures/eu_georgia_en.pdf

Copyright©Giorgi GETSADZE

External Border Cooperation through International Work Contracts

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ion BURUIANĂ

ionburuiianac@yahoo.com

International Relations Institute of Moldova, Moldova
ECSA-Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to analyze the legal framework concerning EU external border cooperation, particularly through work contracts. This paper is based on a study of various legal provisions in order to explore the main legal tools applicable to cooperation in various programmes.

Key-words: EU external border cooperation, international work contracts, European Union and the governments of partner countries, "EC Practical Guide for Contract Procedures for EC External Actions" (PRAG).

The European Union and the governments of partner countries benefit from external border cooperation through the creation of the legal framework, capable for promotion of shared political and economic values and European cooperation methods and prosperity on the border regions of various countries.

The cooperation is based on equal partnership of the parties, the responsibility and benefits remaining at the regional level. Thus, in order to increase commitment to cooperation a various countries and its administrative regions participating in ENPI CBC programmes are encouraged to make their financial contribution.

It is forh mentioning that the territorial cooperation commenced with providing technical assistance, but the experience has proved that this cooperation should be implemented on rules developed for cooperation. Therefore, it is established the proper legislative environment for each budgetary period for external border CBC, which is based on the Neighborhood Programmes.

In the case of indicative programmes adopted under the European Community's technical assistance as provided for in the Council Regulations No 2157/91 of July 1991, No 2053/93 of 19 July 1993 and No 1279/96 of 25 June 1996 the European Communities entered into an international

agreement with respective countries on general rules applicable to technical assistance of the European Communities.

By this kind of agreements the implied parties set up the general technical legal and administrative rules for executing particular projects (which is implemented by a work contract) financed in the respective country under the European Community's technical assistance. The specific details of a specific project may be set out in a Financing Memorandum to be agreed between implied parties. Each project covered under these General Rules is implemented in accordance with the general clauses of them, which are deemed incorporated in each Financing Memorandum.

For matters related to the particular projects covered by both international agreements, i.e. General Rules and Financing Memorandum are represented by the Head of the European Union Delegation accredited to the said country, who shall ensure on behalf of European Commission and in close coordination with the relevant authorities of respective country that projects are implemented in accordance with financially and technically sound management practices.

For the matters relating to the projects covered by these international agreements the Government of said country shall be represented by the National Coordinator, who usually the ministry of economic relations is.

Concerning the funding of projects the amount of each "EU Grant" is laid down in each Financing Memorandum, which shall determine the limit for financial commitment and execution of the payment on the basis of duly approved work contracts. The European Commission may make disbursements of the funds to directly to the contractor or in the case of execution on the basis of work programmes in the form of advances transferred to a specially designated project account from which payments to contractors are made on behalf of the Commission or of the EU Delegation to the implied state, under the supervision of the Commission.

Work contracts are deemed to be technical assistance contracts which shall be concluded following restricted invitation to tender or through a direct agreement procedure.

Work contracts shall be drawn up, negotiated and concluded either by Commission or by the beneficiary country or the authority indicated by

the Government and acting on its behalf. In the last case the contracts are endorsed by the Commission.

When contracting abroad, companies shall take into consideration legal and practical issues involved by this kind of contracts.

The first issue relates to the legal compliance and identifies the various sources of potentially applicable law, because knowledge of the laws that will apply to the work or the transaction is crucial to fully understand the potential liabilities rights, and obligations associated with performing work in the foreign jurisdiction. Work contracts are well elaborated and include standard clause provided in “EC Practical Guide for Contract Procedures for EC External Actions” (PRAG). The Practical Guide provides standard contract forms, which are periodically renewed. The PRAG contains general conditions to be taken into consideration when entering the work contracts. It may include a choice-of-law clause specifying the substantive law governing the interpretation of the contract documents; local laws will also affect various aspects of the contract.

It can be difficult to determine not only what kind of permits are required, bur also who has jurisdiction to issue the necessary permit.

Thus, general conditions allocate the responsibility of obtaining such permits to the Contracting Authority in order to minimize any confusion regarding responsibility for necessary permits, especially in jurisdiction without clearly articulated or established laws, as for example in the post-soviet countries.

The Contracting Authority is responsible to take any measures in order to obtain licenses and permits prior to performing work. These may include construction-related permits, permits to import certain goods and materials, permits to specific types of works, environmental approvals.

The work contracts contain record-keeping and accounting requirements against corrupt practices. Thus, it is prohibited for foreign companies from bribing officials in order to influence any official act, secure an advantage, or obtain business.

A main treat of the contract finances or co-financed out of the EU Grant is that they shall not be subject to any duties, taxes or fiscal charges having equivalent effect. Furthermore, foreign legal persons and citizens, taking part in the European Commission financed projects shall be exempt

from payment of income tax, value added tax and analogous indirect taxes on receipts arising from the EU Grant.

They may also contain provision that exempt the applicability of certain laws that would otherwise apply to foreign companies doing business in signatory countries.

According to General Rules applicable to the technical assistance of the European Union, they provide the opportunity to foreign citizens to be assigned to a cross-border project. They are exempted from paying beneficiary countries income taxes on salaries.

The foreign earned income exemption allows qualified individuals to exempt foreign earned income.

These bilateral agreements also regulate other practical and legal concerns.

Cross-border projects often have restriction on procuring materials and permanent equipment that are not applicable to projects in the beneficiary countries.

This kind of projects requires materials to meet European Commission requirements and require use of the Union European or beneficiary sources or suppliers. It is to be used EC procurement procedures as stated in the PRAG.

Cross-border projects involve added levels of complexity due to the interaction of differing legal, financial and commercial systems and practices and therefore the need of selecting the form of business organization is obvious.

Firstly, construction firms may use of own organization or entity using the most common options available as representative offices, liaison offices, and branch offices. These structures permit to construction firms to operate in a beneficiary (foreign) country without establishing a separate entity in the host country. Most common option for international projects financed by European Commission is a brunch office because a representative or liaison office does not operate as an office conducting the same full scope of business activities that a branch office would conduct. In

many jurisdictions, representative or liaison offices are prohibited from conducting operational of income-generating activities¹.

Secondly, a construction firms also have the option to choose one of the many forms of collaborative business relationships (CBRs) to adopt in connection with a cross-border project. The most common collaborative relationships for this kind of projects is Consortium because it is the simplest method by which parties may agree to associate as independent contractors rather than as shareholders in a company or partners in a legal partnership. Consortiums are generally formed through a consortium agreement among the parties in the consortium group. It provides the rights and responsibilities between respective parties.

European Commission issues periodically renewed Practical Guide for Contract Procedures for EC External Actions, which provide general conditions on entering in technical assistance contracts. This Guide is fair and balanced risk allocation to all parties. Taking into consideration that each project is unique and will require specific terms and conditions, Special Conditions are incorporated of the particular technical assistance contract. This Guide contemplates an independent engineer to monitor the work of the contractor and to keep the balance between the parties. The engineer is able to make any determination in order to settle arisen between the parties' technical disputes quickly and expeditiously. However, it is required specific approval of the Contracting Authority and Funding Agency, including when ruling on the existence of unforeseeable conditions, issuing change orders, or approving the contractor's change proposal. The conditions of the technical assistance contracts require that any dispute to be referred to the engineer and if an amicable settlement is not attempted, the raised question is referred to a Dispute Adjudication Board, as a precondition to arbitration.

The European contract form addresses most of the significant provisions of the technical assistance contracts. Due to the consistent formatting and organization, contract form references to specific clauses, unless otherwise stated. Time for completion is defined as a period set out in the particular conditions and constitute a deadline by which the contractor

¹ Wendy Kennedy Venoit, Artur D. Brannan et al. (eds). *International Construction Law: A Guide for Cross-Border Transactions and Legal Disputes*, pp. 73-79.

is required to complete all the work. According to the conditions of the technical assistance contracts Time of Completion begins on the “Commencement Date”, which must occur within a specified time after the award of the contract; otherwise, the contractor may incur escalation of the labor and material prices above and beyond the prices submitted in the bid. There is an excusable delay provision setting out the circumstances entitling the contractor to an extension of the Time for Completion. The contractor is entitled to extension of time in case of force majeure, unforeseen conditions, suspensions ordered, or other matter specifically mentioned in the contract.

In the PRAG a significant attention is dedicated to force majeure provisions. “Force Majeure” is defined as an exceptional event or circumstance that is beyond a party’s control could not have been reasonably provided against before the contract was made or reasonably avoided or overcome during the course of the work, and prevents the affected party from performing its obligation under the contract. The extent of force majeure relief includes an extension of time as well as entitlement to payment of costs under certain circumstances.

Escalation clauses and adjustments to the contract price are provided for in the technical assistance contracts. The adjustment mechanism is a “two-way” variation clause that allows for increases and decreases in cost, and not only escalations¹.

The PRAG refers a treatment of differing site conditions. Upon encountering differing site conditions, the contractor is to notify the Supervisor (Engineer) and Contracting Authority in writing promptly and before performing additional work. To constitute a differing site conditions, the condition must be (1) a “physical” condition other than climatic conditions or an artificial obstruction, and (2) something that could not have been reasonably foreseen at the date of the contract. Provisions of the contract require the contractor to conduct reasonable due diligence to have obtained necessary information on all matters including the site and sub-surface conditions.

Concerning price and payment provisions the parties to the contract can include the use of fixed or lump-sum prices, reimbursable costs plus a

¹ Deborah DeMasi, Kenneth B. Weiner. *Construction Contracts*, p. 172.

fee, and a combination of these provisions. The “Contract Price” is defined as that amount either defined by the parties in particular conditions of the contract or that amount calculated by Supervisor’s measurement and determination of quantities of inputs. Under a remeasurement contract, the supervisor will measure the net actual quantity of each item specified in the “Bill of Quantities”.

There are several provisions that provide additional clarity to certain assumptions relating to the scope and finality of the Contract price. The Contract Price is stated to not include taxes and duties. The contractor is not responsible for paying taxes and therefore, the Contract Price remains unchanged even if the taxes are changed after the date of the contract¹.

The Funding Agency has 45 days to pay after receipt of the invoice accompanied by documentation of performed work. Interest accrues on late payments at an interest rate to be specified in the contract from the time the payment is late.

One of primary obligations of the contractor is to have the work completed, tested, and accepted by the Contracting Authority on or before the time of completion; otherwise the contractor is responsible for liquidated damages.

The latter is an agreed upon stipulated sum of money representing a genuine pre-estimated of damages that the Contracting Authority (owner) would suffer due to the delay. In practice, however, the amount of damages required to fully compensate an owner for losses will be different for each project, and may be subject to a maximum, or in some cases a reduction, and may be specifically provide for an aggregate maximum cup of the contractor’s liability for liquidated damages expressed as a percentage of the Contract Price.

If the owner were to be in breach of its obligations resulting in termination of the contract, the owner has to pay the contractor the same amount of the liquidated damages.

The duration of liability is not limited under conditions of the technical assistance contracts, and therefore left to determination under the law of the jurisdiction of the work.

¹ Geoff Powell. *Construction Contract Preparation and Management: From Concept to Completion*, p. 37.

Contractors will provide to the owner assurance with respect to the quality of the work performed as well as warranties for a defined period after the date that the owner takes the work from the contractor. These warranties cover the construction as well as engineering design to the extent that this was part of the contractor's responsibilities. To facilitate the performance of the contractor's warranty obligation, the owner is required to notify the contractor of any defects or damages. Where the defect or damage is found to result from the fault of the contractor, then such work shall be carried out at the contractor's risk and cost, otherwise the contractor shall be entitled to compensation by way of a change order.

The PRAG also provides for a final certificate to evidence the end of the Defect Notification Period. While the Performance Certificate evidences acceptance of the work by the owner, it does not prevent claims from subsequently being made with respect to any unfulfilled obligations as of the date of the Performance Certificate or undiscovered defects or damages.

The PRAG entitles the supervisor (engineer) to initiate a change or variation order either by instruction or a request for a proposal from the contractor. Variation may include changes to the quantity of an item of work, changes to the quality or other characteristics. Variation cannot remove work from the scope of the work and must not constitute unrelated work. The contractor has a right to object to a Change requested where the aggregate effect of the change combined with prior changes would be to increase or decrease the original contract price by more than 15%.

PRAG address the rights of the owner and the contractor, respectively, to terminate or take other remedial action under the contract. The contractor is entitled to suspend or reduce progress if the owner fails to pay, fails to approve an invoice, or commit a substantial breach of the contract.

The owner required to return any performance security to the contractor and provide compensation for work performed and demobilization costs. In addition, the owner is obliged to pay to the contractor the amount of any loss of profit or any other loss or damage sustained by the contractor as a result of such termination.

The PRAG establishes the procedures dealing with submission and substantiation of claims by the contractor and the conduct of any dispute

resolution between the parties. Dispute resolution provision involves amicable settlement of dispute, the Dispute Adjudication Board (DAB) and arbitration.

Before proceeding to DAB, the parties are encouraged to attempt to settle the dispute amicably. The Funding Agency assists the parties in order to settle amicably arisen disputes. If this fails, either party gives a notice of the dispute to refer to the Dispute Adjudication Board and arbitration.

Given that the failure to submit timely claim results in the discharge of the owner from liability, the contractor should act diligently in the submission of claims as the project progresses. Claims by the owner against contractor require the owner to provide to the contractor notice as soon as practicable after it becomes aware of the event or circumstances giving rise to the claim¹.

The PRAG contains provisions for a Dispute Adjudication Board (DAB) to assist the project in resolving disputes that arise. The DAB has specific powers and issues binding decisions. It is considered an appropriate mean to assist in the settlement of disputes without forcing the parties to consider litigation as their first option.

The DAB must be constituted under amicable settlement of dispute failed. A dispute may be referred to the DAB-based on a challenge to the supervisor's determination, challenge to the owner's decision or a claim by the parties.

Once the DAB is charging with hearing the matter both parties are to furnish the DAB with all information and access to the site and appropriate facilities as required by the DAB for the purpose of making decision. The DAB is required to render a decision, with reasons, and such decision is binding, unless revised through an arbitral award.

Any party that is dissatisfied with the DAB decision may provide the other party with a notice, setting out the details of why it is dissatisfied. If the dispute is not settled amicably, the interested party may proceed to arbitration. Moreover, failure to give effect to a final and binding DAB decision entitles the party to invoke arbitration.

If there is no DAB in place, due to the failure of a party to cooperate in forming the DAB the matter can proceed directly to arbitration.

¹ William Codwin. *International Construction Contracts: A Handbook*, p. 93.

Work contracts in EC technical assistance domain set out the procedures applicable to arbitration. Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, arbitration before a panel of three arbitrators will be conducted under Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) or under Rules of Arbitration of the Stockholm Chamber of Commerce (SCC). The arbitrators are vested with the full power to open up, review, and revise any certificate, determination, instruction, opinion, or valuation of the owner and any decision of the DAB that is relevant to the dispute.

Bibliography:

1. Codwin William. *International Construction Contracts: A Handbook*, Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell, 2013.
2. DeMasi Deborah, Weiner Kenneth B. *Construction Contracts*, Huntington: Juris Publishing, 2011.
3. Powell Geoff. *Construction Contract Preparation and Management: From Concept to Completion*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012.
4. Venoit Wendy Kennedy, Brannan Artur D. et al. (eds). *International Construction Law: A Guide for Cross-Border Transactions and Legal Disputes*, ABA Book Publishing, 2009.

Copyright©Ion BURUIANĂ

ECONOMIE / ECONOMICS

EU Smart Growth: Achievements, Challenges and Perspectives

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Rodica CRUDU

rodika.krudu@gmail.com

Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: In the context in which smart growth is a must to compete in the nowadays global market, the European Union, through its Europe 2020 strategy, decided to become a smart, sustainable, and inclusive economy. These three mutually reinforcing priorities will help the EU and Member States to deliver high levels of employment, productivity and social cohesion. The present article focuses its analysis on the “smart” side of the strategy. Therefore, this paper fills this gap by investigating the achievements, drawbacks and perspectives of EU Member States towards Europe 2020 strategy targets in the field of smart growth.

Key-words: Europe 2020 strategy, targets, Member States, research and development, innovation, labour productivity, tertiary education, information and communication technologies, broadband.

Introduction

The economic and financial crisis on the scale of recent years determined the European Union (EU) to elaborate an immediate and strong policy response against a background of lower growth and productivity levels than in other developed countries and a rapidly deteriorating economic and social environment in the wake of the worst global financial crisis the EU has ever faced. All the attempts of the EU and Member States’ institutions to rescue their economies made it clear that the “short-term priority (was) a successful exit from the crisis”, but “to achieve a sustainable future” the EU needed “to tackle its structural weaknesses” and “already look beyond the short-term”. The ambition was to “come out stronger from the crisis and turn the EU into a smart, sustainable and inclusive economy, delivering high levels of employment, productivity and social cohesion”¹. Therefore, in 2010, Europe 2020 Strategy was launched as the EU’s strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. It drew the lessons from the Lisbon Strategy for growth and jobs, which was launched in 2000, renewed

¹ COM(2010)2020. Europe 2020: A European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. 3 March 2010.

in 2005 and was in place until 2010. The Europe 2020 Strategy was conceived as a partnership between the EU and its Member States, with a set of goals focused around the priorities of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, and a dedicated delivery system. The main objective of the strategy is to foster the EU's competitiveness while maintaining its social market economy model and improving significantly its resource efficiency. Thus, the Europe 2020 Strategy launched a growth model that goes beyond increasing GDP, promoting smart, sustainable and inclusive growth as a crucial element of economic development. Table 1 shows the interrelated headline targets for the EU to achieve by 2020 in these three key priorities (i.e. smart, sustainable and inclusive growth).

The targets were not exhaustive but considered exemplary of the kind of dynamic change advocated in the strategy (Table 1). To catalyse progress at EU level, the Commission set out seven flagship initiatives, which included specific work programmes in areas identified as important levers for growth. The first three flagship initiatives were set out specifically to meet smart growth targets. In addition, the strategy has served as a frame of reference for action at EU level in the areas of the Single Market, the EU budget for 2014-2020 and the EU's external policy agenda. Nevertheless, we shall concentrate on the analysis of EU performances in the field of smart growth rather than in other directions, even if most of the launched initiatives and targets are interrelated. However, before assessing the smart growth performances, it should be cleared out what it means.

According to Europe 2020 strategy¹, smart growth means improving the EU's performance in:

- research / innovation (creating new products / services that generate growth and jobs and help address social challenges);
- education (encouraging people to learn, study and update their skills);
- digital society (using information and communication technologies).

¹ EC. Europe 2020 in a nutshell: Smart growth.

Table 1

The Europe 2020 strategy's key priorities, headline targets and flagship initiatives

	Targets	Flagship initiatives
Smart Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 % of GDP to be invested in the research and development (R&D) sector; - Reduce the rates of early school leaving to below 10 %, and at least 40 % of 30 to 34 year olds to have completed tertiary or equivalent education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Innovation Union ✓ Youth on the move ✓ A digital agenda for Europe
Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 20 % compared to 1990 levels. - Increase the share of renewables in final energy consumption to 20 %; - 20 % increase in energy efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Resource efficient Europe ✓ An industrial policy for the globalization era
Inclusive Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % of 20 to 64 year old men and women to be employed. - Reduce poverty by lifting at least 20 million people out of the risk of poverty and social exclusion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ An agenda for new skills and jobs ✓ European platform against poverty and social exclusion

Source: Adapted by the author according to European Commission, Europe 2020 — A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, COM(2010) 2020 final, Brussels, 2010.

As the crisis spread and took on new forms, a particular challenge for the EU was to break the vicious circle between rising levels of sovereign debt, contagious financial instability and low or even negative growth. That is why a taking stock of the Europe 2020 strategy is more than necessary. Moreover, analysis of the achieved performances and still existing drawbacks can help to draw up viable perspectives.

In the context of that mentioned above, the main objective of the present article is on the analysis and identification of the main achievements

of EU, in general, and its Member States, in particular, in comparison with what was, and the progress made in meeting the established targets. Therefore, this paper fills this gap by investigating the achievements, drawbacks and perspectives of EU Member States towards Europe 2020 strategy targets in the field of smart growth. In order to accomplish the stated objective and the aims mentioned above, the structure of the paper correlates with the main indicators used to assess “smart” progress. The first section will focus on the analysis of the role of R&D and innovation in addressing the European economic and social challenges. Education and training lie at the heart of the Europe 2020 strategy and are seen as key drivers for growth and jobs, that is why the second section of the present paper highlights the main achievements and barriers faced by the EU in meeting the second objective of the Europe 2020 Strategy target (see table 1). The usage of information and communication technologies by EU Member States and the main barriers encountered by them to achieve the stated targets in the field of digital society represent the object of research of the third section of the present paper. Presentation of the main findings and conclusions are subject to be included in the final section.

Research and development (R&D) and innovation target

Investment in R&D and innovation by fostering an increase or substantial improvement in the quality of innovative goods and services, contributes to the strategy’s smart growth objective, creating jobs and addressing societal challenges. By paving the way towards increased industrial competitiveness, labour productivity and the efficient use of resources, they are also at the heart of sustainable growth. As widely documented in the economic literature, research and innovation play a critical role in determining the economic performance of countries and regions. Innovation, understood in the broad sense to include product, process, market and organizational innovation, is identified as one of the major engines of economic growth, employment and ecological sustainability and accordingly is of critical importance for social progress as well as prosperity. In particular, innovation is an important driver of long-run productivity growth and, as such, is crucial for maintaining the competitiveness of firms over their rivals. This is particularly true for firms in Europe, which more and more compete with firms located in less developed parts of the world and in emerging economies. These are not only catching

up fast in terms of technology but they also continue to benefit from lower labour costs due in part to different standards in the organisation of the labour market, a lack of social protection for workers and lower income expectations, though low labour costs are offset to some extent by lower productivity. From this perspective, innovation, as well as the capacity to assimilate innovation produced elsewhere, can be regarded as an important condition for maintaining the specific features of the European social model.

The steady growth of labor productivity between 2000 and 2007 was blocked by the economic downturn in 2008 and 2009. Although productivity recovered in 2010 and continued to grow in the next years (achieving at the end of 2012 - 32.2 Euro per worked hour), the long-term improvement depends on future labor market adjustments. These could include changes in the flow of workers between countries, sectors and regions and adaptability to different wage labor market conditions.

The analysis of productivity among EU Member States highlights, on the one hand, that in 2013, Luxembourg, Denmark and Ireland had the most efficient workers, producing 58.2, 52.7 and 50.4 euros per hour, respectively. On the other hand, labor productivity in 11 Member States was less than 20 euros per hour (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Labour productivity in EU- 27 (Euro per worked hour)

Source: Elaborated by the author according to Eurostat data (Code: tsdec310)

However, the economies of Central and South-Eastern Europe experienced sharp increases in labor productivity between 2000 and 2012: Latvia (107%), Romania (90%), Lithuania (84%), Estonia (60%) and Slovakia (57%).

Significant divergence in productivity rates among EU member states could be treated as an important structural weakness. Internal and external structural adjustment programs, such as limiting unsustainable residential investment and improving export performance have been implemented in a number of countries such as Ireland, Greece, Spain, Cyprus, Portugal and Slovenia. In these countries, wage increases did not match the level of productivity growth before the crisis. Thus, it is expected that these measures will rebalance labor productivity, boost competitiveness and improve economic performance¹.

The benefits would be larger in the peripheric countries due to a larger scope for reform but also to positive spill-overs from the Euro-area core. Enhancing the quality of human capital, the performance of research, education and training systems and their capacity to foster innovation is also a key to foster productivity. Europe's ageing and shrinking working age population makes it even more pressing to boost productivity gains as a source of growth.

Fore sure modern electronic communications and online services, including e-government, are important economic sectors in their own right but they are also crucial levers of growth and productivity for the economy as a whole.

One of the factors that could drive EU Member States' economies into efficient ones is the investment in R&D and innovation. However, lower investment in and use of ICT in Europe account for a large part of the labour productivity gap between the EU and the US. EU investment in state-of-the-art communications infrastructure is also lagging behind that of its main competitors, especially as regards mobile infrastructure. The average mobile data speed in the EU is half of that of the US², and Europe has only 6% of the world's 4G mobile subscriptions. In South Korea, 58% of households are connected by fiber to the home, but only 5% in Europe³. In the new, data-based economy, European companies are almost absent from the value chain.

¹ European Commission, European Economic Forecast, p. 25.

² IMF. Jobs and Growth: Supporting European Recovery.

³ Cf. Eurostat. Smarter, greener, more inclusive? Indicators to support the Europe 2020 Strategy.

These investments will foster the increase or substantial improvement in the quality of innovative goods and services, will contribute to the strategy's smart growth objective, will create jobs and address societal challenges.

In particular, the "Innovation Union" flagship initiative is the European Union strategy that aims to create an innovation-friendly environment for EU researchers and entrepreneurs that makes it easier for great ideas to be turned into products and services.

Thus, R&D and innovation contribute to a well-functioning, knowledge-based economy. The well-being of the EU's population also depends on scientific and technical solutions being found to global societal challenges such as climate change and clean energy, security, and active and healthy ageing.

One of the main indicators for assessing investment in innovation is the level of national expenditure on research and development (R&D). Technical progress is to a large extent driven by R&D activities and expenditure on R&D indicates the effort devoted by the public sector and firms to generate innovations and new market opportunities. The role played by R&D in supporting key engines of growth has made it a headline target objective of the Europe 2020 Strategy; specifically that expenditure on R&D in the EU should reach 3% of GDP by 2020. According to the latest data available, expenditure on R&D in the EU-28 amounted to 2.02% of GDP in 2013 (Figure 2). The reasons for the increase between 2007 and 2009 include GDP falling more rapidly than overall R&D expenditure and the actions taken by individual EU Member States to step up public R&D investment. However, there is wide variation around the average with EU Member States. (Figure 2)

In 2013 R&D expenditure ranged from 0.48 % to 3.32 % across the EU. Northern European countries such as Finland and Sweden not only share a pattern of high expenditure, they also have the most ambitious national targets. In 2013, Denmark achieved its national target of 3 % and Germany came very close to meeting its target. Countries with lower R&D expenditure levels, below 1 % there were mostly in Eastern and Southern Europe, for instance Romania, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Malta and Greece. Of these countries, Cyprus came closest to its national target. It is worth to be mentioned that each country established its own targets regarding the R&D

expenditure. Finland and Sweden, which already have achieved the Europe 2020 target, established even a higher target for expenditure on R&D, 4% of their GDP. National targets of Denmark and Germany are 3%. Austria, even if the current achievements are lower than those registered by Denmark and Germany, established a higher national target – 3,76%. Cyprus, Slovakia and Greece set the lowest national targets, 0,5%, 1,2% and 1,21% respectively. Czech Republic established national target only for public sector – 1%, but UK has not national target in this field.

Figure 2. Gross domestic expenditure on R&D, by sector of performance, EU-28, 2013 (% of GDP)

Source: Elaborated by the author according to Eurostat data (online data code: t2020_20)

However, when assessing a Member State's prospect to reach its national R&D intensity target, the level of R&D intensity should be

complemented by data on trends over the last decade, to be compared to the rate of progress required to meet the national target. On that basis, the following groups of Member States can be identified:

1) Member States that have already reached or will soon achieve their national target: Slovenia, Cyprus, Denmark and Germany. This group includes both MS with high R&D intensities (Denmark and Germany) and with very low R&D intensity (Cyprus). All of these MS had set their target at a level which was well within their reach given their national context, but in some cases lacked ambition.

2) Member States that are on track to reach their target based on their average rate of progress over the period 2000-2012; Estonia, Hungary and Ireland are in such a situation. If we look to the rate of progress over 2007-2012, remarkable acceleration in Poland, Slovakia and to some extent Belgium put them also in this category.

3) Member States which need to raise their rate of increase in R&D intensity to reach their target: Austria, Finland, France, Italy, the Netherlands and Spain. While these Member States are currently not on track to reach their national target, their required effort (i.e. difference between the rate of increase required and their long-term trend) is lower than or comparable to EU average (3.9 %).

4) Member States that need to substantially raise their rate of increase in R&D intensity to reach their target and whose required efforts exceed EU average: Bulgaria, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta and Romania. In this group, Member States have set very ambitious national targets with regard both to starting levels and past trends. As a result, the required rates of increase far exceed EU average.

5) Member States which need to reverse a decreasing trend in R&D intensity: Sweden, Luxembourg, Portugal and Croatia.

6) Member States which have not set an R&D intensity target: UK and the Czech Republic. The latter has set a public R&D intensity target at just 1 % of GDP.

The analysis of expenditures on R&D by sectors, highlights the two sectors with the highest expenditure on R&D in Europe: business enterprise sector, which made up 63.8 % (EUR 174.4 billion), and higher education sector, which made up 23.2 % (EUR 63.4 billion) of total R&D expenditure in 2013. With a more modest 12.2 % (EUR 33.4 billion) the government sector

plays an important role, especially in terms of long-term stability of R&D expenditure. The importance of private non-profit sector is negligible, spending less than 1 % of the total (EUR 2.3 billion).

When the financial and economic crisis hit Europe in 2008, some EU Member States such as Germany, Austria and the Nordic countries boosted public R&D expenditure to stimulate economic growth and encourage private R&D investment, which remains the largest source of R&D expenditure¹.

In comparison, R&D expenditure of the business sector fell by 3.4 % between 2008 and 2009. During an economic crisis businesses usually decrease their R&D expenditure. However, R&D spending actually started to rise again after 2009 with growth rates of 4.2 % and 7.4 % in 2010 and 2011 and more moderate rates of 4.3 % and 1.9 % in 2012 and 2013 respectively. These rates were still below pre-crisis levels of 7.9 % in 2006 and 6.5 % in 2007. In some countries (Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Cyprus and Greece), R&D effort relies predominantly on the public sector (higher education and government). This indicates conditions for business R&D investment are still insufficiently attractive². Private non-profit sector trends show a succession of ups and downs.

All the efforts towards Europe 2020 Strategy targets in the field of R&D and innovation are supported by the EU's biggest EU research and innovation programme ever – Horizon 2020. It follows up on the previous EU research framework programmes, which were implemented in 1984 and provided funding for a total of almost EUR 120 000 million of wide-ranging research projects up to 2013.

With EUR 78.6 billion (current prices) of funding available for the seven-year period from 2014 to 2020, Horizon 2020 is the financial instrument implementing the 'Innovation Union' in the EU. It focuses on three priorities³:

- Generating excellent science to strengthen the Union's world-class excellence in science;

¹ European Commission, Innovation Union Competitiveness Report 2013, p.38

² Ibidem, p.39

³ Cf. Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 — the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014–2020).

- Fostering industrial leadership to support business, including micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and innovation;
- Tackling societal challenges to respond directly to the challenges identified in the Europe 2020 Strategy by supporting activities covering the entire spectrum from research to market.

Horizon 2020 aims to achieve the Europe 2020 ambitions for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth and jobs. The goal is to ensure that Europe produces world-class science, removes barriers to innovation and makes it easier for the public and private sectors to work together to deliver innovation.

The biggest part of the Horizon 2020 budget, 37.7 %, representing EUR 29.7 billion is devoted to tackling societal challenges in the field of environment (including climate change), energy, transport, health and demographic changes, and security. Almost one-third (31.1 %) of the budget is allocated to bringing about excellence in science, namely through the European Research Council. Another 21.6 % is devoted to increasing industrial leadership, in particular in enabling and industrial technologies such as information and communication technology (ICT), nanotechnologies and space. The European Institute of Innovation and Technology and Euratom — the research funding programme for the peaceful use of nuclear energy in the EU — receive 3.4 % and 2.0 % of the funding respectively.

While EU funding seeks to target all countries, an innovation divided across Europe's members remains. There appears to be a national innovation paradox, whereby those countries characterized by established innovative activity maintain their position as innovative leaders (such as the Nordic countries), while those that trail behind fail to catch up, despite efforts to target these countries for funding and policy prescriptions¹.

According to the European Commission's communication "Taking stock of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" with a level of 2.06% in 2012 and limited progress over time, the 3% target for 2020 is unlikely to be met. Investment in R&D is forecast to

¹ Cf. European Commission, Research and innovation statistics at regional level.

increase to 2.2% by 2020. If Member States meet their national targets, this share could amount to 2.6%¹.

Tertiary educational attainment towards Europe 2020 targets

Tertiary education, with its links to research and innovation, can help to provide the highly skilled human capital that the EU needs to create jobs, economic growth and improvements in social welfare². A well-educated workforce is a key to prosperity. It tends to be a strong correlation between the educational attainment of a region's workforce and median earnings in the region. In addition, attaining a relatively high education level tends to mean less risk of being unemployed. The share of people aged 25–64 with a high educational attainment level (i.e. with tertiary qualifications), however, varies significantly across countries.

Current skill mismatches are a threat to Europe's innovation capacity at a time of increasing technological needs (see also chapters on Employment and Education). Demand in Europe for highly qualified people is predicted to rise by almost 16 million in the period up to 2020³. In particular, the stock of human resources such as scientists, researchers and engineers is insufficient⁴, a situation which Horizon 2020 and the European Research Area (ERA) initiative attempt to improve by supporting researchers' careers and mobility and further facilitate the entry and stay of third-country researchers⁵.

Knowledge and skills are crucial for gaining new scientific and technological expertise and for building the economy's capacity to absorb and use this knowledge. R&D expenditure covers a substantial part of expenditure on skills and education and, therefore, constitutes a vital enabling factor for human capital. In this regard, the EU will need to train and employ at least one million new researchers compared with 2008 level if it is to reach the R&D target of 3 %.

¹ Cf. COM(2014) 130 final/2. Taking stock of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.

² Cf. European Commission (2012), Education and training monitor 2012.

³ Cf. European Commission, Researchers' report – Final report 2013, Brussels, 2013, p.26.

⁴ Cf. European Commission, Commission staff working document — A rationale for action accompanying the Europe 2020 Flagship Initiative Innovation Union, p.34.

⁵ COM(2012) 392 final. A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth, pp. 12-15, p.34.

In line with Europe’s declared intention to become the world’s most competitive science-based economy, a well-functioning research and innovation system is expected to promote excellence in education and skills development and ensure a sufficient supply of (post)graduates in science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

Between 2008 and 2012, the number of tertiary graduates in science and technology grew by 17.9 %, from 14.5 graduates per 1 000 inhabitants in 2008 to 17.1 graduates per 1 000 inhabitants in 2012. This trend varies considerably across EU Member States (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Tertiary graduates in science and technology by country, 2008 and 2012 (*) (Graduates per 1 000 inhabitants, 20 to 29 years old)

Source: Elaborated by the author according to the Eurostat data (online data code: tps00188)

In 2012, the number of science and technology graduates ranged from about 23 per 1 000 inhabitants in Lithuania to 9 per 1 000 inhabitants in Cyprus (Luxembourg being an exception with only 2.8 per 1 000 inhabitants). This gap has serious implications for labour mobility and the notion of an open EU labour market. All countries except Finland have increased their graduation from tertiary education rates since 2008. Between 2008 and 2012, Cyprus doubled its tertiary graduate rate, while the rate grew by more than 50 % in Hungary, Croatia, Slovenia and Malta.

In recent years, significant progress has been made and the EU has increased its stock of researchers. However, as already stated, it was estimated that in 2010 one million more researchers — an increase of more than 60 % — were still needed to meet the objective of 3 % R&D intensity by

2020. This figure takes into consideration the number of researchers who will retire and the existence of a persistent 'brain drain' from the EU to the United States¹.

EU digital society towards meeting Europe 2020 Strategy targets

Access to high capacity telecommunication networks is a key factor of competitiveness and economic growth. The provision of digital services and the capacity to operate successfully in a global business environment increasingly rely on fast and effective broadband connections.

ICT infrastructure is therefore a major determinant of the development potential of EU countries. Furthermore, ICT development and usage skills are a new driver for employment and R&D in Europe. The value added of the ICT sector, including information industries, accounted for 4 % of GDP in 2010. In addition, the sector represented 2.5 % of EU total employment while R&D personnel in ICT made up 20 % of total R&D personnel. In the same year, R&D intensity in the ICT sector amounted to 5.2 %². A number of EU policy strategies under the Europe 2020 strategy umbrella tackle the issue of ICT connectivity and skills at business and citizen levels and address knowledge circulation among the research community.

A large part of the EU's population is, however, still affected by a digital literacy deficit. The exclusion of many people from the digital knowledge-based society and economy is holding back the large multiplier effect that ICT take-up has on innovations and productivity growth. These skills do not only improve employability, they also enhance societal learning, creativity, emancipation and empowerment.

Infrastructure availability is vital to the process of diffusing the digital and knowledge-based economy into the very corners of society. Increased broadband internet access opportunities for private and business usage are an important enabling factor for this process. The share of European households and business with broadband internet access rose considerably between 2007 and 2013 in line with advances in the global internet, wider network coverage and increased affordability. Enterprises' usage of

¹ COM(2012) 392 final. A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth, p.15.

² European Commission, Innovation Union Scoreboard 2014, p.3.

broadband internet connections increased by 13 percentage points over the same period from 77 % to 90 %.

The extent of broadband coverage has increased significantly in the EU in recent years. In 2012, 96% of households in the EU-27 had access to at least one fixed broadband network, while, as regards wireless technologies, High Speed Packet Access (HSPA) is available to 95% of them and there is full coverage of high capacity KA-band satellite broadband in all but four Member States (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Sweden). However, coverage is much higher than take-up and in 2012 only around 70% of households with access (67% of the total) had a fixed broadband subscription.

Growth in access to ICT infrastructure is also reflected at Member States' level. Between 2007 and 2013 the share of both households and enterprises with broadband internet access increased in all countries. The only exception is enterprise access in Croatia, which fell by 3.8 %. In 2013, the share of household connectivity exceeded EU average in 11 Member States with rates ranging from 78 % in France to 88 % in Finland. The other 17 countries had lower access rates from 54 % in Bulgaria to 74 % in Slovenia. In general, the highest growth rates over the period 2007 to 2013 were mainly in Eastern and Southern European countries. Some of these, such as Romania and Greece, had access rates in 2013 that were about seven times higher than in 2007.

The main challenge in this field is that even if the gaps in the digital and transport networks are being filled and broadband availability is close to 100% in nearly all regions, the access to the next generation of links to the internet is largely limited to the most urbanized areas.

Therefore, increases in internet skills across the EU in general reflect connectivity improvements. Thus, it is not surprising that several Member States, such as Belgium, Ireland, Greece, Cyprus, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden and the United Kingdom, increased the share of people with advanced internet skills by close to or more than two times.

A dynamic business environment is essential for the promotion and diffusion of innovations. The challenge is to make use of R&D through entrepreneurship and creativity to trigger innovation and economic competitiveness. Therefore, measures targeting knowledge diffusion and absorption, for example, through the creation of technology markets and licensing schemes, are just as important as investment in knowledge

generation. The higher the uptake and use of ideas from R&D, the more likely those innovative players are to invest in future knowledge generation through increased private R&D expenditure.

Significant progress in achieving knowledge diffusion and absorption is measured through growth in innovative firms, the number of patent applications, the export of high-tech products and the number of patents related to societal challenges such as climate change.

The EU has become more innovative in recent years, rising from an innovation performance index of 0.493 in 2006 to 0.554 in 2013. As a result, the EU has decreased its innovation gap with the United States and Japan, although it still lags behind these countries and South Korea¹.

While all Member States have become more innovative, differences in innovation performances are still high and are diminishing only slowly. This is particularly visible in business innovation co-operation, and knowledge excellence and internationalization².

The overall ranking within the EU remains relatively stable. Four 'innovation leaders' include Sweden at the top, followed by Denmark, Germany and Finland. At the other end of the scale, 'modest innovators' are made up of three Eastern Member States. In between, two large groups of 11 'moderate innovators' and 10 'innovation followers' can be observed.

Portugal, Estonia and Latvia have shown the best improvement over the past few years. In these countries the index increased by more than 25 % between 2006 and 2013. The least progress was made by the innovation leader Sweden and the innovation follower UK. In these two countries the index has increased by a mere 0.02 points. Most progress achieved by countries lies in the openness and attractiveness of EU research system as well as business innovation collaboration and the commercialization of knowledge as measured by license and patent revenues from abroad. However, the growth of public R&D expenditure over the past few years has been offset by a continuous decline in venture capital investments and non-R&D innovation investments by companies.

Main challenges to meet Europe 2020 Strategy targets in the field of smart growth

¹ European Commission, Innovation Union Scoreboard 2014, p.5.

² Ibidem, p.6.

While a well-functioning research and innovation ecosystem is crucial to foster innovation-driven economic growth, the European Commission Annual Growth Survey identifies several challenges that could impede the emergence EU smart growth:

a) Non-attractive national research systems. Low salaries for researchers in universities and other public research institutions lead to a loss of attractiveness for domestic and foreign talent resulting eventually in brain drain. Recent cuts in public support to R&D in some Member States risk seriously damaging their research and innovation capacities and delaying the transformation of these countries into knowledge-based economies;

b) Non-efficient public research system. In a number of Member States, critical structural reforms are still required to increase the efficiency, effectiveness and excellence of their public research system. The Communication on a Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth adopted in July 2012 sets a common agenda defining the reforms of national research systems required to complete the European Research Area. These include for instance fair, open and transparent recruitment to academic positions and the allocation of research funding on a competitive basis;

c) Poor cooperation research institutions and businesses and inadequacy vis-à-vis their needs. While for some Member States, the urgency is to modernize their public research systems, others have excellent ones, but need to find ways to better harness this strength to create economic wealth. Thus, the needs to address the growing skills mismatches that are particularly affecting knowledge-intensive sectors and to foster public-private cooperation are more than crucial to identify. By identifying scientific and technological specializations consistent with each country or region's potential for the development of competitive economic activities, a smart specialization strategy is critical to maximize the economic impacts of public research funding, ensuring a leverage effect on private investments and thereby driving the transformation of our economies;

d) Poor match between supply- and demand-side measures. Public efforts to support knowledge supply will fail to bring the expected socio-economic benefits if they are not matched with demand-side measures (e.g.

product market regulation, innovative and pre-commercial procurement) as part of an integrated and comprehensive policy approach;

e) Inefficient public incentives to stimulate business R&D (e.g. grants, R&D tax incentives, measures to facilitate access to private funding). Another key aim of public R&D funding and indirect support measures is to give the business sector incentives to engage in more R&D activities;

f) Bottlenecks that restrict the growth of firms in innovative sectors. Only a very few Member States have so far adopted a truly systemic approach identifying the obstacles that need to be overcome to create a business environment in which innovative firms are more likely to grow.

Besides the mentioned above sector specific challenges, there are also some challenges regarding the achievement or progress assessment. Many quantified objectives and indicators exist at EU level to monitor performance over time, between countries and across policy areas. They were established in such a way as to better perform a quantitative assessment. But in the case of smart growth, a qualitative assessment remains necessary. That is why the analysis of these targets highlights, in some cases, their limits. The target on R&D is essentially an “input” target where the share of public and private expenditure is reported. That is why, as a complement to this target, the European Council requested, and the European Commission is developing, a complementary indicator also looking at innovation “outputs”¹. Likewise the targets on employment and education do not say much about the quality of the work occupied or the levels or adequacy of skills achieved. Moreover, averages at EU or national level often hide very significant age, gender or regional differences. Complementary indicators, more specific analysis as well as qualitative information, are thus important to interpret the targets and the actual situation in Member States. It is also important to bear in mind that some targets – such as education – are more directly within the realm of public authorities, while others – such as employment or spending on R&D – reflect broader economic trends.

However, the targets are illustrative of the dynamic change promoted by the Europe 2020 Strategy. Although the EU has no shortage of

¹ Cf. COM(2013) 624 final. *Measuring innovation output in Europe: towards a new indicator.*

indicators, the current set of targets has allowed for a sense of focus on the three dimensions of the smart, sustainable and inclusive growth model advocated by the strategy. In this respect, the targets express the longer-term direction necessary to sustain Europe's future and serve as benchmarks to guide policy. Moreover, they are closely interrelated and self-reinforcing with progress in one dimension feeding into progress in another. Another advantage is that they can be easily measured and monitored, thus helping to steer political awareness and policy focus at both national and EU level.

Conclusion

The present article has focused on the analysis of what happened in the framework of the Europe 2020 Strategy, relating more deeply to EU smart growth targets.

The EU is facing increasing competition but remains a main knowledge production center of the world, accounting for almost a third of the world's science and technology production. Over the past 30 years, Europe has supported wide ranging research projects developed by Member States, spending almost EUR 120 000 million by 2013. It will have another EUR 78.6 billion at its disposal for the period from 2014 to 2020. The EU's investment in R&D and innovation is increasingly targeted at supporting growth enhancing policies to strengthen its human capital and knowledge base. The EU increased its output of tertiary graduates in science and technology by 17.9 % between 2008 and 2012.

The EU also invested in developing its population's digital literacy and improving the ICT connectivity of both businesses and households. At the global level, even though the EU is an attractive location for R&D investment, it is still lagging behind its Asian and American competitors in terms of R&D expenditure, in particular by business enterprise.

The Europe 2020 Strategy tries to overcome the economic crisis and its impacts by addressing the shortcomings of the European growth model. It also attempts to create the conditions for a different type of growth through more effective investments in education, research and innovation. However, with a current level of 2.02 % in 2013 and limited progress over time, the R&D intensity is expected to remain below the 3 % objective that the EU has set itself for 2020.

Besides context-specific factors that influence R&D investment, the distance to the EU's target can be ascribed to various challenges that have not been yet fully overcome by the actions and instruments put in place by the European Union.

Bibliography:

1. COM(2010)2020. Europe 2020: A European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. 3 March 2010. <http://ec.europa.eu/eu2020/pdf/COMPLET%20EN%20BARROSO%20%20%20007%20-%20Europe%202020%20-%20EN%20version.pdf> [Accessed on 12 March 2015].
2. COM(2014) 130 final/2. Taking stock of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. Brussels, 19.3.2014. http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/europe2020stocktaking_en.pdf [Accessed on 30 March 2015].
3. COM(2012) 392 final. A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth. Brussels, 2012, pp. 12-15.
4. COM(2013) 800 final. Annual Growth Survey 2014. Brussels, 13.11.2013. http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/2014/ags2014_en.pdf.
5. COM(2013) 624 final. Measuring innovation output in Europe: towards a new indicator. Brussels, 13.9.2013. http://ec.europa.eu/research/press/2013/pdf/indicator_of_innovation_output.pdf [Accessed on 12 June 2015].
6. EC. Europe 2020 in a nutshell: Smart growth. http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/europe-2020-in-a-nutshell/priorities/smart-growth/index_en.htm [Accessed on 10 May 2015].
7. European Commission, European Economic Forecast, Spring 2013.
8. European Commission, Innovation Union Competitiveness Report 2013, Brussels 2013.
9. European Commission, Commission staff working document — A rationale for action accompanying the Europe 2020 Flagship Initiative Innovation Union. SEC(2010) 1161 final, Brussels, 2010.
10. European Commission, Innovation Union Scoreboard 2014, Brussels, 2014.
11. European Commission, Education and training monitor 2012. 2012.

12. European Commission, Researchers' report – Final report 2013, Brussels, 2013.
13. European Commission, Research and innovation statistics at regional level, Statistics Explained, Luxembourg, 2014.
14. European Commission (2013), Broadband lines in the EU, Communications Committee Working Document.
15. Eurostat. Smarter, greener, more inclusive? Indicators to support the Europe 2020 strategy. Eurostat statistical books. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2015.
16. IMF. Jobs and Growth: supporting European Recovery, 2014.
17. Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014–2020).

Copyright©Rodica CRUDU

Sustainable Development and Poverty in the Peripheries of Hungary

Prof. Dr. István SÜLI-ZAKAR

suli-zakar.istvan@science.unideb.hu

University of Debrecen, Hungary

Abstract: Sustainable development and poverty represent an antagonism: the first means those treasures, positive things, which are to be preserved (or built up). The latter means the intolerable reality is to be discontinued. As a consequence of their antagonism, we have to say both things are impossible to attain for a realistically-minded researcher, but this obstacle can't hinder our aims, ambitions to attempt reaching sustainable development and reducing of the pauperized people. The estimated number of Hungarian poor is 3.2 million. Almost half of this, but at least 1.5 million people in the working-age population has not got those abilities and possibilities, which can help them to maintain themselves. Sustainable development means we must make these people's world more human, with the creation of the opportunity to make a real difference and a viable future. Social geography and regional development play an important role in this human fight.

Key-words: poverty, sustainable development, rural areas, geographical periphery, pauperization.

Introduction. The Hungarian industrial revolution started in the second half of the 19th century, which caused the re-evaluation of the rural areas in Hungary. By the way the source of the development of the secondary sector was the rural areas of Hungary and the Hungarian agriculture (primary sector). The “granary of the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy” didn't show decreasing before 1918, but the Treaty of Trianon – after the collapse of the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy – brought to light spectacularly. The rural areas of Hungary lost their foreign markets and became the “country of three million beggars”. At that time the poor peasant masses in the villages and towns trapped in misery that became the most serious domestic problem, due to the stuck industrial revolution. The socialist industrialization of systems of Rákosi and Kádár absorbed the surplus of rural labour, but the industrialization meant the redistributive exploitation of the agricultural areas (the persecution of kuláks, the

collectivization and the compulsory deliveries) and the further impoverishment. The liberalization of household farming and the limitless food-demand of the CMEA meant a certain remedy.

After the transition, the rural Hungary could not be the “pantry of the CMEA”, and the final crisis of Hungarian agricultural sales finalized the deformation of the three-quarters of Hungary, the major part of the rural areas in Hungary. In recent decades the brain drain worked in the Hungarian peripheries, the disinvestment and the pauperization.

The emerging latifundiums and the monoculture commodity production operate independently, separated from the Hungarian rural people in the sense of ownerships and production. Because of these negative processes, a significant part of the rural society has been declassed and lumpened. In this hopeless situation only a conscious regional policy (enforcement of the regional preferences), and above all, a very well-considered education (launched for the 3 years old children with pre-school socialization – schooling – secondary and tertiary high ability education) are able to offer a chance for the break.

The rural areas of Hungary, as a geographical periphery. The rural development has been started by the European Economic Community in the 1960s, when the leaders of the Common Market realized that the global economic structure changes had a negative effect to the rural areas and their population. The more and more industrialized agriculture had less and less demand for man hours (in the most of the Western European countries the ratio of the agriculture means less than 1-2% on the labour market).

So the agriculture had less and less role in the maintenance of the rural settlements. The price gap between agricultural and industrial products widened, therefore the European Economic Community (the predecessor of the European Union) has started to build-up a conscious agricultural supporting policy¹. The possible problems urged the specialists of the European Union to consider the rural development as a complex activity. The rural development was drawn up as a new territorial policy, and the agriculture is only a component of this. The rural areas have nature protection, culture land protection, recreation roles, which have been appreciated. During the building-up of the social market economy,

¹ SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 2003.

significant funds were deprived from the urban areas and were forwarded to rural development¹.

It is almost an impossible task to make an exact definition about the rural areas. From a geographical point of view, we have to consider that a hilly and a plain area has different physical makings, and it has different effects to the local socio-economic patterns. The scope of the rural development covers the developing of the farms, the villages, communities and small towns, the growing, the employment and the incomes, the local and producer infrastructure, protecting the treasures of the living and built environment, and the development of the rural communities. According to this definition, the rural development affects more than 85-90% of the area of the European Union².

According to the Hungarian scientific literature, the rural development means those economic, social, cultural, and ecological factors, which develop the whole nation via the rising of the economic, cultural, and living standard in the area. At the same time, they save and protect the natural resources, the environment, the landscape, as well as the local cultural heritage³. The aim and also the tool of the rural development is the integration between the sectors, the back-to-back developments, the cooperation of the local entrepreneur, civilian and self-governmental sectors, and building up an active, viable rural society⁴.

In the last centuries, the regional inequalities of Hungary became more and more determined, and as a part of this, the rural areas dropped behind faster in socio-economic sense⁵. Presently, there are pronounced territorial differences in the country. The different parts of the country adjusted to the varied circumstances in different ways, and it resulted that the regional differences became more and more conspicuous⁶. In spite of this, in the Hungarian public life, the territorial policy does not get enough

¹ ENYEDI, GY. 1975/a.

² BERÉNYI, I. 1995.

³ BUDAY-SÁNTA, A. 2001.

⁴ ENYEDI, GY. 1975/b.

⁵ SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1991/B

⁶ RECHNITZER, J. 1993.

emphasis, however a number of scientists tried to call attention to the serious signs of the crisis and the regional problems¹.

On the basis of the investigation of the Hungarian society and economic life, we can observe a deeper and deeper gap between the capital (and its surroundings), the northern part of Transdanubia and the other parts of the country. Thus the country was divided into two or three parts in the daily media and in the scientific literature and this has its own basis². Those areas which lie South and East of Budapest and the centrum area (especially the rural areas without cities) have a deeper and deeper territorial crisis. The socio-economic backwardness of the rural Hungary is not a new problem, but its acceleration and generalization is more and more perceptible nowadays. By the end of the 1980s, the economy of the Hungarian Great Plain, the Southern part of Transdanubia and the Northern Hills depreciated in the competition³. The areas of the crisis areas became bigger since 1920. The "victims" of the redistribution, the rural areas of the county-borders, the internal peripheries and the market towns of the Great Plain are connected to the frontier rural areas, which lost their centres.

The earlier small trade and agricultural trade roles of the market towns of the Great Plain eclipsed, and the industrial investments of the last decades also preserved their backwardness⁴. If we consider the structure and the technological composition of the industrialization, the policy of the rural industrial investments of the 1960s and 1970s strengthen the backwardness. The infrastructure development of Hungary was determined mainly by the demands of the heavy-industries, thus the infrastructural backwardness of our agricultural areas was preserved. It affected the life-conditions of the population negatively, so this and the collectivization generated a significant migration – demographic erosion in the underindustrialized areas⁵.

The leaders of the regional policy in the Rákosi and Kádár regimes considered that the socialist industrialization (which absorbs the rural unemployment) and the socialist transformation of the agriculture can solve

¹ NEMES NAGY, J. 1996; MÉSZÁROS, R. 1982; SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1992/B.

² BELUSZKY, P. 1976; BARTA, GY. 1990; BARTKE, I. 1991.

³ BÖHM, A. 1991; SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1991/A, TÓTH, J. 1991.

⁴ BARTKE, I. 1971; BARTA, GY. – ENYEDI, GY. 1981.

⁵ ANDORKA, R. – HARCSA, I. 1992; DÖVÉNYI, Z. 1993.

the development problems of the whole country satisfyingly. Under the pressure of necessity, the leaders of the country observed in the 1980s, that the socio-economic problems didn't decrease in the mass of the rural areas of Hungary (VÁGVÖLGYI, A. 1982). Thus, the leaders of the Party and later the Council of Ministers were forced to admit the existence of the backwardness of rural areas¹ or “accumulated disadvantageous areas” as it was declared a little bit mannered (Figure 1).

Over the agricultural areas, the “rust areas” were also in a very bad condition. The industrial areas of Borsod and Nógrád – they were the pride of the socialist industrialization – ran into a very hopeless situation by the years of transition. If the structure change is delayed – on the basis of European instances – the significant budget aids are also ineffectual, this caused mainly by the difficultly modifying the structure of the employment of the heavy industry areas and the mining districts².

The crisis of the state-owned industry was very spectacular in the case of the territorial “contraction” of the industry of Hungary, when the industrial enterprises of the Eastern part of the country went bankrupt and stopped their production first. The collapse of the “giant factories” of the “rust areas” and the outworker industry of the market towns of the Great Plain caused significant unemployment firstly in the counties of the Eastern part of Hungary and Southern-Transdanubia³.

¹ LACKÓ, L. 1986.

² ENYEDI, GY. 1993.

³ SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1992/A.

Figure 1: Accumulated disadvantageous rural areas in the middle of the 1980s

Edited by: István Süli-Zakar

The pauperizations of the peripheries of Hungary. As a result of the transition, the collective farms were liquidated; the individual farming was started again. However, in conjunction with the collapse of the Soviet Union, the CMEA has also collapsed, so the Hungarian agriculture ran into a serious distributive crisis. The problems were piled on, because the large-scaled unemployment and pauperization – caused by transition – meant a drastic decrease of inner consumption. (The Hungarian agribusiness lost their market, its 40% was caused by the decrease of the inner consumption) On the other hand, the fast extension of the transnational store chains – they marketed the accumulated food supplies of Western Europe on a dumping price – caused that the pauperized consumers preferred the cheap import goods.

Naturally, the Hungarian agribusiness, which was deprived from the donation, couldn't compete with the dumping prices. However, a significant

part of the Hungarian food industry has been privatized by foreign companies; the food industry activity was stopped in the factories and the buildings operate as logistic, cooling and warehouse bases. The privatization of the Hungarian food industries and the closing of the factories (for instance, only one sugar factory produces in Hungary nowadays) increased the rural unemployment significantly¹.

The Hungarian right-wing policy (Smallholders Party) attempted to re-establish the small-peasant farming. However, this ambition totally turned out success, because of the great international competition and the social transformation after 1960. The depressed prices of the agricultural lands and the dispiritedness of the farming caused the deterioration of the compensation coupons, and favoured the buying of agricultural lands by the speculators and urban investors who had no landed interests. Especially, in Transdanubia the foreign investors appeared who hoarded great Hungarian agricultural areas by the help of “pocket-contracts”.

These resulted that the agricultural concentration has been started in our better agro-potential areas and the productional latifundiums have emerged. More than three-fourth of the area of the country became internal or external periphery after the transition and the rural population had less agricultural incomes there, and they became inactive members of the society as a retired, unemployed or assistance (MOLNÁR NAGYNÉ, M. 2011). By the middle of the 1990s, the spatial structure has been changed in Hungary: the earlier “industrial axis” has disappeared; an exact formation of external and internal peripheries was noticeable in a conclusive part of the country (Figure 2).

¹ SÜLI-ZAKAR, I.–KOMAREK, L. 2012.

Figure 2: Centrum and peripheries of Hungary in the middle of 1990s
 Edited by: István Süli-Zakar

The future development significantly depends on the state, initiative and innovation-sensitiveness of the local society. According to some opinions, the achievement of middle-class status in the market towns was built upon the autonomic peasant-properties in the past, so the middle-class traditions can be regenerated quickly after the transition, and the societies of the market towns can adapt to changes very quickly. However, after 1990, the Hungarian smallholder culture and lifestyle couldn't be able to regenerate and reborn. Nevertheless, a new farmer level – in Western or American sense – also couldn't be able to emerge (KOPÁTSY, S. 1991). Namely, after the collectivization, rural masses lost their affection for the agriculture; they worked in the household farming and cooperated with the collective farms (SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1994). However, they didn't follow a multi-coloured small-scale farming, but they contracted solely for one production – mostly for fattened pigs. The collective farms assured the feeding stuff and the young animals to them. Basically, the earlier small-scale farming went

on only in the household farms, also the small- and middle-class farming had almost totally disappeared. The peasant lifestyle remained only in those small areas, which were avoided by the collectivization and were peripheries almost in the second half of the 20th century. They are mostly hill-country areas with small settlements or fragment farms, which are absolutely disadvantageous in social and physical geographic sense (FARAGÓ, L. –HRUBI, L. 1987).

Among the circumstances of the market economy, the direct intervention of the state is small-scaled; it doesn't take place directly in the economy and not through the public administration, but with the integration of banks, development institutions. The intensive development of the infrastructure has to be the primary aim of the intervention of the state. It undoes the isolation and creates the human basis of the uprising with the help of the educational and retraining preparation (CSÉFALVAY, Z. 1994). The forming of a network of small- and middle-scaled growing centres has to be accelerated with the help of government subsidy and the foreign capital. These "oases" catch and transmit the innovation impulses, mobilize the local sources and undo the isolation.

The transformation created a new situation in Hungary. As a result of that the peripherization of the rural areas has accelerated. The loosing of the internal and external markets as well as the liquidation of the producer collective farms resulted in significant changes. There are some positive phenomena, for instance, the decreasing amount of the used toxic chemicals, but the commodity production of the cultivation and livestock production declined drastically in the 1990s. This recession hardly appeared on the surface, because the Hungarian agriculture had a huge loss of markets after the transition. The Western European agricultural goods outplaced the Hungarian products from the post-soviet states, the impoverished Hungarian customers bought cheap, Western European foodstuff (SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. –KOMAREK, L. 2012).

Otherwise, the rapidly growing unemployment and pauperization affected the contraction of the internal markets. The privatization and later the closing of the food industrial units (for example milk industries, sugar industries and slaughterhouses) also caused the decrease of the demands in case of a number of agricultural products (sugar beet, swine and cattle). The

food industry is a vertical integration from which a unit is deleted then the whole system collapses.

The cultivation of sugar beet is almost ceased in Hungary, the number of dairy cows decreased drastically. The cheap import pork caused the closing of hundreds of swine-growing yards and the Hungarian meat industry came to a crisis. These effects affected the Hungarian agriculture, hereby the Hungarian rural areas even more devaluated (Kovács, T. 2003).

In the years of transition an intense impartiality appeared toward the agricultural activity. The croplands were very cheap and it was evident from the inflation of the compensation coupons. The offspring of the peasant economies practically wasted the compensation coupons. It can be experienced that particular urban intellectual or upstart entrepreneur groups abused this inflation and a real landlordism formed in a few years in the Hungarian rural areas. As a result of this the fate of the Hungarian village and the agriculture was divided. The villagers lost their industrial jobs (they reached it by commuting), but simultaneously the croplands around them got out of their hands. The owners, who live far away, frequently in cities, adopted extensive agricultural monocultures (maize, wheat, etc.) on their latifundiums, which can be cultivated effectively with intense mechanization. On these latifundiums, the demand for living-labour is extremely low because of the modern agricultural machines, i.e. the manpower of the villagers is unrequired (SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. 1994).

Nowadays, the cultivation reached again – moreover, concerning some grains (maize, oil-seeds) it exceeded – the crop of the 1980s. However, the achievements of the livestock production decreases for the present day, thereby projects an extremely unfavourable image. Compared to the livestock of cattle in the 1980 (about 2 millions), this number didn't reach the 700 thousand in Hungary in 2010; and the poultry stock decreased to its two thirds. The decrease of the pig population is really drastic: it was 8.330 thousand in 1980, nowadays it is 3.169 thousand. In 2013, the Hungarian agriculture closed a successful year. The cultivation exceeded the preceding year with 17%, still the livestock production decreased with 3%. In comparison with the field cultures – this can be cultivated extensively with a maximal mechanization – the demands for living labour of the livestock production and the greengrocery production is much bigger. Also the real answer can be the large-scale development of these sectors from the point

of view of unemployment. The real tragedy for the future of the Hungarian rural areas is the disinvestment, since the profit, which produced here, isn't utilized significantly in the rural areas, because of the not local owners.

A considerable ethnic exchange has been proceeding in the geographical peripheries of Hungary. The villages have been emptied and Roma population moved there, mainly because of the low house prices. This ethnic exchange meant a deeper pauperization for the rural peripheries and it raised the level of the poverty (PÁLÓCZI, Á. 2013).

Aspirations of the regional development for the liquidation of the poverty and the peripheral situation. The local society became one-sided and its structure depreciated in the villages of the peripheral areas and the former so-called socialist industrial towns. Masses become resigned to their fates, waiting for the social benefits from the state and vegetating in the rural Hungary. The only employer is the local authority in our small villages in the hilly countries in the North-Eastern and South-Transdanubian areas. In these villages, the public work-program means the sole job opportunity.

The level of the Hungarian labours fall behind from the requirements of the global economy. Nowadays, at least 1,5 million people (are in working age) live in Hungary, who don't have that abilities and chances, which can help them to produce the sources of their subsistence. Excluding some ghettos in the cities, these people live in the rural peripheries. Not only the lack of work, but also the lack of ability to work hinders the development on the most underdeveloped rural peripheries. Consequently, this means that if there is (or could be) capital for job creation, there won't be real receptiveness on the major part of the rural settlements.

The idea of the free enterprise zones (also known as special economic zones) emerged in Hungary in June 2012 by the Ministry of National Economy. According to original plans, the companies – operating in the enterprise zones – can obtain tax concession on very easy terms. The government meeting decided about that on 23rd January, 2013 in Vásárosnamény (Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County). The earlier plans contain 903 settlements, but finally, further 177 settlements became favoured (Figure 3). With the help of law-defined provisions, the government want to participate in the economic development of the free enterprise zones by the provision of development resources for the employment and investments (TAFFERNER, B. 2013).

Figure 3: Spatial structure of Hungary (2015)

Radical changes occurred in both the educational system of the globalized world and Hungary in the near past. These changes in the school education and higher education move on generally the international trends. Certain countries and their regions / settlements are colourful, so they are heterogeneous also from educational geographical point of view. We can declare that the level of the education and the real chance of taking part in it determine significantly the competitiveness of the people and their geographical surroundings. By the progress of the technical-technological development, it became more and more true.

The government sees clearly the key role of the education in the uplift of the rural areas. The investments in education mean a special activity, which return long time and positive proceeds, occurred sometimes 15-20 years later.

Conclusion. The essential say of our study is a deep and serious regional crisis and poverty emerged in Hungary, mainly in the peripheral rural areas. Because of the decades of the redistribution, the rural economy and society has a degraded and unhealthy structure. After the change of regime high number of regional differences in development plans and measures have been taken. Naturally, the ideas were doomed without long-

term political and financial support, in the storms of the Hungarian Parliament rotation. It shouldn't be forgotten that the maintenance of rural cultural landscape is a national interest, but it should be recognized that rural Hungary's political weakness is also responsible to enforce their interests that the regional differences and the social divisions are growing in our country from year to year. It can be concluded that in order to uplift the rural areas the system of regional preferences should be applied and especially strengthen the fundamentals of human advancement through the education. The rural peripheries should have a development path, where the higher economic level of the expected socio-economic sustainability would be effective. We have to consider the decisions of the Government Program of Vásárosnamény as the most important new phenomenon, but the next few years will decide that the rural development and the "work instead of grants" program as well as education reorganization how much will be able to help the uplift of the disadvantageous masses of poverty people.

Bibliography:

1. ANDORKA, R. –HARCSA, I. (1992) A községi népesség társadalomstatistikai leírása, In: A falu a mai magyar társadalomban, (Szerk.: Vágvölgyi A), Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, pp. 179-236.
2. BARTA, GY. (1990) Centrum-periféria folyamatok a magyar gazdaság területi fejlődésében? In: Tér-Idő-Társadalom MTA RKK, (Szerk.: Tóth J.), Pécs, pp. 170-190.
3. BARTA, GY.– ENYEDI, GY. (1981) Iparosodás és a falu átalakulása, Közgazdasági és Jogi Könyvkiadó, Budapest, 206 p.
4. BARTKE, I. (1971) Az iparilag elmaradott területek ipari fejlesztésének közigazgatási kérdései Magyarországon, Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, 183 p.
5. BARTKE, I. (1991) A regionális válság és a piacgazdaságra való átmenet, In: Válságtérsegek Magyarországon, (Szerk.: Lackó L.), Budapest, pp. 79-84.
6. BELUSZKY, P. (1976) Területi hátrányok a lakosság életkörülményeiben. Hátrányos helyzetű területek Magyarországon, In: Földrajzi Értesítő XXV. évf. 2-4. sz., pp. 301-312.
7. BERÉNYI, I. (1995) A falusi térségek átalakulásának lehetőségei, In: Pro Geographia Humana (Szerk.: Probáld F.), Eötvös Kiadó, Budapest, pp. 119-131.

8. BÖHM, A. (1991) A hátrányos helyzetű térségek helyi társadalmának néhány időszerű vonása, In: Válságtérségek Magyarországon (Szerk.: Lackó L.), Budapest, pp. 67-70.
9. BUDAY-SÁNTHA, A. (2001) Agrárpolitika - vidékpolitika, Kiadó: Dialóg Campus Kiadó, Budapest-Pécs, 464 p.
10. CSÉFALVAY, Z. (1994) A modern társadalomföldrajz kézikönyve, Ikva Könyvkiadó, Budapest.
11. DÖVÉNYI, Z. (1993) Munkanélküliség az Alföldön, In: Alföldi Társdalom IV. kötet, Békéscsaba, pp. 107-121.
12. ENYEDI, GY. (1975/a) Falukutatás a falufejlesztésért, In: Földrajzi Közlemények XXIII. 3-4., pp. 269-276.
13. ENYEDI, GY. (1975/b) A magyar falu átalakulása, In: Földrajzi Értesítő XXIV. évf. 2. sz., pp. 109-124.
14. ENYEDI, GY. (1980) Falvaink sorsa, Magvető Könyvkiadó, Budapest, 184.p.
15. ENYEDI, GY. (szerk.) (1993) Társadalmi-területi egyenlőtlenségek Magyarországon, Közgazdasági és Jogi Könyvkiadó, Budapest, 383 p.
16. FARAGÓ, L.– HRUBI, L. (1987) Az elmaradott falusi térségek felzárkóztatásának lehetőségei, In: Tér és Társadalom 4., pp. 72-80.
17. KOPÁTSY, S. (1991) Nagyüzem Kisbirtok Farmergazdaság, In: Társadalmi Szemle XLVI. évf. 11., pp. 24-34.
18. KOVÁCS, T. (2003): Vidékfejlesztési politika, Kiadó: Dialóg Campus Kiadó, Budapest-Pécs, 286 p.
19. LACZKÓ, L. (1986) A területi fejlődés jellege, In: Területi Statisztika XXXVI. 3., pp. 205-220.
20. MÉSZÁROS, R. (1982) A falusi átalakulás alapvető térfolyamatai a Dél-Alföldön, Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, 141. p.
21. MOLNÁR NAGYNÉ, M. (2011) A területi egyenlőtlenségek főbb összefüggései, In: Regionális gazdaságtan (Szerk. Káposzta József), Szent István Egyetem, Gödöllő, pp. 200-250.
22. NEMES NAGY, J. (1996) Centrumok és perifériák a piacgazdasági átmenetben, In: Földrajzi Közlemények CXX. (XLIV.) kötet, 1. szám, pp. 31-48.
23. RECHNITZER, J. (1993) Szétszakadás vagy felzárkózás (A térszerkezetet alakító innovációk) MTA RKK, Győz, 208 p.
24. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (1991/b) Mélyülő szakadék két országrész között, In: Juss IV. évf. 2. szám, Hódmezővásárhely, pp. 18-23.

25. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (1992/a): A mezőgazdasági kisvállalkozások szociálgeográfiai hatásai Kelet-Magyarországon I.-II., In: Comitatus, Önkormányzati Szemle II. évf. 4-5. szám, pp. 19-23; 35-38.
26. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (1992/b) Kelet-Magyarország társadalmi-gazdasági leszakadása, In: Regionális politikák és fejlesztési stratégiák az Alpok-Adria térségében, XXXIV. Georgikon napok (Szerk.: Ligetvári F.-né), Keszthely, pp. 97-110.
27. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (1994) A vállalkozás-élénkítés agroökonómiai, szociológiai és szociálgeográfiai problémái hátrányos helyzetű alföldi térségekben (Szerk.: Süli-Zakar I.) KLTE Társadalomföldrajzi Tanszék, Debrecen, 119 p.
28. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (2003) A magyar területfejlesztés az EU regionális politikájának tükrében, In: Társadalomföldrajz – Területfejlesztés I.-II. (Szerk.: Süli-Zakar I.) Kossuth Egyetemi Kiadó Debreceni Egyetem, Debrecen. pp. 639-666.
29. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. (1991/a) Az Alföld periférikus területei, In: Tisza-klub füzetek 1. (Szerk.: Rakonczai J.), Békéscsaba, pp. 36-37.
30. SÜLI-ZAKAR, I. –KOMAREK, L. (2012) A Kárpát-medence élelmiszer-gazdasága, In: A Kárpát-medence földrajza (Szerk.: Dövényi Z.) Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, pp. 562-602.
31. TAFFERNER, B. (2012) Egy lehetséges gazdaságfejlesztési eszköz: a szabadvállalkozási zóna, In: Falu Város Régió, 19 (1-2), 11.
32. TÓTH, J. (1991) Az Alföld elmaradottsága, In: Tisza-klub füzetek 1. (Szerk.: Rakonczai J.), Békéscsaba, pp. 16-18.
33. 328/2009. (XII.29.) KORM. RENDELETE
34. 157/2010. (V. 6.) KORM. RENDELETE
35. 27/2013. (II.12.) KORM. RENDELETE
36. 147/2013. (V.14.) KORM. RENDELETE

Copyright©István SÜLI-ZAKAR

Economic Development of EU Member States and European Perspective of the Republic of Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mihai HACHI

mihaihachi@gmail.com

Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Moldova

ECSA-Moldova

Lecturer Corina CIUMAC

ciumac.corina@gmail.com

Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: The European Union presents itself as a pole of global economic power. The economic strength of the community derives from the synergy of the integrated states. Despite the differences in economic potential and degree of socio-economic maturity, EU Member States continue integration of economic policies having common goals and interests. The Republic of Moldova makes considerable efforts to get closer to what European security and prosperity means, in this regard, several levers aimed at developing the country's European perspective. Even if the instruments applied through EU neighborhood policy do not foresee Moldova's integration in the near future economic reorientation vector towards the European market offers real opportunities for socio-economic recovery and statehood save.

Key-words: convergence criteria, economic delocalization, economic premises, geopolitical and demographic integration, strategic partnership.

Introduction. The European Union is an economic, political, cultural construct, which consolidates its position in Europe and worldwide through various programs, policies in relation to the states from Europe and the close neighborhood. Thus, in 2004 the European Neighborhood Policy (ENP) was developed in order to prevent the emergence of new dividing lines between the enlarged EU and its neighbours and to strengthen the prosperity, stability and security of all. It is applied in relation to 16 countries neighboring the EU including six ex-Soviet nations. This new approach is intended to enhance EU cooperation with neighboring states for creating an area of prosperity and good neighbourhood. Aspirations and European values are shared differently from country to country. For Moldova, the European perspective is perhaps the unique geopolitical, economic, and

identity dimension that could save its statehood. Through this article, the authors propose an analysis of the basic features of the economy of EU Member States and their intensification perspective by Moldova coming from its European aspirations.

The **research methods** used are: statistical and mathematical, comparative, analysis and synthesis, historical.

The European Union (EU) is one of the poles of economic power in the world. European economic power derived from the synergy of integrated states. Despite the current financial and economic issues, but also identity, the EU remains the undisputed leader among integration groupings of the world. We can deduct this not only from statistical and economic indicators under quantitative aspects, but also from high social standards, the efficiency of the Community institutions, etc. Usually, EU Member States are divided into two distinct groups: countries with functioning market economy and transition economy, their delimitation being a conventional one. Another delimitation of EU Member States refers to euro membership, division being, in this respect, the EU-19 and EU-9 (2015).

Europe is the cradle of modern civilization, in the modern era it was the center of the world. From Europe there have been launched the main scientific, cultural and political mainstreams, from here started the great explorers of space; here it was invented democracy, parliamentarism. Europe is the cradle of the industrial revolutions, managerial and of other nature.

After the Second World War, Europe weakened a lot, making possible the US to rise. World power for the next period was shared by the US and the former Soviet Union, this rivalry named as 'cold war' lasted from 1945-1989, Europe remaining in shadow. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russian Federation the "greater among equals" lost its status of world power and will be harder to recover it, because of unstable economic situation, large social and territorial disparities, but also the loss of a considerable part of the "precious" territory in geopolitical terms.

After the war, Europe had to start a process of *self-definition* and *self-financing*. The brightest minds of the old continent have called for a common Europe, a united Europe. This centuries-old dream was accomplished by creating the most powerful EU bloc (elite club), although

Member States are very different, but with a united history, culture, close value system, which has been an important prerequisite in the unification of Europe. The basic principles of European idea were geographical proximity, civilization drive.

It started from the idea that no state could hold economic and political supremacy and could not cope alone with major issues and challenges of different nature in the modern period. The focus was on creating large economic regions. The future was determined by the inauguration of a new development model based not only on the potential of a country, but of a large region.

Inviting former socialist countries of Central and Eastern Europe and the Baltic States in the EU meant, in fact, their exclusion from the sphere of Russian influence, but also an attempt to oversize the European space. Eastward enlargement seems to be justified considering the competition between the other centers of economic power. By inviting the Baltic countries in the Western elite club, the EU isolated itself from Russian Federation, depriving its access to the Baltic Sea and isolating it from the West. Then again, the accession of Romania and Bulgaria to the EU, inviting Turkey to the negotiating table regarding the adherence is likely to further isolate the Russian Federation, for these reasons it does not welcome the West, currently focusing on strategic alliances with Asia (especially with China). Turkey as a pivotal country in the world has a strategic importance for the West, allowing the EU to exercise influence in the Islamic conservative and fundamentalist world. Cyprus and Malta, two small countries, but with a very good position to control the Mediterranean and influence upon the African continent counted in the decision of European integration through their important geostrategic position.

The EU current population is more than 510 million inhabitants, which exceeds a lot the US population (316 million inhabitants, 2014). If we take into account the geopolitical and geo-economical principle "The power of nations rises and falls as their population does"¹, the decision to extend the community eastward is justified, especially given that Western Europe is marked by an aging population, by a high demographic pressure, by a slow population growth, phenomenon that may have in future impact on

¹ S. Mehedinti, *Premise și concluzii la Terra, amintiri și mărturii*, p.107.

Member States budgets. The decision for a common Europe has demographic, geopolitical, geostrategic and economic premises. The expansion decision is a political and economic one. The EU will control the Baltic Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Black Sea; will control major trade routes in the area, extending its area of influence.

If in the 1970's there were thoughts of Europe's fall, now it is discussed the rebirth of Europe. Of course, there are many problems for the community to solve. At the beginning of the 21st century rhetoric like "One Europe" continues to be characterized by individual nation-states and rival nationalities attentive to their own political and economic interests. Despite the important objectives of building a political and economic unity, European nations are not always willing to sacrifice their economic autonomy and political independence even in favor of a political and economic actor valued worldwide. However, it went too far to give up, though it will take many years / decades to determine how far will go European integration, forward direction and the effects it will have on Europe and the whole world.

In order to become a world power the EU should strengthen its institutions, extend the single currency, to have a common diplomacy and defense policy.

In this context, the Republic of Moldova, a young country in Europe with an inheritance of the former socialist system, continues to be one of the most underdeveloped economies in Europe, trying hard to return to the Western sphere of influence, having many advantages in this respect. Although the policy choices of the population are separated, a lot of effort is committed to the implementation of cooperation agreements with the EU, the European perspective remains to be the economic, social, political force able to ensure sustainable welfare of the population and to restore the historical truth.

Basic characteristics of EU economy and main achievements.

Although now more frequently one refers to EU economy as a whole, which is justified by transferring more and more competences from national level to community level, Member States' economies remain functional entities, and certainly, the subject of economic analysis. In order to track the overall performance or EU issues the necessity to compare the main economic, financial and social indicators appears. Among these there are GDP, GDP per

capita, unemployment rate, inflation rate and related indicators such as imports and exports, capital investment etc.

Gross domestic product (GDP) is the most frequently used indicator to assess the overall size of an economy, while the derived indicators, such as GDP per capita, are widely used to compare living standards, or in order monitor the process of convergence to the EU.

In addition, the development of specific components of GDP and related indicators such as the economic production, imports and exports, consumption and investment, as well as data on income distribution and energy consumption, can provide relevant information about driving forces of an economy and thus represent the basis for the design, monitoring and evaluation of specific EU policies.

A comparative analysis of the main economic indicators in the Member States present significant differences (Table 1). The value of PPP reported to GDP increased in 2013 by 25% compared with 2009, although in the last 5 years the EU faced a deep economic and financial crisis. The highest increase had Central and Eastern European countries, considering the need for recovery in development, which they have to perform in order to achieve the average EU level or the level of EU-15 countries.

Table 1. Basic macroeconomic indicators in the Member States in 2009 and 2013

States	GDP to PPP, mln. \$		GDP, % EU 28		GDP/capita to PPP, \$		GDP/capita to PPP, % in comparison to average UE 28	
	2013	2009	2013	2009	2013	2009	2013	2009
EU	15 850 000	11 808 717	100	100	34 500	23 600	100	100
Germany	3 227 000	1 566 741	20,4	20,4	39 500	27 300	114	116
Great Britain	2 386 000	1 566 741	15,1	13,3	37 300	27 400	108	116
France	2 276 000	1 907 745	14,4	16,2	35 700	25 300	103	107
Italy	1 805	1 520	11,4	12,9	29 600	29	83	102

	000	870				600		
Spain	1 389 000	1 051 151	8,8	8,9	30 100	24 500	87	104
Poland	814 000	310 070	5,1	2,6	21 100	14 300	61	61
Netherlands	699 700	570 208	4,4	4,8	570 208	30 700	126	130
Belgium	421 700	337 284	2,7	2,9	37 800	27 200	110	115
Sweden	393 800	292 680	2,5	2,5	40 900	28 400	119	120
Austria	361 000	270 074	2,3	2,3	42 600	28 800	123	122
Romania	288 500	115 869	1,8	1,0	14 400	10 400	42	44
Czech Republic	285 600	137 246	1,8	1,2	26 300	19 000	76	81
Greece	267 100	237 494	1,7	2,0	23 600	22 300	68	94
Portugal	243 300	167 633	1,5	1,4	22 900	18 500	66	78
Denmark	211 300	222 893	1,3	1,9	37 800	27 700	110	117
Hungary	196 600	93 086	1,2	0,8	19 800	14 900	57	63
Finland	195 500	170 971	1,2	1,4	35 900	26 100	104	111
Ireland	190 400	163 543	1,2	1,4	41 300	30 900	120	131
Slovakia	133 400	63 332	0,8	0,5	24 700	16 900	72	72
Bulgaria	104 600	33 877	0,7	0,3	14 400	10 400	42	44
Croatia	78 900	45 379	0,5	-	17 800	15 700	52	67
Lithuania	67 430	26 650	0,4	0,2	22 600	12 500	66	53
Slovenia	57	34 894	0,4	0,3	27 400	20	79	86

STUDII EUROPENE

	360					300		
Luxemburg	42 670	37 755	0,3	0,3	77 900	63 000	226	267
Latvia	38 870	18 539	0,2	0,2	19 100	11 400	55	48
Estonia	29 940	13 730	0,2	0,1	22 400	14 600	65	62
Cyprus	21 620	16 947	0,1	0,1	24 500	23 200	71	98
Malta	11 220	5 720	0,07	0,07	29 200	18 300	85	78

Source: Calculated and adapted according to www.cia.gov/library

Main economic power is concentrated in five countries: Germany, Great Britain, France, Italy and Spain accounting for about 70% of the GCP (Global Community Product). At the same time the first 3 countries: Germany, Great Britain and France account for half of the global income, while Germany ranked in the European economic top accounts for 1/5 of GCP. Other seven states hold 20% of the GCP with a growing role that attests acceding states Poland, Romania and the Czech Republic, but also states of medium size, but with very high economic turnovers, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, Sweden and Austria. The remaining member states have insignificant contributions in shaping GCP, less than 1.5% each.

Regarding the contribution of EU Member States in GDP to PPP in the last five years the situation has not changed significantly. The largest growth of this indicator had Poland with a 2.5 pp (percentage points), United Kingdom (1.8 pp) and Romania (0.8 pp). This is explained by the relatively large size of the economies of countries from Eastern Europe; moreover, the results of economic reforms carried out, while the stability of Great Britain is explained through the conservatism of the Anglo-Saxon model and permanent reformation required in order to adapt to the new conditions of regional and international market.

Analysis of another measurable macroeconomic indicator GDP per capita to PPP denotes higher values or close to the Community average for the EU-15 and values below the Community average for the EU-13. Differences between countries are significant, the highest value in 2013 being in Luxembourg (a small country, irrelevant for comparison) - \$ 77,900, which is 2.6 times higher than the EU 28 average, followed by the

Netherlands, Austria, Sweden, Ireland, medium-sized countries, but holding important positions in international competitiveness. The most modest results are in Romania, Bulgaria and Latvia, which have values less than 50% of the Community average for this indicator. A key issue of these states is large regional disparities in development, which will be recovered by applying basic principles and objectives of Community regional policy, but also with supported own efforts.

Reaching an advanced level of integration was possible due to the application of the unique economic and financial conditions in the Member States. Among them there are convergence criteria adopted at Maastricht (the Netherlands) in 1991, which actually means economic and financial “discipline” monitored by the monetary authorities of the Member States and by ECB (European Central Bank). Compliance with financial and economic convergence criteria is a condition imposed also to candidate countries to European integration. They concern inflation rate, long-term interest rates, budget deficit, public debt etc.

An analysis of these indicators in 2014 shows a deviation from the convergence criteria for most states, which actually indicates the continuing economic crisis in the Member States, although several economies gave signals of return to a stable situation (Table 2).

Table 2. Convergence criteria of EU Member States (2013)

		Inflation rate (%)	External debt (% from GDP)	Public budgetary deficit (%)	Long-term interest rate, %
1.	Germany	0,8	76,9	0.0	3,94
2.	Great Britain	1,5	87,2	-7,7	4,06
3.	Italy	0,8	127,9	-2,9	4,60
4.	France	0,6	92,2	-4,5	3,43
5.	Austria	1,5	81,2	-2,9	3,30
6.	Portugal	-0,2	128,0	-6,1	5,71
7.	Spain	-0,2	92,1	-7,4	8,09
8.	Finland	1,2	56,0	-1,9	2,68
9.	Sweden	0,2	38,6	-0,3	4,28
10.	Ireland	0,3	123,3	-8,5	3,81
11.	Denmark	0,3	45,0	-4,0	4,50
12.	Belgium	0,5	104,5	-3,3	3,93
13.	Greece	-1,4	174,9	-7,6	7,15

STUDII EUROPENE

14.	Netherlands	0,3	68,6	-5,1	3,18
15.	Luxembourg	0,7	23,6	-0,9	2,60
16.	Latvia	0,7	38,2	-2,7	6,39
17.	Lithuania	0,2	39,0	-4,3	5,78
18.	Estonia	0,5	10,0	-2,4	6,10
19.	Czech Republic	0,4	45,5	-3,2	5,72
20.	Hungary	0,0	77,3	-2,7	8,34
21.	Slovakia	-0,1	54,6	-4,2	3,70
22.	Cyprus	-0,3	102,2	-4,2	6,80
23.	Malta	0,8	69,8	-3,9	4,76
24.	Romania	1,4	37,9	-2,3	12,12
25.	Bulgaria	-1,6	18,3	-1,4	10,62
26.	Slovenia	0,4	70,4	-4,9	5,82
27.	Poland	3,6	55,7	-2,1	8,47
28.	Croatia	0,2	75,7		
	Average or total EU	0,6	85,4	-4,5	7,52
	Moldova	4,6	18,9	-2,9	14,4

Source: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=fr&pcode=tec00118&plugin=1>, cited on 14.04.2015

The most difficult situation is recorded at the external debt chapter. This indicator reached one of the highest levels since the introduction of the single currency. The precarious financial situations as regards this indicator have Greece, Italy, Portugal and Ireland, external debt surpasses 2 times and more the limits of convergence. For comparison, in 2009 it was 79.9%. Considerable efforts are required to be made by Member States to overcome the situation of the public budgetary deficit, which in total for the 27 Member States exceeded by 1.5 pp (percentage points) established norm. Even though in 2013 was registered a slight decrease in the budgetary deficit, it still exceeded by 2.5 times the level set by the Maastricht Treaty for Ireland, Great Britain, Greece and Spain. A relatively good situation is recorded at indicators like inflation and long-term interest rates. Comparing the Republic of Moldova with European states regarding compliance with the convergence criteria for 2013 it is attested a good situation at variables

like external debt and budgetary deficit, the others being weak compared to EU average.

Another distinctive feature of the economies of EU Member States refers to the high share of tertiary and quaternary sectors in the GDP (Table 3).

Table 3. Structure of the economy of EU countries by sector and employment, 2013

Nr.	States	Share of the sector in GDP:			Active population employed in sector			Unemployment rate, 2014.01.01
		primary	secondary	tertiary	primary	secondary	tertiary	
1.	Germany	0,8	30,1	69,1	1,6	24,6	73,8	5,1
2.	Great Britain	0,7	20,5	78,9	1,4	18,2	80,4	6,6
3.	France	1,9	18,7	79,4	2,9	20,6	76,4	10,1
4.	Italy	2,0	24,4	73,5	3,9	28,3	67,8	12,6
5.	Austria	1,6	26,0	68,5	5,5	26,0	68,5	4,7
6.	Portugal	2,6	22,2	75,2	11,7	28,5	59,8	14,3
7.	Spain	3,1	26,0	70,8	4,2	24,1	71,7	25,1
8.	Finland	2,9	25,7	71,9	4,4	22,6	69,0	8,5
9.	Sweden	2,0	31,3	66,8	1,1	28,2	70,7	7,8
10.	Ireland	1,6	28,0	70,4	5,0	19,0	76	12,0
11.	Denmark	1,5	21,7	76,8	2,6	20,3	77,1	6,5
12.	Belgium	0,8	22,6	76,6	2,0	25,0	73	8,5
13.	Greece	3,5	16,0	80,5	12,4	22,4	65,1	26,8
14.	Netherlands	2,6	25,4	72,1	2,3	18,8	78,9	7,0
15.	Luxembourg	0,3	13,3	86,4	1,2	19,4	79,4	6,3
16.	Latvia	4,9	25,7	69,4	8,8	24,0	67,2	11,4
17.	Lithuania	3,7	28,3	68,0	7,9	19,6	72,5	11,0
18.	Estonia	3,9	30,0	66,2	4,2	20,2	75,6	7,9
19.	Czech Republic	2,4	37,3	60,3	2,6	37,4	60	6,3
20.	Hungary	3,4	28,0	68,7	7,1	20,7	63,9	7,9
21.	Slovakia	3,1	30,8	47,0	3,5	27,0	69,4	13,9
22.	Cyprus	2,4	15,9	81,7	8,5	20,5	71	15,3
23.	Malta	1,4	25,3	73,3	1,4	22,4	76,4	1,4
24.	Romania	6,4	34,2	59,4	29,0	28,6	42,4	6,4
25.	Bulgaria	6,7	30,3	63,0	7,1	35,2	57,7	6,7
26.	Slovenia	2,8	28,9	68,3	2,2	35,0	62,8	2,8
27.	Poland	4,0	33,3	62,7	12,9	30,2	57	9,6
28.	Croatia	5,0	25,8	69,2	2,1	29,0	69	16,3
	Average or total	2,8	25,9	71,3	5,7	20,2	74,1	10,3
	Moldova	13,8	19,9	66,2	26,4	13,2	60,4	5,8

Source: <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/tgm/table.do>,
www.cia.gov/library

In the economic structure, EU countries are moving towards capital-intensive industries with high added value, human intellect consuming branches, high-tech, IT, biotechnology, robotics, organic chemistry etc., considered "leading industries" of national economies. In this way the largest share in the GDP hold branches of tertiary and quaternary sectors (R&D). The share of agriculture in the GDP is less than 5% in EU-15, while to the tertiary sector is attributed 70-80%. The prominence of the tertiary sector occurred on the background of reduction or disappearance of traditional branches, resource intensive, polluting, with high costs. These branches were transferred to the regions of the world with lower costs of production factors. Among other factors for relocation of traditional branches of national economies are: high fiscal and environmental pressure, high labor cost; capital from these states being directed to countries and regions with lower costs, but also to emerging economies.

Intensive agriculture with high productivity diminished the share of the population involved in agriculture; this trend is currently pursued in EU-13. The largest share of the agricultural population is in the states that adhered recently, like Romania (29%), Poland (12.9%) and some countries in Southern Europe, Greece (12.9%), Portugal (11.7%) with significant shares of plants cultivation and labor intensive sub-branches, which have a lower labor productivity compared to Central and Northern Europe.

Agriculture has a small contribution in the formation of the wealth of Member States. Even in countries with high agricultural potential and with an important role on the agricultural community market, such as France, the Netherlands, Spain, Denmark the share of agriculture in GDP does not exceed 4%. Only in three countries, Bulgaria, Romania and Croatia this value is bigger than 5%.

Former socialist states are characterized by a considerable share of the secondary sector. Industry and construction were priority areas in the structure of these states. In the industry structure of these countries, the traditional branches have significant shares. Currently, essential qualitative changes occur in these branches under the influence of EU industrial policy and the general trend is decreasing traditional branches in favor of intensive branches in human and financial capital.

In all Member States, the main role in the economy is played by service sector. Share of this sector both in the GDP and in the employment

rate of active population is determined. Thus, the largest share of the tertiary sector have the United Kingdom, France, Italy, Greece, Belgium, Denmark and economies of small states, like Luxembourg, Cyprus, Malta with values that exceed 75% of the total workforce employed.

EU Member States are now marked by a series of macroeconomic imbalances. One of these is the high rate of unemployment. Unemployment values change from year to year, increasing during the economic and financial crisis, being lower during the economic upsurge. In the economic theory an unemployment rate of 5% is considered natural and would maintain competition on the labor market. In 2013, the unemployment rate values in EU Member States were 10.3%, the minimum value was recorded in Austria (4.5%) and the maximum value of 24.1% in Spain. The most affected labor markets are those of the South European countries: Spain, Greece (23.3%), Portugal (15%) and Croatia (15.7%). A more favorable situation at this chapter is in Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Germany, the latter registering a considerable decrease of the unemployment rate by 2.5 percentage points in the last five years coming close to the admissible level according to the rules of economic and financial convergence set by the European Central Bank. Countries from Central and Eastern Europe deal with a more complicated situation, where economic restructuring is accompanied by macroeconomic imbalances.

EU Member States' economies are dependent on external markets both within the Union and on the world market as a whole. Thereby, the EU is an important commercial actor on international arena, being the first importer and second largest exporter. The Member States have a high degree of openness, being in such a way vulnerable to external shocks (Table 4). The degree of economic openness is very high both in the Member States with small domestic markets, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Austria, and in large countries like Germany, France, Great Britain and France, which are characterized by a high level of economic openness, marked both by the commitments within the EU and by international ones with a growing trend to liberalize economic exchanges.

Table 4. External trade indicators of EU member states, 2013

Nr.	States	Export		Import		Trade balance TB=E-I, mil.\$	Coverage rate of I through E Cr=E/I * 100	Degree of openness D= (E+I/2)/GDP x 100
		Mil.\$	% EU 28	Mil. \$	% EU 28			
	EU	6066,6	100	5730,9	100	335,7	105,9	43,3
1.	Germany	1452,8	23,9	1187,3	20,7	265,5	122,4	40,9
2.	France	579,6	9,6	680,7	11,9	-101,1	85,1	27,7
3.	Great Britain	541,3	8,9	654,4	11,4	-113,1	82,7	25,0
4.	Netherlands	663,5	10,9	590,3	10,3	73,2	112,4	89,6
5.	Italy	517,7	8,5	477,3	8,3	40,4	108,5	27,6
6.	Belgium	468,8	7,7	450,3	7,9	18,5	104,1	108,9
7.	Spain	315,5	5,2	338,8	5,9	-23,3	93,0	23,6
8.	Poland	202,1	3,3	203,6	3,6	-1,5	99,3	24,9
9.	Austria	174,3	2,9	182,3	3,2	-8,0	95,6	49,4
10.	Sweden	167,5	2,8	158,4	2,8	9,1	105,7	41,0
11.	Czech Republic	161,4	2,7	143,3	2,6	18,1	112,6	53,0
12.	Ireland	114,2	1,9	65,1	1,1	49,0	175,4	47,1
13.	Denmark	111,3	1,8	97,2	1,7	14,3	114,5	49,7
14.	Hungary	108,2	1,7	99,8	1,7	8,4	108,4	52,9
15.	Slovakia	86,3	1,4	81,6	1,4	4,7	105,8	60,0
16.	Finland	74,2	1,4	77,2	1,3	-3,0	96,1	38,7
17.	Romania	65,8	1,2	73,4	1,2	-7,6	89,6	30,5
18.	Portugal	62,8	1,0	75,2	1,3	-12,4	83,5	28,4
19.	Greece	36,5	0,6	62,2	1,1	-25,6	58,7	18,0
20.	Slovenia	34,1	0,6	33,4	0,5	0,7	102,1	58,8
21.	Lithuania	32,6	0,5	35,2	0,6	-2,6	92,6	50,1
22.	Bulgaria	29,5	0,4	34,3	0,6	-4,8	86,0	30,5
23.	Luxembourg	19,5	0,3	27,0	0,5	-7,5	72,2	54,4
24.	Estonia	16,3	0,3	18,2	0,3	-1,9	89,5	57,7
25.	Latvia	14,5	0,2	17,6	0,3	-3,1	82,4	41,3
26.	Croatia	11,8	0,2	20,9	0,4	-9,1	56,5	20,7
27.	Malta	3,5	0,06	5,8	0,1	-2,3	60,3	41,4
28.	Cyprus	2,0	0,03	6,3	0,1	-4,3	31,7	19,2
	Moldova	2,4		5,5		-3,1	43,6	29,7

Source: http://www.wto.org/french/res_f/statis_f/statis_bis_f.htm?solution=WTO&path=/Dashboards calculated and adapted accordingly

More than half of EU Member States have a negative trade balance. This refers mainly to EU countries that adhered recently that continue the process of adaptation to the conditions of regional and international market in conditions of harsh and qualified competition. These states are marked by structural reforms. Negative trade balances have even some states with a prosperous economy such as Great Britain and France. This economic imbalance was emphasized on the background of massive export of capital

and loss of some important positions in foreign trade in favor of traditional competitors.

Another feature proving the loss of competitiveness of EU Member States in favour of other states and regions is the loss of the status “workshop of the world” by migration of the productive capital.

An analysis of the evolution of Moldova’s foreign trade in the period 1997-2013 attests an increase in the value of exports and imports throughout the period considered with the exception of 2009-2010 due to the deepening of the financial crisis in the global economy in general but also in the partner states of Moldova in foreign trade. Thus, in 2013, the value of foreign trade reached its peak, exports accounted for \$2399 M, and the imports \$5492.7 M. Imports have tended to increase more than exports. Thus, in the period 2000-2014 exports increased more than 5 times, while imports increased more than 7 times.

Tendențele comerțului exterior al Republicii Moldova

Figure 1. Evolution of foreign trade of the Republic of Moldova 1997-2014
Source: Elaborated by the author based on NBS data

Since Moldova gained independence, the external trade had a negative value, the maximum being reached in 2008 - \$3307.8M. The main causes to this matter derive from the structure of exports, but also from the loss of competitiveness of a wide range of products made for export. The

economic decline of Moldova was one of the largest among CIS, the economic structure of the country being strongly connected to that of the former USSR. In addition, the economic structure was poorly adapted to the existing potential of the country.

Another measurable indicator of foreign trade is the coverage of exports by imports. Even though in the last 5 years there has been a slight increase in this indicator, the current value of 43.7% denotes the low competitiveness of domestic products in comparison to those imported. The market opening, according to international commitments, has largely affected the domestic producer that could not adapt to the new conditions of competition.

Table 5. The foreign trade of the Republic of Moldova in 2000-2014 (mil. \$)

	Structure, %					
	2000	2005	2007	2008	2010	2014
Export	471,5	1099,3	1340,0	1591,1	1541,5	2339,5
Import	776,4	2292,3	3689,5	4898,8	3855,3	5317,0
Balance of trade (E-I)	- 304,9	- 1201,0	-2347,8	-3307,8	-2313,8	- 2977,5
The degree of coverage of exports by imports (E/I x 100%)	60,7	48,0	36,3	32,5	40,0	44,0

Source: Calculated on the basis of NBS data

Another aspect of foreign trade is related to its geographical structure. Moldova's foreign trade was reoriented from the exclusive CIS market to the EU market. This qualitative change in the medium and long term will have positive effects due to the high standards prevailing on EU market, although costly in time those will give the expected performance. The diversification of trading partners allows the reduction or elimination of the risk related to the high dependence on some markets both import and export.

The structure of exports and imports by sections and chapters reveals a major component in exports of agricultural products and those of

light industry produced through contracts of Lohn production, which shows the vulnerability of foreign trade which is dependent on agricultural productivity and its low profitability as well as maintaining the low price level and the slow change of the prices compared to industrial products, which are capital intensive. The situation is complicated if we compare the degree of assurance of the European market with products that Moldova specializes in.

Table 6. The exports and imports of the Republic of Moldova, by sections and chapters, according to the International Trade Standard Classification

Export, total	100	Import, total	100
1. Diverse manufactured items	22,6	Mineral fuels	23,0
2. Foodstuff and livestock	20,3	Machinery and equipment	20,8
3. Machinery and equipment	15,7	Goods manufactured by raw material	18,1
4. Beverages and tobacco	11,5	Chemical products	13,5
5. Goods manufactured by raw material	10,1	Foodstuff and livestock	10,3
6. Inedible raw materials	7,7	Diverse manufactured items	9,1
7. Chemical products	7,2	Beverages and tobacco	2,9
8. Oils, fats	4,2	Inedible raw materials	2,0
9. Mineral fuels	0,7	Oils, fats	0,3

Source: National Bureau of Statistics

The share of innovative, capital-intensive products is low. Moldova has a comparative advantage in agricultural products, food and some light industry products, which will not ensure a sustainable income perspective (Table 6.7).

Table 7. The comparative advantages of the Republic Moldova in 2013 (top 10 chapters)

N.o.	Chapter code HS	Description	RCA
1.	08	Edible fruit and dried nuts	18.715
2.	57	Carpets and rugs	18.404

STUDII EUROPENE

3.	22	Beverages, spirits and vinegar	15.040
4.	15	Animal and vegetable fats	8.324
5.	12	Oil seeds and oleaginous fruits, seeds and fruit, industrial or medicinal plants, straw and fodder	8.175
6.	20	Preparations of vegetables and fruits and other parts of plants	8.104
7.	24	Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes	7.046
8.	62	Articles and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted	6.460
9.	17	Sugars and sugar confectionery	5.427
10.	60	Textile materials, knitted or crocheted	5.402

Source: Calculated by the author based on NBS data

The Republic of Moldova has now oriented its external trade to EU Member States. They have become major trading partners of Moldova. The enhancement of commercial trade was determined by a number of acquired facilities, such as programs, projects, important documents, such as SGS, SGS, plus asymmetrical trade, and the recently signed Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA), which is to be implemented. Romania became the main trading partner.

An important role in the economy of EU countries has the capital investment and, in particular, foreign direct investment (FDI). The European Union is one of the largest investors in the world. FDI is a major tool for economic development and growth. They enable large-scale projects, attracting advanced technologies and launching new practices for corporate governance. FDI contributes to the growth of GDP, to the gross creation of fixed capital and to the balance of payments. The level of economic development and its evolution, estimated through the value of GDP and its annual variations directly affect both the supply of capital investment and the attractiveness of potential host countries. Studies have estimated that a percentage of GDP growth in developed countries, results in a 3.5% growth in FDI flows.

EU countries as a whole have an important place in the movement of financial flows worldwide, being a region of net capital exporter, characteristic feature for high developed states of the world. Thus, in 2012,

the amount of capital outflows surpassed with 2,031,560 million \$ USA the capital inflows (Table 5).

In 2012 foreign direct investment in the European Union were still affected by the global economic and financial crisis. In the same year, the European Union's external investment dropped sharply by 53% less than in 2011, its lowest level since 2004. The same situation was in the case of investment inflows in the EU, which fell by 34% reaching its lowest level since 2005. Thus, the inflows and outflows of FDI in 2012 reached a level below 60% of the record level reached in 2007.

The situation in EU Member States is very different. EU-15 is usually capital-exporting countries, while the others are capital importing countries (Table 5). For instance, in 2012, the stock of capital outflows was greater than inflows in 13 Member States. The largest exporters of capital are Great Britain (18.4%), Germany (15.7%), France (15.2%), Belgium (10.5%) and the Netherlands (9.9%). These five countries account for 70% from the export of capital of the EU. For the capital inflows stand the same countries that account for 60% of the stock of FDI entering the EU (Table 5).

Table 5. Foreign direct investments stocks in EU Member States, 2012

Nr.	State	FDI stocks inflows		FDI stocks outflows	
		Mil.\$ SUA	% EU 27	Mil. \$ SUA	% EU 27
	EU	7 805 297	100	9 836 857	100
1.	Great Britain	1 321 352	16.9	1 808 167	18.4
2.	Germany	716 334	9.2	1 547 185	15.7
3.	France	1 094 961	14.0	1 496 795	15,2
4.	Belgium	1 010967	13.0	1 037 782	10.5
5.	Netherlands	572 986	7.3	975 552	9.9
6.	Spain	634 539	8.1	627 212	6.4
7.	Italy	356 887	4.6	565 085	5.7
8.	Sweden	376 181	4.8	406 851	4.1
9.	Ireland	298 088	3.8	357 626	3.6
10.	Austria	158 109	2.0	215 364	2.2
11.	Denmark	147 672	1.9	229 470	2.3
12.	Luxembourg	121 621	1.6	171 468	1.7

STUDII EUROPENE

13.	Finland	89 992	1.2	142 313	1.4
14.	Portugal	117 161	1.5	71 261	0.7
15.	Poland	230 604	3.0	57 525	0.6
16.	Greece	37 801	0.5	43 728	0.4
17.	Hungary	103 557	1,3	34 741	0,4
18.	Czech Republic	136 442	1,7	15 176	0,2
19.	Slovenia	15 526	0,2	7 796	0,1
20.	Cyprus	20 962	0,3	7 120	0,1
21.	Estonia	18 826	0,2	5 791	0,06
22.	Slovakia	95 816	1,2	4 413	0,04
23.	Lithuania	15 796	0,2	2 521	0,03
24.	Bulgaria	48 871	0,6	1 867	0,02
25.	Malta	15 821	0,2	1 526	0,02
26.	Romania	74 171	1,0	1 417	0,01
27.	Latvia	13 254	0,2	1 104	0,01
	Moldova	3 339		108	

Source: Elaborated relying on the World Investment Report 2013, http://unctad.org/en/publicationslibrary/wir2013_en.pdf

Changing the economic and political system in the zone of Eastern Europe at the end of the last decade and the beginning of the current one opened an important market for attracting foreign direct investment. The size of the domestic demand, significantly affected and limited by the economic downturn that has accompanied, at least for a while, the transition to a market economy, remains a major one. A number of other factors, such as low production costs, especially that of the labor force, its high degree of qualification, the existence of an appropriate infrastructure, moreover, the adoption of liberal regulations and incentives for foreign investors, are major elements to attract FDI both within the EU and outside it.

Tabel 9. Foreign direct investments (FDI) accumulated in the economy of the Republic of Moldova (end-of-period stock, mil. \$)

Indicators	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Accumulated FDI in the national economy, total	2809	3139,3	3329,6	3568,9	3603,8
Growth rate of FDI, in %, compared to previous year	105,7	111,8	106,1	107,2	100,1

Source: Ministry of Economy

Until the last decade of the 20th century, Moldova's foreign economic relations were 96% oriented to the east, while the contact with the Western European countries was limited. Gradually there was a reorientation of economic flows to other markets, the nearest and the most attractive one being the EU. The gradual liberalization of trade was originally made in foreign trade, then in the field of foreign capital investment and labor migration. If the geographical reorientation of foreign trade to the Community market was slower because of objective reasons, then foreign investment flows from EU countries compared with those received from CIS countries were much larger due to the financial possibilities of EU Member States.

The ratio of investments in Moldova's economy by the two geo-economical spaces denotes the financial superiority EU Member States, even if the investment climate in our country was not very attractive for the capital of Member States.

The structure of FDI in the Republic of Moldova from EU states, 01.01.2015

Country	Invested capital (mln MDL)	%	Number of enterprises	%
Netherlands	2025,6	20,5	149	1,7
Italy	1330,7	13,5	972	11,3
Cyprus	833,2	8,4	273	3,2
Germany	590,5	6,0	388	4,5
Great Britain	456,2	4,6	208	2,4
Romania	452,0	4,6	1327	15,5
Spain	318,1	3,2	62	0,7

Poland	198,6	2,0	68	0,8
Bulgaria	51,9	0,5	165	2,0
Total	9875	100	8566	100

Source: Adapted according to State Registration Chamber of the Republic of Moldova <http://www.cis.gov.md/statistica#g>, accessed on 28.01.2015

According to the number of enterprises with foreign capital, EU countries far outweigh the CIS. Thus, at 01.01.2013, from the total number of enterprises with foreign capital (8566) recorded by the State Registration Chamber of Moldova, 1327 were from Romania, which constitutes about 15% of the total, followed by Italy and Germany, with 972 (11.3%) and 388 (4.5%) enterprises respectively. This situation is explained by the geographical proximity of Moldova to Romania, but also by historical and cultural affinities between them. Geoeconomic and geopolitical position as an important link with the Eastern market resulted in the transfer of activities from Romania to Moldova. The large number of companies with foreign capital from Italy could be explained by established business relationships of our migrant compatriots as Italy is one of the preferred destinations of labor migration from Moldova.

Conclusions:

1. Currently the European Union presents itself as a power pole of the world economy. Economic power derives from Member States' synergy. Member States have passed through all stages of economic integration; market integration preceded the integration of economic policies. Although more competences were transferred from the national level to EU level, now we can make reference more to economies with common rules rather than a single economy.

2. The basis of formation of a united Europe served premises of historical, economic, and social order. Ensuring economic and social prosperity of Europe, in qualified and tough competition with other centers of economic power in the world, has become possible only through common economic, strategic (political), social (demographic, civilization), etc. efforts. Economic project, originally drawn, extended to the political dimension, resulting in the revival of Europe after a long period of recession that followed the Second World War. Undoubtedly the EU is currently a successful economic project, despite numerous periods of economic recession and challenges to which it is and was exposed.

3. The economic structure of the Member States followed the classical model of the developed countries, namely economic tertiarization with an increased productivity in the primary and secondary sectors. The same model follows the recently adhered EU states (mostly former socialist states of Eastern Europe) by continuous transformations and adaptations that followed in the process of integration to the single market and common economic policy. Although more recently adhered countries achieved great economic and social performance in the post-accession period, they remain far behind the group of so-called EU-15.

4. Analysis of data and economic indicators denote large differences between the Central and Northern European countries compared with South and East European countries. The division between EU-15 and EU-13 is not only symbolic, but confirmed by significant quantitative and qualitative differences of the indicators taken into consideration for comparative analysis.

5. The Republic of Moldova, a state with European aspirations, redirected its economic exchanges in the period of state independence to European integration. The biggest part of foreign capital investments from EU Member States entered the economy of the country; foreign trade now exceeds 50% of total trade. Some other economic flows have also increased on the European dimension, even if there is still no agreement which would specify integrationist finality of our country. It is very important for the authorities to maintain the European vector through reforms in all fields. The beneficial effects of European course are present more and more, which gives pro-European political parties basis to demonstrate through concrete actions continuity in European course.

6. Almost all the benefits of Moldova are related to the agro-food and textile industry. This shows the vulnerability of the national economy, considering the high competition on EU market towards which Moldova has reoriented. In perspective it would be better to focus on human capital intensive industries, particularly skilled labor force and relatively cheap, which could create products and services with high added value in this respect attracting foreign capital. We should learn from the experience of Asian emerging markets by moving from the stage “Made in Moldova” to “Created in Moldova”.

7. Investment policy should be directed towards strategic areas of Moldova (ICT, manufacturing, branches and areas that would contribute to import substitution etc.), taking into account the balanced territorial development.

Bibliography:

1. Camera Înregistrării de Stat, Ministerul Justiției, <http://www.cis.gov.md/content/6>.
2. Central Intelligence Agency, www.cia.gov/library.
3. Cheibaș, R. Respecialization of transition countries and reorientation of trade flows, Chișinău, Litera, 2002.
4. Mehedinți, S., Tufescu, V. Terra - introduction to geography as a science. Bucharest, Ed. Enciclopedică, 1994.
5. Moldovan, D., Benea, E., Stratan, A. Moldova's European integration: premises, benefits and lost opportunities. Chișinău, Ed. Știința 2009.
6. Moldovan, D. "Moldovan economy in the trap of globalization and transition". Chișinău, Ed. ARC, 2004.
7. Organisation mondiale du commerce. http://www.wto.org/french/res_f/statis_f/statis_bis_f.htm?solution=WTO&path=/Dashboards.
8. Republic of Moldova 2013: State of the Country Report. Expert-Grup, Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, Chișinău, 2013.
9. Șișcan, Z., Hachi, M. Evolution and prospects of economic relations between Moldova and the European Union, <http://www.studiieu.org/files/publications/SE%202-2013.pdf>.
10. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. http://unctad.org/en/publicationslibrary/wir2013_en.pdf.
11. Your key to European statistics. <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do>.

Copyright©Mihai HACHI
Copyright©Corina CIUMAC

New Sources of Own Resources of the European Union

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Agnieszka KłOS

aklos1@sgh.waw.pl

Warsaw School of Economics, Poland

Abstract: The goal of this article is to present the problem of the EU in obtaining new own resources based on VAT and financial transaction taxes. The article elaborates on the sources of own resources of the European Union, proposed changes in how VAT is calculated by Member States in line with the European Commission's proposals, the pros and cons of the current VAT calculation methods and of the method put forward in the Commission's proposals. The article indicates actions aimed at modernizing the administration of the VAT system, which the Member States should take. Work on this article involved the utilization of research methods such as analysis and synthesis based on drafts of legal acts, documents and literature.

Key-words: budget of the European Union, new own resources of the EU, reform of EU revenues.

Introduction

The European Communities, which were formed in the 1950s and later transformed into the European Union, were to undertake all measures to reduce disparities in economic development between Member States and their regions. These objectives were achieved, among others, through the implementation of trade policies, agricultural policies, cohesion policies, competition policies and others. The need to obtain funds in order to effectively complete the tasks that were brought on by treaties and other legislation was an inextricable part of the functioning of the European Union and its strive to fulfil its own objectives. The goal of this article is to present the problem of the EU in obtaining new own resources based on VAT and financial transaction taxes. The article elaborates on the sources of own resources of the European Union, proposed changes in how VAT is calculated by Member States in line with the European Commission's proposals, the pros and cons of the current VAT calculation methods and of the method put forward in the Commission's proposals. In addition, the article indicates actions aimed at modernizing the administration of the VAT system, which the Member States should take. Work on this article involved

the utilization of research methods such as analysis and synthesis based on drafts of legal acts, documents and literature.

Multiannual financial framework as a financing plan of the European Union

Since December 1, 2009, when the Lisbon Treaty entered into force, the European Union has become an international organization with legal personality. The Treaty is not a new constitution; however, it is based on the EU Treaty and the Treaty establishing the European Community (currently called the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, TFEU).

Due to the tasks that rest with the European Union as an international organization a need exists to obtain funds and develop a financial plan (a so-called financial framework) to execute tasks. Work on the financial framework, just as on the annual EU budget, concerns both expenditures and revenues and all planned spendings must be covered by adequate funds that will allow the European Union to implement the objectives given in a financial perspective¹.

In the 1980s a system to improve the functioning of the budgetary procedure was created. Based on an interinstitutional agreement, the European Parliament, the Council, and the Commission draw up the main budgetary priorities for several years in advance. The interinstitutional agreement contains rules and procedures for the annual revision of the multiannual financial framework (i.e. technical adjustments, adjustments related to or designed to prepare for the enlargement of the EU and procedures for changing the financial framework). This allows improving the functioning of the annual budgetary procedure. Each year the Commission, acting on its own responsibility, makes technical adjustments to the financial framework for the upcoming year. These concern adjusting for the inflation rate to maintain the original purchasing power at ceiling level for each department. Technical adjustments are usually done at the end of year n-2 for year n, based on latest data and available economic forecasts. The ceiling of own resources is expressed as percentage of GNI. Therefore, the technical adjustment ought to be based on the latest EU GNI data. It is in those

¹ E. Małuszyńska, M. Sapała, *Multiannual financial framework of the European Union for 2014-2020*, p. 111.

circumstances that the balance between total appropriations for payments and available own resources is verified.

The Commission may also present a proposal of financial adjustments to the two arms of the budgetary authority in the following two cases:

- reallocation of payment appropriations available for the structural actions in the event of a delay in the programming of such activities;
- reassessment of needs within some departments in connection with the accession of new Member States.

At the request of the Commission both arms of the budgetary authority may introduce changes into the financial framework. This allows the EU to take action, in accordance with the ceiling of own resources, in the event of circumstances which could not have been foreseen at the time when the financial perspective was determined.

Sources of own resources of the European Union

The general budget of the European Union is, with no prejudice to other revenues, financed entirely from own resources of the Communities. In Council Decision of 7 June 2007 on the system of own resources of the European Communities¹ sources of those resources were indicated. EU's own resources system must ensure adequate resources for the EU policies in specific areas in an orderly manner, taking into account the need for strict budgetary discipline. At the same time no Member State shall sustain a budgetary burden which is excessive in relation to its relative prosperity. For the purposes of this Decision, gross national income (GNI) is defined as annual GNI at market prices as provided by the Commission in application of the European system of national and regional accounts in the Community (referred to as ESA). The Commission communicated the new ceilings to the Council and the European Parliament on 28 December 2001. The ceiling of own resources was then set at 1.24 % of the total GNIs of the Member States at market prices and a ceiling of 1.31 % of the total GNIs of the Member States was set for appropriations for commitments².

The revenue from the following sources is what constitutes own resources entered in the general budget of the European Union:

¹ 2007/436/EC, EURATOM, OJ EU of 23.06.2007, L 163/17.

² Ibidem.

- a) levies, premiums, additional or compensatory amounts, additional amounts or factors, Common Customs Tariff duties and other duties established or to be established by the institutions of the Communities in respect of trade with non-member countries, custom duties on products under the expired Treaty establishing the European Coal and Steel Community as well as contributions and other duties provided for within the framework of the common organisation of the markets in sugar;
- b) revenue deriving from any new charges introduced within the framework of a common policy, in accordance with the EC Treaty or the Euratom Treaty also constitute own resources entered in the general budget of the European Union¹;
- c) other revenues (about 1 %) include taxes and other deductions from salaries of the employees of EU institutions, bank interests, contributions by non-EU countries for some programs, interest on late payments and fines²;
- d) VAT.

The Member States retain 25% of the amounts referred to in point a) as collection costs that is to cover the costs related to customs administration. In accordance with Council Decision a uniform rate is applied valid for all Member States to the harmonised VAT assessment bases determined according to Community rules. The basis for calculations is not to exceed 50% of the GNI for each Member State. The uniform rate has been fixed at 0.30% and it remains valid for the 2014-2020 financial perspective³. As for the Value Added Tax (VAT), the European Council decided on a uniform rate of call and exceptions were made for Austria, Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden, as well as additional UK corrections were introduced⁴. UK corrections is an agreement concluded in

¹ Art. 2 Council Decision of 7 June 2007 on the system of the European Communities own resources.

² http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-1004_pl.htm [accessed on 26.08.2014].

³ For the period 2007–2013 the VAT rate of call for Austria was set at 0.225 %, for Germany – at 0.15 %, and for the Netherlands and Sweden – at 0.10%.

⁴ In the 2014-2020 financial perspective: Denmark, the Netherlands and Sweden will benefit from gross reductions in their annual GNI contribution of EUR 130 million, EUR 695 million and EUR 185 million respectively; Austria will benefit from gross reduction in its annual GNI

Fontainebleau, 1984, which granted the UK a rebate based on the difference between its participation in VAT payments and its participation in the Community's expenditures. This meant a reduction in the UK VAT base, and the costs of that reduction were to be financed by all Member States in proportion to their VAT contributions; with the exception of Germany, which was granted a rate reduced by 1/3 to UK correction. As a result three VAT rates were introduced – applying accordingly to the UK, Germany and other Member States. These were meant to be transitional measures; however, these provisions remain in force to this day¹.

Customs duties are levied when goods are imported from non-member countries (they are levied uniformly on the basis of the Common Customs Tariff) and the fees on producers of sugar and isoglucose are levied within the common organization of the sugar market. These fees are collected from traders (importers) and collected by the state on behalf of the EU, which is a customs union. Each Member State transfers $\frac{3}{4}$ of its revenue from customs duties and agricultural levies to the EU budget².

Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1311/2013 of 2 December 2013 on the 2014-2020 multiannual financial framework³ maintained the ceiling of own resources for MFF 2014-2020 at the level of 1.24% GNI, which was introduced by Council Decision 2007/436/EC, Euratom. For each of the years covered by the MFF, the total appropriations for payments required, after annual adjustment and taking account of any other adjustments and revisions is not be such as to produce a call-in rate for own resources that exceeds the own resources ceiling set in accordance with Decision

contribution of EUR 30 million in 2014, EUR 20 million in 2015 and EUR 10 million in 2016; reduced VAT call rates for Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden will be fixed at 0.15%. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-1004_pl.htm [accessed on 26.08.2014]; see also L. Skiba, *The Budget of the European Union*.

¹ European Parliament, working document on own resource based on the value added tax, Committee on Budgets, 19.06.2012, PE491.364v01-00, pp. 5-6.

² E. Kawecka-Wyrzykowska, VAT as an EU budget resource (a study prepared at the request of the Office for European Integration in Poland in the framework of consultations on the EU Budget Reform), p. 5.

³ OJ EU of 20.12.2013 L 347/884.

2007/436/EC, Euratom¹. For MFF 2014-2020 the level was set at 1% of GNI for payments and 1.05% for commitments.

New rules for obtaining own resources for the European Union

Own resources based on VAT were introduced in 1970 as potentially genuine own resources on the assumption that a continuous process of harmonization of laws of various countries in the field of VAT would lead to full harmonization of the national bases of value added tax. However, 42 years later, with 21 new countries having joined the EU, a reverse trend can be observed. Own resources based on VAT are becoming more intricate and their calculations more complex and less understandable. As the European Parliament has observed, what was once seen as genuine own resources based on VAT has nowadays transformed into a purely statistical device, which is just another derivative of GNI and is transferred from national budgets. On 29 June 2011, the Commission presented its proposals for new multiannual financial frameworks for 2014–2020, jointly with a set of proposals on the reform of the European Union’s own resources system. Those include a proposal for the VII Own Resources Decision that call for the abolition of the existing VAT own resource and its replacement by a new EU VAT resource that is based on a simplified and more transparent calculation method, but does not entail the creation of a new pan-European VAT².

Existing legal framework concerning the VAT as own resource of the EU was introduced by the following legal acts:

- Council Own Resources Decision (ORD) 2007/436 and
- Council Regulation (EEC, EURATOM) No 1553/89 of 29 May 1989 on the definitive uniform arrangements for the collection of own resources accruing from value added tax³.

Council Regulation No 1553/89 defines the technical arrangements for the VAT calculation. What is more, it states the rules of informing the Commission by Member States about their procedures for registering taxable persons, determining VAT and VAT collection and about existing

¹ Art. 4 of Council Regulation (EU, EURATOM) No 1311/2013 of 2 December 2013 laying down the multiannual financial framework for the years 2014-2020.

² European Parliament, Working document on own resource based on the value added tax, p. 2.

³ OJ L 155 of 7.6.1989, p. 9; as last amended by Council Regulation (EC) No 807/2003 of 14 April 2003.

forms and results of their VAT control systems. Pursuant to that regulation, the Commission, together with a given Member State, can consider whether the national practice of the Member State in concern can be improved in regard to its efficiency. To this end, every three years the Commission prepares a report on procedures in Member States and possible improvements.

The Lisbon Treaty significantly changed the EU's legal architecture in relation to own resources. Article 311 of the TFEU provides that *"without prejudice to other revenue, the budget shall be financed wholly from own resources"* and that the Council *"may establish new categories of own resources or abolish an existing category"*. Additionally, the Treaty provides that the Council may lay down implementing measures for the Union's own resources system by means of regulations in accordance with a special legislative procedure and after obtaining the consent of the European Parliament. Whereas Article 322§2 of the TFEU lays down provisions on the methods and procedures whereby the budget revenue provided under the arrangements relating to the Union's own resources *"shall be made available"* to the Commission. On the basis of the above, the Commission's proposals on the VAT own resources related to (see also ill. 1):

A. Council decision on the system of own resources of the EU¹, which envisaged the termination of the current VAT as of 31 December 2013 and the creation of a new resource based on EU VAT. It was also proposed to maintain traditional own resources and apply a uniform rate based on the total GNI of all Member States. The proposal also included an introduction of two new categories of own resources:

- a financial transaction tax (FTT) – its share is not to exceed the minimum rates set out in FTT Directive²;
- new resources based on VAT – which shall not exceed 2% of the standard rate of VAT in every Member State.

A share in taxes and the rate of call of own resources are determined by Council regulations laying down implementing measures. In the new decision the collection costs have been set at 10% for traditional own

¹ European Commission, amended proposal for a Council Decision on the system of own resources of the European Union.

² That is 0.1% for financial transactions other than ones relating to derivative instruments and 0.01% for financial transactions regarding derivative instruments.

resources (compared to 25% today). It was also suggested to change the ceiling on own resources from 1.24% to 1.23% of the sum of the Member States' GNIs at market prices for appropriations for payments and set the ceiling for appropriations for commitments at 1.29 % of the sum of the Member States' GNIs. The proposal for the Council decision also envisaged abolishing the UK correction and other existing rebates and replacing them, as of January 2014, by a new system of lump sums in the form of reductions in the annual GNI-based contributions – Germany (EUR 2 500 million), the Netherlands (EUR 1 500 million), Sweden (EUR 350 million) and the United Kingdom (EUR 3 600 million)¹.

B. Council regulation laying down implementing measures for the system of own resources of the European Union, which set out the applicable shares and rates for own resources based on FTT and VAT, such as:

- EU VAT: at 1.0% of the net value of goods or services subject to a standard VAT in all Member States;
- FTT: 2/3 of the minimum rates set out in the FTT Directive shall be used as a share of own resources.

The regulation also defines the method of calculation of the reference GNI and of the budgetary balance and it sets all the necessary provisions concerning control and supervision².

C. Council regulation on the methods and procedure for making available the traditional and GNI-based own resources and on the measures to meet cash requirements, which is necessary to define the method Member States should use to calculate the new resource as well as the procedures for making it available to EU budget³. The objective of the proposal was to ensure that *“cash requirements will be met under the new structure of EU financing introduced by the proposal for a Council Decision on the system of own resources of the European Union and these new proposals”*. Thus, the document defined the procedures for making available

¹ European Parliament, Working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, pp. 5-6; see also European Commission, amended proposal for a Council Decision on the system of own resources of the European Union.

² Ibidem.

³ European Parliament, Working document on own resource based on the value added tax, pp. 3-4.

the EU VAT by Member States, i.e. practical guidelines on accounting principles and administrative arrangements, the timing for making own VAT-based resources available (a system of monthly reports), interest in case of delay as well as putting forward a notion to create a comitology procedure (an advisory committee on own resource). The analysis of the current system shows that up to two twelfths of GNI-based and current VAT own resources are systematically brought forward in the first quarter of the year to cover cash requirements due mainly to expenditure of the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF). The structure of EU financing is expected to change considerably with the ending of the current VAT own resource and the introduction of new own resources as from 1 January 2014. The estimated share of the GNI-based and the current VAT own resources in EU budget revenue for 2012 is 85% (74% and 11%, respectively). In 2020, the current VAT own resource will no longer exist while it is estimated that the share of the GNI-based own resource will fall to 40%. This means that the share of own resources based on a regular financial stream, pre-defined in the context of the budgetary procedure, will be halved compared to today. Similarly, advance payments of twelfths of the corresponding GNI-based own resource will only bring cash to EU budget for about half of the current amounts, *ceteris paribus*. The possibility of calling in advance other own resources, in particular the proposed new own resources based on VAT and on the FTT, appear less practicable. Those resources will be based on actual receipts collected by the Member States and the amounts made available to EU budget will fluctuate accordingly. Organizing a payment of twelfths would require mechanisms of forecasts, and subsequent adjustments or balances' exercises, thus making the system unnecessarily complex. Since it can be assumed that cash requirements will be in excess of the assets of the accounts in the first quarter of every year, even after calling in advance two GNI twelfths, it is proposed to double the number of twelfths available in advance (from two to four) in order to compensate the decrease of the GNI share in EU financing¹.

¹ European Parliament, Working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 6; see also European Commission, amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedure for making available the traditional and GNI-based own resources and on the measures to meet cash requirements.

D. Council Directive on a common system of financial transaction tax. The purpose of the proposal is to create a financial transaction tax at EU level, which could that fully or partly serve as own resources in EU budget. The proposal specified minimum rates for the FTT: 0.1% in respect of the financial transactions other than those related to derivatives agreements and 0.01% in respect of financial transactions related to derivative agreements¹. This Directive applies to all financial transaction, such as purchase and sale of financial instruments, e.g. shares, bonds, foreign exchange instruments, units in collective investment undertakings, structured products and derivatives as well as concluding or modifying derivative contracts, provided that at least one party to the transaction is established in the territory of a participating Member State and that a financial institution (investment firms, organised markets, credit institutions, insurance and reinsurance undertakings, collective investment undertakings and their managers, pension funds and their managers, other institutions or bodies, for which financial transactions are an important part of their portfolio) established in the territory of a participating Member State is party to the transaction, acting either for its own account or for the account of another person or is acting in the name of a party to the transaction. The following entities have been excluded from the scope of this directive:

- European Financial Stability Facility;
- international financial organisations established by at least two Member States, which aim to mobilise funding and provide financial assistance to the benefit of its members that are experiencing or threatened by severe financing problems;
- Central Counter Parties (CCPs), meaning legal entities that mediate between parties of a financial transaction;
- national and international central securities depositories.

This Directive does not apply to the following transactions:

- primary market transactions, especially relating to the issuing of shares and bonds;
- in some cases, transactions with the European Union, the European Atomic Energy Community, the European Investment Bank and with

¹ European Parliament, Working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 7.

bodies set up by the European Union or the European Atomic Energy Community and other international organizations and institutions;
- transactions with the central banks of Member States.

The FTT becomes chargeable for each financial transaction at the moment it occurs. Subsequent cancellation or rectification of a financial transaction has no effect on chargeability, except for cases of errors. In the case of financial transactions other than those relating to derivative instruments, the taxable amount is everything which constitutes consideration paid or owed, in return for the transfer, from the counterparty or a third party. In the case of financial transactions related to derivative contracts the taxable amount of the FTT is the notional amount referred to in the derivatives contract at the time of the financial transaction. Notional amount means the underlying nominal or face amount that is used to calculate payments made on a given derivative contract. In cases when the value is expressed in a foreign currency, the applicable exchange rate shall be the latest selling rate recorded at the time the FTT becomes chargeable on the most representative exchange market of the participating Member State concerned or at an exchange rate determined by reference to that market¹.

E. Council Regulation on the methods and procedure for making available own resources based on the financial transaction tax. This proposal sets the method and the procedures for Member States to make the FTT-based own resource available to EU budget. In doing so, it spells out the practical arrangements in respect to the accounting and administrative arrangements, the timing for making the FTT own resources available (system of monthly reports), interest in cases of delay, etc. It also proposes the setting of a committee procedure (an advisory committee on own resources) in connection with implementing powers proposed to be given in parallel to the Commission to ensure uniform conditions for the implementation of this regulation².

¹ http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/internal_market/single_market_services/financial_services_general_framework/mi0087_pl.html [accessed on 26.08.2014].

² European Parliament, Working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 7; see also amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedures for making available the own resource based on the financial transaction tax.

F. Council Regulation on the methods and procedure for making available own resources based on VAT. This regulation is necessary to define the method Member States should use to calculate the new resource as well as the procedures for making it available to EU budget. It proposes a new calculation method and also – alike the proposal concerning the Council's regulation on methods and procedures for making available own resources based on FTT – it defines the procedures for making EU VAT available by Member States: guidelines on accounting principles and administrative arrangements, the timing for making own VAT-based resources available (a system of monthly reports), interest in case of delay, as well as putting forward a notion to create a comitology procedure (an advisory committee on own resource)¹.

Proposed changes ought to increase the volume of own resources. According to estimations presented in Table 1, an increase in EU budget revenues would occur: from EUR 131.1 billion resulting from the current system of obtaining own resources (data for 2012) to EUR 162.7 billion in 2020. This increase would stem from the inclusion of the financial transaction tax to the current system of obtaining own resources and to the introduction of a harmonised EU VAT for Member States (see Table 1).

¹ European Parliament, Working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 7; see also European Commission, amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedures for making available the own resource based on the value added tax.

ill. 1 European Commission proposal package on own resources

Source: European Parliament, working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 3.

Table 1. Changes in the structure of own resources

Estimated impact on own resources structure	2012		2020	
	Bil. EUR	% of OR	Bil. EUR	% of OR
Traditional own resources	19,3	14,7	30,7	18,9
Existing national contributions	111,8	85,3	65,6	40,3
of which:				
- VAT-based OR	14,5	11,1		
- DNB-based OR	97,3	74,2	65,6	40,3
New own resources			66,4	40,8
of which:				
- EU VAT			29,4	18,1
- EU financial transaction tax			37,0	22,7
Total own resources	131,1	100	162,7	100

Source: European Parliament, working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, p. 4

The advantages and disadvantages of introducing the new method for calculation of the VAT-based own resource

The procedure of calculating the current VAT-based own resource is incomprehensible to the average European citizen. What is more, besides the complexity of the very method of calculating current rates, the procedure involves rebates and corrections to rebates. As the Court of Auditors has stated in a response to the Commission's communication ("Reforming the Budget, Changing Europe"): the system is "not fully auditable"¹. Finally, the current system is a considerable financial burden on Member States as they have to maintain adequate administrative resources, which have to collect a large amount of data and perform a range of complex calculations in order to calculate the VAT share they have to submit to the EU.

¹ European Parliament, Working document on own resource based on the value added tax, p. 9.

The new EU VAT own resource is based on a share of the VAT on supplies of goods and services, acquisitions and importations “subject to a standard rate of VAT in every Member State”. It moves, therefore, from a theoretical concept of the statistically-estimated current VAT to the actual harmonisation that already exists in those goods and services with a standard rate across the EU. In addition, the new system moves the largest share of calculations currently done by Member States to the European Commission¹.

A percentage rate set out in implementing Council Regulation on own resources should be applied to the actual value of the VAT own resources base (maximum rate (2%) is set in ORD with operative rate (1% in implementing Regulation)².

Among the advantages of the new method for calculation of the VAT-based own resources the following should be named:

- increased transparency since the calculation will be based only on goods and services taxed by the standard VAT rate in all Member States and only real actual receipts obtained by Members will be used;
- less corrections to the VAT base for some Member States (only fines and penalties, refunds to non-taxable persons, receipts from non-EU territories, account for multiple standard rates), compared to the currently existing 22 compensations;
- only goods and services taxed with the standard VAT rate will be used for the calculations, equal treatment of all EU Member States – there will be a uniform percentage applicable to all Member States, contrary to the current different call in rates;
- focus on materiality: the new resource will be based on actual receipts and not statistics;
- no capping will be applied;

¹ European Parliament, Working document on own resource based on the value added tax, p. 10.

² Ibidem, p. 12.

- the system is flexible and could adapt to any future reform of the VAT tax without the need to introduce changes to the current own resources proposal¹.

Disadvantages of the system include a still relatively complicated methodology, involving several steps and complex calculations. Moreover, the new VAT will still not be an own resource directly accruing to EU budget but will pass through national treasuries².

Recommendations regarding the modernisation of the administration of the VAT system in Member States

Council Regulation No 1553/891 on the definitive uniform arrangements for the collection of own resources accruing from value added tax requires the Commission to prepare a report on procedures in Member States for registering taxable persons, determining VAT and VAT collection and about existing forms and results of their VAT control systems. This report is to be done every three years and presented to the European Parliament and the European Council. Since 1989 seven reports have been handed in, the most recent one (the seventh one) was handed in on 12 February 2014. It included conclusions from audits carried out since 2011, during which a need for modernisation of the VAT administration in Member States was observed. Ever since the beginning of the recession and the financial crisis in 2008, the VAT gap has grown being estimated at around 1.5% of the GDP of EU-26 in 2011. However, there are great disparities in the VAT gaps of individual Member States. In particular, Member States that are harder hit by the crisis have been struggling with a larger VAT gap and have not been able to improve their situation substantially over time. However, as the VAT gap also constitutes an indicator of the efficiency and effectiveness of VAT administration, Member States will have no choice but to modernise VAT administration in order to reduce the VAT gap. This is not only important from the perspective of VAT revenue and own resources, but also from the perspective of businesses and governments when dealing with administrative costs. Modernisation of VAT administration is crucial and inevitable for those Member States that are

¹ European Parliament, Working document on own resource based on the value added tax, p. 13.

² Ibidem.

hardest hit by the financial crisis and that have difficulties handling their budgetary deficits. If these Member States are willing to change established administrative practices and to improve their administrative processes, they can really gain substantial benefits from modernisation¹.

Actions to be taken by Member States have been grouped according to main thematic areas:

1. VAT identification, registration and deregistration: Member States need to improve the quality of the information available in foreign languages on the requirements and process of VAT registration. At the same time, they also need to develop an end-to-end process for registration, especially by implementing post-registration monitoring programs for risky traders and fast-track deregistration processes for missing (disappearing) traders. Poland is not among countries to which these suggestions were addressed.

2. Customs Procedure 42: Member States should ensure that the VAT identification numbers (of both the importers and the customers) are systematically checked and that all information on the transaction is transmitted domestically to the tax administration. These recommendations were addressed also to Poland. What is more, Poland and a few other Member States are required to identify Customs Procedure 42 as an additional risk in domestic risk analysis systems and reinforce the exchange of information on fraudulent transactions and traders, among others by actively participating in Eurofisc.

3. Filing VAT returns and VAT payments: most Member States (including Poland) still need to implement a systematic approach to monitor late and non-filing and payment of VAT. The Member States are strongly recommended to investigate the efficiency of their interest and penalties schemes for late and non-filing and payment of VAT.

4. VAT collection and VAT recovery: in general, half of the Member States (Poland excluded) must implement write-off procedures for debts proven uncollectable at a reasonable cost. Without an on-going write-off programme, the tax administration risks wasting valuable resources pursuing uncollectable amounts. Additionally, Member States should

¹ European Commission, Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament, Seventh report under Article 12 of Regulation (EEC, Euratom), p. 13.

develop non-sequential and integrated debt collection processes – this includes Poland as well.

5. VAT audit and investigation: the recommendations include, on one hand, the abolition of obligatory audits of certain taxpayers for all years and, on the other hand, the application of risk-based system. These suggestions are addressed to Poland as well.

6. Tax dispute resolution system: a number of Member States (Poland excluded) should consider implementation of a compulsory independent administrative dispute resolution process whereby the disputed amounts remain fully or partly collectable during the appeal procedure

7. VAT compliance: Member States need to (further) develop and implement compliance risk management strategies and to assess the outcome of the measures implemented in order to identify best strategies to influence behaviour of taxpayers to voluntarily comply with their tax obligations. This recommendation is addressed to Poland as well¹.

Conclusions

The need to obtain funds in order to effectively complete the tasks that were brought on by treaties and other legislation is an inextricable part of the functioning of the European Union and its strive to fulfil its own objectives. This article presented the problem of obtaining new own resources by the European Union in the form of a uniform VAT, which would apply equally to all Member States and in the form of a financial transaction tax. These issues have been widely discussed in recent times. Despite the efforts made, these taxes will not be typical own resources, which directly accrue to EU budget, because they will need to first pass through national treasuries or through economic entities (in the case of the financial transaction tax) and will still be dependent on the system and tax rates in a given Member State. The amount of VAT paid to the general budget of the European Union is therefore heavily dependent on the tax system of a Member State and its fiscal and budgetary policies. Every three years the Commission carries out an audit of the effectiveness of the system and prepares proposals, which the Member States should implement in order to

¹ European Commission, Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament, Seventh report under Article 12 of Regulation (EEC, Euratom), pp. 14-15.

improve the financial condition of EU budget and to enable the EU to implement its public policies. In the current socio-economic realities, the need to seek for new sources of obtaining funds for the general budget of the European Union can prove challenging for Member States that face problems concerning the stability of their own public finance system (e.g. Member States that are subject to the excessive deficit procedure). The system of obtaining funds that are based on VAT is based on budget revenue of a Member State, which means that a share of VAT revenues is transferred to the general budget of the EU, which in consequence could prejudice budget revenues of a given Member State and affect its ability to fulfil its responsibilities towards its citizens. The need to find additional revenues may in fact lead to fiscal tightening in the Member States in order to increase the tax base and to thus increase budget revenues. This is of considerable importance also because Member States are required to comply with appropriate budgetary procedures (arrangements established in the so-called six-pack) that stabilize public finances.

Bibliography:

1. Council Decision of 7 June 2007 on the system of the European Communities own resources, 2007/436/EC, Euratom, OJ EU of 23.06.2007 L 163/17.
2. European Commission, amended proposal for a Council Decision on the system of own resources of the European Union, Brussels, 9.11.2011, COM(2011) 739 final version.
3. European Commission, amended proposal for a Council Regulation laying down implementing measures for the system of own resources of the European Union, Brussels, 9.11.2011, COM(2011) 740 final version.
4. European Commission, amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedure for making available the traditional and GNI-based own resources and on the measures to meet cash requirements, Brussels, 9.11.2011, COM(2011) 742 final version.
5. European Commission, amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedures for making available the own resource based on the financial transaction tax, Brussels, 9.11.2011 COM(2011) 738 final version.

6. European Commission, amended proposal for Council Regulation on the methods and procedures for making available the own resource based on the value added tax, Brussels, 9.11.2011, COM(2011) 737 final version.
7. European Commission, Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament, Seventh report under Article 12 of Regulation (EEC, Euratom) No 1553/89 on VAT collection and control procedures, 12.02.2014, COM(2014) 69 final version.
8. European Parliament, working document No 1 on the system of own resources of the European Union, Committee on Budgets, 1.12.2011, PE478.360v01-00.
9. European Parliament, working document on own resource based on the value added tax, Committee on Budgets, 19.06.2012, PE491.364v01-00.
10. Council Regulation (EEC, Euratom) No 1553/89 of 29 May 1989 on the definitive uniform arrangements for the collection of own resources accruing from value added tax OJ L 155 of 7.6.1989, p. 9; as last amended by Council Regulation (EC) No 807/2003 of 14 April 2003.
11. Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 1311/2013 of 2 December 2013 laying down the multiannual financial framework for the years 2014-2020, OJ EU of 20.12.2013, L 347/884.
12. EUR lex Access to European Union law. http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/budget/l34012_pl.htm [accessed on 24.08.2014].
13. EUR lex Access to European Union law. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-1004_pl.htm [accessed on 26.08.2014].
14. EUR lex Access to European Union law. http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/internal_market/single_market_services/financial_services_general_framework/mi0087_pl.htm [accessed on 26.08.2014].
15. Kawecka-Wyrzykowska E., *VAT as an EU budget resource* (a study prepared at the request of the Office for European Integration in Poland in the framework of consultations on the EU Budget Reform), Warsaw, January, 2008.
16. Małuszyńska E., M. Sapała, *Multiannual financial framework of the European Union for 2014-2020*, Sejm's Office of Analyses, No. 3(31) 2012.

17. Skiba L., *The Budget of the European Union*. In: P. Kowalewski, G. Tchorek, J. Górski, (ed.), *The Mechanisms of the Euro Area*, National Bank of Poland, Warsaw, 2010.

Copyright©Agnieszka KŁOS

ISTORIE POLITICĂ / POLITICAL HISTORY

Governarea de coaliție: posibilități de aplicare eficientă a resurselor puterii politice

Prof. univ. dr. hab. Ludmila ROȘCA

rosca@irim.md

Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Moldova
ECSA-Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: Actuality and practical significance of the study are determined by numerous political crises caused by in the coalition government in Moldova, supported by three pro-European parties: LDPM, DP, LP, which for 5 years constituted three alliances: EIA-1; EIA-2; EIA-3. There are applied different theoretical concepts on coalition governance, participatory democracy, political culture, political culture of participation, in order to highlight the effective application possibilities of political power's resources, state power. The author argues that the coalition governance can achieve its political, economic and social programme only in strict compliance with the principles of political power: reality, measure, legitimacy, accountability, collegiality, consensus, transparency. All these ensure the efficiency of any governance, including the coalition one.

Key-words: coalition governance, political culture, political culture of participation, participatory democracy, principles of political power, consensus.

Governarea de coaliție este o temă a teoriei politice, care avansează pe agenda savanților europeni. Descifrarea secretelor guvernării de coaliție este un obiectiv important al cercetărilor aplicative din motiv că democrația liberală este caracterizată de pluralism de opinii și pluripartitism. Actualitatea și semnificația acestui studiu este susținută de modificările din realitatea politică a Republicii Moldova, care la moment este guvernată de o coaliție formal minoritară. În acest studiu ne propunem să valorificăm experiența altor state, conduse de coaliții de guvernământ, să sensibilizăm opinia publică, oferindu-i electoratului din Republica Moldova posibilitatea cunoașterii conținutului celor două fenomene: guvernarea de coaliție și cultura politică participativă. Considerăm important momentul cunoașterii celor două fenomene, deoarece doar în așa caz, atât conducătorii instituțiilor de stat, cât și cetățenii vor reuși să le coreleze prin acțiuni adecvate. Asimilarea principalelor concepte și abordări teoretice a

guvernării de coaliție ne permite să constatăm că succesele partidelor care își unesc eforturile, resursele, orientându-le către realizarea unui scop, este determinat de mai mulți factori, printre care dominanți sunt: cultura politică participativă, democrația liberală, pluripartitismul moderat, o clasă politică responsabilă, o societate civilă matură.

Studiul este întemeiat pe teoria politică contemporană a puterii politice, a democrației liberale, reflectând principiile abordării sistemice, behavioriste. Actualizarea interpretărilor identității sociale, identității individuale, oferite de reprezentanții cognitivismului, și ai teoriei culturii politice, elaborate de G. Almond și S. Verba, este justificată prin faptul că liderii partidelor politice din Moldova au un comportament conflictual, deși resping în discursul lor paradigma conflictuală. Obiectivul central al studiului rezidă în verificarea ipotezei de lucru: poate fi eficientă guvernarea de coaliție în condițiile Republicii Moldova, care sunt factorii ce asigură / sporesc eficiența guvernării. Metodele aplicate în realizarea studiului sunt: analiza situațională, analiza factorială, analiza de conținut. Studiul este construit în baza principiului unității dialectice dintre teoria și practica politică.

Guvernarea poate fi realizată fie de un singur partid, fie de o coaliție de partide. În cazul guvernării de coaliție există nuanțe care nu pot fi ignorate de participanții la guvernare. T. Shmacikova consideră că pentru constituirea unei coaliții este necesar ca potențialii participanți să satisfacă un set de cerințe: să accepte scopul unic al guvernării, bine și clar definit; să activeze resurse importante, care ar servi scopului propus, să participe la dialogul deschis, axat pe un schimb conștient de informații; să se pregătească pentru negocierile active, dar în oricare situație să poată atinge compromisul¹.

Experiența istorică ne arată: coalițiile se formează mai mult pe segmentul de dreapta a eșichierului politic. În majoritatea cazurilor coalițiile au devenit o metodă de promovare a unor partide politice, care, în acest mod, se poziționează ca pivotul dreptei. Pe de altă parte, coalizarea este o dovadă de sinceritate a partidului și un argument că acesta conștientizează

¹ Шмачкова Т.В. Теория коалиций и становление российской многопартийности, с.66

necesitatea unirii forțelor – moment perceput și de electoratul respectivelor formațiuni¹.

Așadar, pentru guvernarea de coaliție o importanță majoră o are categoria teoriei politice contemporane - consensul. La rubrica *consens*, DEX ne oferă următoarea interpretare: *înțelegere, acord, identitate de păreri*². Reieșind din faptul că subiectul relațiilor sociale este omul, grupul de oameni, o semnificație majoră o are intermedierea lor. Aceasta este misiunea de bază a politicii: de a elabora mecanismul corelării intereselor diferitor indivizi / grupuri sociale și prin aceasta de a crea condițiile favorabile dezvoltării dinamice a sistemului social, a fiecărui element al acestuia³. Un pilon constructiv al consensului îl constituie atingerea *identității de păreri* sau a identității sociale. În teoria politică contemporană conceptele de identitate socială sau identificare socială au fost aplicate în interpretarea / explicarea unor fenomene sociale complexe, cum ar fi: conflictele interetnice, diferențierile lingvistice, dreptății sociale. Experiența acumulată de Republica Moldova, care din 2009 este guvernată de coaliții pro-europene, ne sugerează necesitatea aplicării acestui concept cu scopul de a găsi răspuns la întrebarea: care sunt cauzele insucceselor, ineficienței guvernelor, conduse de Vlad Filat (1), Vlad Filat (2), Iurie Leancă?

În concepția lui J. Turner se subliniază că individul formează grupurile sociale categorisindu-se pe sine în raport cu ceilalți. În acest context, procesul afirmării identității sociale reprezintă un mecanism cognitiv al realității sociale, axat pe poziționarea persoanei în sistemul relațiilor sociale. Corelând identitatea persoanei cu identitatea socială, J. Turner subliniază: nu este vorba despre două forme diferite de identificare, ci despre auto-identificarea și categorisirea persoanei în diverse situații: personalitatea se caracterizează în calitatea sa de membru a unui partid, a unei coaliții de guvernare, respectiv ea se poate poziționa mai aproape sau mai departe de cei doi poli. Concepția lui J. Turner ne permite să înțelegem și să explicăm formarea Guvernului Filat 2, când Partidul Liberal, condus de Mihai Ghimpu, nu a făcut parte din coaliția cu Partidul Liberal Democrat din Moldova și Partidul Democrat. Coaliția pro-europeană 2 s-a constituit grație scindării

¹ I. Rusandu, R. Cărbune, *Evoluția eșichierului politic moldovenesc: esență și controverse*, p.85-90

² DEX, p.213

³ L. Roșca, *Filosofia. Ghidul afacerii de succes*, p.296-318

Partidului Liberal și apariției unei noi formațiuni politice: Partidul Liberal Reformator. Deși liberalii reformatori explicau decizia lor prin faptul că au cerut demisia președintelui Partidului Liberal Mihai Ghimpu și alegerea în această funcție a vice-președintelui Partidului Liberal, Dorin Chirtoacă, și solicitarea nu le-a fost satisfăcută. În realitate, totul a fost mai complicat, mai serios. Coaliția pro-europeană (1) s-a confruntat cu dificultăți majore, deoarece cei trei lideri de partide: Vlad Filat, Marian Lupu și Mihai Ghimpu, percepeau diferit scopul guvernării, interesul național, necesitățile electoratului care i-a delegat în Parlamentul Republicii Moldova. Mai mult ca atât, fiecare lider avea probleme de calcul matematic: nu putea corela numărul mandatelor, oferite de popor, cu calificativul ponderii parlamentare a propriei formațiuni. Cât privește aprecierea calității serviciilor prestate, a impactului asupra situației politice din țară, toți liderii partidelor, ce formau coaliția, și-au demonstrat cele mai serioase calități – de a se pune în valoare, de a se supra-aprecia. Amintim că scopul AIE – 1 și AIE - 2 a fost clar definit, dar actorii procesului politic / procesului decizional din Moldova l-au perceput diferit și respectiv se deplasau pe segmentul politicii interne și externe a statului, fără a medita prea mult asupra consecințelor, actualizând și intensificând constant situația de conflict.

În teoria politică deosebim două opinii asupra corelării percepție – strategie comportamentală a persoanei / grupului, explicate / interpretate de reprezentanții cognitivismului. Conform primei opinii, comportamentul determină apariția reprezentărilor sociale, și invers: una din funcțiile comportamentului social constă în determinarea actelor comportamentale. J. K. Abric subliniază că anume reprezentările sociale produc și orientează actele conflictuale cotidiene, menționând: „reprezentările sociale – reprezintă o formă a cunoștințelor, funcția cărora constă în producerea actelor comportamentale și a comunicării între indivizi”¹. A doua opinie este reprezentată de K. Flaman, care a demonstrat că între percepție și comportament conflictual există o relație de interdependență. Generalizând cele două opinii, J. Saman sublinia că dacă reprezentarea socială înseamnă pregătire de acțiune, apoi aceasta înseamnă doar că reprezentarea socială reorganizează / restructurează elementele ambianței. În concluzie putem menționa că cel mai important indicator al comportamentului conflictual

¹ Современные проблемы психологии управления, с.243

este situația socială. Interpretările situației sociale pot fi variate, datorită faptului că percepțiile individuale sunt diferite. Strategia și tactica comportamentului individual în situația de conflict, la fel ca și starea emoțională, depind de capacitățile cognitive ale persoanei, de percepția și aprecierea situației curente, de evaluarea propriului potențial cognitiv și creativ, de estimarea colegilor, de caracterul relațiilor ce se stabilesc între membrii grupului.

Tezele argumentate de reprezentanții cognitivismului, fiind suprapuse pe comportamentul liderilor partidelor politice ce au format coalițiile pro-europene, ne permit să înțelegem și să apreciem nivelul de dezvoltare și manifestare a conștiinței lor politice, a moralității, demnității și responsabilității lor. Fiind preocupați de interesele propriului grup / partid, de imaginea acestuia, liderii celor trei formațiuni au uitat promisiunile, declarațiile referitoare la asumarea responsabilității pentru actul guvernării și conducerii țării către integrarea europeană: economică, politică, socio-culturală. Trebuie să recunoaștem rolul grupului de deputați, care au creat fracțiunea parlamentară a Partidului Liberal Reformator, grație votului cărora AIE și-a continuat activitatea în alt format. Fiind în opoziție, liderul PL Mihai Ghimpu, a urmărit alt scop: să-l înlăture din funcție pe liderul PLDM, Vlad Filat. Analiza activității lui Vlad Filat, a lui Marian Lupu, care au pierdut funcțiile de conducere din instituțiile statului, în lumina ultimelor evenimente, demonstrează că tactica acestora a fost una greșită. Liderul PLDM, care are ambiția imoralității să se adreseze poporului cu fraza: *Al vostru Vlad Filat*, fiind scos din funcția de Prim-ministru al Republicii Moldova, a oferit acoperire politică *jafului secolului* de la cele trei bănci: Banca Socială, Banca de Economii, Banca Națională a Moldovei¹.

Al treilea Guvern al coaliției pro-europene, condus de Iurie Leancă, a depus eforturi considerabile și a demonstrat instituțiilor europene că Republica Moldova are intenții serioase în ceea ce privește aderarea la UE. Poate nu atât au reușit conducătorii instituțiilor politice de la Chișinău, cât ne-a favorizat situația politică din regiune. Cumulând influențele activității Guvernului Leancă cu cele ale factorului geopolitic, am ajuns la semnarea Acordului de Asociere cu Uniunea Europeană. Cineva a muncit, cineva a acumulat voturi. Până la urmă am avut de pierdut noi, cetățenii Republicii

¹ Cf. L. Roșca, L. Mătășaru, Sfera publică europeană și controlul financiar public

Moldova, care am promovat hoții, delegându-i iarăși la 30 noiembrie 2014 în Parlament. Ceea ce a urmat, nu doar a tensionat populația Moldovei, dar a supărat-o, a sensibilizat-o până la lacrimi. Moldovenii cunosc unele lucrări ale înaintașilor noștri, ei știu cum aprecia funcționarul Moțoc poporul, categorisind masele ca *proști*. De data aceasta funcționarii instituțiilor statului, l-au depășit pe Moțoc, oferind maselor statut de *dobitoc social*. Iată de ce moldovenii, țărani conservatori prin origine, se trezesc și se revoltă, cerându-le să le restituie demnitatea și țara, și să le întoarcă banii furați.

După alegerile parlamentare din 30 noiembrie au urmat noi negocieri între reprezentanții partidelor, care și-au propus constituirea unei noi coaliții de guvernare. Obiectivele principale ale negociatorilor vizau: stabilirea priorităților de guvernare, armonizarea promisiunilor pre-electorale cu angajamentele prestabilite de Acordul de Asociere cu Uniunea Europeană. În rezultatul negocierilor celor aleși de noi ne-am ales cu un guvern minoritar, susținut formal de către PD și PLDM, și neformal – de către PCRM. În loc să-și asume responsabilitatea guvernării, să promoveze deschis valorile europene și să determine membrii coaliției de guvernare să-și onoreze promisiunile date liderilor Uniunii Europene, liderul PL Mihai Ghimpu a intrat în nesfârșite discursuri, îndepărtând și mai mult cetățenii Republicii Moldova de la procesul politic / procesul decizional. Acuzațiile, fără prezentarea dovezilor, intervențiile controversate: la un canal al televiziunii publice se oferea o informație, la alt canal se susținea ceva contrar și așa au ținut-o luni de zile în timp ce alți înalți demnitari furau Banca Națională a Moldovei. Acum, când au fost publicate mai multe articole, când jurnaliștii de la Jurnal TV au realizat mai multe emisiuni, prin care informează publicul despre cei implicați și despre cei ce au dirijat din umbră *jaful secolului*, cetățenii înțeleg necesitatea de a se informa, de a-și asuma responsabilitatea pentru cele întâmplate.

Barometrul opiniei publice din aprilie 2015, realizat de Institutul de Politici Publice, cu sprijinul financiar al Fundației Soros, pune în evidență percepția cetățenilor Republicii Moldova. Studiul a fost realizat de Centrul de Investigații Sociologice și Marketing CBS-AXA, în perioada 28 martie – 7 aprilie, pe un eșantion de 1104 de persoane din 85 de localități, reprezentativ pentru populația adultă a Republicii Moldova (cu excepția regiunii transnistrene), marja de eroare fiind de $\pm 2,8\%$). Conform acestui sondaj 33% din populație se interesează de politică, încă 24% au indicat că

aceasta îi interesează nici mult, nici puțin. Partidele politice au înregistrat cel mai scăzut nivel de încredere al populației – 10% au menționat că au o oarecare încredere în acestea, în timp ce 54% n-au încredere și 33% nu prea au încredere. O situație similară se observă în cazul Parlamentului (88% n-au încredere), al Președintelui (86% n-au încredere), al Guvernului (76% n-au încredere), în Justiție (76% n-au încredere).

După părerea majorității, Republica Moldova nu este guvernată de voința poporului (81%).

Distribuția răspunsurilor la întrebarea: Cum credeți Dvs., Republica Moldova este guvernată de voința poporului?

Populația nu dorește să susțină un guvern minoritar, această părere o susțin 55% din cei intervievați, 11% sunt gata să susțină un astfel de guvern, iar 19% n-au putut aprecia dacă ar susține sau nu, oferind un răspuns neutru.

Distribuția răspunsurilor la întrebarea: Spuneți-mi vă rog în ce măsură susțineți guvernul minoritar format de către PLDM și PDM?

Concepția în conformitate cu care guvernarea de coaliție rezidă în posedarea unei viziuni și în conformarea cetățenilor cu această viziune în Republica Moldova n-a fost asimilată nici de reprezentanții clasei politice, nici de majoritatea cetățenilor. Deși această concepție are limitele sale, deoarece tratează situațiile de adaptare (cum sunt tranzițiile) ca tehnice, ar trebui să medităm asupra interpretărilor date de reprezentanții cognitivismului. Situația guvernării de coaliție se complică și prin faptul că Republica Moldova se mai află în tranziție, nu este elaborat și respectiv adoptat mecanismul legal al interacțiunii celor trei puteri: legislativă, executivă și judiciară. Teoria politică a statului democratic de drept susține că Guvernul trebuie să intuiască, să determine și să justifice direcția evoluției țării, iar cetățenii, care susțin programele partidelor aflate la guvernare, să urmeze această direcție. Conducerea este o combinație a puterii de înțelegere / interpretare cu arta de a convinge cetățenii. Dialogul dintre conducătorii instituțiilor statului cu liderii societății civile, cu cetățenii, organizați în diferite grupuri sociale, poate fi realizat conform schemei ce urmează, doar în condițiile unei culturi politice de participare.

Sursa: Adaptat după R. A. Heifetz și Donald L. Laurie, *The Work of Leadership*, Harvard Business Review, ianuarie-februarie, 1997.

Analiza situațională a dificultăților cu care s-a confruntat guvernarea de coaliție din Republica Moldova, începând cu anul 2009, ne-a determinat să realizăm și analiza factorială a eficienței oricărei guvernări, constituite și realizate în baza principiilor și valorilor democratice. Actorul principal al statului democratic este cetățeanul activ implicat în procesul politic, în procesul decizional, posesorul unei culturi și conștiințe politice. Într-o formă consolidată, acestea se întâlnesc doar în modelul culturii politice de participare. Pentru a însuși conținutul culturii politice, pentru a ne orienta în diversitatea formelor, nivelurilor, aspectelor, modelelor culturii politice vom apela la teoria politică.

Cultura politică este un fenomen de o semnificație majoră pentru funcționarea eficientă a instituțiilor socio-politice. În antichitatea elenă manifestările sociale ale culturii politice au fost observate, descrise de către filosofii Platon și Aristotel. Filosofii antichității observă necesitatea în educația și instruirea civică a omului. Ei au constatat caracterul activ al culturii politice. Cultura politică este rezultatul unei interferențe permanente a persoanei, a subsistemului politic cu domeniile sociale adiacente: economic, social, juridic, spiritual etc. Cultura politică influențează activitatea tuturor componentelor sistemului politic, deoarece este o manifestare a includerii omului în procesele sociale în calitate de subiect sau obiect. Subiectul puterii reprezintă un început activ al puterii politice. În calitate de subiect al puterii, se poate afirma un cetățean, o organizație, o comunitate de oameni. Subiectul și obiectul politicii se află

într-o relație de putere. Pentru a vorbi despre relațiile de putere este necesar ca subiectul să dispună de un șir de calități, printre care mai importante sunt: dorința de a conduce, voința de putere, care se manifestă în dispoziții sau ordine. Majoritatea oamenilor nu intenționează să acapareze puterea. Mai mult ca atât, pentru ei puterea nu reprezintă o valoare. Mulți dintre actualii politicieni ar refuza funcțiile de conducere și responsabilitățile pe care acestea le presupun, dacă puterea nu le-ar deschide un șir de posibilități de a obține bunuri, profituri. În aceste cazuri lupta pentru putere are un caracter instrumental, deoarece puterea este apreciată ca mijloc de atingere a altor scopuri. Acest moment este foarte important în studierea fenomenului culturii și conștiinței politice, deoarece înțelegerea corectă a motivației activității subiectului puterii, a scopului urmărit de către cetățean ne permite să realizăm unele modificări în procesul socializării individuale.

Cultura politică este clasificată în baza mai multor criterii. Clasificarea realizată de autorii teoriei culturii politice G. Almond și S. Verba este bazată pe *specificul interacțiunii diferitor culturi politice cu mediul politico-cultural*. Respectiv sunt evidențiate trei modele de cultură politică: patriarhală, de supunere și de participare.

Cultura politică patriarhală reprezintă cel mai redus nivel al activismului civic și politic al persoanei / grupului social, de aceea nu-i vom oferi spațiu în studiul nostru.

Cultura politică de subordonare se manifestă prin pasivitatea indivizilor. Purtătorii ei se supun instituțiilor puterii de stat, nu încearcă să influențeze prin mijloace politice puterea. Ei nu-și cunosc drepturile și libertățile politice și respectiv nu sunt înzestrați cu abilitățile necesare activității politice. Supunându-se puterii ei, așteaptă de la instituțiile ei anumite înlesniri, garanții, ajutoare sociale etc. Aceste modele ale culturii politice au caracterizat comportamentul majorității cetățenilor Republicii Moldova până în luna aprilie curent. Protestul de la 3 mai, organizat de platforma civică pentru *Demnitate și Adevăr*, poate fi perceput ca primul pas al electoratului din Moldova, care dorește să cunoască adevărul, să fie tratat cu demnitate, să-și asume responsabilitatea civică. O astfel de abordare a politicului este caracteristică culturii politice de participare / culturii politice civile.

Cultura politică de participare este o calitate a persoanelor active, care se deosebesc prin intensitatea trăirii proceselor politice. Purtătorii ei influențează puterea prin diverse mijloace, determinând-o să adopte legile necesare, să elaboreze programe ale dezvoltării economice, orientate spre satisfacerea necesităților primare și secundare ale cetățenilor. Mijloacele utilizate de purtătorii culturii politice de participare sunt: alegerile, demonstrațiile, grevele de protest. În societățile cu tradiții democratice guvernarea reacționează prin decizii și măsuri concrete la toate manifestările de protest ale cetățenilor, grupurilor sociale. În așa mod sistemul politic își asigură condițiile favorabile activității. Absența sau întârzierea reacției guvernării la manifestările purtătorilor culturii politice de participare poate conduce la intensificarea unor conflicte, la unele schimbări radicale.

Autorii teoriei culturii politice susțin că în societatea contemporană este des întâlnit modelul mixt al culturii politice, definit și prin formula: cultura cetățeniei. Acest model este descifrat prin analiza însușirilor purtătorilor ei. G. Almond și S. Verba subliniază că purtătorul culturii cetățeniei este înzestrat cu următoarele calități:

- apreciază pozitiv activitatea guvernului național și este conștient de necesitatea instituțiilor lui;
- manifestă un interes sporit față de activitatea guvernului și este bine informat în acest domeniu;
- trăiește sentimentul mândriei pentru instituțiile politice ale țării sale;
- este convins că i se va oferi o atitudine egală și atentă din partea persoanelor responsabile;
- discută în anturajul prietenilor și cunoșcuților problemele politicii;
- este deschis colaborării cu purtătorii opiniei grupurilor din opoziție;
- trăiește satisfacția realizării sau participării la un eveniment politic;
- utilizează competent mijloacele juridice de a influența puterea, de a nu-i permite să facă abuz, să-și lărgească nemotivat împuternicirile, din contul libertăților și drepturilor civile;
- este convins că democrația participării este cel mai eficient, cel mai dorit, cel mai necesar sistem al guvernării de stat.

Analiza materialului factologic, empiric le permite autorilor teoriei culturii politice, a conceptului culturii civice să-și corecteze concluziile inițiale, subliniind că în idealul culturii civice, activismul și încadrarea cetățenilor sunt echilibrate de o anumită pasivitate și neparticipare¹.

Conform altei clasificări deosebită: cultura politică a conștiinței civice, cultura politică de elită, cultura politică de participare². În acest model cultura politică de participare fixează atitudinea subiectului față de procesul politic, care poate fi condiționată de factori interiori sau exteriori. Cultura politică a conștiinței civice reprezintă cel mai înalt mod de abordare și încadrare în procesul politic. Purtătorul acestui model este o personalitate conștientă de propria poziție în societate, de posibilitățile sistemului și regimului politic, de rolul său ca subiect și obiect al puterii. Este un cetățean, care nu trebuie motivat pentru a-și onora funcțiile politice. Implicarea în diverse activități purtătorul acestui model al culturii politice o apreciază ca pe o obligațiune, ca pe o datorie. Cultura politică de elită este interpretată controversat, deoarece în cadrul acestui model politica este apreciată în spiritul teoriei lui Platon – „domeniul de activitate a celor aleși”, respectiv majoritatea socială reprezintă beneficiarii, dar nu subiecții procesului politic. Caracteristica culturii politice de participare din această tipologie este dualistă. Pe de o parte, încadrarea activă a cetățenilor în activitatea politică este o condiție a funcționării eficiente a instituțiilor politice ale sistemului democratic. Pe de altă parte, cetățenii pot fi motivați atât prin mijloace politice, juridice, cât și stimulați economic. În realitatea politică a Republicii Moldova în timpul companiilor electorale sunt oficializate (publicații în presă, demersuri în ședințele în plen din Parlament etc.) date despre cointeresarea materială a alegătorilor. În așa fel, nu putem vorbi despre un nivel al conștiinței civice caracteristic participării la evenimentele politice în cazul când a fost reclamat beneficiul economic. Totodată nu putem să constatăm că asemenea situații în Republica Moldova sunt o excepție.

Descifrând conținutul culturii politice de participare, dorim să accentuăm semnificația ei pentru societatea democratică, pentru fiecare cetățean, care dorește să trăiască cu demnitate. A trăi frumos, cu demnitate este posibil în societatea democratică, unul dintre obiectivele sistemului

¹ Cf. www.deschide.md

² Cf. G. Almond, S. Verba, *Cultura civică*

politic al acesteia este crearea condițiilor favorabile pentru afirmarea modelului respectiv. Dar realizarea practică a oricărui model politic, axiologic este determinată multiplu, inclusiv și de factorul subiectiv, manifestat prin atitudini, abordări, aprecieri ale politicului. De decizia și încadrarea persoanei în sistemul politic depinde crearea unei societăți, în care legea ar avea un caracter universal, în fața căreia toți ar fi egali. Acest model al organizării sociale poate fi realizat doar de un subiect al relațiilor politice, sociale activ, care a însușit și respectă concluziile, expuse în tratatele înțelepciunii universale: suntem respectați în măsura în care respectăm legea, ordinea; în măsura în care conștient ne organizăm viața, activitatea social-utilă; în măsura în care ne cunoaștem drepturile, libertățile, ne onorăm obligațiunile și responsabilitățile. Atitudinea fiecăruia față de procesul politic are o semnificație majoră nu numai pentru afirmarea propriei personalități, dar și pentru instaurarea unui sistem democratic, pentru ameliorarea condițiilor de trai. În realitate persoana nu are de ales: să se încadreze sau nu în procesul politic, să-și asume sau nu obligațiunile de subiect al politicii. Alegerea pe care o facem zilnic se referă la valorile și normele pe care le selectăm pentru a le respecta, pentru a le transmite altor generații. A venit timpul să medităm împreună asupra chestiunii: ce vom transmite urmașilor noștri? În acest sens avem multe de făcut. În opinia noastră, modelul culturii politice de participare este realizabil, însă trebuie de orientat socializarea individului către conștientizarea poziției în societate, în sistemul politic, în grupul social. Activitatea social-utilă, acțiunea politică sunt desfășurate cu succes când motivele persoanei sunt convingerile. În concepția despre lume a omului contemporan, convingerile reprezintă cel mai important element. În acest context instruirea politică, orientată către formarea convingerilor, urmărește două obiective: dezvoltarea abilităților profesionale necesare pentru gestiunea și organizarea procesului social și afirmarea unui subiect activ al politicii. Considerăm că obiectivele menționate vor fi realizate de învățământul superior doar în condițiile când profesorii, studenții împreună vor elabora și vor coordona programe, orientate spre socializarea politică a diferitor categorii de cetățeni. Sub aspect teoretic acest obiectiv trebuie fundamentat în baza ideii integrității, suveranității statului Republica Moldova. Doar așa vom contribui la realizarea statului de drept, la afirmarea instituțiilor democratice. Poziția de observator, de beneficiar al sistemului politic este dăunătoare și trebuie

eliminată, în primul rând, din instituțiile de învățământ superior, care-și propun să pregătească specialiști pentru domeniul politic, al administrării publice locale, al relațiilor internaționale. Caracteristica purtătorului culturii civile, oferită de savanții americani G. Almond și S. Verba, în acest context, este semnificativă. Nu trebuie să elaborăm modelul, este necesar să studiem potențialul mijloacelor accesibile și condițiile Republicii Moldova pentru a-l implementa în practica socială.

Puterea politică cunoaște multiple definiții. Cele mai potrivite pentru realitatea politică contemporană desemnează capacitatea unui individ sau grup de a afecta comportamentul altui individ sau grup într-un anumit mod. Puterea, în acest sens, este asemănată cu influența și respectiv poate lua forma mecanismelor influenței. Este vorba despre persuasiune (influențare fără a promite vreo recompensă sau fără a amenința cu pedeapsa), mergând până la presiune externă, forță sau coerciție (amenințarea cu o pedeapsă sau pierdere). Puterea politică este un fenomen social complex, bilateral, caracteristicile căruia sunt: autoritatea și voința conducătorului, asimetria și relativitatea. Puterea întemeiată pe interese, convingeri și autoritate deseori ia forma identificării celor două părți: conducătorului și condusului, subiectului și obiectului. În astfel de condiții este atinsă forma maximă de influențare a puterii, deoarece subiectul este perceput de obiect ca reprezentantul său, ca apărătorul intereselor lui. Identificarea subiectivă a condușilor cu conducătorii lor poate fi explicată prin:

- capacitatea omului de a-și înțelege corect, adică dublu, atitudinea sa față de putere, relația sa cu puterea, în cadrul căreia persoana / cetățeanul se prezintă în calitate de obiect și subiect al puterii politice;
- posibilitatea de a sesiza comunitatea intereselor și valorilor conducătorilor și condușilor, prin apariția / dezvoltarea simțului unității persoanei cu întreaga comunitate.

Toate acestea se manifestă, se întâlnesc, sunt promovate doar în condițiile societății democratice, a modelului democrației participative.

Un motiv important al supunerii unor oameni altora a fost și rămâne distribuția neuniformă a resurselor puterii. Prin resursele puterii subînțelegem *tot ce individul / grupul social poate utiliza pentru a-l influența pe altul*. În această formulă resursele puterii includ factorii capabili într-un fel sau altul să influențeze puterea. Printre acestea menționăm: calitățile

subiectului: competența, capacitatea de a organiza / de a atrage masele în jurul unei idei, uni program de activitate; unele caracteristici ale obiectului, precum ar fi: încrederea grupului în liderul politic, obiceiul de a se supune conducătorului sau în limbajul confucianist: de a nu-i pune la îndoială vorbele, dispozițiile, autoritatea. O situație favorabilă pentru activitatea / manifestarea subiectului puterii o creează creșterea productivității muncii, care asigură realizarea programelor sociale, axate pe creșterea bunăstării populației, condițiilor ei de trai și activitate. Puterea politică este caracterizată de mai multe principii, prin confluența cărora este asigurată eficiența guvernării. Mai importante sunt: principiul realității, măsurii, legitimității, responsabilității, colegialității, consensului, transparenței. Conținutul acestora trebuie însușit cu mult înainte de lansare în politică. Astfel, le-am enumerat doar ca liderii partidelor de la guvernare să știe ce să caute în dicționarele de analiză politică sau în manualele de Politologie.

Concluzii. Guvernarea de coaliție poate fi eficientă, rezultativă, benefică pentru societate și mase. Pentru aceasta este nevoie ca liderii partidelor politice să lase aroganța și să studieze teoria procesului politic, procesului decizional, puterii politice, democrației participative, culturii politice. Principalul obiectiv al AIE-3, al guvernului condus de Valeriu Streleț este unirea societății moldovenești în jurul unei idei / program de activitate. Realizarea acestui obiectiv este posibilă prin abordarea pragmatică a realității politice din Republica Moldova, țară europeană sub aspect geografic și istoric, stat în tranziție sub aspect economic și socio-cultural. Moldovenii au dreptul la un trai mai bun, dar n-au găsit până în prezent echipa de guvernatori care cu adevărat le-ar apăra și reprezenta interesele.

Bibliografie:

1. Almond Gabriel, Verba Sidney, Cultura civică. București: Editura Style, 1996.
2. DEX. Ediția a II-a. București: Univers enciclopedic, 1996.
3. Roșca Ludmila, Filosofia. Ghidul afacerii de succes. Chișinău: Print-Caro, 2013.
4. Roșca Ludmila, Mătășaru Lucia, Sfera publică europeană și controlul financiar public // Managementul public și guvernarea în Uniunea Europeană. Chișinău: Print-Caro, 2015, p.60-67.

5. Rusandu Ion, Cărbune Radj, Evoluția eșichierului politic moldovenesc: esență și controverse // Revista de Filozofie, Sociologie și Științe Politice, nr.1, 2009, p.85-90.
6. Современные проблемы психологии управления. Ответств. ред.: Т.П.Емельянов, А.Л.Журавлёв, Г.В.Телятников. М. 2002.
7. Шмачкова Т.В., Теория коалиций и становление российской многопартийности // Полис. 1996. №5.
8. www.deschide.md

Copyright©Ludmila ROȘCA

Diasporas' Role in the Integration Paths: the Cases of Armenia and Moldova

Lecturer, Ph.D. Candidate Tigran YEPREMYAN

yeptigran@gmail.com

Yerevan State University, Armenia

Lecturer, Ph.D. Candidate Andrei ENACHI

enachi.andrei@gmail.com

State University of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: The paper examines comparatively the role of Diaspora in the integration paths of two post-Soviet Eastern European states, Armenia and Moldova. Both countries are members of the Eastern Partnership and share some common situations with their Diasporas that are increasing their role in the foreign policy of their homelands. Both countries were supposed to sign Association agreement and DCFTA with the EU, while Moldova signed, but Armenia has not, announcing its U-turn intention to join the Russian led Customs Union and to participate in the formation of the Eurasian Economic Union. The paper goes beyond the reasons of the integration choices of these countries. The main reflections are oriented on the issue of the Diasporas' influence on the integration choices and its implications for Diaspora communities. Thus, the research is concentrated on the case-studies of Armenian and Moldovan Diasporas as foreign policy assets in the host land-homeland relations. This issue can be better understood by setting its study within the shared theoretical framework of constructivism and liberalism: both constructivism and liberalism are likely to explain the impact of both identity and domestic activities on international sense.

Key-words: Armenia, Moldova, Diaspora, constructivism, European Union, integration, Russia.

Introduction

As important transnational actors Diasporas have considerable influence on behavior of states on international arena in many cases such as in the cases of Armenia and Moldova. In this regard the way and the extent that the host state allows the community to exert certain influence affect the worth of the Diaspora as a foreign policy asset in the eyes of the homeland. For instance, the Armenian and Moldovan Diasporas had substantial influence in the integration paths of their homelands. Armenia

and Moldova share some common situations with their Diasporas that are increasing their role in the foreign policy of their homelands and are important factors in foreign policy planning. Both countries were supposed to sign Association agreement and DCFTA with the EU, while Moldova signed, but Armenia has not.

On September 3, 2013, the President of Armenia Serzh Sargsyan abruptly shifted the direction of Armenia's long-praised integration preference with the EU and announced "Armenia's decision to join" the Russia-led Customs Union and participate in the processes of formation of the Eurasian Economic Union. To make his move more profound and convincing, the President accentuated that Armenia depends on Russia for security reasons and the largest Armenian community resides in Russia. These were critical determinants for Armenian integration preferences. In the aftermath of the visit "securitization" started taking place with the choice being presented as a security issue. "It's a rational decision¹ - said the president, - Our society has always clearly aspired to have a state system anchored in the system of European values. (...) There has recently been much talk about the civilizational choice of the countries, members of the Eastern Partnership initiative. (...) We don't believe it is right to view the issue in that dimension"². Consequently, the Armenian decision of joining to Russian led Customs Union is not a matter of identity but a rational choice.

On 27 June 2014, Moldova signed the Association Agreement with the EU, including the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA). This Agreement represents a concrete way to exploit the dynamics in EU-Moldova relations, focusing on support to core reforms, on economic recovery and growth, governance and sector cooperation in areas such as energy cooperation, transport, environment, public health, consumer protection, education, training and youth as well as cultural cooperation³. Thus, the EU increased its cooperation with Moldova, becoming its major partner in terms of trade, business and economic relations.

¹ The RA President Serzh Sargsyan's Remarks at the Press Conference on the Results of the Negotiations with the RF President Vladimir Putin 03.09.2013.

² Statement of Serzh Sargsyan, the President of the Republic of Armenia in the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe 02.10.2013.

³ EU-Moldova Association Agreement, What does the Agreement offer?

The paper goes beyond the reasons of the integration choices of these countries. The main reflections are oriented on the issue of the Diasporas' influence on the integration choices and its implications for the Diaspora communities.

The Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, Diasporas have been regarded as challenging traditional state institutions and as an important feature of the relationship between domestic and international politics¹. Since social threats are constructed and not naturally given², Homeland-Diaspora relations are not static as their mutual perception might change due to changes in governmental power, global dynamics and relations with the host-land³. Diasporas operate as ethnic lobbies in liberal host lands and are a force in the global economy assisting homelands' economies⁴. Diasporas' activities can be better understood by setting their study within the shared theoretical framework of *constructivism* and *liberalism*: both constructivism and liberalism are likely to explain the impact of both identity and domestic activities on international sense.

Constructivism tends to explain the actors' identities, motives and preferences, while liberalism deals largely with explaining their actions once the preferences are settled. Diasporas identity-based motivation should therefore be an integral part of the constructivist effort to explain the construction of national identities⁵. As A. Wendt outlines, "The daily life of international politics is an on-going process of states taking identities in relation to Others, casting them into corresponding counter-identities, and playing out the result"⁶. Similarly, a Diaspora may have multiple identities linked to institutional roles and therefore interests. Thus, Diasporas do not have interests independently from the social context⁷.

¹ Y. Shain, A. Barth. "Diasporas and International Relations Theory", p. 449.

² A. Wendt. "Anarchy is what States Make of it: The Social Construction of Power Politics", p. 405.

³ B. Baser, A. Swain. "Diaspora Design versus Homeland Realities: Case Study of Armenian Diaspora", p. 49.

⁴ Y. Shain and A. Barth. Op. cit., p. 450.

⁵ Ibidem, p. 451.

⁶ A. Wendt. *Social Theory of International Politics*, p. 21.

⁷ Idem. "Anarchy is what States Make of it: The Social Construction of Power Politics", pp. 397-398.

Liberalism rejects the conventional assumptions that states are the primary actors in international affairs. Therefore, from liberalist viewpoint, the state is not an independent actor, but rather a representative of interests of different groups. Consequentially, states pursue particular interests preferred by the specific coalition currently in power¹. The dynamics within the triadic mechanism - homeland, host land and the Diaspora are extremely important for determining to what extent the Diaspora can be influential on policy making procedures in the homeland. In the cases of Moldovan and Armenian Diasporas, one may observe that policy making in the homeland is highly vulnerable to Diaspora involvement, since the host land and its liberal values provide all the room that a Diaspora needs to influence both the homeland and the host land politics².

Diaspora communities also tend to be integrating into the social, political and economic spaces of receiving countries. In addition, the preferences of the representatives of Diaspora have been shaped out by national ideologies, which mean that the policy of Diaspora may differ from homeland's preferences. Therefore, Diasporas may even sometimes act against their homeland interests. An interesting dimension for explaining the Diaspora involvement in homeland politics is the dynamics between the host-land and the Diaspora organizations. Essentially, Diaspora institutions come to confront individuals as more or less coercive social facts. On this view, institutionalization is a process of internalizing new identities and interests, not something occurring outside them and affecting only behavior³.

Therefore, the political system in the host land is highly important, since it determines the extent to which the Diasporas might influence the homeland politics in addition to the host land ones. The more liberal the host land's political system is, the easier it is for Diaspora to influence on foreign policy matters in the host land towards the homeland. In case of authoritarian host land Diaspora organizations are becoming a policy tool in the hands of the authorities of host land. Thus, the nature of the host land regime determines the way that the Diaspora community organizes and

¹ Y. Shain, A. Barth. "Diasporas and International Relations Theory", p. 460.

² B. Baser, A. Swain. "Diaspora Design versus Homeland Realities: Case Study of Armenian Diaspora", p. 54.

³ A. Wendt. "Anarchy is what States Make of it", p. 399.

interacts among it and also with homeland¹. Significant part of diaspora communities maintains a transnational existence. Residing in a host land they maintain social, cultural and sometimes economic and political ties with the homeland. Moreover, Diasporas may be interested in influencing events in their homeland. Such kind of actions may be in favour or in opposition to homeland's acting government².

The Global Armenian Diaspora

Armenia has a large and well organized global Diaspora which comes to compensate the state's smallness. The Armenian Diaspora exceeds the overall population of Armenia about three times, and being well integrated within the countries of domicile it is active in many areas of political, economic and social affairs of those countries. The largest Armenian Diaspora communities reside within such important international actors as the United States, Russia and France. As Khachig Tölölyan outlines, "The sun never sets on the Armenian Diaspora"³. Hence, the Armenian interests are geographically transcendental and the Republic of Armenia has to plan its foreign policy also in accordance with the interests of "the Armenian Transnation". Therefore, the wide range of issues comprising Armenia-Diaspora relations presents a significant component of the National Security Strategy of the Republic of Armenia⁴.

Additionally, within the context of the framework of contemporary globalization and glocalization processes the Armenian Diaspora no longer consists of a series of exile communities, fragments of the nation awaiting real or even symbolic return, but, rather, it is a permanent phenomenon. Therefore, the global Armenian Diaspora is constructed of communities that have "necessarily and inevitably developed local, host country-specific, "ethnic" features". Thus, according to Khachig Tölölyan, the "diaspora is undergoing an accelerating transition from exilic nationalism to diasporic transnationalism"⁵.

¹ B. Baser, A. Swain. "Diaspora Design versus Homeland Realities: Case Study of Armenian Diaspora", p. 50.

² M. J. Esman. *Diasporas in the Contemporary World Polity*, pp. 121-122.

³ K. Tölölyan. "Elites and Institutions in the Armenian Transnation", pp. 107-136.

⁴ "The National Security Strategy of the Republic of Armenia".

⁵ K. Tölölyan. Op. cit., pp. 107-108.

Next to the traditional parties, new Diaspora organizations such as the Armenian Assembly of America, the Forum of Armenian Associations of Europe and the Union of Armenians of Russia have evolved since Armenia's independence. While the first two structures, which have succeeded in gaining a certain influence, limiting their activity to lobbying for Armenia's interests in Washington and Brussels, getting additional foreign aid, getting support for the Armenian point of view in the Karabakh conflict, and fighting to receive recognition for the Genocide¹, the Armenian Diaspora structures of Russia have become an important tool in the hands of Moscow to influence on Armenia's foreign policy. In contrast to the Armenian diaspora organisations in the United States and France, where there are strict and transparent procedures for the election of the heads of organizations, in Russia diaspora organizations are often led by representatives of large businesses that are considering the post of the head of the diaspora organisation on a personal level as a prestigious and authoritative business office. It is often noted that the level of organization of the Armenian diaspora in Russia does not correspond to its potential. Until now, the results of large diaspora projects have mainly become organizations that give an impression of lobbying centres of economic interests of individuals or groups, rather than the Armenian interests in general².

The Role of Armenian Diaspora in Russia

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia received a new wave of immigration from Armenia. As a result, today the Armenian population of Russia estimates 1.2 million according to the population census³ and around 2.5 million according to experts⁴. Armenians in Russia are quite successful economically and professionally, and constitute socially and politically well-organized national communities⁵. "The largest Armenian community resides in Russia and the members of that community are much respected people. We have never made a step aimed against Russia and have no complex which would compel us to make such a step", stated President Serzh

¹ T. Manaseryan. "Diaspora the Comparative Advantage for Armenia", p. 20.

² А. Э. Захарян. Армянская диаспора в России и в мире, с. 93-95.

³ The Results of the National Population Census of Russia 2010.

⁴ В. Дятлов, Э. Мелконян. *Армянская диаспора: очерки социокультурной типологии*, с. 103.

⁵ T. Manaseryan. Op. cit., p. 5.

Sargsyan at the Joint Press Conference with the President of the Republic of Poland Bronisław Komorowski on 25 June, 2013¹. “Today the strategic partnership with Russia also derives from the existence of more than 2.5 million Armenians living in Russia. (...) We must consider that we are from those unique nations that have a large Diaspora, and the Diaspora obliges us to be able to maintain a balanced relationship with all”, stated the former Secretary of the National Security Council of Armenia Artur Baghdasaryan on 25 April, 2014, during the press-conference after announcing his resignation². Accordingly, the policy priorities of the Diaspora might not always coincide with the policy priorities of homeland especially in the context of integration processes between the Russian led Eurasian Union and the European Union. The Association Agreement with the EU including a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) would deepen Armenia’s political association and economic integration with the EU³. The membership in the Customs Union will greatly facilitate the life of Armenian citizens working in Russia as it will eliminate the visa regime, which Russia would introduce from 2015 for all citizens of the CIS, with the exception of CU members. Regarding this issue the president of the Union of Armenians of Russia Ara Abrahamyan stated: “The Choice between the EU and CU was hard for Armenia. (...) It must be said that Russia hosts the largest Armenian Diaspora in the world. And in this regard, Armenia cannot remain indifferent to the fate of its compatriots living in the Russian Federation”⁴.

The successful Armenian community in Russia sends huge amount of capital to Armenia. Moreover, today Russia is the number one country for labor migration from Armenia⁵. Annually, about 60.000 labor migrants seek jobs in Russia. A survey by OSCE for the period 2002-2005 found that almost

¹ Statement by President Serzh Sargsyan at the Joint Press Conference with the President of the Republic of Poland Bronisław Komorowski.

² Ա. Բաղդասարյան. “Հայաստանը պետք է վարի բալանսավորված արտաքին քաղաքականություն”.

³ “Joint Statement by High Representative Catherine Ashton and Commissioner Stefan Füle on completion of negotiations on the future Association Agreement with Armenia”.

⁴ Интервью президента Союза Армян России Ара Абрамяна, опубликованное в газете «Голос Армении». Ара Абрамян о Таможенном Союзе.

⁵ Ա. Ժամակոչյան. *Հետխորհրդային երկրների հայկական համայնքների ինքնության խնդիրները և տեղեկատվական ռեսուրսները*, ր. 160.

90% of labor migrants from Armenia went to Russia. In 2007, 96% of labor migrants from Armenia travelled to Russia¹. Speaking about the problems of the regime introduced on January 1, 2014, in Russia, which sets a maximum period of 90 days staying on the territory of Russia for foreign citizens, including labor migrants, the Secretary of National Security Council Arthur Baghdasaryan announced that Armenian citizens living or working in Russia and facing problems due to this new migration regime² could be divided into several groups: the first group is about 60.000 people, who are already banned to visit Russia, second group of about 210.000 people already have violations of the emigration laws and could be deported, and the third group is about 500.000 people who are at risk of the violation of the regime³. Such a situation could have a destabilizing political effect and pose a challenge to the regime in Armenia. In this regard Arthur Baghdasaryan addressed to his Russian colleague Nikolai Patrushev requesting an amendment to the Russian migration legislation. So the simplification of the stay of Armenian labor migrants in Russia will significantly improve the socio-economic situation of Armenian citizens⁴.

Such processes are essential sources of influence both for Russia and the Armenian community in the spheres of economy and politics. According to the Armenian Central Bank in 2005 the amount of Diaspora remittances reached 940 million US dollars, which is more than 15 percent of Armenia's GDP. In 2006 Armenian Diaspora in Russia transferred 604 million US dollars to Armenia which is 10 percent of the total capital that Russia sent to CIS countries⁵. In 2011, through the banking system by individuals for non-commercial purposes, the volume of money transfers amounted about 1 billion 547 million dollars. And about 84 percent of total transfers belongs to Russia (1 billion 295 million dollars). This means that another country

¹ Migration and Development: Armenia Country Study.

² «О внесении изменений в статью 27 Федерального закона «О порядке выезда из Российской Федерации и въезда в Российскую Федерацию» и статью 5 Федерального закона «О правовом положении иностранных граждан в Российской Федерации».

³ Ա. Բաղդասարյան. «Հայաստանը պետք է վարի բալանսավորված արտաքին քաղաքականություն».

⁴ Интервью «Голосу России» научный сотрудник Института экономики РАН Александр Караваев 10 февраля.

⁵ For more see - Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Armenia – 2006, p. 12.

indirectly provides 30% of Armenia's domestic consumption¹. Moreover, non-commercial money transfers of individuals from Russia to Armenia via the banking system in 2013 amounted around 1 billion 606.6 million US dollars, in case that total money transfers of individuals from Russia to Armenia via banking system in the same year was around 1 billion 727.9 million US dollars². The statistics show that both non-commercial and total money transfers in 2013 were higher than in 2008 pre-crisis period, and this dynamics tends to increase (see figure 1 and figure 2). The largest number of Diaspora investors also came from Russia (29% of all investors)³. They have some business and political connections with both Russian and Armenian policymakers. Some of the Armenian businessmen are among the 200 richest people in Russia with total net assets worth of \$21 bln⁴. Some of the largest companies are Tashir Group (Samvel Karapetyan), Rosgosstrakh (Khachaturov Danil), Reso (Sergey Sarkisov and Nikolay Sarkisov), and Ameriabank (Ruben Vardanyan), Uniastrum bank (Gagik Zakaryan), BAMO (Murad Muradyan), etc⁵.

Consequently, the flows of the capital of Russia's Armenian community to Armenia provide a unique opportunity for Russia to reinforce its economic and political influence on Armenia. The Diaspora community simply cannot operate in Russia without coinciding its interests with the economic, political and foreign policies of Russia. Thus, it can be assumed that many business and financial organizations of the Armenian Diaspora of Russia are agents of Russian policy. This phenomenon has both domestic and foreign implications for Russia. It is a fact that rich and influential Diaspora with more than 2 million people has quite big significance, and it is necessary for Russia to provide societal consensus. The main part of the Armenian Diaspora in Russia is concentrated in Moscow; historically large Armenian colonies are located in Krasnodar, Stavropol and Rostov regions⁶. However, the Russian Armenian Diaspora is not homogeneous. In general,

¹ For more see - Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Armenia – 2011, pp. 18-19.

² Ibidem.

³ Migration and Skills In Armenia Results Of The 2011/12 Migration Survey On The Relationship Between Skills, Migration And Development, pp. 14-15.

⁴ Seven Armenians named Russia's richest businessmen in Forbe's ranking.

⁵ А. Э Захарян. Армянская диаспора в России и в мире, с. 98.

⁶ Ibidem, с. 94.

we can distinguish three types of communities within the Armenian Diaspora in Russia. First, the members of the “old” Diaspora communities who came to Russia before Perestroika they are integrated within the Russian society and, simultaneously, form an active Diaspora community. For example, the Armenian Diaspora of Rostov and Krasnodar regions descend from migrants of the 18th century¹. Second, they are successful businessmen from the wave of immigration in the 1990s, who are mostly interested in lobbying on behalf of their economic interests through the Diaspora institutions. Finally, there are the immigrants without legal status. In this view, it is difficult to speak about the Armenian Diaspora in Russia in terms of commonly accepted social identity and collective interests².

An important instance of how the Diaspora shapes and affects bilateral Russian-Armenian relations in post-Soviet period was the anti-Armenian policy pursued by Krasnodar governor Aleksandr Tkachev. In 2003, the presidents of Russia and Armenia discussed the issue in Krasnodar, and then the anti-Armenian rhetoric stopped. However, even today xenophobia, in the context of Moscow’s displeasure at Armenia’s contacts with the USA and the EU, remains one of the key issues between Russia and Armenia. Therefore, Russia can reinforce its interests in the South Caucasus more actively. There are many channels for influence, not only in the political elites, but in Diaspora community, and not only officially, but also via “unofficial” activity through regional initiatives, nationalist groups and other resources³.

In order to legitimate its relationships and to be parts of international order the Armenian Diaspora communities in Russia established different institutions and agents. Institutes of national and cultural societies are formed to deal with the activities in the public sphere. These organizations with different efficiencies are functioning across the entire Russia and the national-cultural autonomy is formed. The Armenian Apostolic Church in Russia is represented with its two dioceses (Russia and

¹ S. Markedonov. “Russia’s “Internal South Caucasus”: The Role and Importance of Caucasus Societies for Russia”, p. 12.

² M. Oussatcheva. “Institutions in Diaspora: The Case of Armenian Community in Russia”, pp. 20-21.

³ S. Markedonov. Op. cit., pp. 13-14.

New Nakhichevan; South Russia) and around 40 churches¹. However, the largest Armenian organization is “the Union of Armenians of Russia” (UAR), which has its regional branches in 70 federal regions and more than 340 cities of Russian Federation. Only in Krasnodar region it holds more than 40 regional offices². In 2003, UAR initiated and organized the founding session of the Pan-Armenian National Congress where 350 delegates from 52 countries participated. The presidents of Armenia and Russia also attended the session³. Through such an initiatives the economic, political and cultural elites of each of these heterogeneous Diaspora communities share a commitment “to maintain institutionalized, transnational connections and exchanges with other segments of the Diaspora and with the homeland: money and political advice, books and newspapers, disks and videotapes, paintings and films, information and propaganda, priests and party activists circulate through the Armenian transnation”⁴.

The UAR also has ambitious political objectives of mobilizing Armenians during both regional and federal elections, which was successfully done since its foundation in 2000. The growing political significance of the UAR makes it an important factor in relationships between Yerevan and Moscow⁵. In this context, the Armenian non-governmental organizations and business companies established in Russia (Union of Armenians of Russia, Tashir Group of Companies ect.) which are transnational in character are playing an important role.

In this context, it is interesting the statement of the Russian president V. Putin on October 6, 2003, at the founding session of the Pan-Armenian National Congress: “Great Russian reformer Tsar Peter the Great in one of his edicts wrote the following, it sounds interesting: “Caress the Armenians as possible and facilitate properly wherein needed, in order to give an addiction for more of their arrival”. Putin made a pause and then

¹ Armenian Diaspora Yearbook, Ministry of Diaspora of the Republic of Armenia, p. 438.

² Ա. Մամակոսյան. *Հետխորհրդային երկրների հայկական համայնքների ինքնուրույն խնդիրները և տեղեկատվական ռեսուրսները*, p. 161.

³ В. Дятлов, Э. Мелконян. *Армянская диаспора: очерки социокультурной типологии*, с. 127.

⁴ К. Тölölyan. “Elites and Institutions in the Armenian Transnation,” p. 109.

⁵ В. Дятлов, Э. Мелконян. *Op. cit.*, с. 128.

added: "It has passed nothing – three hundred years"¹. Thus, the Diaspora institutions operate in accordance with the interests of Russia foreign and domestic policies.

Moldovan Diaspora

Large flows of migration from Moldova started from 1990s and determined the formation of many Diaspora communities abroad. Moldovan societies began forming abroad once Moldova proclaimed its independence (in 1991) and the citizens got the right to travel to other countries (emigration, marriage, family reunions, studies etc.). During the second part of the 1990's, the process received a mass-character with the development of Moldovan labor-migration to Russia, EU states and Israel².

From the beginning of its formation, the Moldovan Diaspora has focused on ensuring cultural ties with its homeland and later on the socio-economic and political relations. This was conditioned by the increasing collaboration with states receiving Moldovan labor migrants as well as the growing interest of Moldovan political leaders to get support during elections from the migrant workers³. Moldovan Diaspora communities abroad started initially from small communities, later on forming ethno-cultural associations of emigrants in foreign countries. Their initial role was in establishing relations between the Diaspora and Moldova, building a bridge between two countries.

Today, the major destination countries for migrants from Moldova continue to be the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and other countries: Italy, Romania, Portugal, Spain, Turkey, Israel, Great Britain, Greece, etc.

In 2013, the Bureau of Interethnic Relations registered 154 associations from more than 30 countries (118 associations from 18 EU countries)⁴. Overall Moldovan Diaspora is estimated to one million citizens, reaching 25 percent of its entire population, which according to the last

¹ В. В. Путин. Глава Российского государства цитировал сенатский Указ, подписанный Государем России Петром Первым в 1711 году.

² Cf. V. Moşneaga. Republic of Moldova: Diaspora and Diaspora Policy.

³ Ibidem, p. 149.

⁴ Ibidem, p. 162.

census in 2014 counts almost 3 million people¹. According to estimations, about 200,000 Moldovans are thought to be working in Russia, mainly in construction. Another estimate puts the number of Moldovans in Italy at 200,000. Meanwhile, members of the 160,000 - strong Gagauz minority (a Christian community in the southern part of the country) are drawn predominantly towards Turkey².

Identity is an important aspect of Moldovan Diaspora due to the historical evolution of the Moldovan statehood, an important part of Moldova's citizens still identifies on ethnic base as Romanians. Due to their close historical and cultural links, Moldovan citizens have also had the opportunity to acquire Romanian citizenship if they can demonstrate that their grandparents lived on Romanian land after 1918 (when Moldova became part of Romania). Most of these people, therefore, have dual citizenship, even if unofficially³. The possibility of having dual citizenship is allowed in the Republic of Moldova. This contributes to the current difficult situation in which the amount of the Moldovans who decided to regain the Romanian citizenship increased in the last 5 years due to the reform of the citizenship done by Traian Basescu, the former President of Romania. The process of regaining the citizenship of Romania is based on the historical fact that the territory between the Prut and the Dniester (Moldova and Ukraine) was a Romanian land and the Republic of Moldova is the second Romanian state. According to the information from the Romanian Authority for Citizenship, they processed more 445 000 of cases⁴. The incentives of obtaining the Romanian citizenship for the majority of migrants from Republic of Moldova consist mainly in the benefits of freely traveling in the EU and for a legal stay in Member States.

Initially, the policy on forming Moldovan Diaspora has focused on ensuring cultural ties with its homeland, and later on the socio-economic and political relations. This was conditioned by the increasing collaboration with states receiving Moldovan labor migrants as well as the growing interest of Moldovan political leaders to get support during elections from

¹ Informative Note on the preliminary results of 2014 population and housing census of the Republic of Moldova.

² M. Jandl. Moldova Seeks Stability Amid Mass Emigration.

³ Ibidem.

⁴ Unofficial report: About half a million Moldovans got the Romanian citizenship.

the migrant workers¹. In recent years the Moldovan government was trying to minimize the negative effects and risks of mass emigration by pursuing a policy of emigration and Diaspora. Today the Moldovan politics is deepening in the context of cooperation with the European Union in the framework of the Eastern Partnership and the immediate neighborhood with the EU.

Thus, Moldovan Diaspora started to play a greater role in society by being recognized as an asset of the country development and prosperity. In this sense, during the first edition of the conference “Moldova 2020: *Diaspora Contribution to the Development of the Country of Origin*”, the former Prime Minister of Moldova, Ion Sturza noted that “diaspora is a pride because in the host countries it can lobby for Moldovan interests”². The political class, officials and civil society are showing a greater interest towards Diaspora and are recognizing its major assets and a valuable contribution for national interest and the important role in consolidation of the Moldovan state.

During the last three years the Moldovan Government started to increase its attention to the Diaspora and implemented the needed legislative policy framework for creating more possibilities for Diaspora involvement and contribution to the Europeanization and development process. This leads to a more active role of Diaspora population in shaping the home state policies and creating more opportunities for migrants to participate in the future of Moldova.

Moldovan Diaspora between Russia and the EU

The Moldovan citizens established in Russia emigrated during the URSS and now have families and work there. They meet to speak the Romanian language and to remember the traditions and customs of Moldova³. Moldovan Diaspora in Russia is determined by specific features, which makes it different from Moldovan Diaspora in the Western countries. Russia and Italy are considered to be the main destination countries for labor migration from Moldova. The general characteristics of migrants according to their destination vary from country to country. The migrants to EU countries are preponderantly females (60.1%), well-educated persons,

¹ V. Moşneaga. Republic of Moldova: Diaspora and Diaspora Policy, p. 150.

² Moldovan diaspora's contribution to development of home country, appreciated in Chisinau.

³ Cf. D. Cheianu-Andrei, V. Mukomel. Moldovan Diaspora Mapping.

but migrants going to Russia are more likely male (56.2%), with a medium level of education and mostly employed in the field of construction (around 68%)¹.

Another important aspect of Moldovan Diasporas in Russia is the religion, Christian Orthodox faith being practiced by majority of the population in the both countries. In Moldova, according to the last census in 2004, Orthodox believers are about 93%. However, there is no an autocephalous church, Moldova being a part of Russian Orthodox Church. According to the statute of Russian Orthodox Church, its jurisdiction includes people of Orthodox faith living on the canonical territory in: Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Moldova, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Estonia, and other Orthodox Christians living in other countries that joined voluntarily in this jurisdiction².

The church is an essential element in the life of Moldovans abroad, just like in the Republic of Moldova. The Moldovan migrants go to the Moldovan Orthodox or Romanian Orthodox church. Most frequently, church is the place where co-nationals meet for religious holidays, where they commemorate the most important life events - weddings, baptisms, - which make them feel like at home³. The Moldovan migrants usually go to Moldovan Orthodox or Romanian Orthodox churches⁴. Church is the place where they meet for different important life events, celebrations, holidays but also where they can meet their co-nationals, get the needed supports and exchange news and important information regarding their homeland. The church is quite active in co-operation with Moldovan communities abroad. Within many European and CIS countries (Russia, Italy, France, Portugal, and Spain) Moldovan Orthodox church priests, especially those who are sent to serve abroad, conduct church services in the native language of the Moldovan migrants. Moreover, the Moldovan Metropolitan Church of Russian Orthodox Church promotes creation of ethnic, cultural and religious communities and associations of Moldovans abroad⁵.

¹ Moldova Labour Force Survey. National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova.

² Statute of Russian Orthodox Church.

³ D. Cheianu-Andrei. Mapping of the Moldovan Diaspora in Italy, Portugal, France and the United Kingdom. *Moldovan Diaspora Mapping*, p. 16.

⁴ Ibidem.

⁵ V. Moşneaga. Republic of Moldova: Diaspora and Diaspora Policy, p. 164.

Remittances are another important aspect of Moldovan migrants abroad. According to the financial inflow to Moldova it is considered among top recipients of remittances. In 2008, money sent by emigrants continued to be a major source of revenue in the Republic of Moldova. Funds sent by nationals abroad amounted to 36.2% of national GDP. In 2009, the members of Moldovan diaspora officially sent close to one billion Euros via banks¹. In 2011 the level of remittances reached the level of 23 % of GDP². In 2013, Moldova received net remittances of 2.6 billion USD, amounting to almost 32% of GDP. Remittances from Russia of 1.5 billion USD made up almost 60% of total remittances received by Moldova. Remittances from Russia are currently perceived to be subject to severe cyclical and political risk³.

Speaking about the role of Diaspora in Moldova and Russia bilateral relations, it is worth mentioning that during the last years there were several cases when the Moldovan Diaspora community was trying actively to influence the policy or decisions of the Russian government for the benefit of Moldova. In this regard, we can analyze the embargo of the Russian Federation on the import of wine from Moldova. In this case the associations of the Diaspora Coordination Council have released a statement to reprobate the embargo put by the Russian Federation on Moldovan wine, mentioning that the economic, political or commercial threats are unacceptable in the relations between states⁴. This was a unifying issue that called upon Diaspora community to defend their homeland interests. In their statements, they condemned such kind of actions oriented against their country free choice for the development path, which is now oriented towards EU markets.

Moldova achieved one of the great objectives from its European agenda by signing the Association Agreement including the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) on 27 June 2014. This achievement boosted Moldova's export to the European market, shifting its traditional trade partners Russia and CIS countries.

¹ P. Păduraru. Moldova's diaspora looking for a way home.

² World Bank. 2012. Developing Countries to Receive Over \$400 Billion in Remittances in 2012.

³ D. Saha, R. Giucci. Remittances from Russia: Macroeconomic implications of possible negative shocks, p. 3.

⁴ A. Cheptene. Moldovan diaspora reprobates Russia's actions.

In this sense, Moscow punished Moldova for choosing to follow the European path by hiking gas prices, banning wine imports and threatening to impose visa restrictions on Moldovans working in Russia. A showdown of sorts seemed inevitable. In an interview, Oazu Nantoi, the director of the Institute of Public Policy, a respected and seasoned political commentator, appreciates the situation as follows: “We are conscious of the existence in the Republic of Moldova of a fifth column financed by the Russian federation”¹. Russia continues to perceive Moldova as one of its former regions and tries to keep it as close as possible. The main tools used by Russia in this sense are oriented towards creating a negative image about the European Union. The results are totally different, because these actions are pushing Moldova for building closer ties and relations with Romania, Ukraine and EU countries.

Italy is considered to be the second largest destination country for Moldovan migrants after Russia. The real figure of all Moldovans in Italy is difficult to quantify because a good part of them are illegally established there and cannot be monitored. According to the former Moldovan ambassador in Italy Gheorghe Rusnac, who confirms that the total number of Moldovan citizens in Italy would reach 200.000². Thus, the real number can be much bigger according to some estimation that counts more than 300.000, taking into account the illegal emigrants or Moldovans with Romanian citizenship residing in Italy. Moldovans in Italy as the largest community of Moldovans in the EU is providing income for a large proportion of households in Moldova³. The situation of Moldovan migrant communities in Italy is the same as in other European countries. The diverse problems that they are facing motivates them to create Diaspora associations, forums and joint platforms of cooperation by joint efforts to solve their issues and maintain their contacts and links with their homeland.

Diaspora participation in voting is based on its willingness to contribute for the future of its homeland. During the last three rounds of parliamentary elections in the last two years, pro-European parties managed

¹ Moldova: Under the influence. With the conflict between Russia and Ukraine getting bloodier, fears are increasing that Moldova could be next.

² Gh. Rusnac. Issues of Moldovan citizens in Italy, p. 118.

³ J. Leppink. Moldovan female migrants in Italy: Expectations of migration vs. migration experiences, p.5.

to obtain that missing edge that changed elections and dismissed the old political regime. What happened is that more than 90% of votes from the Diaspora were given to pro-European parties, only 45% - from the Russian Federation¹.

In 2009 the Moldavian Diaspora gave the decisive votes in the election for a pro-European future and new government without the Communist Party. The role of Diaspora communities, the NGOs, civil society was very important in delivering clear messages for supporting a common position for the future development and integration path for their country. In this sense, they did a lot of promotion to help increase pro-European voter turnout and to obtain victory for the democratic parties. After Russia failed to tighten its grip on the Communist Party, it reoriented visibly towards alternative political projects on the left flank. The Socialist Party of Moldova, run by Igor Dodon, a former member of the government under the Communists, received a substantial boost from Russia. Its leader benefited from photo opportunities with Russian politicians and Patriarch Kirill, and organized a concert with an anti-government message for the Moldovan diaspora in Moscow (there are around 300,000 Moldovans who work in Russia)².

During the last parliamentary elections from 30 November 2014, Moldova organized 95 voting sections abroad for diaspora community. Members of Moldovan diaspora from Europe expressed a strong support for the pro-European parties and for European integration. In Italy for these elections there were organized 25 polling stations, compared with only 5 in the Russian Federation³. The decision was argued by the low participation of Moldovan diaspora in the voting process in the Russian Federation. At the same time this decision was seen critically by civil society and international organizations, mentioning lack of transparency in determining how many polling stations to be opened abroad⁴.

The main achievements of Moldova's pro-European governing alliance for European integrations are considered to be EU visa liberalization

¹ R. Rusu. The impact of Diaspora on political processes in Republic of Moldova, p. 107.

² Cf. S. Secieru. How to Offset Russian Shadow Power? The Case of Moldova.

³ V. Vasiliu. Diaspora moldovenească votează pentru Europa.

⁴ D. Brett, E. Knott. The Moldovan Elections of 2014 are more than about Putin or the EU: Corruption, Poverty and Parties.

(April 2014) and signing the EU Association Agreement (June 2014), Deep and comprehensive Free Trade Area. At the same time these results were not enough to convince the voters from Russia of the progress in European integration and valuable achievements from the reforms development programs. The result was that Moldovan citizens residing in Russia gave their vote and support mainly for the pro-Russia parties, showing their disappointment for the pro-European party coalition.

Although the name and the structure of the ruling coalition changed during the last five years, the European integration has remained its main purpose. That is why some important leaders of the Diaspora, for example, urge the pro-European parties to re-unite for a coalition¹. The majority of citizens are still expecting that pro-European parties will mobilize their forces in order to secure the European path of the country. In this sense, Diaspora is supposed to choose between supporting Russia or Europe. However, it is obvious that pro-European views are the strongest and are winning this hard battle at the moment.

Conclusion

This comparative study reveals that diaspora plays an important role in the foreign policy and the integration paths of Armenia and Moldova. The Armenian and Moldovan Diasporas are increasing their role on the foreign and security policies of their homelands and on the countries of domicile. The article can serve as baseline data for developing a more systematic analysis of the role of Diasporas in international relations. As the integration path of Armenia showed, the existence of a large and powerful Armenian Diaspora in Russia provides an opportunity for Russia to strengthen its influence on social, cultural and economic space of Armenia. The argument that the state is “small” and “weak” because of resource scarcity is only partially applicable to the Armenian case as global Armenian Diaspora compensates its smallness. However, the Armenian Diaspora in Russian being connected with Armenian ruling business and oligarchy circles operates in accordance with the rules of game created by Russian and Armenian ruling groups’ interests. Thus, it can be assumed that many business and financial organizations of the Armenian Diaspora of Russia are agents of Russian policy. These facts also make the Russian interference into

¹ T. Cojocar. Moldova Between the Soviet Ways and the European Path.

the Armenian affairs much easier. However, as the case of Moldova shows, the Government of Moldova during recent years could use the potential of its diaspora communities to continue the European integration path. And due to the comparative political weakness of the Moldovan diaspora in Russia, it couldn't affect European integration path of Moldova. Thus, the national policies were adjusted to reflect some of the main needs and problems of the Diaspora communities.

Bibliography:

1. Armenian Diaspora Yearbook. Ministry of Diaspora of the Republic of Armenia, Yerevan, 2009.
2. Baser Bahar, Swain Ashok. "Diaspora Design versus Homeland Realities: Case Study of Armenian Diaspora", *Caucasian Review Of International Affairs*, Vol. 3 (1), Winter 2009.
3. Brett Daniel, Knott Eleanor. The Moldovan Elections of 2014 are more than about Putin or the EU: Corruption, Poverty and Parties. <http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/lsee/2014/12/17/the-moldovan-elections-of-2014-are-more-than-about-putin-or-the-eu-corruption-poverty-and-parties/>.
4. Cheianu-Andrei Diana, Mukomel Vladimir. Moldovan Diaspora Mapping Series I. Moldovans in the Russian Federation: socio-economic profile and policy challenges. IOM Mission to Moldova. Chişinău, 2013.
5. Cheianu-Andrei Diana. Mapping of the Moldovan Diaspora in Italy, Portugal, France and the United Kingdom. Moldovan Diaspora Mapping Series II. IOM Mission to Moldova. Chişinău, 2013.
6. Cheptene Adrian. Moldovan diaspora reprobates Russia's actions. Tribuna. <http://tribuna.md/en/moldovenii-din-diaspora-condamna-actiunile-rusiei/>.
7. Cojocaru Tudor. Moldova Between the Soviet Ways and the European Path. <http://4liberty.eu/moldova-between-the-soviet-ways-and-the-european-path/>.
8. EU-Moldova Association Agreement, What does the Agreement offer? http://eeas.europa.eu/moldova/pdf/quick_guide_eu_md_aa_en.pdf.
9. Esman Milton. J. *Diasporas in the Contemporary World Polity*, Malden, M.A. 2009.
10. Informative Note on the preliminary results of 2014 population and housing census of the Republic of Moldova.

- http://unstats.un.org/unsd/demographic/sources/census/2010_PHC/Moldova/MDA-2015-01-13.pdf.
11. Jandl Michael. Moldova Seeks Stability Amid Mass Emigration. December 2013. Migration Policy Institute MPI. <http://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/moldova-seeks-stability-amid-mass-emigration>.
 12. "Joint Statement by High Representative Catherine Ashton and Commissioner Stefan Füle on completion of negotiations on the future Association Agreement with Armenia", Brussels, 25 July 2013, A 401/13. http://www.consilium.europa.eu/uedocs/cms_Data/docs/pressdata/EN/foraff/138404.pdf, accessed on August 4, 2013.
 13. Leppink Jana. Moldovan female migrants in Italy: Expectations of migration vs. migration experiences IS Academy Policy Brief No. 12, 2013.
 14. Manaseryan Tatoul. "Diaspora the Comparative Advantage for Armenia", *DFI International & AIPRG Working Paper No. 04/14*, January, 2004.
 15. Markedonov Sergey. "Russia's "Internal South Caucasus": The Role and Importance of Caucasus Societies for Russia", *Caucasus Analytical Digest* No. 04/09.
 16. Migration and Development: Armenia Country Study, ILO, 2009, ILO Sub-regional Office for Eastern Europe and Central Asia, 2009, http://www.ilo.org/public/english/region/eurpro/moscow/info/publ/migr_dev_study_en.pdf (20.05.2014).
 17. Migration and Skills. In Armenia Results of the 2011/12 Migration Survey on the Relationship between Skills, Migration and Development, European Training Foundation and Caucasus Research, Resource Centers (Armenia) 2013.
 18. Moldova Labour Force Survey. National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova. Chisinau 2011. http://www.statistica.md/public/files/publicatii_electronice/ocupare_somaj/Forta_Munca_eng_2011.pdf.
 19. Moldova: Under the influence. With the conflict between Russia and Ukraine getting bloodier, fears are increasing that Moldova could be next. 17 July 2014. <http://www.aljazeera.com/programmes/peopleandpower/2014/07/moldova-under-influence-20147178139162372.html>.

20. Moldovan diaspora's contribution to development of home country, appreciated in Chisinau. 26 August 2014. <http://trm.md/en/social/contributia-diasporei-moldovene-ti-la-dezvoltarea-tarii-de-origine-apreciata-la-chisinau>.
21. Moşneaga Valeriu. Republic of Moldova: Diaspora and Diaspora Policy. Institute of Social Sciences, Slovak Journal of Political Sciences, Volume 14, 2014, No. 2, UCM in Trnava, Slovakia.
22. Oussatcheva Marina. "Institutions in Diaspora: The Case of Armenian Community in Russia", WPTC-01-09, Institute of Social & Cultural Anthropology, University of Oxford. 2009.
23. Păduraru Pavel. Moldova's diaspora looking for a way home. 26 November 2010. Timpul, Chişinău. <http://www.voxeurop.eu/en/content/article/406921-moldovas-diaspora-looking-way-home>.
24. Rusnac Gheorghe. Issues of Moldovan citizens in Italy//Republic of Moldova: migration challenges, Chisinau, 2010.
25. Rusu Rodica. The impact of Diaspora on political processes in Republic of Moldova. Academia de Administrare Publică de pe lângă Preşedintele Republicii Moldova. Revista: Administrarea Publică, nr. 4, 2012.
26. Saha David, Giucci Ricardo. Remittances from Russia: Macroeconomic implications of possible negative shocks. German Economic Team Moldova. Berlin / Chişinău, 2014.
27. Secieru Stanislav. How to Offset Russian Shadow Power? The Case of Moldova. Polish Institute for International Affairs. No. 125 (720), 31 October 2014.
28. Seven Armenians named Russia's richest businessmen in Forbe's ranking. Tert.am. 08 September 2014. <http://www.tert.am/en/news/2014/04/17/forbes/>.
29. Shain Yossi and Barth Aharon, "Diasporas and International Relations Theory", *International Organization*, Vol. 57, No. 3, Summer 2003.
30. Statement by President Serzh Sargsyan at the Joint Press Conference with the President of the Republic of Poland Bronisław Komorowski, 25.06.2013, <http://www.president.am/en/interviews-and-press-conferences/item/2013/06/25/President-Serzh-Sargsyan-press-conference-with-the-President-of-Poland/>.

31. Statement of Serzh Sargsyan, the President of the Republic of Armenia in the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe 02.10.2013. <http://www.president.am/en/statements-and-messages/item/2013/10/02/President-Serzh-Sargsyan-participated-at-the-session-of-the-PACE-speech/> (25.05.2014).
32. Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Armenia – 2006, https://www.cba.am/EN/ppperiodicals/vich_2006_eng.pdf (14.05.2014).
33. Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Armenia – 2011, https://www.cba.am/EN/ppperiodicals/vich_tex_12_eng.pdf (14.05.2014).
34. Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Armenia – 2013, https://www.cba.am/EN/ppperiodicals/vich_tex_13_eng.pdf (11.09.2014).
35. Statute of Russian Orthodox Church. 2000. <http://www.patriarchia.ru/db/text/133115.html>.
36. “The National Security Strategy of the Republic of Armenia”, approved at the session of National Security Council at the RA President office on January 26, 2007. http://mfa.am/u_files/file/doctrine/Doctrineeng.pdf, accessed on March 10, 2014.
37. The RA President Serzh Sargsyan’s Remarks at the Press Conference on the Results of the Negotiations with The RF President Vladimir Putin 03.09.2013. <http://www.president.am/en/interviews-and-press-conferences/item/2013/09/03/President-Serzh-Sargsyan-press-conference-working-visit-to-Russian-Federation/> (25.05.2014).
38. The Results of the National Population Census of Russia 2010. http://www.gks.ru/free_doc/new_site/perepis2010/croc/Documents/Vol4/pub-04-01.pdf (19.04.2014).
39. Tölölyan Khachig. “Elites and Institutions in the Armenian Transnation”, *Diaspora: A Journal of Transnational Studies*, Volume 9, Number 1, Spring 2000.
40. Unofficial report: About half a million Moldovans got the Romanian citizenship. <http://www.moldova.org/unofficial-report-about-half-a-million-moldovans-got-the-romanian-citizenship/>.
41. Vasiliu Vadim. Diaspora moldovenească votează pentru Europa. http://adevarul.ro/moldova/actualitate/diaspora-moldoveneasca-voteaza-europa-1_54744ad4a0eb96501e11577a/index.html.

42. Wendt Alexander. "Anarchy is what States Make of it: The Social Construction of Power Politics", *International Organization*, Vol. 46, No. 2, MIT Press, Spring 1992.
43. Wendt Alexander. *Social Theory of International Politics*. Cambridge, New York, Melbourne: Cambridge University Press, 1999.
44. World Bank. 2012. Developing Countries to Receive Over \$400 Billion in Remittances in 2012. Press release, November 20, 2012. <http://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2012/11/20/developing-countries-to-receive-over-400-billion-remittances-2012-world-bank-report>.
45. Բաղդասարյան Արթուր. "Հայաստանը պետք է վարի քաղաքականություն": <http://www.hartak.am/arm/index.php?id=16269> (24.05.2014).
46. Ժամակոչյան Աննա (ed.). *Հետխորհրդային երկրների հայկական համայնքների ինքնության խնդիրները և տեղեկատվական ռեսուրսները*: Եր. Նորավանք, 2010.
47. Дятлов Виктор, Мелконян Эдуард. *Армянская диаспора: очерки социокультурной типологии*. – Ер.: Институт Кавказа, 2009.
48. Захарян А.Э. Армянская диаспора в России и в мире / Армения и мир. Сборник статей. / Под ред. Э. Р. Григорьяна. – М.: Институт социальных наук, 2013.
49. Интервью "Голосу России" научный сотрудник Института экономики РАН Александр Караваев 10 февраля. http://rus.ruvr.ru/2014_02_10/Armenija-rasschitavaet-chto-Rossija-smjagchit-migracionnie-pravila-5768/.
50. Интервью президента Союза Армян России Ара Абрамяна, опубликованное в газете «Голос Армении». Ара Абрамян о Таможенном Союзе, Еркрас / Аналитика. 30 СЕНТЯБРЯ 2013, 21:45. <http://yerkramas.org//2013/09/30/ara-abramyan-o-tamozhenom-soyuze/> (21.05.2014).
51. «О внесении изменений в статью 27 Федерального закона «О порядке выезда из Российской Федерации и въезда в Российскую Федерацию» и статью 5 Федерального закона «О правовом положении иностранных граждан в Российской Федерации»». http://www.fms.gov.ru/foreign_national/izmenzakon/ (24.05.2014).

52. Путин Владимир Владимирович. Глава Российского государства цитировал сенатский Указ, подписанный Государем России Петром Первым в 1711 году. <http://sarinfo.org/armw/?c=armenians> (19.04.2014).

Copyright©Tigran YEPREMYAN

Copyright©Andrei ENACHI

“Romanian and Bulgarian” – Communication and Stereotypes about European Integration¹

Lecturer Dr. Gabriela GOUDENHOFT

gabrielagoudenhoft@yahoo.com

University of Oradea, Romania

Abstract: The negative stereotypes on immigrants are often present in media discourse. After the January 2007 a new stereotype occurs describing an *ad-hoc* group, newly acceded into the European Union, including Romanians and Bulgarians. They are being accused of “costing money”, burdening the social security, putting pressure on health care services, jeopardizing job access and increasing unemployment, increasing crime and bringing beggars, large families, poor and illiterate into the Western European countries. The public discourse abandoned the Muslims and Turkish integration issues, tackling the new one: Romanians and Bulgarians. This paper is part of a research on media discourse on Romanian diaspora living in Germany, emphasizing the links between public discourse, identity, communication and media.

Key-words: identity, media discourse, stereotype, diaspora, poverty immigration.

Introduction

Diaspora, conceived as any national group of people scattered from their homeland to other places around the globe or as national segments of population dispersed outside traditional homeland is the object of interest of a lot of research all the more it is talking nowadays by different forms and types of diaspora. Robin Cohen for instance is talking on *victim diaspora, labor diaspora, imperial diaspora, trade and business diaspora, homeland diaspora, cultural diaspora*².

Diaspora’s discourse – political, scholar, journalistic – emphasizes a lot of aspects of the phenomenon: social, cultural, linguistic, economic, political, communicational and historical and occurs wherever the

¹ This paper is part of an ongoing research project developed within the ERSTE Foundation Fellowship for Social Research 2015/2016.

² Cf. Robin Cohen, *Global Diaspora. An introduction*.

phenomenon of population dispersion appears: “Where once were dispersions, there now is diaspora”¹.

The methodology of this research is mainly based on discourse analysis and content analysis of some articles published in the German press about the group of new arrivals in the EU, Romanians and Bulgarians, which otherwise is an important and growing segment of the new wave of migrants in Western Europe.

Without the magnitude of the phenomenon met in the press from the UK, Romanian and Bulgarian migrants seem to “enjoy” some attention in the German press as well.

Romanians and Bulgarians in the German press

In May 2011, *Der Spiegel* published an article on the special situation of Romanian and Bulgarian members of the EU, but also who cannot fit into any pattern. “Die EU-Bürger leben in einer Schattenwelt”², meaning EU citizens living in a world of shadows, they are the new immigrants, the new problem for the German cities. For a long time the Muslims (Arabians and Turkish) were the problem and the object of integration. But the newcomers “look different from the many Arabs and Turks in their neighborhood, anxious, rushed”.

Making a case study from this problem, the article revealed by visiting schools, talking to children, teachers and directors that it was “a rapidly growing problem” with Bulgarians and Romanians. There have been noticed “children frustrated, who cannot read or write”, unable to understand the German language and that’s the reason they are receiving OB³ in the mid-year report, not necessary, because they are unable to think but because they cannot communicate with their teachers, who in turn cannot give them marks.

Statistically it seems that Romanians and Bulgarians are the largest groups of immigrants in Germany for some years, and many more that are not covered by any statistics. “Most hardly speak German, many run for three euros hourly wage an underground life. As an EU citizen they fall through each grid: For Turkish or Arab descent migrants there is integration

¹ Kachig Tölölyan, “Rethinking diaspora(s): stateless power in the transnational moment”, p.

3.

² Özlem Von Gezer, “Integration. Legale Sklaverei”, pp.44-45.

³ “Ohne Beurteilung” germ. = “Without judgment”.

courses and grants. Bulgarians and Romanians left to themselves. Already the old error of the Foreign Policy seem to repeat form parallel societies, in turn, look Politics and government inaction or often powerless. Employment, housing, education - all no convincing answers to the influx of South Eastern Europe”¹.

A Romanian-born journalist, living in Germany, Dani Rockhoff, noted² the interest showed by the German Press on the Romanian “issue”. For instance in a print edition of the weekly German publication *Der Spiegel* from May 2011, she noticed there are eight pages dedicated to Romanians and, of course the article signed by Özlem Gezer, cited above, where Romanians are described as a real problem for the German cities. The Romanian journalist marks expressions like “poor, exploited, partly illiterate children, they are described as “EU citizens who do not enroll in any pattern”.

On the issue of integration of immigrants in Germany, the journalist shows that Turkish, the largest community in Germany (over three million people) arrived after the war had different trajectories of integration, but there are a relatively recent trend among young people (second or third generation of immigrants) against the idea of integration. Chancellor Angela Merkel herself has found that “multiculturalism has failed” and ghettoization of immigrants in Germany is an obvious fact, at least in cities as Berlin, Hamburg, Köln or Düsseldorf. It is also easy to note the increasing aggressiveness of schools that have become ethnically heterogeneous lately.

The repatriation of ethnic Germans, on the other hand is a separate issue. After the fall of the Iron Curtain, there were repatriated ethnic Germans from the former USSR – over two million –, and about another 230,000 from Romania. They do not come but after criteria German immigrants category. After recognizing the identity documents, they are considered true-born German citizens³.

Many politicians, experts, NGOs, priests and imams debated, argued and decided that the integration of Turks and Arabs in Germany is not an

¹ Özlem Von Gezer, “Integration. Legale Sklaverei”, pp.44-45.

² Dani Rockhoff, “Spiegel: Români și bulgarii devin „grupul cu probleme” din Germania”.

³ Ibidem.

exquisite problem anymore. Another one is on the agenda nowadays: Romanians and Bulgarians.

Romanians and Bulgarians are compared with ancient Helots, exploited alike, out of statistics ignoring German language, living from wages under three Euros per hour. It cannot be ignored the conclusion of the Turkish journalist from *De Spiegel*, who thinks that Romanians and Bulgarians seem to repeat the experience of “host-workers”, the first wave of Turkish in Germany from 50 years ago, working as slaves, making their left behind families dependent by their remittances.

In the online edition of *Online Spiegel* from 03.02.2013, again German cities¹ have complaints on the invasion of Romanians and Bulgarians. We have noticed the constant use of the generic expression *Deutsche Städte* (German cities)². Not Germans, not German Government or German authorities, but German cities complain (*Deutsche Städte klagen*) on immigrants. Then a very often used stereotype occurs: “they (the immigrants) cost a lot of money!” The cost concerning municipalities would arise “by this poverty migration and its’ significant costs” for temporary shelter, medical care and social services. They (Romanians and Bulgarians) also endanger the social peace and social equilibrium. The article assigns the presence of a large number of Roma people which are identified as Romanians.

Dani Rockhoff shows an ambivalent attitude of German media towards migrants and implicitly towards Romanians. In the printed edition of *Der Spiegel* from 21 January 2013, on a neutral or down to optimistic key, a reassuringly situation presenting the “balance of foreign immigrants”, which compensates positively the declining birthrates in Germany. She noticed the resentfulness of the big cities representatives, upset to lose money and turned in anti-immigration, considering it as a result from an

¹ There are some German cities nominalised to be affected by Romanian and Bulgarian migration: Berlin, Dortmund, Duisburg, Hamburg, Hanovra, Munchen and Offenbach, according to *Online Spiegel*, 03.02.2013, <http://www.spiegel.de/politik/deutschland/deutsche-staedte-klagen-ueber-zuwanderer-aus-rumaenien-und-bulgarien-a-881212.html>.

² With reference to association of representatives of cities and municipalities - *Darstellung des Städtetages*.

internal dispute between German Länder towards redistribution issue¹. In this fight on the principle of solidarity and redistribution Romanians and Bulgarians seem to gain the role of scapegoat, they being blamed by the cities “impoverished” by the invasion of immigrants who do not speak German, are not professionally trained, who have many children and collect welfare from the local community who have to spend a lot in accommodating and integrating them.

Identity - something gained, something lost

In an article named “As a third-class citizens”, published in the online edition of *De Zeit*, from 23 of January 2014², in the column of “reader articles”, Cristina Meyer, a Romanian-born, wrote an interesting confession as a part of a Romanian family living for nearly 30 years in Germany. Author’s conclusion is that a German passport and state examination is not enough for a person born in Romania or Bulgaria. They will be always looked at as third-class citizens and they will always face and fight deep-seated prejudices.

First, it was the neighbor’s query towards foreign newcomers. The Romanian origin caused many unpleasant comments from colleagues, acquaintances. In order to stop it and to integrate in the German community the author made big efforts to acquit of the specific accent revealing the origin, gain a high German proficiency and German citizenship, graduated from high school and passed state exams. The final step to integration was made by changing last name through marriage.

The author struggles in gaining a German identity and she succeeded in disembarassing her origin. But despite her success to get rid of prejudice and of the stigma of its origin, the confession continues by the following: “Since then something is missing”.

Gains and losses in adapting to a new community are inherent. But the way of experiencing it, their perception on the situation is important because it brings definitive changes in the self-consciousness. In fact one of the ways in defining diasporans’ consciousness is the preservation of a

¹ There is a German Federal Agreement, completed till 2019, aiming to maintain a proportional uniform development and standard of living and relatively uniform for the full country and according to it, poorer regions receive funds from donor Länder. See Dani Rockhoff, “Românii și bulgarii, țapi ispășitori într-o ceartă germană”.

² Cristina Meyer, „Wie ein Bürger dritter Klasse”.

distinctive identity vis-à-vis a host society (Brubaker, 2005, Andersen, 2006). The concept of Diaspora could survive because of the special link towards homeland and new link towards hostland. Diaspora is oriented and is defining itself as identity through what homeland can survive out of its borders, meaning collective memory, national myths, an ideal kinship with a homeland as a virtual possibility of returning. Preserving identity even reshaping the idea of homeland helps diasporans and it is conditioned by maintaining boundaries in and towards host country (Goudenhoofd, 2015).

The influence of language in the process of building identities is decisive, even for the fact of identity negotiation through language often documented by many scholars. It is to be mentioned at least the approach of Ruth Wodak on the relationship between language/discourse and identity in her *Critical Discourse Analysis*, where the author uses the idea of discourse (“language use in speech and writing”) as “social practice” implying a dialectical relationship between the discursive event and situations, institutions, social structure, where there is a two-way influence every element of the relationship shaping and being shaped by the others. “That is, discourse is socially constitutive as well as socially conditioned – it constitutes situations, objects of knowledge, and the social identities and relationships between people and groups of people. It is constitutive both in the sense that it helps to sustain and reproduce the social status quo, and in the sense that it contributes to transforming it”¹.

Nevertheless, the identity is crystalized at the intersection of many perceptions and representations. It depends on “how the individual perceives himself”, but also “how the person is popularly perceived”² and it is marked by prejudices and stereotypes as we try to document in our study case.

The motivation on posting an article on the online wall of the *Die Zeit online* is presented explicitly by the author. Cristina Meyer noticed the recurrent usage of the expression “Romanian and Bulgarian” in the German media as a source or proliferation of biases and stereotypes and she felt the urge of correcting it, to offer another perspective on the issue. Beyond this

¹ Gilbert Weis, Ruth Wodak, “Introduction, Theory, Interdisciplinarity and Critical Discourse Analysis”, p.13.

² Ted C. Lewellen, *The anthropology of globalization: cultural anthropology enters the 21st century*, p.92.

motivation one can easily see the special relationship of a diasporan with the homeland. One can never bar from homeland even when succeeds a proficient language acquisition, diplomas and passport. Cristina Meyer inferred how on a field fertilized by fear one can easily cultivate a big amount of stereotypes. “Romanian and Bulgarian” expression has developed a bad connotation, because they are associated with poverty, social tourism, prostitution, Hartz IV¹. Any attempt to compensate these stereotypes is not helping too much and in fact compensation through opposite statement doesn’t help. For example, saying that in Romania there is the lowest rate of unemployment or that women can make a successful career there sounds unlikely.

Politics and Prejudice

The year 2013 was marked on the topic we are tackling by the political statements, much publicized in German media of a CSU² politician, Hans-Peter Friedrich, the Interior Minister of Germany at that time³. He vehemently opposed Romania’s entry into the Schengen and reiterated the issue (stereotype) of migration poverty brought by Bulgaria and Romania in Germany.

At the beginning of march 2013 *Der Spiegel* magazine published an article entitled “Am Veto scheitern”, in fact an interview with the German Interior Minister, who stated that Germany would not allow Romania or Bulgaria to join the European open-border Schengen zone⁴. He explained his position based on the insufficient progress made by Romania fighting corruption⁵. The statement was publicized by German media and had had

¹ The fourth stage of the social and employment reform in Germany took effect by January 1, 2005. Addressed to people affected by unemployment and long-term unemployment ('Arbeitslosenhilfe') it concerns welfare benefits ('Sozialhilfe') and *Sozialhilfe* (social assistance).

² Die Christlich-Soziale Union in Bayern e. V.

³ Hans-Peter Friedrich - the Interior Minister of Germany during 3.03.2011 – 17.12.2013.

⁴ *Der Spiegel*, issue 10/04.03.2013, p.17, cf. to the online edition: <http://www.spiegel.de/international/europe/interior-minister-friedrich-says-no-schengen-for-bulgaria-and-romania-a-886704.html>.

⁵ Ibidem, SPIEGEL: What are the reasons for your position?

Friedrich: The EU has long been evaluating whether or not Romania and Bulgaria are ready for acceptance in the Schengen Area. The last annual report showed progress, but it’s not enough. Bulgaria and Romania still have to be more decisive in the fight against corruption.

many reactions from Romanian media and international media, as from EU institutions as the Commission.

Leaving the Schengen issue, we noticed the politician's position of the incidence of Romanians' migration on the German social welfare system. We have to mention that Friedrich made many controversial political populist and anti-immigration statements. The interview contains a question on "poverty migration", expressing the warning of the mayors of German cities towards the "huge levels of poverty migration" once Romanian and Bulgarian workers are to be allowed to work and live anywhere in the EU in 2014. Minister Friedrich alluded to "those who only come to receive social welfare" as persons abusing the freedom of movement and he assigned "they must be effectively prevented from doing so" through specific measures:

"The European Commission has to ensure that Romania and Bulgaria actually use the funds that are available to them for the benefit of their citizens. In addition, I would like to strengthen the penalties for attempted welfare fraud. Such penalties could, for example, include a ban on the return of those we have deported. I will promote such measures in Brussels. We cannot allow a situation to develop whereby people from all over Europe come to Germany because we have the highest social welfare payments"¹.

Deutsche Welle released the Minister statement and his call to the European Commission – "Side-swipe at the Commission": "The European Commission will have to learn to pay closer attention to the points of view and sensibilities of people within the member states"².

Die Zeit took up the ball and disclosed the minister's intentions of expelling the EU's social scammers ("EU-Sozialbetrüger"), targeting

Those who acquire a visa through bribery could travel all the way to Germany without further controls. Our citizens will only accept an expansion of the Schengen Area if some fundamental conditions have been met. That is not yet the case".

¹ *Der Spiegel*, issue 10/04.03.2013, p.17, cf. <http://www.spiegel.de/international/europe/interior-minister-friedrich-says-no-schengen-for-bulgaria-and-romania-a-886704.html>.

² <http://www.dw.de/minister-germany-would-veto-bulgaria-romania-in-schengen/a-16642617>.

Romanian and Bulgarian migrants, albeit they are EU citizens¹. According to the weekly publication, the German Interior Minister Hans-Peter Friedrich (CSU) has announced a hard line against immigration from Romania and Bulgaria stipulating that the “federal government would continue to respond in case of misuse of social benefits with expulsion and entry bans” in a declaration at a meeting of EU interior ministers in Luxembourg². He grounded his attitude based on the German communities’ complaints against the increasing cases of people particularly from Romania and Bulgaria, which allegedly targeted going to Germany to apply for benefits. Friedrich also urged Bulgaria and Romania again to improve the living conditions of immigrants, mostly referring to the Roma minority.

Der Spiegel renewed the topic with Friedrich statement who affirmed he wants to “align the issue with our current national legislative initiatives” and give these new arrivals a message: “If you are working here illegally – no matter how – then please go back to where you came from!”³. Friedrich used the expression persons „defrauding social services” or in “fraudulent enter” and he reiterated the intention of expelling them despite their right to work and travel throughout the member states as citizens of the EU and to ban them from returning to Germany.

Albeit his thundery statements, the European Commission rejected the idea of authorization expelling groups. EU Home Affairs Commissioner Cecilia Malmström pointed out that there are insufficient proves, figures or examples to document the above complaint of the German politician, reassigning that restricting the free movement of EU citizens is “out of the question”.

The endorsement from the Netherland, the UK and Austria for Friedrich’s point of view ceased eventually. Although initially Johanna Mikl-Leitner, the Internal Ministry of Austria signed a common letter for the limitation of the free movement for some categories of people (Roma

¹ *Die Zeit*, 07.06.2013, <http://www.zeit.de/politik/deutschland/2013-06/Friedrich-Einwanderer-Armut-Bulgarien-Rumaenien>.

² *Ibidem*.

³ “Interior Minister: Germany to Deport 'Poverty Immigrants'”, *Der Spiegel*, 03.07.2013, <http://www.spiegel.de/international/germany/german-interior-minister-expell-eastern-european-poverty-immigrants-a-904415.html>.

people to be read)¹, she finally admitted that the “poverty migration” is not a problem to be acknowledged in Austria.

It is easy to see that this migration issues such as poverty immigration burdening the German state with new social costs, relating to the increasing criminality to the arrival of Southeastern Europe’s immigrants, the language barrier making barely impossible any integration effort are topics used and discarded by politicians for electoral purposes in a populist way to gain the sympathy of the population and in an attempt to show some empathy.

In an article published in *Die Welt* from 24.07.2013², Konrad Putzier emphasized the link between xenophobia and the election campaign in a Germany receiving “the poorest of the poor (...) often poorly trained, without knowing the language”. In this country, growing xenophobia, during the election campaign the theme plays a role. He also noticed that particularly “xenophobia against Roma in this country is a particularly sensitive issue”³. There were expressed some fears against the stigmatization of Roma “the unholy tradition of centuries of discrediting, exclusion and persecution” and the declarations of the German Minister of the Interior, Hans-Peter Friedrich statements promoting limitation of free movement in specific cases are not meant to reassure us. The author underlined some disagreements to the proposed restrictions, citing Rainer Münz, migration expert at Erste Bank Group and EU former adviser who appreciated that “immigrants who live at the expense of the welfare state, are not a mass phenomenon”⁴.

The stereotype of associating Romania and Bulgaria with “poverty immigration” (“Armutszuwanderung”) is the most significantly created by politicians and released in media and debunked also of journalists analyzing facts.

For instance an interesting analysis was made by the *MiGAZIN* from 21.05.2013, a German journal for migration and integration, questioning the

¹ She came in for a lot of criticism, even accused for racism in Austrian media. Cf. newspaper *Linkswende*, June 2013.

²<http://www.welt.de/wall-street-journal/article118332572/Europas-Arme-kommen-nach-Deutschland.html>.

³ Ibidem.

⁴ Ibidem.

problem raised by German Internal Minister, regarding the alleged “Wildfire” (“Flächenbrand”) of the “poverty migration” brought from Romania and Bulgaria and presented some data offered by the Berlin Institute for Population and Development¹. There are two concerns to assess not only in terms of their legitimacy but also as myths able to be debunked: are the Romanian and Bulgarian immigrants really poor? and Which is the real number of Romanian and Bulgarian immigrants in Germany? According to the investigation cited “statistics show that immigrants from Romania and Bulgaria are not all poor”².

According to the German Association of Cities 147,000 people are the ones who have migrated in 2011 from Romania and Bulgaria. This number isn’t so as an absolute figure but related to the peoples who left Germany in the same year, and their number is assessed to 89,000, resulting about 58,000 people from Romania and Bulgaria who came to Germany in 2011. Many of this received a work permit proving a high or medium qualification and according to Eurostat, only 30 percent of Romanians and 44 percent of Bulgarians were not in a position to cover basic living needs (rent, heating or two meals a day) in 2011. Romanians and Bulgarians have also the opportunity to be professionally active even without a job in Germany, but developing an independent business. For example, only in the Berlin district of Neukölln, according to a report of the local district office, the number of Romanian and Bulgarian trade of 2,867 in early January 2013 has grown to 3,002 in late February³.

A real problem is the unregistered immigration. Although there are no benefits for non-registered, the Neukölln district office estimates the actual total number of people living in Neukölln from both countries, Roma more than 10,000 people. This situation indicates there are thousands of people living without income and therefore exposed to a high risk of poverty. Since they are not officially reported, they cannot operate either as employees, nor earn a living as a self-employed and they cannot receive social security benefits. To earn their living, they depend on begging income where they often involve their children or they are busy with prostitution

¹ Berlin-Institut für Bevölkerung und Entwicklung.

² <http://www.migazin.de/2013/05/21/einwanderung-aus-rumaenien-und-bulgarien/>.

³ Ibidem.

and crime. This perspective is not as frightening as is presented to be by politicians and cities' representatives but is a complex one and requires a nuanced approach.

In response to the new created stereotype in the German media, Romanian press reacts in its own way. For example *Capital* pretends the issue of social burden of Romanian and Bulgarian immigrants in Germany is overestimated: "Much ado about nothing?" – wrote a Romanian journalist¹. According to the cited article from Deutsche Welle, in June 2013, there were 32.600 Romanians and Bulgarians who received child benefit (Kindergeld) in Germany, with 44% more than a year ago. However, this means only 0.4% of those who receive this allowance in Germany. The journalist made out a case that the same situation is documented for long-term social benefits for chronically unemployed and people with low incomes (Hartz IV). Yes, there are 35.400 people (Romanian and Bulgarian) who received the social aid in April 2013, meaning with 39% more than the same period from 2012. But if we look at the whole picture, compared to the whole of Germany, Romanians and Bulgarians who receive Hartz IV represent only 0.6% of the total. From an overall of around 300,000 Romanians and Bulgarians living in Germany (with 71,000 more than a year ago), most of them do not receive any Hartz IV and no child benefit. The fact is "most Romanians and Bulgarians work hard and contribute greatly to the economic growth of Germany, paying taxes and social security"². The Romanian journalist admitted the possibility of some abuses claimed by German cities³ but he disclosed that normally they are not entitled to receive aids from Hartz IV. Finally he rallied to Viviane Reading, the Vice-President of the European Commission, labeling this rethoric as a populist one.

¹ Ovidiu Suci, "DEUTSCHE WELLE: Imigranții sărăciei din România și Bulgaria abuzează de ajutoarele sociale germane".

² This is also the position of Laszlo Andor, the EU commissioner on social problems.

³ Immigrants using the self-employed status who do not earn enough or those who have lost jobs can receive these social benefits. German authorities however complain that more recent immigrants come from Romania and Bulgaria to set up companies, then quickly bankrupt those companies only with the purpose to receive the aid provided by the state. Similarly immigrants would abuse of the child allowances.

Conclusion

A few months ago, *The Guardian*¹ published an interesting research, involving writers from *The Guardian*, *Le Monde*, *El País*, *Süddeutsche Zeitung* and *La Stampa*, in order to observe how several claims, complaints on migration are valid or not in their country. With the same occasion an inventory of the myths on migration was made so that one can notice which are the stereotypes released by media, politicians, etc.: “They are tacking our jobs”; “They deplete welfare budgets”; “They don’t integrate”; “They come here illegally”; “Where there are immigrants you’ll find crime”; “They dilute our values”; “They won’t learn local languages”; “Relaxing immigration laws would lead to the country being inundated”; “Basic services such as hospitals and schools collapse”; “They don’t return to their own countries when their situation improves”.

We have already analyzed some of this statement and we have noticed that many of the allegations regarding Romanian and Bulgarian immigration in Germany are actually part of a larger biased representation of the migrant. In the inquiry given by *The Guardian* there are some answers from the German media to the proposed statements. Isabel Pfaff from *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, noted there are many terms containing embedded prejudice: “ghettoization”, “no-go area”, “mafia” linking immigrants to the crime. But she also appealed to a survey made by a German criminologist, Cristian Walburg who made clear that “adult immigrants in Germany are not more inclined to commit crimes than a native German person”². However, statistically there are more non-German young suspects, but he concluded “the appetite for violence and crime has more to do with social marginalization than the origins”.

Concerning the values dilution, the same journalist determined that we cannot consider the values static, either pure. “Values are always the sum of the beliefs of the individuals that are negotiated as we live together. The more these individuals widen their horizons through immigration, the wider their spectrum of values gets”³. One cannot say myths and stereotypes on immigration would ever stop, because immigration is a topic

¹ “Ten myths about migration”, *The Guardian*, 21.10.2014, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/oct/21/ten-myths-migration-europe>.

² *Ibidem*.

³ *Ibidem*.

which has polarized politics for a good while. Is there immigration a threat or an asset? This question brings many debates and disputes and they are visible in the media.

Politicians always use the immigration topic in election campaigns to gain votes, local communities need someone to blame for budgets dissipation or for the budgets deficiency, people have dissatisfactions, they are affected by economic crises, unemployment, crime and the easiest way of bearing all of this is to find a scapegoat. Romanian and Bulgarian are an ad-hoc group, became the new bone to be chewed in any opportunity. They came from the South East of Europe, they are associated with poverty, lack of education, poor skills and qualification, no German language proficiency, predisposed to abuse social welfare burdening the system, increasing the crime and the extremity. And these allegations are documented with numbers. Statistically the percentage of immigrants exploded. But sometimes numbers are deceitful. We presented some data showing the number of Romanian and Bulgarian in Germany is not so big actually and the welfare benefits as it is Hartz IV is not as burdened by this group as it is claimed to be. Not every Romanian and Bulgarian is poor or uneducated; actually there are many of them highly qualified, skillful, and able to adapt and easily to be considered an asset not a risk.

It is the media function to release not only fears towards immigration, opinion on distinct issues, but also to correct prejudices to put a correct light on social and political phenomenon, beyond casual interests.

Bibliography:

1. ANDERSON, Benedict, *Imagined Communities. Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*, revised edition, Verso, London / New York, 2006.
2. BRUBAKER, Rogers, The 'diaspora' diaspora, in *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, vol.28, no1, jan.2005, pp.1-19.
3. COHEN, Robin, *Global Diaspora. An introduction*, second edition, Routledge, London / New York, 2008.
4. VON GEZER, Özlem, "Integration. Legale Sklaverei" in *Der Spiegel*, no.21/2011, 23.05.2011, pp.44-45.
5. GOUDENHOOF, Gabriela, "Diaspora is going online. Identity, language and digital communication", in *Journal of Roumanian Literary Studies*, issue 6/2015, pp.150-160.

6. LEWELLEN, Ted C., *The anthropology of globalization: cultural anthropology enters the 21st century*, Bergin & Garvey, Westport, Connecticut and London, 2002.
7. *Media: Agero, Capital, Der Spiegel, Die Zeit, Die Welt, Deutsche Welle, MiGAZIN, Süddeutsche Zeitung, The Guardian*.
8. MEYER, Cristina, "Wie ein Bürger dritter Klasse", in <http://www.zeit.de/gesellschaft/2014-01/integration-deutschland-rumaenien>.
9. ROCKHOFF, Dani, "Românii și bulgarii, țapi ispășitori într-o ceartă germană" in *Agero*, 09.02.2013, <http://www.agero-stuttgart.de/REVISTA-AGERO/ACTUALITATEA%20GERMANA/Romanii%20si%20bulgarii%20tapi%20ispasitori%20de%20Rockhoff.htm>.
10. ROCKHOFF, Dani, "Spiegel: Românii și bulgarii devin „grupul cu probleme“ din Germania" in *Agero*, 4.06.2011, <http://www.agero-stuttgart.de/REVISTA-AGERO/ACTUALITATEA%20GERMANA/Romanii%20si%20bulgarii%20devin%20grupul%20cu%20probleme%20de%20Rockhoff.htm>.
11. SUCIU, Ovidiu, "DEUTSCHE WELLE: Imigranții sărăciei din România și Bulgaria abuzează de ajutoarele sociale germane" in *Capital*, 10 of October 2013.
12. TÖLÖLYAN, Kachig, "Rethinking diaspora(s): stateless power in the transnational moment", in *Diaspora: a journal of transnational studies*, 5(1), 1996, pp. 3–36.
13. WEIS, Gilbert, WODAK, Ruth, "Introduction, Theory, Interdisciplinarity and Critical Discourse Analysis" in Weis, G. and Wodak, R. (eds.), *Critical Discourse Analysis. Theory and Interdisciplinarity*, Plagrove MacMillan, London, 2003, pp.1-32.

Copyright©Gabriela GOUDENHOFT

Theory of Differentiated Integration in Practice – from the Western Balkans to the Eastern Partnership

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mircea BRIE

mbrie@uoradea.ro

University of Oradea, Romania

Lecturer Daniela BLAGA

msdanielablaga@gmail.com

University of Oradea, Romania

Abstract: The relationship between the European Union and the Western Balkans offers the backdrop for testing the concept of differentiated integration based on a key initiative that is the regional approach. Regional approach pushes states toward forms of regional cooperation that need to be achieved if progress is sought in their contractual relations with the EU. The same integration ladder is applied to some of the Eastern European states, too, notably the six Eastern Partnership states. As the EU has enlarged, these countries have become closer neighbours and their security, stability and prosperity is increasingly affecting those of the EU's. This regional approach of the EU looks great on paper, but in practice, these two regions are not uniform, they do not have constants in the regional characteristics, in terms of identity, culture, and political and economic development. The space of Eastern Europe has a different kind of history than the rest of the continent. Can all these countries be pushed into a single regional approach? The popular idea of "core Europe" suggests that membership of the EU is considered a privilege, not a right. Ethnic barriers have been passed by some countries with great difficulty, and the prospect of European integration does not entail a solution to all disagreements. Moreover, some states / nations are at an early stage of identity construction process, often involving claims or amendments to / from other countries. Our work will attempt to sieve through determiners in the integration process of the Western Balkans and to see if this is a first model of differentiated integration on which other regions, notably the countries from the Eastern Partnership, have been molded onto.

Key-words: EU, Western Balkans, Eastern Partnership, (differentiated) integration, ethnicity, cooperation, region, enlargement.

The political and scientific relevance of this topic is perceived as increasingly larger and although the overall research on this topic used to be

characterized by little and disparate data, with a poor theoretical framework that was relatively unfocused on the explanatory analysis, nowadays many researchers have focused their scientific investigations on attempting to provide a theoretical foundation for differentiated integration. Nevertheless, by trying to develop a theory for this phenomenon, the approach is inductive, that is the existing models have not followed theoretical models, but tried to provide quick solutions to problems raised by certain states.

The relation between the EU and the Balkans provides scholars with a new insight on the differentiated integration applied on various binds that are forged between the EU and non-EU states (in the case of the Balkans we can address the states as a group). Most studies of differentiated integration used to be limited to the European Union, to the relations between the Member States and to various institutional arrangements. Different states at different moments have entered contractual agreements with the Union in order to consolidate their European perspective¹.

Because of their history and the way in which their respective societies have developed the states of the Western Balkans are on different trajectories for EU accession. A large range of initiatives are made available for the Western Balkans out of which we would like to single out for the purpose of our study of the regional approach. The regional approach is a Procrustes Bed for the states of the Western Balkans, towards forms of regional cooperation that must be attained as a condition to move forward with the contractual agreements with the EU. Thus, the region of the Western Balkans is not one to share regional characteristics, either in terms of identity, culture, or political and economic development². They share geographical proximity, a history that has been agitated and EU policy to bring and maintain together. It has been proven difficult for the EU to define in clear lines where the Western Balkans lie; it was much easier to define the Western Balkans in terms of shared recent violent past. Various policies could be designed based on the economy of these countries, but the regionalism promoted by the EU is based on pushing the hostile states

¹ D. Leuffen, B. Rittberger, F. Schimmelfennig, *Differentiated Integration, Explaining Variation in the European Union*, pp. 2-6

² *Ibidem*, pp. 26-28

towards cross-border cooperation while their accession to the EU is postponed until local problems are somehow mitigated.

What happens eastward from the Balkans is equally different from the core Europe. *Different* is the key word here. Not only Eastern Europe has a different history (the years of communism shaped it differently) than Western Europe, but also the dissolution of the USSR left a series of countries on a path that is different from what it used to be and different from what the rest of Europe is on. No longer under the Russian administration, but under the confluence of Russia, the EU's and NATO's interests: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine signed the Eastern Partnership in their express wish to join the EU. Launched in 2009, the Eastern Partnership is a joint initiative between the EU, Member States and the Eastern European partner countries. The partner countries interested in moving towards the EU and increasing political, economic and cultural links are enabled to do so based on a shared commitment to international law and fundamental values – democracy, the rule of law and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms – and to the market economy, sustainable development and good governance. Each partner country has its own path to step on and the final target is to improve relations between the individual countries.

Europe is far from being a single-tier space. Just like the Western Balkans, Europe knows variety, it is a multi-identity space. Identity cleavages are present everywhere: Catholic Europe-Orthodox Europe; Western Europe-Eastern Europe; Christian Europe-Muslim Europe; Europe – the EU; Europe – the Non-EU¹. But in this European area, the Balkans is not lost among the other states; it does not conform to the European standards. It remains rather off-standish. Europe did not know and does not know how to manage the Balkans; it has been easier for Europe to regard the Balkans as the Other. The same label has been applied to the former Soviet states. The multiple identities are found in the approach of the European policies. Rethinking a theoretical model focused on the Balkans is therefore necessary. Rethinking a theoretical model focused on the former Soviet states is also necessary. There is great need of refining policies and of

¹ M. Brie, I. Polgar, F. Chirodea, *Cultural Identity, Diversity and European Integration. Introductory Study*, pp. 9-11

improving the knowledge about the space. Improving knowledge means an improvement of the entire situation and this means better integration.

1. First things first, what is differentiated integration?

Textbooks give directions; researches have demonstrated that economic and social progress is closely related to the coexistence in time and space of the actual world of nations. Things are not what they used to be, lines have been increasingly blurred; we live in the global village. In a post-war era in which we talk of globalization and mondialization, integration has become part of usual terminology. Assimilation is no longer officially happening. Economic integration is a complex process; it is based on the development of relations of cooperation and collaboration of an organized and systematic nature, between several countries seeking to achieve larger economic areas of action or “larger assemblies” that allow the full and more efficient use of production capabilities, as well as the more active promotion of the common interests of the partners in the global market. In this way, between the participating countries will take shape not only relations of cooperation, but also systematic and stable economic interdependence¹.

Let us see how we got from A to B, notably how we got from integration to positive or negative discrimination, or in other words to differentiated integration. In a very general sense, **economic integration** can be defined as the process of interaction and development of economic interdependence between the states through various forms and methods, which, on the one hand, ensure the continuity and the deepening of mutual exchanges and, on the other hand, increase the degree of interpenetration of national economies in a body diverse in presentation, but unified and homogeneous in its functionality².

In terms of the nature and contents of relations between countries, economic integration leads to the following categories:

- *preferential* relations between the Member States within a group or an organization, but also *protectionist* treatment towards third party countries;

¹ Gh. Crețoiu, V. Cornescu, I. Bucur, *Economie*, p. 270

² *Ibidem*, pp. 582-583

- relations of cooperation between Member States and competition or competitive relations between some integrationist organizations;
- specific relations of cooperation or tension between regional and global organizations.

So, we have reached a first level of differentiation: preferential treatment in terms of economic integration.

The inductive approach (of members of academia and think tankers) has come up with explanations and possible definitions for a European reality. Thus, **preferential integration**, or **flexible integration**, or **differentiated integration** refers to the territorially fragmented validity of the EU norms, be it economic policies or social policies. *The integration is differentiated if: the individual EU norms are not applied to some Member States; the individual EU norms are applied to some non-EU states; or both.* The specialists in European Studies, together with politicians and members of international organizations believe that the territorial and functional enlargement of the EU resulted in an increase of the need for differentiated integration¹.

The consequence? Various solutions were designed for various Member States with different priorities and different capacities to move on the path of progress towards a deeper integration at various speeds².

Differentiated integration, in one form or another, has long been practiced. Like any concept put in practice, it can present both advantages and disadvantages.

Why we want differentiated integration?

Differentiated integration does not prevent progress, but rather unifies the integration results in relation to the whole (i.e. the entirety of the member states).

Differentiated integration is a consequence of the diversity and plurality of the Member States and provides not only a legal framework for countries that want to submit their application, but also ways of expressing individual will by separating from the whole (see the case of the *opt-out*).

¹ <http://www.eup.ethz.ch/research/diffintegration>, viewed at 29.08.2014

² *Differentiated Integration in An Enlarged Union*, published in March 27, 2002, revised in January 29, 2010, <http://www.euractiv.com/future-eu/differentiated-integration-enlarged-union/article-117073>, viewed at 29.05.2015

In general, differentiated integration is addressed to the states that are not integrated (see the cases of Macedonia and Serbia) or states that are excluded (see the case of the UK before it was accepted to join).

If differentiated integration provides different ways and different speeds for membership and / or living in the Union then it also offers a reversed potential for separation from the Union, at one level or more (see the discussion regarding Greece and Spain, the euro zone, etc.).

Why we don't want differentiated integration?

A first reaction to the differentiated integration policies enforced in states that have not yet received permanent membership status is that the progress within the EU (especially regarding EU enlargement) is hindered by a number of uneven policies. If we regard this issue through the lens of local realities seen by comparison with European realities, it can be argued that differentiated integration policies were issued and applied precisely in response to these local realities (see the case of Romania and Bulgaria - corruption or Serbia - human rights).

Another argument against differentiated integration is the uneven enforcement of European rules only in some of the states and addressed only to some European citizens (see the Schengen area or the cooperation in security and intelligence exchange between states).

The most serious objection relates to obtaining benefits from differentiated integration without assuming the costs of participation in such integration (see the differentiated monetary policy or the safety and defense case, especially in the context of EU-NATO relations).

1. Differentiated integration in the space of former Yugoslavia. A possible first model

Different Balkan states signed different contractual agreements with the European Union, with the expressed wish to consolidate their "European perspective"¹. The EU has a large range of initiatives, already implemented or in the process of implementation, for the Western Balkans. One such key initiative is the regional approach, which pushes the Western Balkan states toward forms of regional cooperation that need to be achieved if progress is sought in their contractual relations with the EU. This approach of the EU is salutary in theory, but in practice, the region of the

¹ K. Dyson, A. Sepos (eds), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, pp. 5-8

Western Balkans is not uniform, it does not have any constants in the regional characteristics in terms of identity, culture, and political and economic development.

The Western Balkans space cannot be treated as a whole. The dissolution of Yugoslavia brought Europe to face a new problem: the new state borders are not the same with the frontiers between the nations. Although the Christian denominations (particularly the Orthodox confession, but also Catholicism in Slovenia and Croatia) are the majority here, the Muslim communities in the Western Balkans are not an artificial creation; they are the result of a long history (the migration of Muslim population from Asia and the conversion of local population to Islam)¹. These differences in religion and ethnicity have led to political disagreements, the relations between states being managed unequally by them (see the cases of Croatia-Serbia, Serbia-Kosovo-Albania or Macedonia-Greece) not to mention that Europe's reactions to the Balkan movements are divided (see the recognition of the independence of Kosovo).

In view of the complex features of the Balkans, it is questionable why Europe has been intent on treating the Balkans as a whole region. There is a historical reason that adds to the psychological reason to prove that the nations and ethnicities living within the geographical space of the Balkans do not share the same traits. Let's have a look at the Yugoslav wars or the disintegration of Yugoslavia that only made more visible that the unification that gave the former Republic of Yugoslavia was a political one and it was not shared by the inhabitants of the newly created state.

The Balkans and its inhabitants still raise negative reactions, and the events of 1990 onwards have "helped" to consolidate their negative image. In terms of identity and territory, the Balkans proved to be an easy target for the European critique. From the assassination of the Archduke Franz Ferdinand to Yugoslavia's violent collapse, the modern history of the Balkans is easily condemnable. The expression "Balkans, the powder keg of Europe" is copied, enhanced and almost always used to describe the politics developed in the region. The long period Western perception of the Western Balkans is beyond that of a region with problems, but by judging after European marks, the perception is that of a foreign region, an alien

¹ J.-F. Gossiaux, *Pouvoirs ethniques dans les Balkans*, pp. 37-39

region located at the very heart of Europe; the Other, geographically in Europe, but in attitudes and actions with no roots in Europe. Some dispute this image, arguing that whatever image created in the mind of the Western Europe is that of some “imaginary Balkans”. An inextricably geographical region of Europe, but culturally constructed as Alterity, the Balkans have often served as a repository of negative characteristics on which a positive image of the “European” was built¹.

All these had a tremendous influence on the modern understanding of the Balkans and consequently on the impact on the EU’s policies towards the region.

When the Federative Republic of Yugoslavia was amid a bloody conflict, of ethnical purging and genocide, Europe was transforming as well: in the East – the fall of communism; in the West – the European project (Treaty of Maastricht and the creation of the European Union); in other words, a true redesign of the continent. This has been more than a spatial and territorial redesign; it was one of cultural and ideological change where the Europeanness was gaining ground with its new norms and democratic ideals. It was a time for the nation-state to change face. The European project turned the table around, the nation-state was starting to lose ground. Nationalism raised once more with the fall of communism and with it so was the question of ethnical identity in some states. Not much importance was given to nationalism and ethnic identity as the new wave of democratic reconstruction of a universal European space was the new height. Against this euphoric backdrop, whatever European conflict that was simmering in the Balkan region neighbouring both Eastern and Western Europe was impossible to grasp. It was easier for Europe to turn a blind eye and to return to Todorova’s explanation of the “imaginary Balkans”. Robert D. Kaplan comes up with another explanation, a stereotype, finding plausible ground for the Yugoslav wars being rooted in the much older hypotheses referring to a “non-European” part of the continent².

The “Balkans” became a pejorative term for a continental region amid the war³. Following the conflict in Yugoslavia, the rest of the region

¹ Cf. M. Todorova, *Imagining the Balkans*

² R. D. Kaplan, *Balkan Ghosts: A Journey through History*, pp. 79-181

³ K. Dyson, A. Sepos (eds), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, pp. 120-128

was perceived as having the same problems with the same enmities that fuelled the Yugoslav wars. Again, Europe looked at the Balkans as a region, on a whole. The main reason for confusion was the lack of a clear distinction between the geostrategic threats and the consequences of Yugoslavia's break-up, and the socio-cultural problems that are at the core of the conflicts in the area¹. The general view was that the Yugoslav wars and thus the Balkans politics were ones of nationalistic fight by placing one ethnic group against the other². And that was seen as an anachronism in a new Europe on its way to advanced integration.

Susan Woodward, analysing the causes of the Yugoslav wars³, maintains that the problems of Yugoslavia were not the problems of Europe. Romania and Bulgaria, for instance, were not caught by the same ethnical problems as Yugoslavia. Incapable to reach some consensus as to what to do with the Balkans and moreover, without any coercion mechanisms, the EU set out an isolation policy; isolation against war, against refugees and economic migrants. This was the policy applied to the entire region until the second half of the 1990s when after the end of the war in Bosnia (December 1995), some states perceived as being Balkan – Slovenia, Romania and Bulgaria – entered in contractual agreements with the EU and later on even started their negotiations for accession.

Western Europe realized in the whole process that the Union maintained separate relations with separate states and groups of states from the region. Thus, a new term appeared the South-Eastern Europe (SEE) that replaced the term “Balkans” and Romania and Bulgaria received the green light for a different path to join the EU. Romania and Bulgaria applied for EU membership in December 1995, the Luxembourg European Council issued a favourable response in December 1997, and the negotiations for full membership began in early 2000.

Romania and Bulgaria's accession to the European Union is an example for decision-making and policies of differentiated integration. The big gap of time between the issuance of a favourable opinion and the beginning of negotiations was because while politically and strategically the

¹ M. Glenny, *The Fall of Yugoslavia: The Third Balkan War*, pp. 92-105

² S. Economides, “The Balkan Agenda: Security and Regionalism in the New Europe”, pp. 142-156

³ S. Woodward, *Balkan Tragedy: Chaos and Dissolution after the Cold War*, pp. 22-31

EU wanted to encourage Romania and Bulgaria, in reality, these countries could not fulfill the criteria for membership in the short term.

Slovenia followed a different path once it emerged free from the Yugoslav Federation: Slovenian approaches to the EU were viewed much more favourably due to Slovenia's ability to meet the accession criteria and the *acquis*, but also because of the strong support within the EU (France, the UK, Germany, despite strong objections from Italy), and the general belief that Slovenia is a central European state and not a Balkan one.

With three countries on different paths, echoes were not late to appear. There are several implications of the differentiated integration within the regional context: on the one hand, the Balkans is treated differently from other European regions undergoing enlargement, and on the other hand, notwithstanding the great inclination that the EU has for regionalism, the Union does differentiate between certain parts of the Balkans in terms of integration.

Now the reverse side of the coin comes: how does the Balkans regard the European Union? The answer can be kept simple, with euroscepticism. The regional approach from the EU does not sit well with the different dates of accession and with the various requests in order to receive official candidate status.

Let us see: in 2004, Slovenia joins the EU. Croatia became a member on July 1, 2013. Serbia received full candidate status on March 1, 2012. The accession negotiations with Montenegro started on 29 June 2012.

Albania is in a more delicate predicament: in October 2012 the European Commission evaluated the progress of Albania to comply with several key priorities, being conditional to achieve official candidate status and start accession negotiations. Out of twelve, four key priorities were found to be met, while two were well in progress and the remaining six were in moderate progress. The report concluded that if Albania manages to hold a fair and democratic parliamentary election in March 2013, and implements the remaining changes also to comply with the eight key priorities still not fully met, then the Council of the European Union would recommend to grant Albania official candidate status¹.

¹ European Commission, "Key findings of the 2012 Progress Report on Albania", retrieved 11 October 2014

Macedonia has been a candidate for accession to the EU since 2005 since it submitted its membership application in 2004, thirteen years after its independence from former Yugoslavia. As of 2012, it is one of five remaining candidate countries, together with Iceland, Montenegro, Serbia and Turkey, after the latest round of enlargement that brought membership to Bulgaria and Romania. Among current obstacles to full membership is the on-going dispute with Greece over the country's name, which is also the reason why it is officially addressed by the European Union with the provisional appellation "Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia", rather than its constitutional name, "Republic of Macedonia". Another problem is the strained relations between Macedonia and Bulgaria due to the ethnic groups and their allegiance to either country (the Macedonian Question).

To keep true to its own descriptors, the Western Balkan region is not heterogeneous in terms of their views of Europe: *Gallup Balkan Monitor*¹ describes a complex image that incorporates a wide range of perceptions pertaining to the European Union. The opinions recorded in poles vary from the euphoria of the EU (in Kosovo and Albania) to a beginning of an alienation feeling (in Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina).

These situations render difficulties the creation of a comprehensive policy². Because the Balkans have presented a series of challenges (geostrategic, political and economic, and socio-cultural), the EU has struggled to formulate and to implement a range of policies to accommodate all. But when we deal with different territories (and types of territories) it has proven to be quite difficult to integrate all these countries as a region.

The Western Balkan countries have been but a spectator to the accession of countries in South Eastern Europe. The insistence of the Union in terms of regional cooperation mostly related to the region ethnical issues, which would be indications that their accession prospects are dark. Why were they just treated differently and why were they not offered an early entry to the EU as a way to accelerate the reform and to introduce EU

¹ *Gallup Balkan Monitor*, GBM in short

² *Gallup Balkan Monitor, Insights and Perceptions: Voices of the Balkans*, "Perceptions of the EU in the Western Balkans", 2009, http://www.balkan-monitor.eu/files/Gallup_Balkan_Monitor-Focus_On_EU_Perceptions.pdf, viewed on 2.05.2015

membership as a mechanism for conflict resolution? But how far do the Europeans want to draw the borders of Europe? Where and when they want to stop expansion?¹ Is it possible that the insistence on regional cooperation combined with the current European crisis and the general recession is a means to accelerate the transition to the EU or is it just a way to build a form of regional integration, which will act as a substitute for enlargement (with preferential sectoral agreements with the EU)?²

There is no simple answer, nor easy solutions as these questions have myriad ramifications. The EU advocates unity in diversity, but how diverse can diversity be in order to concoct some unity? The European future of the Western Balkans is subject to a larger European debate referring to merits seen through a European lens. Serbia's European future was not hampered by the inability to satisfy the technical aspects of the *acquis*, but because of Serbia's refusal to cooperate with the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY), concerning the arrest of indicted war criminals, a return to the violent collapse of Yugoslavia that has come to characterize the Balkans³.

2. Differentiated integration as observed in EU partnerships with third countries - candidates and potential candidates

It is established already that differentiated integration deviates from the principle of equal involvement of all Member States; the issue remains with the drivers of such differentiated integration. Scholars circulate widely terms like *broadening*, *widening* and *deepening*. The effects of differentiation are controversial: initially believed detrimental to the project of European integration because it created sub-groups and divisions, recent studies have shown how differentiated arrangements have had a centripetal effect⁴.

¹ M. Brie, I. Polgar, F. Chirodea, *Cultural Identity, Diversity and European Integration. Introductory Study*, pp. 12-15

² I. Polgar, "Hungarian historiography between the concept of «Europe without borders» and autonomy of the «Szeklers Land»", pp. 46-48

³ K. Dyson, A. Sepos (eds), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, pp. 57-81

⁴ F. Matarrelli, *The Macro-regional Concept as a New Model of Differentiated Integration*, <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?func=downloadFile&recordOid=2542949&fileOid=2682440>, retrieved on 2.06.2015

If we look at the governance of the European continent as a whole it becomes obvious that the EU itself is a form of differentiated integration. The 'core' Europe attracts outsiders and defines different modes of integration based on own interests / affairs (from trade, through broader cooperation, to more intense association agreements including the European Economic Area)¹.

Tekin, in her study *Differentiated Integration at Work*, sums up various forms of differentiated integration that are pre-defined by the treaties as well as the policies relating to territorial enlargement.

Graph 1: Europe – United in Diversity

Source: *Differentiated Integration at Work*²

This graph excludes broader forms of variable geometries (such as the European Economic Area, the Customs Union, etc.) and displays the state of differentiated integration reality as of September 2011.

Europe maintains an overlapping system of treaties and policies for the governance of areas as security and defense (the North Atlantic Treaty Organization [NATO] and the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe [OSCE]), human rights (Council of Europe) and reconstruction and development (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development [EBRD], the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund [IMF] and the World Trade Organization [WTO]). Some treaties were created (like the EBRD) and transformed (like NATO, OSCE and the Council of Europe) in response to

¹ G. Marks, F. W. Scharpf, Ph. C. Schmitter, W. Streeck, *Governance in the European Union*, p. 132

² F. Tekin, *Differentiated Integration at Work*, p. 20

developments after the end of the Cold War. Some transcend Europe, i.e. the IMF, the World Bank and the WTO. Dyson and Sepos demonstrate that on this wider level of analysis, Europe comprises a complex, evolving network of differentiated integration that includes but extends beyond the EU: "The contested nature of Europe's borders comes to the fore, especially in sensitive relations to Russia, Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia and Turkey to the East. This contest goes beyond the question of where the EU borders should lie to questions about which borders should take priority and how these borders should be managed"¹.

The incoherent position of the EU towards Russia and the consequent vulnerability remain a challenge in the EU policies. The EU Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR) appears to be determined and somehow easier and smoother to implement. The Danube is the world's most international river and many of the countries of its basin are non-EU members. Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Moldova and Ukraine are listed but open slots remained for other possible partners in the region. We have to bear in mind that the signatory countries are either candidate countries for EU membership or potential candidates, so the strategy is relevant to a possible enlargement in the Balkans. The Strategy states that targets will apply only to Member States while non Member States would be still encouraged to achieve them².

The Energy Community is another important partnership created in view of a better integration. It brings together the European Union, the countries of the Western Balkans and some of the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) countries³. The intention is not singular: to create the common energy market in the region and at the same time to prepare the candidate and potential candidate countries for their accession to the EU⁴.

Launched in 2009, the Eastern Partnership is a joint initiative between the EU, Member States and the Eastern European partner

¹ K. Dyson, A. Sepos (eds), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, p. 17

² CEC Commission of the European Communities, 2010a. Communication concerning the European Union Strategy for Danube Region, p. 4

³ Current membership includes the European Union, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia Kosovo, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro and Ukraine. Georgia is a candidate country.

⁴ A. Zowski, "Flexibility and Homogeneity: two uneasy bedfellows".

countries. It enables partner countries interested in moving towards the EU and increasing political, economic and cultural links. It is underpinned by a shared commitment to international law and fundamental values – democracy, the rule of law and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms – and to the market economy, sustainable development and good governance. Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine signed the Association Agreements, including on Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Areas. These were ratified by the respective countries' parliaments and the European Parliament. The Partnership promotes democracy and good governance, strengthens energy security, promotes sectoral reforms and environment protection, encourages people-to-people contacts, supports economic and social development, provides additional funding for projects to reduce social inequality and increase stability¹.

The Eastern Partnership Summit in Riga held on 21-22 May 2015 was eagerly awaited for. Hopes and plans run high. Documents were reviewed by Brussels and then submitted for input to the six Eastern Partnership countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine.

An exclusive interview, given to MOLDPRES State News Agency by the Deputy Prime-Minister, Minister of Foreign Affairs and European Integration Natalia Gherman, states clearly the official position of Moldova:

“If differentiated approach is ensured, the next step should be shaping of the future relation between Moldova and the EU. We shall see how that will be covered in the documents of the Riga Summit. We firmly declare and reiterate the message that Moldova, as a European state through history, heritage, civilisation and values, deserves to be a full-fledged EU member in the foreseeable future. We recognise, at the same time, that this requires a number of conditions that each aspiring state must implement before applying for membership”².

A month before the Riga Summit, Europe, the candidate countries and all interested parties held a collective breath until they found out who's who.

¹ http://eeas.europa.eu/eastern/index_en.htm

² <http://www.moldpres.md/en/news/2015/04/08/15002326>

Conclusions

There is a current opinion, which suggests that there were too many EU policies towards “problem states” since the mid-1990s¹ and that such states have been too much tried by too many initiatives. Generally speaking, these initiatives aim at the reconstruction, the states development and the institutional consolidation, and finally at EU accession.

While some countries have made progress within the process of EU accession following a route set through European Agreements, the commencement of negotiations and finally the accession. The countries from the Western Balkans and former USSR are required to negotiate and sign a series of “pre-contracts” before anyone could contemplate applying for full membership. Some see this as “obstructionist tactics”, others see it as “a more permanent obstacle” to EU accession. However, what it does is to increase the spatial concept of differentiated integration and create “a parallel process of temporal differentiated integration”².

Since the 1990s these regions seem to become more narrow and compact as ever. The Balkans have remained a region synonymous with war, many have not been able to see the past ethnic crises in Kosovo and Serbia, and the involvement of other countries and organizations to restore peace has been on-going since then. By the end of the Kosovo crisis, the overall Balkan region, also known as South-Eastern Europe, acquires a new political identity in the eyes of Europe: “Western Balkans”. Just the same, Russia and the ensuing geopolitics are determiners in the inconsistent position of the EU with regards to candidate countries that have resulted from the breakup of the USSR.

In reality, these regions have become “problem states” with great need for differentiated integration requirements.

How can one advance if there are countries that are able and do wish to go ahead when there are countries that have no wish to do so or are unable to move forward? The flexibility is the functioning principle that would allow the EU to come up with methods of differentiated integration³,

¹ J. Rupnik, “The Balkans as a European Question”, pp. 17-30; A. Mungiu-Pippidi, “A house of cards? Building the rule of law in the Balkans”, pp. 154-160

² S. Economides, “The Politics of Differentiated Integration: the case of the Balkans”, pp. 28-31

³ i.e. Positive or negative integration

as opposed to the institutional rigidity that would entail the exclusive enforcement of EU system in all cases and for all countries¹.

As we have already mentioned, there is no simple answer, nor easy solutions as these questions have myriad ramifications. Right, unity in diversity, but again, how diverse can diversity be in order to concoct some unity? History will tell if such a complex knots of ethnicities and populations with different beliefs and under different conditions will be able to be funnelled through the integration motors of the European Union.

Bibliography:

1. BRIE, Mircea; POLGAR, Istvan; CHIRODEA, Florentina, *Cultural Identity, Diversity and European Integration. Introductory Study*, in Mircea Brie, Istvan Polgar, Florentina Chirodea, *European Union. Identity, Diversity and Integration*, Oradea: Editura Universitatii din Oradea 2012.
2. CREȚOIU, Gheorghe; CORNESCU, Viorel; BUCUR, Ion, *Economie*, București: All Beck, 2003.
3. DYSON, Kenneth; SEPOS, Angelos (eds), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010.
4. ECONOMIDES, Spyros, "The Balkan Agenda: Security and Regionalism in the New Europe", in *London Defence Studies 10*, Brassey's Centre for Defence Studies, 1992, p. 142-156.
5. ECONOMIDES, Spyros, "The Politics of Differentiated Integration: the case of the Balkans", in *Greece Paper No 18*, Hellenic Observatory Papers on Greece and Southeast Europe, September 2008.
6. GLENNY, Misha, *The Fall of Yugoslavia: The Third Balkan War*, 2nd edition, London: Penguin, 1993.
7. GOETZ, Klaus H., "The Temporal Dimension", in: Kenneth Dyson, Angelos Sepos (eds.), *Which Europe? The Politics of Differentiated Integration*, Basingstoke: Macmillan Palgrave, 2010, pp. 67-81.
8. GOSSIAUX, Jean-Francois, *Pouvoirs ethniques dans les Balkans*, Paris: Presses Universitaires de France, 2002.
9. ILIESCU, Ion, *Integrare și globalizare. Viziunea românească*, București: Presa Națională Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003.

¹ C. Closa Montero, *Differentiated Integration and Flexibility in the EU under the Lisbon Treaty: Challenges for the Trio Presidency*

10. KAPLAN, Robert D., *Balkan Ghosts: A Journey through History*, New York: Picador, 2005.
11. LEUFFEN, Dirk; RITTBERGER, Berthold; SCHIMMELFENNIG, Frank, *Differentiated Integration, Explaining Variation in the European Union*, London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013.
12. MARKS, Gary; SCHARPF, Fritz W.; SCHMITTER, Philippe C.; STREECK, Wolfgang, *Governance in the European Union*, London: Thousand Oaks, SAGE Publications, 1996.
13. MUNGIU-PIPPIDI, Alina, "A house of cards? Building the rule of law in the Balkans", in *The Western Balkans and the EU: 'the hour of Europe', Chaillot Paper*, No. 126, June 2011, pp. 145-160.
14. POLGAR, István, "Hungarian historiography between the concept of «Europe without borders» and autonomy of the «Szeklers Land»" in Gábor Kozma (ed.), *New results of cross-border co-operation*, Debrecen, 2011, pp. 41-50.
15. RUPNIK, Jacques, "The Balkans as a European Question", in *The Western Balkans and the EU: 'the hour of Europe', Chaillot Paper*, No. 126, June 2011, pp. 17-30.
16. TEKIN, Funda, *Differentiated Integration at Work*, Studies on the European Union Series, vol. 6, ed. W. Wessels, 2012.
17. TODOROVA, Maria, *Imagining the Balkans*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.
18. WOODWARD, Susan, *Balkan Tragedy: Chaos and Dissolution after the Cold War*, Washington: The Brookings Institution, 1995.
19. Zowski, Adam, "Flexibility and Homogeneity: two uneasy bedfellows", in Steven Blockmans (ed.), *Differentiated integration in the EU. From the inside looking out*, Centre for European Policy Studies, 2014.

Online resources

20. CEC Commission of the European Communities, 2010a. *Communication concerning the European Union Strategy for Danube Region*. COM(2010) 715, Brussels.
21. CLOSA MONTERO, Carlos, *Differentiated Integration and Flexibility in the EU under the Lisbon Treaty: Challenges for the Trio Presidency*, in *Think Global – Act European, The Contribution of 14 European Think Tanks to the Spanish, Belgian and Hungarian Trio Presidency of the*

European Union, directed by Elvire Fabry, Gaëtane Ricard-Nihoulraport, 2010, published on the official website *Notre Europe*, <http://www.notre-europe.eu/en/axes/visions-of-europe/works/publication/think-global-act-european-ii/>, viewed on 2.05.2015.

22. *Contribution de Michel Barnier et António Vitorino à la Convention européenne sur „La méthode communautaire” (3 septembre 2002)*, <http://www.cvce.eu/collections/unit-content/-/unit/d5906df5-4f83-4603-85f7-0cab24b9fe1/356d1e8d-3396-4cf0-9031-e6939faf75f1/Resources#6605c830-7a2d-451e-a4de-3f27d49d19e8>, last viewed on 25.05.2015.
23. *Differentiated Integration in An Enlarged Union*, published in March 27, 2002, revised in January 29, 2010 available at: <http://www.euractiv.com/future-eu/differentiated-integration-enlarged-union/article-117073>, viewed on 29.05.2015.
24. European Commission, “Key findings of the 2012 Progress Report on Albania”, retrieved 11 October 2014.
25. *Gallup Balkan Monitor, Insights and Perceptions: Voices of the Balkans*, “Perceptions of the EU în the Western Balkans”, 2009, http://www.balkan-monitor.eu/files/Gallup_Balkan_Monitor-Focus_On_EU_Perceptions.pdf, viewed on 2.05.2015.
26. *Gallup Balkan Monitor, Insights and Perceptions: Voices of the Balkans*, “The Gallup Balkan Monitor: the Western Balkans’ most wide-ranging survey ever”, 2010, <http://www.balkan-monitor.eu>, viewed on 25.05.2015.
27. http://ec.europa.eu/enlargement/key_documents/index_en.htm
28. http://eeas.europa.eu/eastern/index_en.htm
29. <http://www.eup.ethz.ch/research/diffintegration>
30. <http://www.moldpres.md/en/news/2015/04/08/15002326>
31. Matarrelli, Federico, *The Macro-regional Concept as a New Model of Differentiated Integration*, <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?func=downloadFile&recordId=2542949&fileId=2682440>, retrieved on 2.06.2015.
32. *Official website of the European Commision*, „Extindere, Procesul de Stabilizare si Asociere”, http://ec.europa.eu/enlargement/pdf/enlargement_process/accession

- _process/how_does_a_country_join_the_eu/sap/sap_composite_paper_annex1_en.pdf, viewed on 29.05.2015.
33. *Report from the Commission, The Stabilisation and Association process for South East Europe, Second Annual Report – Annex 1*, Brussels, 26.3.2003, http://ec.europa.eu/enlargement/pdf/enlargement_process/accession_process/how_does_a_country_join_the_eu/sap/85349_en.pdf, viewed on 12.09.2013.
34. Tekin, Funda, *Differentiated Integration at Work*, vol. 6, The “Studies on the European Union” Series, ed. Wolfgang Wessels, 2012.
35. *Thessaloniki Agenda*, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32004R0533:RO:HTML>, viewed on 29.05.2015.

Copyright©Mircea BRIE
Copyright©Daniela BLAGA

INTERCULTURALITATE / INTERCULTURALITY

Crearea unui spațiu intercultural autentic – o oportunitate pentru Republica Moldova

Conf. univ. dr. Tamara CRISTEI

tcristei2009@gmail.com

Universitatea Academiei de Științe din Moldova, Moldova

Abstract: The article analyzes the concept of intercultural area by providing advantages to Moldova and its citizens. By its diversity, European integration has faced experiences of interculturalism, pluriculturalism, multiculturalism in a united Europe. It is made use of the comparative method when observing the cultural space of the European Union and Moldova.

Key-words: diversity, European integration, interculturalism, Moldova, multiculturalism, unity, values.

O problemă de necesitate stringentă este astăzi păstrarea funcțională în spațiul societății moderne a diversității formelor de existență umană: istorică, spirituală, economică, politică, culturală etc., care a fost, este și va fi o condiție sine qua non a viabilității civilizației omenеști. Această condiție vitală de prim rang trebuie, în opinia noastră, să se întemeieze pe acceptarea ideii generale că viața, trecând peste toate legitățile biologice și genealogice, este cel mai uluitor și cel mai important miracol existențial. Este știut că viața a apărut în Galactică deja de aproape 4 mlrd. de ani, iar oamenii viețuiesc pe pământ doar circa 200 mii de ani, însă specimenul nostru a reușit să producă un dezastru de fond pe cea mai frumoasă planetă din sistemul solar, distrugând, aproape definitiv, balanța ecologică, iar fără de ea, afirmă savanții din diverse domenii, perpetuarea vieții este imposibilă. În special, în cercetările din ultimele decenii, s-a demonstrat pericolul uriaș ce s-a conturat din cauza ignorării de către oameni a legii coexistenței armonioase a tuturor fenomenelor, vietăților și lucrurilor intrate în macrosistemul existenței terestre. Din acest macrosistem fac parte și civilizațiile, și culturile diverse create de popoarele Terrei, condiție și un rost major al dăinuirii acestora în timp prin coexistența lor armonioasă și grație metalimbajelor care asigură comunicarea valorilor ce le conțin.

Așadar, culturile popoarelor care întrunesc cele mai semnificative date ale experienței particulare, ale spiritualității, credințelor, moralei, artelor, științelor etc. – toate cuprinse în cunoscuta metaforă a scriitorului

filosof L. Blaga: „corola de minuni a lumii” – constituie un tip de „fundament” existențial al umanității și, în același timp, elemente vitale ale civilizației contemporane, păstrarea și cunoașterea cărora asigură evident autenticitatea și viabilitatea valorică a continuității noastre în timp. În acest sens, ne permitem să invocăm și concluzia eului liric din clasică artă poetică blagiană: „Eu nu strivesc corola de minuni a lumii / și nu ucid / cu mintea tainele, ce le-ntâlnesc / în calea mea, / ... eu, cu lumina mea, sporesc a lumii taină, / ... căci eu iubesc / și flori, și ochi, și buze, și morminte”. Afirmăția merită să și-o asume astăzi fiecare dintre noi în calitate de „măsurariu” atitudinal a ceea ce reprezintă valorile culturale a tuturor popoarelor cu care conviețuim pe glob și, mai ales, cu care ne este dat să contactăm nemijlocit în existența noastră cotidiană. Prin „lumina” fiecăruia, considerată capacitate a cunoașterii, și prin înțelegerea și aprecierea valorilor spirituale exprimate simbolic prin: „flori”, „ochi”, „buze” și „morminte”, ne putem determina unicul comportament civilizată față de orice valori culturale create de viețuitorii Terrei, cel de păstrător-recreator: *eu nu strivesc, nu ucid, ci eu sporesc*, comportament ce se manifestă la cota maximă de conștientizare și înțelegere umană – **iubirea** a tot din ce este constituit și ce te înconjoară ca parte integrantă din viață. Că viziunea mitologică a lui Blaga are o carcasă științific a fost demonstrat de către exegeza blagiană, iar propunerile savanților antropologi, sociologi, filosofi, culturologi, precum și din domeniile pragmatice, converg în ideea justă a restabilirii cu adevărat a paradigmei existențiale ce a asigurat persistența umanității în timp, ea fiind articulată pe conceptele de teaurizare și continuitate a valorilor spirituale și culturale.

În această ordine de idei, este necesar să punctăm câteva considerații de bază și, în primul rând, să precizăm ce este un tezaur cultural creat de un popor, o națiune într-o perioadă îndelungată de timp? Pentru a răspunde la această întrebare, e necesar să pornim de la invocarea unei astfel de definiții a culturii, care să fundamenteze soluționarea problemei de primă importanță a societății noastre și care este, în opinia noastră, **crearea unui autentic spațiu intercultural ce va asigura satisfacția existențială a tuturor cetățenilor din Republica Moldova și va proiecta o cale de succes spre prosperarea statului modern de astăzi**. Una dintre definițiile care deține consensul cel mai cuprinzător în antropologia modernă ne orientează la ansamblul de abilități, noțiuni și forme de comportament pe care indivizii

îl dobândesc ca membri ai unei societăți anume. Așadar, cetățenii trebuie să aibă conștiința certă că sunt membrii societății contemporane a țării noastre și de aici sentimentul responsabilității față de ea, materializat în intenția și în insistența de a dobândi abilitatea de a cunoaște și a aprecia *iubind* (în sens uman și axiologic) și având un comportament securizant față de zestrea culturală creată în timp în spațiul istoric al țării. Este evident că accentul cade pe necesitatea formării și dobândirii de către cetățeni a unei astfel de conștiințe și a unui astfel de comportament, ce ar crea mai întâi premise, iar apoi ar consolida societatea „divizată” pe diverse criterii inadecvate orizontului de așteptare al timpului modern. În acest sens, răsună descurajant pentru comunitatea socială de azi lamentațiile diriguitorilor politici despre obstacolele de netrecut în calea progresului țării din cauza „societății împărțite”. Volens-nolens, se impune întrebarea: care sunt cauzele acestui regretabil fenomen? Cunoașterea și înlăturarea lor ar pregăti evident pista pentru evoluția progresivă a societății, concomitent intenționându-se pe bune consolidarea ei. Procesul este unul complex, dar necesar și realizabil prin diverse politici și programe de stat pentru a conferi, prin cultură, integritatea necesară societății noastre.

Cercetătorul C. Geertz consideră cultura drept o matrice de sensuri transmise istoric, întrupate în simboluri, drept un sistem de concepții moștenite, exprimate în diverse formule simbolice, prin intermediul cărora oamenii își comunică, își transmit și-și dezvoltă în permanență cunoștințele și atitudinile despre viață¹. Deci valorile culturale și valorile vieții în general formează un liant indestructibil și, în numele lor, un stat trebuie să-și ierarhizeze oportunitățile. Este necesar însă de reținut, în acest context al judecăților, că individualitățile umane sunt determinate atât de gradul și tipul de cultură, ceea ce conturează similaritate și fond comun, dar și de un anume mod în care se produce diferența între grupuri de indivizi, cultura fiind, în felul acesta, generatoare de o consistentă diferență. Susținem ideea că, în acest sens, conceptul de cultură implică, în fapt, coexistența unei pluralități de culturi și el trebuie așadar înțeles prin prisma relativismului cultural, care afirmă principiul egalității diferitelor culturi în termeni de valoare intrinsecă și descurajează orice tentativă de a proclama o cultură anume ca fiind superioară sau inferioară altora. Valorile, normele,

¹ C. Geertz, *The Interpretation of Cultures*, p. 89

simbolurile unei culturi se promovează și se evaluează după funcționalitatea lor firească și viabilă și nu după criteriile altei culturi sau după cantitatea indivizilor care o reprezintă.

Coexistența mai multor culturi în același spațiu a dat naștere unui set de concepte înrudite: *multicultural*, *pluricultural*, *intercultural*, *unicultural*, precum și *multiculturalism*, *interculturalitate* ș.a. În pofida unei înțelegeri superficiale care ar promova un sens sinonimic al termenilor, binomul de concepte **multicultural / intercultural** prezintă unele diferențe esențiale. Astfel, „multicultural” este un termen descriptiv, referitor la o stare de fapt, la conviețuirea mai multor grupuri în aceeași societate, ceea ce se atestă și în Republica Moldova. Conceptul a tins însă și să evidențieze diferența sau chiar separarea dintre culturi și grupuri, percepute ca fiind diferite, acesta fiind folosit, cu precădere, în societăți post-coloniale (Marea Britanie, Țările de Jos), unde, deseori, este vorba de conviețuirea paralelă a grupurilor etnice, fără o adevărată relaționare unele față de celelalte¹. Trebuie să menționăm însă că acest concept a evoluat, modernizându-și sensul în funcție de realitățile culturale și demografice care s-au constituit în diverse țări europene ca urmare a puternicului flux migraționist.

Așadar, prezența diversității de culturi conduce la acceptarea ideii de coexistență a mai multor culturi și la adoptarea **multiculturalismului** ca politică de gestionare a acestei diversități. Termenul este, de fapt, un echivalent al pluralismului cultural, politic, religios etc., mizându-se pe recunoașterea existenței mai multor grupuri etnice și de aici o derivată a politicii naționale. Specialiștii au constatat însă că multiculturalismul a limitat acțiunile la aspectul politic al recunoașterii coexistenței mai multor grupuri etnice în cadrul aceleiași entități statale și la acceptarea superficială a modului de interacționare dintre aceste grupuri².

Oricum, noi considerăm că studierea și achiziționarea unor idei și practici ale manifestării multiculturalismului ca gestionare a diversității este pentru țara noastră importantă în condițiile aplicării de durată a politicii imperiale de deznaționalizare a poporului basarabean prin programe de schimbare artificială, din interes politic, a spectrului demografic din ținut,

¹ C. Giordano, *De la criza reprezentărilor la triumful prefixurilor. Un comentariu la propunerile lui Adrian Severin și Gabriel Andreescu*, p. 38

² Cf. C. Taylor, *Multiculturalism and “The Politics of Recognition”*

prin „spălarea” conștiinței de sine, ca valoare individuală, și a conștiinței naționale, ca valoare spirituală a unei comunități umane importante pentru palmaresul popoarelor europene, prin denigrarea originii spirituale a tuturor românilor basarabeni și a culturii lor istorice, prin promovarea unui kich cultural moldovenesc, ce a anulat autenticitatea tradițiilor folclorice tezaurizate în acest spațiu, toate acestea având obiectivul politic să adeverească, totodată, „deosebirile” flagrante dintre folclorul moldovenesc din Basarabia și cel de peste Prut și să reliefeze exagerat „împrumuturile generoase” de la „marile” culturi împrejmuitoare, în special de factură slavă. Acest fapt urma să infiltreze și să întemeieze ideea creării unui alt popor în spațiul Basarabiei ocupate de Imperiul rus, „noul” popor moldovenesc, care n-are nici o comunitate cu poporul român de aceeași origine, și „noii culturi sovietice moldovenești”, ceea ce și s-a obținut, în definitiv, prin aplicarea alfabetului chirilic, a limbii ruse ca unica limbă oficială și de cult și în special prin aplicarea întregului sistem de educație sovietică politizată și întemeiată pe concepția imperială falsă a împărțirii popoarelor și culturilor. Acest fenomen este una dintre cauzele producerii divizării aproape impermeabile a societății din statul nostru, care a acceptat menținerea numeroaselor elemente din sistemului sovietic în diverse domenii, amânându-se nejustificat (mai mult din incompetența, nedorința și teama liderilor politici) schimbările de fond necesare pentru bunăstarea populației. De aceea insistăm în ideea conceptualizării și implementării unor politici culturale și educaționale în scopul aplanării și readucerii la normalitate a conviețuirii sociale și culturale a tuturor cetățenilor din țară și renunțarea la activități eterogene cosmetice sau „de paradă”, care n-au un impact profund formativ asupra conștiinței și a comportamentului populației / societății, ci sunt chiar condamnabile pentru că, în fapt, mențin artificial în surdină neînțelegerile și confruntările interetnice.

În schimb, conceptul de „intercultural” pune accentul pe interacțiunea dintre grupurile percepute ca distincte din societate, referindu-se, mai curând, la un dinamic proces de schimburi, de dialog, de negociere între grupuri, precum și de identificare a unui limbaj și a unui spațiu comun în care să se desfășoare comunicarea. Caracterul intercultural al unei acțiuni este adevărat de faptul că se pune accent pe relația reciprocă dintre elementele constitutive ale schimburilor, ceea ce prilejuiește asigurarea coexistenței și evoluției firești a acestora. Conștiința profundă a

deținerii unei anumite culturi implică, cel puțin indirect, și raportarea la o altă cultură față de care individul se delimitează, ceea ce fundamentează o conștientizare interculturală a propriei valori culturale și a valorilor altor culturi, ce solicită necondiționat aprecierea, păstrarea și îmbogățirea lor. Or, faptul că o anumită cultură este percepută ca fiind diferită în raport cu alta nu presupune promovarea superiorității unei culturi față de alta, ci doar relevă beneficiul coexistenței și interacțiunii lor, păstrându-și, totodată specificul național. În acest sens, acceptăm ideea că „interculturalitatea” se referă la spațiul dintre două sau mai multe culturi, care este prin excelență un spațiu dinamic, în permanență supus proceselor de negociere existențială dintre două grupuri percepute ca aparținând unor culturi diferite. Merită reținut sensul concret mai relevant pe care-l comportă prefixul „inter” în ceea ce privește termenul, ceea ce înlesnește înțelegerea comportamentală pe care o conține conceptul de *interculturalitate* și care presupune inerent activizarea proceselor indicate de cercetătorul M. Rey: interacțiune echitabilă, reciprocitate sinceră, schimburi benefice de valori culturale, efort în anularea barierelor în acest sens și instaurarea unei solidarități umane ce ar consolida întreaga societate¹. Toate acestea solicită angajarea dialectică a generațiilor beneficiare și un dinamism evolutiv care să nu distrugă valorile create, ci să le repună în valoare din perspectiva orizontului de așteptare al timpului contemporan, ceea ce înseamnă că valorile culturale se reconstruiesc în permanență, dar nu pe calea născocirii diverselor kitsch-uri, ci pe calea îmbogățirii cu sensuri noi, capabile să păstreze intactă autenticitatea valorică. Astfel ia naștere, în acest spațiu, o comunicare interculturală beneficiară, care presupune un „dialog între subiectivități, o negociere identitară, o interacțiune între indivizi și grupuri percepute ca diferite din punct de vedere cultural”². Dacă luăm în calcul specificul realității din Republica Moldova, atunci realizăm că în spațiul mental al populației ei, au drept de funcționalitate atât conceptul de multiculturalitate, care, la nivel descriptiv, favorizează înțelegerea și acceptarea realității culturale din țară, și cel de interculturalitate, care, la nivel normativ și aplicativ, condiționează mai evident comportamentul

¹ Cf. M. Rey, *De la o logică „mono” la logica de tip „inter”*. Piste pentru o educație interculturală și solidară

² M. Abdallah-Pretceille, *L'education interculturelle*, p. 49

acțional al cetățenilor statului. Miza cea mare cade, fără îndoială, pe activitățile de interculturalitate. Conștientizarea sensurilor ambelor concepte și aplicarea comportamentului adecvat acțiunii interculturale ar asigura (în context cu politicile economice și sociale promovate de guvern) mai întâi deconstrucția conceptelor rigide și nocive buneii înțelegeri între diverse etnii, moștenite de la statul sovietic (nație superioară - nație inferioară / cultură mare - cultură mică ș.a.), apoi întemeierea și construirea unei adevărate mentalități democratice ale timpului modern contemporan.

Formarea unei mentalități adecvate spiritului modern al timpului, un imperativ al politicilor din Republica Moldova. Considerațiile expuse adevăresc necesitatea stringentă a implementării unei politici educative care, la nivel ideatic și pragmatic, va demonstra evident, prin acceptare benevolentă, faptul că statul are în grijă păstrarea și promovarea valorilor culturale atât a poporului originar ontologic, cât și a etniilor conlocuitoare, care, împreună, își construiesc atât prezentul, cât și viitorul. Concomitent, este necesar de deblocat ideile preconcepute, ce țin de șovinism, xenofobie, promovate cu ambiții politice de handicap, de exclus toleranța, condamabilă uman, a denigrării poporului român în general, ca entitate culturală, și a identității spirituale a poporului român, care sunt băștinașii istorici de drept în stat, ceea ce intimidează, atacă integritatea persoanei, și provoacă îngrijorarea celorlalte etnii conlocuitoare pentru confortul decent al vieții, focare de suspiciune, neîncredere, disconfort psihologic și confruntări distructive, în ambele cazuri, și condiție de a menține un conflict artificial permanent, care, în definitiv, împiedică realizarea politicilor de prosperare a societății noastre. Odată declarate și implementate clar, aceste oportunități (și nu neadevăruri declarate impertinent și orientate să mușamalizeze pe moment problemele, dar, de facto, le aprofundează, punând societatea în pericol), societatea s-ar regenera, ar accepta un numitor comun constructiv, de la care pornind, ș-ar instaura stabilitatea și efortul dorit de a crea bunuri spirituale și materiale pentru țară în baza păstrării tezaurului cultural, care pentru Republica Moldova reprezintă „valuta” națională, datorită căreia tot mai multe state ne-ar accepta în circuitul mondial de valori, condiție vitală a statului nostru în lipsa unui număr convingător de valori economice și în contextul globalizării, problemă atât de discutată astăzi. Semnificative, în acest plan, sunt sfaturile lui Mihai Eminescu, nu numai un poet de valoare incontestabilă, dar și o personalitate

culturală de primă mărime în palmaresul culturii universale, care, grație gândirii sale ancestrale, ne-a edictat cu drept de testament: „Noi trebuie să fim o țară de cultură în această parte înăsprită a lumii”, avându-se în vedere salvarea și perpetuarea neamului și statului în timp în condițiile urmării interesul geopolitic al așa-ziselor „mari puteri” ale lumii, care se adeverește evident și astăzi.

Așadar, posedarea unui tezaur cultural este, în sens larg, certificarea prezenței condiționate și justificate a poporului nostru în procesul devenirii sale istorice și devenirii istorice a umanității pe Terra, certificarea contribuției valorice a acestuia la procesul constituirii civilizației umanității, la consolidarea idealului de viață umană întru păstrarea și prosperarea în general a vieții pe planeta noastră, este, în definitiv, un metalimbaj de valoare majoră ce învață noile generații și asigură comunicarea și transmiterea cunoștințelor valorice acumulate de omenire. De aici și cea de a doua accepție comprehensivă a acestei noțiuni, cea în sens restrâns, tezaurul cultural însumând o totalitate de bunuri spirituale și materiale create de un popor pe parcursul perioadei sale istorice civilizatorii, care-i determină existența și identitatea spirituală și națională și care se transmite prin generații ca valori emblematice intrinseci ale acestuia, ce sunt și parte integrantă a valorilor simbolice generale ale umanității. Este evident, în această ordine de idei, dreptul inviolabil la existență a fiecărei culturi civilizatorii și datoria omenirii de a păstra și îmbogăți acest tezaur, condiție *sine ira* a constituirii și viabilității unui stat modern.

De aceea Uniunea Europeană, ca una din megazonele geopolitice create benevolent de către statele continentului, pentru a facilita colaborarea dintre națiuni și popoare în scopul realizării idealurilor general umane și a menținerii păcii și a vieții pe glob, promovează, în cadrul activității sale, concepția construirii unui spațiu european în baza coexistenței civilizatoare a diversității culturale și a unei comunicări interculturale în diverse forme și formule. Cercetătorii au desemnat că în spațiul european s-au afirmat mai multe modele de integrare a diverselor grupuri etnice și culturale, dominante fiind trei: a) *asimilarea*, model promovat de Consiliul Europei în deceniile șapte-opt, ca urmare a obiectivului de a soluționa problema de integrare a migranților; b) *multiculturalismul*, promovat cu precădere în anii '80-'90 ca proiect integraționist. Începutul mileniului trei este marcat de străduința Consiliului

Europei de a realiza cel de al treilea model, c) *interculturalismul*, ca posibilitate reală de punere în legătură inter-individuală și colectivă o mare și valoroasă diversitate culturală.

Și pe plan politic, dialogul intercultural este un rezultat așteptat al gestionării diversității culturale, fiind definit în documentele Consiliului Europei drept „un schimb deschis de păreri, respectuos și bazat pe înțelegerea reciprocă, între indivizi și grupuri care au origini și un patrimoniu etnic, cultural, religios și lingvistic diferit. El are loc la toate nivelurile – în mijlocul societăților, între societățile europene și între Europa și restul lumii”. Recunoașterea modelului intercultural ca cel mai ofertabil în scopul realizării unui spațiu existențial benefic pentru diversă și marea familie a popoarelor din spațiul european, diversificată și mai mult în rezultatul puternicei mișcări migraționiste, a determinat ca forurile europene să-i concretizeze punctual anumite obiective, printre care prioritare sunt: elaborarea instrumentelor eficiente de gestionare a diversității culturale conturate actualmente, renovarea și racordarea la condițiile reale concrete a modelelor de integrare a variilor culturi sau elemente culturale, consolidarea axiologică a unui fundament de valori comune, crearea unui spațiu existențial benefic comun, gestionarea plurilingvismului, a învățării limbilor și a educației interculturale etc.

Încadrarea Republicii Moldova, de facto și de jure, în spațiul european ne-ar facilita și ne-ar ajuta în efortul societății noastre de a se integra în baza unor valori incontestabile pentru viabilitatea ei. În primul rând, pentru că agenda Consiliul Europei conține deja de 10 ani obiectivul realizării dialogului intercultural, aplicând diverse politici educaționale, sociale și economice. Cercetarea, preluarea și aplicarea, racordată la condițiile țării noastre a unor practici europene este rentabilă și benefică pentru a nu repeta eșecurile și a proiecta calea cea mai adecvată prosperității societății noastre. Și în cadrul republicii este absolut necesară o pertinentă și activă acțiune de durată în consultarea unor factori culturali decizionali în realizarea unor proiecte aplicative eficiente, care să focalizeze, după obținerea unei schimbări de mentalitate și a unui șir de acțiuni rezultative, cu un an de demonstrare a rezultantei acestora printr-un an / decadă a dialogului intercultural în țară, o formulă a prezentării publice a modului modern de înțelegere și realizare a acestui tip de inter-relații culturale, care să demonstreze o formulă autohtonă a aplicării dezideratelor

Cărții albe a dialogului intercultural „*Să trăim împreună, în mod egal, cu demnitate*”, cu statut de ghid de referință în soluționarea problemei, în care se regăsesc noțiuni, valori, recomandări ce se referă la fenomenul de interculturalitate. Conturând elementele definitorii ale cadrului politic, *Cartea albă* indică, înainte de toate, ca bază, asigurarea drepturilor omului, libertate în alegerea modulului acceptabil de exprimare, principiile toleranței, egalității și respectul reciproc al demnității umane, interpretate din perspectiva universalității, ceea ce consolidează sentimentul de cetățean european și bucuria de a te bucura de drepturile acestuia¹. Concomitent, aceste principii universale atrag după sine, într-o împletire armonioasă, respectarea diversității identităților / diferențelor culturale și promovarea egalității între toți cetățenii unei țări anume.

Pentru cetățenii din țările foste republici sovietice socialiste, ce fac parte din spațiul geopolitic european, reîncadrarea în acest spațiu este o revenire la matricea istorică existențială, la reperele practice ale unei experiențe parcurse, păstrată încă în memoria istorică a generațiilor, și de aceea construirea unei paradigme comune de conviețuire multiplanică, din care face parte și cea culturală, se impune ca imperativ al modernității noastre. Această oportunitate este dictată și de faptul că aceste țări cuprind grupuri etnice și culturale distincte, migrate în conformitate cu o politică de deznaționalizare forțată în scopul megamajor al politicii fostei Uniuni imperiale de formare a unei „noi” entități naționale, „poporul sovietic”, din care categorie face parte și Republica Moldova.

Drept urmare, cazul țării noastre este unul foarte complicat, deoarece este un teritoriu rupt în mai multe etape, în urma războaielor ruso-turce desfășurate în această zonă, din trupul unei mari țări europene, „așezate (conform unei justificate remarci a cronicarului Gr. Ureche) în calea tuturor răutăților” geopolitice, și devenit, în afara oricăror legi, un stat artificial, mai întâi cu statut de un nou ținut / gubernie rusească, apoi de republică sovietică socialistă. Făcând hotar cu țara-mamă, România, imperiul răpitor era în pericol s-o piardă, de aceea a decis să-i confere statut de „hotar viu”, populând masiv teritoriul ei, după programe speciale, cu reprezentanți ai etniei găgăuze, cu ruși, ucraineni, în ultimele decenii libertatea deplină de migrare în țară având-o și țiganii rusificați.

¹ Cf. A. Nedelcu, *Fundamentele educației interculturale*

În consecință, nu numai că s-a modificat substanțial raportul demografic, ci, ținta fiind cu bătaie lungă, majoritatea locuitorilor de astăzi au moștenit falsul „mit” al formării unei mari și puternice societăți sovietice uniforme, actanții căreia trebuiau să aibă, de asemenea, o identitate uniformă: omul sovietic, absolut deosebit de cetățenii statelor de alt tip sociopolitic, care, neapărat, erau trecuți în categoria dușmanilor de clasă împotriva cărora trebuia „de luptat cu îndârjire”. De aici derivă și concepția formării unei false culturi sovietice determinante pentru toate așa-numitele republici-surori și promovate prin intermediul unei singure limbi ale „națiunii velico-ruse”, ce își însușise, în calitate de hegemon, rolul fratelui mai mare, căruia îi aparținea partea leului în toate domeniile de afirmare prioritară. Pentru a implementa această nocivă și distrugătoare politică culturală, a fost promovată o specială programă de educație la toate nivelurile, menită să cultive ideea superiorității așa-numitei culturi sovietice, având la bază componenta „marelui popor rus”, în care trebuiau să se dilueze elementele culturale ale minorităților naționale.

Așadar, era aplicat, într-o variantă dură, modelul asimilării totale a culturilor numeroaselor etnii și popoare printr-o politică autoritară a unui megastat totalitar. În acest scop, erau organizate și „vestitele” decade culturale, concepute de către creierul politic de la centru, Ministerul Culturii al fostei Uniuni Sovietice, evenimente programate cu rigurozitate, care se reduceau la prezența în republici a unor grupuri speciale („membrii delegațiilor culturale” fiind cu rigurozitate politic selectați prin aprobarea comitetelor de partid și a celor speciale), care se întâlneau cu locuitorii, dialogau doar în rușește, ca să fie înțeleși de către toți, se citeau texte poetice în rusește, se demonstrau filme în rusește despre „măreția” „statului eliberator” și „constructor al comunismului salvator”, despre „marea cultură sovietică”, vorbitorii ajungând, în afirmațiile lor extaziate din acele momente de paradă, a se dezice de identitatea lor culturală și națională, ceea ce, de facto, se urmărea cu mult fariseism prin așa-numita „prietenie de nezdruncinat” a popoarelor frățești din fostul imperiu sovietic. În același sens „lucrau” și alte domenii ale vastului spațiu cultural, în general, instituțiile vitale, forurile științifice și de cultură, fiind centralizate, în fond, pe teritorii istorice ale statului rus, iar toate mințile luminate ale popoarelor calificate drept minoritare în raport cu calificativul însușit abuziv de „mare popor rus”, fiind atrase în programe de anvergură politică și, în definitiv,

nevoite să accepte dependența de politica imperială sovietică la toate nivelurile ei de manifestare. Domeniile istoria și lingvistica au fost științele ce au suportat cele mai oribile falsuri, pe care savanții nu reușesc să le filtreze nici după un sfert de veac de la căderea imperiului. Politica „fratelui mai mare” a lucrat în folosul creării imaginii unui „stat-rechin”, de care, mai ales popoarele din fosta uniune, au dobândit sindromul fricii, manifest evident și la populația din țara noastră, mai ales după așa-numitului război de pe Nistru și, propriu-zis, dezmembrarea Republicii Moldova, și actualmente, în contextul acaparării de către Rusia a Crimeii și a dezlănțuirii focarului secesionist din Ucraina. Din această cauză, starea de spirit a populației din Republica Moldova este una complicată și duală, iar limpezirea și stabilitatea ei s-ar putea face cu ajutorul formării unei mentalități sănătoase, bazate, întâi de toate, pe valorile vieții și a unui autentic dialog intercultural.

Repere ale unui program eficient de modernizare a unui dialog intercultural. Prioritar în politicile statului trebuie să devină obiectivul promovării pe toate canalele informative și educative a valorilor științifice și culturale autentice, căci acestea fundamentează integritatea personalității umane, condiție a unei societăți moderne. Forurile științifice și culturale trebuie să aibă grijă și să-și asume responsabilitatea majoră de pertinența elaborărilor și a diverselor materiale orientate spre formarea opiniei publice și a instruirii / educației populației majore și minore în baza adevărilor științifice incontestabile, de investirea unor specialiști foarte bine pregătiți și onești cu dreptul de a elabora asemenea materiale. Și acest fapt pentru că știința, cultura, politicul și economicul trebuie să aibă un singur fundament constituit din aliajul indestructibil dintre o gândire modernă, adevăr științific, valori culturale, producere / elaborare prin colaborare și dialog intercultural. Nu există valori științifice care contravin celor economice, politice și, cu atât mai mult, celor culturale. Iar omul modern este în primul rând o entitate culturală.

Una dintre condițiile consolidării societății și realizării dialogului cultural este, în special, datorită reprezentanților conducerii de toate nivelurile, a personalităților publice și a reprezentanților mass-media să se reperateze, în discursuri, pe mesaje clare, constructive, ce îndeamnă spre colaborare și atitudini empatică. Cultura unui dialog public nu acceptă enunțarea neadevărurilor și a mofturilor proprii, a atacurilor la persoană și a

limbajului ce perturbază comunicarea eficientă, elemente inadecvate atât de frecvente în replicile sau discursurile reprezentanților de conducere, a personalităților politice și publice, încât nici vorbă de realizarea unui dialog intercultural între cetățenii țării (să nu uităm înțeleptul proverb popular: „peștele de la cap se strică”). Un semnal îngrijorător este rezultatul unui sondaj de opinie, care atestă că din 350 de intervieuați, locuitori urbani și rurali, la întrebarea: *Prezintă interes și ascultați mesajele conducătorilor și personalităților politice în emisiunile radio și TV ?*, circa 43% - „nici nu doresc să-i ascult, că se sfădesc între ei și nu se îngrijesc de popor”, 30% au răspuns că încearcă să-i asculte, dar atestă că mesajul este fals, „joacă fariseic și prin cuvinte”; 11% că mesajele „sunt dușmănoase” sau „orientează spre violență”, 14% - „ascult atent doar mesajele unor lideri (...) cum sunt Lurie Leancă, Maia Sandu, Dorin Chirtoacă” și 2% nu s-au pronunțat. Așadar, este imperios ca personalitățile publice să-și modernizeze discursul funcțional și să dispună ajustarea la normele de corectitudine etică și gramaticală a discursurilor publicitare care influențează mentalitatea populației și promovează modele iconice și structuri de comunicare.

Cetățenii țării trebuie ajutați să accepte un fond comun de cunoștințe inerente la capitolul istoria adevărată a devenirii țării și poporului ei, a valorilor incontestabile pe care le reprezintă, prioritară fiind ideea că spațiul vital al țării este cea mai mare valoare pe care trebuie să o întrețină cetățenii ei, iar diversitatea culturală este bogăția spirituală, este „corola de minuni” care etalează statul nostru, de aceea trebuie protejat și îmbogățit. Cu atât mai mult că se atestă premiza principală a relizării acestui obiectiv, motivația intrinsecă a cetățenilor. Un indicator calitativ al acesteia sunt răspunsurile interveviaților la întrebarea: *Doriți într-adevăr să cunoașteți concret, „pe viu” particularitățile culturii concetățenilor ce aparțin altor grupuri etnice?* În rezultat, s-a constatat: 69% au bifat: *Doresc și mă interesează foarte mult*; 28%. *Doresc, dar să mi se ofere posibilități* și doar 3% *Nu pot să mă pronunț*. Așadar avem, în Republica Moldova, în fond, o societate cu evidente însemne ale unei comunități deschise, dar încă nepregătită pentru a realiza un model de viață modernă printr-o formulă evoluată a unui dialog intercultural.

În scopul realizării acestui deziderat în cazul Republicii Moldova, se impune parcurgerea câtorva dimensiuni, dintre care prima ar fi debarasarea de sindromul „micimii”, de a ne reconstrui integritatea umană din

perspectiva unei mentalități moderne și de a ne recunoaște și asuma valoarea identității naționale prin care să contextualizăm cu orice societate modernă de astăzi și în diverse activități umane civilizate. De aici și cea de a doua: formarea, la cetățenii țării noastre, a unei conștiințe moderne de conviețuire culturală prin respectul îndubitabil al legislației în vigoare a țării și nu prin manifestarea neîntemeiată a unor mofturi individuale sau a unor interese de grup. Fiecare locuitor al țării trebuie să conștientizeze că este, în primul rând, cetățean al acestei țări și, în al doilea rând, reprezentant al unei culturi ce-și merită existența prin valorile umane și spirituale pe care le promovează în folosul prosperității țării și nu invers.

Contextul politic nociv din țară, creat de interesele înguste de partid și de scopul major al deținerii hegemoniei politico-economice a unui grup de oligarhi este în detrimentul intereselor de prosperitate economică și culturală a cetățenilor statului în general, nu contribuie la afirmarea valorică a statului și creează a atitudine diminuantă față de tot ce reprezintă de jure și de facto statul nostru, în același plan, și față de însemnele simbolice ale statului, cum sunt stema, drapelul, limba și elementele definitorii ale culturii emblematice ale țării. Acceptarea în continuare a falsurilor științifice de ordin istoric și lingvistic în privința identității naționale și culturale a poporului băștinaș a provocat neîncrederea populației în adevărul științific, chiar dacă acesta este certificat de savanți, întrucât politica de denigrare a identității românești a populației băștinașe din țară, de creare a imaginii denigratoare a României (de fapt, un stat care ne-a acordat întotdeauna ajutor substanțial și ne-a oferit o colaborare eficientă), promovată cu nerușinare de reprezentanții diplomați ai Rusiei pe diverse canale, atât în republică, cât și în plan internațional, este distructibilă pentru concepția existenței de bună vecinătate, integrare economică și culturală a două state românești în același spațiu european, de unde miza crescândă astăzi și pe ideea unei integrări politice salvatoare cu statul de origine istorică a populației băștinașe. Astfel, lupta politica greșită și fățarnică a guvernanților din țară, determinată evident de interesul geopolitic al Rusiei, al cărui joc riscă să-l facă partidele politice, în primul rând cele actualmente aflate în opoziție, și, în al doilea rând, și cele de la guvernare, s-a impregnat puternic pe mentalitatea și conștiința culturală a cetățenilor de diferite grupuri etnice conlocuitoare în țara noastră.

Mai mult decât atât, temenii funcționali în spațiul cultural al țării, precum: limba română, denumirea științifică corectă a limbii de stat, popor român / naționalitate românească, calificarea corectă din punct de vedere a originii istorice a identității naționale a poporului băștinaș, alte elementele semnificative emblematic ale spiritualității și culturii românești, au fost inoculate cetățenilor țării de către unii lideri politici ca idei și concepții suspicioase sau chiar dușmănoase, periculoase, de destabilizare politică, confirmate și susținute și prin politica embargourilor economice de tot soiul, care au bătut în rădăcina stării economice a populației din țară. În felul acesta s-a obținut divizarea societății pe false criterii, ceea ce facilitează înfăptuirea jocurilor perfide ale oligarhilor și ale partidelor patriotarde, care promovează interesele geopolitice ale Rusiei în regiune, după cunoscuta și diabolica lege „divide et impera”.

Această stare de lucruri a condus și la neînțelegerea adecvată a ceea ce înseamnă un dialog intercultural, care să-și atingă obiectivul civilizat scontat. Or, concentrarea forțelor competente din țară pentru elaborarea și implementarea diverselor proiecte și programe interculturale, promovate în permanență de politicile statului, ar constitui pași reali pe făgașul integrării societății printr-un pertinent dialog intercultural, ceea ce constituie a treia, și mai consistentă în activități, dimensiune. Faptul este susținut și de limbajele culturale care sunt canale de comunicare prin interacțiunea valorilor, prin promovarea umanului și frumosului într-un spațiu dominat de atitudine empatică, relații benevolente de interculturalitate, iar diversitatea culturală, întreține spectrul fascinant al entităților spirituale, motivație existențială intrinsecă. Or, acestea ar asigura și o veritabilă comunicare a populației astfel ca orice mesaj constructiv să fie auzit și corect înțeles și s-ar produce o reală interacțiune dintre diversele grupuri culturale percepute ca distincte în societatea noastră și un activ schimb de valori spirituale, comportamentale, profitabil pentru toți cetățenii. Aceste repere indică spre elaborarea unui model eficient de conviețuire interculturală a locuitorilor din țara noastră, care ar oferi o experiență și altor state cu prezență a mai multor grupuri etnice.

În felul acesta, devine evidentă una dintre condițiile existenței unui stat modern actual: promovarea și realizarea de facto al unui veritabil dialog cultural, care este un context benefic pentru colaborarea interetnică în direcția progresului economic și a stabilității politice atât în interiorul unei

țări, cât și în perimetrul unei macrozone sau chiar în plan global. În scopul realizării acestui deziderat este necesară implementarea unei educații interculturale zi de zi, la nivel de familie, instituție școlară, comunitate, bazele căreia au fost enunțate de sătre cercetătoarea A. Nedelcu în documentatul studiu cu opțiuni practice *Fundamentele educației interculturale*.

În condițiile Republicii Moldova, acestea ar putea fi diriguite de primărie, diverse instituții specializate, credibile pentru populație, ce ar include manifestări de interacțiune culturală, cum ar fi: crearea prin colaborarea locuitorilor a muzeelor localităților, tabere de vacanță cu ateliere folclorice și de meșteșuguri tradiționale, concursuri, colocvii științifice și de popularizare cu participarea savanților și a oaspeților din alte localități ș.a., care să realizeze o adevărată interacțiune prin „lucrare împreună” și trărea satisfacției și bucuriei existențiale în aceste condiții.

Astfel se va crea efectul unei „școli vii” pentru ca generația în creștere și populația adultă să perceapă importanța, în viața modernă, a diferenței culturilor, să o protejeze ca pe o deosebită bogăție ce le stă la îndemână și care achiziție este profitabilă pentru orice personalitate umană, nu numai în sensul lărgirii orizontului comprehensiv de viață, dar și în cel al punerii în valoare a propriei personalități, al multiplicării posibilităților de realizare a unei cariere de succes și de prosperare a țării, grație acestor fapte țara se va încadra cu demnitate în spațiul european.

Bibliografie:

1. Abdallah-Pretceille M., *L'education interculturelle*, Paris: PUF, 1999
2. *Cartea albă a Consiliului Europei. Să trăim împreună, în mod egal, cu demnitate*, Strasbourg, 2008
3. Geertz C., *The Interpretation of Cultures*, New York: Basic Book, 1973
4. Giordano C., *De la criza reprezentărilor la triumful prefixurilor. Un comentariu la propunerile lui Adrian Severin și Gabriel Andreescu* // Poledna R., Ruegg F., Rus C., *Interculturalitate. Cercetări și perspective românești*. Cluj-Napoca: Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2003
5. Nedelcu A., *Fundamentele educației interculturale*, Iași: Editura Polirom, 2008

6. Rey M., *De la o logică „mono” la logica de tip „inter”. Piste pentru o educație interculturală și solidară* // Dasen P., Perregaux C., Rey M., *Educația interculturală*, Iași: Editura Polirom, 1999
7. Taylor C., *Multiculturalism and „The Politics of Recognition”*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1992

Copyright©Tamara CRISTEI

La République de Moldova entre passé et l'Union européenne. Confluences des valeurs

MCF. Dr. Carolina DODU-SAVCA

carolina.dodu-savca@studiieu.org

Institut de Relations Internationales de Moldova, Moldova
ECSA-Moldova

Abstract: In this article, the author proposes an overall analysis of the Europeanization of the Republic of Moldova from the axiological perspective. The thematic progression relies on: the components of the national framework and the ways of Europeanization in terms of premises, opportunities, priorities; the dual axiological values and the issues of social solidarity; the axiological foundations of the European integration; the intellectual elite and Intangible Cultural Heritage; the political culture and high moral (moral political culture); algorithms of European values (multilateral dialogue, citizenship, reintegration, providential democracy). The methods derive from the following approaches: analytical, synthetic, and dialectical. The principles of the axiological integration consist of shared traditions, cultural identity, liberal-democratic policies and beliefs, societal aspects and common social standards. Treating this sensitive subject, the author aims to highlight the criteria that would bring the balance in a country that has been the object, and lately the tool, of intimidation that is targeting, first, the mutilation of values.

Key-words: Europeanization of the Republic of Moldova, European values, axiological foundations of the European integration, issues of social solidarity, morality, algorithms of European values.

Introduction

Les problèmes soulevés dans cet article tracent une analyse d'ensemble de l'eupéanisation de la République de Moldova sous l'angle axiologique de l'intégration (fédéralisation des valeurs) et des mécanismes d'adaptation en matière de modernisation. Les démarches thématiques s'appuient sur les approches suivantes: l'approche analytique, synthétique et dialectique, respectivement. Il faut traiter ce sujet délicat – et cette question épineuse pour une certaine catégorie politique – avec prudence, car il ne s'agit pas de contenter les uns ou les autres. La tâche est de créer un équilibre appuyé sur les valeurs générales et universelles; et, avouons-le,

c'est un équilibre difficile à trouver dans le contexte actuel de la République de Moldova. Cet équilibre s'exprime dans une concession des convulsions linguistiques, culturelles, identitaires, politiques et pour autant dans une sécurité et stabilité sociale et économique, quasi-utopique en général et quasi-impossible à regagner sur un horizon de court terme. Symboliquement, l'équilibre recherché entre l'Occident et l'espace postsoviétique comme donnée extérieure et entre langue-identité culturelle comme tête d'affiche des ségrégations intérieures met en lumière une dynamique à perturbations axiologiques déconcertantes. Les limites méthodologiques de cet article nuancent les critères d'une européanisation hypothétiquement assumée par la République de Moldova. Les leviers conceptuels de cet article mettent en avant la valorisation – sélective et thématiquement filtrée – du cadre national (les espaces politiques, juridiques, économiques, sociaux, culturels) en accentuant les opportunités de l'européanisation par la priorité du dialogue européen et l'opportunité de l'approche proactive des élites politiques et administratives, intellectuelles et médiatiques.

Composantes du cadre national et pistes pour l'européanisation: prémisses, opportunités, priorités. L'intertitre que nous proposons problématise la question de l'européanisation de la République de Moldova dans le contexte de l'option d'intégration européenne. Nous envisageons le dialogue (des modèles théoriques et applicatifs du dialogue politique, social, interculturel, (inter)générationnel, interethnique, scientifique, académique, institutionnel, professionnel etc.) comme prémisses à l'européanisation, opportunité de modernisation et mécanisme premier de l'intégration européenne.

Comment s'actualise le concept d'européanisation dans le cadre autochtone? Quel est le décalage axiologique entre l'UE et la République de Moldova? Voilà les deux objectifs qui déterminent la trame de réflexion dans la présente incursion. Pour dégager les valeurs de l'européanisation dans le cadre national et les conditions d'une valorisation juste des politiques à appliquer, il faut faire resurgir l'importance et la force des valeurs dans les accords et les désaccords des élites politiques, bureaucratiques, fonctionnaires et juristes, d'une part, et des acteurs non-étatiques (d'acteurs du développement), autorités locales et citoyens, d'autre part. La valorisation d'une voie juste requiert une révision des

valeurs par une analyse de ses capacités à mieux discerner les valeurs, à concéder et dépasser les divergences, à s'adapter aux transformations et savoir appliquer de nouveaux principes, dans une nouvelle logique. Il s'agit donc d'aborder aussi les lacunes dans le système des valeurs, la résistance à l'impératif européen, la politisation des valeurs, l'exode de la ressource humaine, les moyens de l'éducation nouvelle.

L'impératif européen est aussi celui des problèmes culturels sur la dimension européenne, problèmes qui sont malheureusement réduits à un rôle secondaire dans un siècle matérialiste¹. Dans le cas de la République de Moldova, nous traitons l'europanisation en termes d'exportation du modèle européen et d'adaptation en tenant compte des contextes locaux et de la volonté culturelle de la République de Moldova. Les deux enjeux incontournables pour former une volonté politique, sociale et culturelle pertinente sont, d'une part, l'aspiration vers l'idéal déclaré de l'espace communautaire – la démocratie – et, d'autre part, la morale/moralité comme catalyse de l'efficacité et de l'efficacité de la politique menée.

Or la société moldave contemporaine est plutôt consciente des idéaux auxquels elle renonce – doit renoncer ou est forcée d'y renoncer – que des idéaux qu'elle aimerait/devrait cultiver et c'est pour cela que le processus de démocratisation rencontre des difficultés et contradictions² dans la conception d'une nouvelle politique.

Dédoublement des valeurs versus solidarité axiologique.

L'intégration européenne se présente dans le contexte moldave comme une pomme de discorde. Il est à remarquer donc que la bipolarité qui caractérise la société les dernières décennies de transition s'est transposée dans une dualité d'aspirations politiques et de positions civiques. Le dédoublement phénoménologique attesté – *République de Moldova versus les Moldova parallèles* – expose le problème d'un pays à multiples facettes disparates, où valeurs et pseudo-valeurs cohabitent et se substituent dans des visions

¹ «În congresele politice se manifestă reaua deprindere de a trata problemele culturii ca pe niște rude sărace care trebuie să cedeze întâietatea problemelor economice și sociale, atât de la modă în acest secol ce se dorește materialist peste măsură». Ciorănescu dans le chapitre „Despre cultura occidentala”. Ciorănescu George. *Europa unită. De la idee la întemeiere*. p.382.

² *Puterea politică și coeziunea socială în Republica Moldova din perspectiva integrării europene*. p.171.

distortionnées. Les valeurs européennes se sont formées dans des traditions historiques de patriotisme et de pacifisme, entre l'idéologie coloniale et l'idée de «mission civilisatrice». Les traditions et les valeurs culturelles nationales autochtones se sont constituées dans des traditions d'une culture harcelée, d'un territoire colonisé à plusieurs reprises, d'un sentiment de résistance aux occupants et des «entractes» de réintégrations territoriale, nationale, identitaire, culturelle etc. Cette fragmentation – historiquement perpétuée – du fond patrimonial, des valeurs et du développement humain a engendré certaines carences visibles dans la culture politique, sociale, économique, professionnelle etc. La dysfonctionnalité du système a mis à l'ordre du jour les injustices sociales et a donné naissance au dualisme existentiel, ontologique, linguistique, identitaire.

La dualité de la société moldave par rapport à l'eupéanisation a nuancé davantage ses réactions incohérentes aux différents problèmes. Si le problème se dédouble, il y a une crise de valeurs à l'origine. D'ailleurs, la crise des valeurs spirituelles est un problème commun de la civilisation contemporaine. Déclenchée au XX^{ème} siècle par le décalage entre le développement scientifique et humain, cette crise a dégénéré dans une fracture entre le (progrès) technologique et (l'évolution de) la moralité. Au niveau quotidien, cette crise prend la forme «d'une perte de confiance et manque d'espoir dans l'avenir, sentiment de désespoir et désespérance»¹. Les recherches sociologiques confirment par des données statistiques «l'affaiblissement de la moralité, des sentiments patriotiques des citoyens, la manifestation d'un faible intérêt pour la politique et pour la participation aux activités publiques»².

Actuellement, la dualité de la société traduit l'opposition quasi-parabolique entre les partisans de l'Est, sympathisants du facteur russe et nostalgique du soviétisme, d'une part, et les adeptes de l'Ouest, les eupéanistes, favorables à l'édification de la République de Moldova au sein de la famille européenne, d'autre part. Les représentations partagées des moldaves sur l'UE donnent cours soit à une réception enthousiasmée soit à une réticence évidente, même à un rejet des valeurs européennes comme un acte de «patriotisme» (qui n'est qu'un chauvinisme aberrant).

¹ Roșca Ludmila. *Filosofia. Ghidul afacerii de succes*. p.283.

² Cf. Vianu Tudor. *Studii de filosofia culturii*.

L'intégration européenne ne serait pas un défi si la société autochtone est prête à délimiter le bien-juste-utile des manipulations intérieures et intimidations extérieures. Cela sera le cas quand la société moldave dépassera la crise des valeurs et pourra valoriser le rapport du national à l'europpéen; or le cas ne se présente pas encore¹. Un consensus sur l'europpéanisation n'a pas encore vu le jour au sein de la classe politique et, respectivement, de la société moldave. C'est un sujet qui crée des lignes de clivages politique, social, idéologique, dans certains cas des clivages d'ordre confessionnel ou ethnique, ou encore linguistique et identitaire. En fait, ni les élites des partis politiques, ni les agents étatiques ou non-étatiques, les facteurs médiatiques ou les fonctionnaires, ne devraient pas créer de clivages (puisque dans la grande majorité des cas ce sont des clivages artificiels), tout comme aucun citoyen moyen ne devrait faire partie des clivages politisés et imposés.

Il faut voir l'idée d'identité et d'intégrité dans une dimension nouvelle du dialogue de l'intégration européenne; or, dans un pays à héritage culturellement riche, les impédiments à l'europpéanisation (où l'europpéanisation veut dire, dans un contexte axiologique, la reconnaissance des valeurs communes) restent multiples: les convulsions linguistiques et identitaires, les contrastes et les paradoxes intrinsèques à la société moldave, l'état d'incertitude de la culture moldave et de l'histoire sociopolitique de la République de Moldova. Les deux derniers sont des problèmes extrêmement sensibles demeurant dans la zone des frustrations d'injustices, de manipulation et d'intimidation de la démocratie.

D'ailleurs, les outils d'intimidation ciblent premièrement les valeurs. Telle est l'attitude officielle – et politisée – de la Fédération Russe qui en opposant les valeurs occidentales aux «valeurs morales traditionnelles» déclare l'invalidité des premières et reconnaît un handicap moral grave du monde occidental. À ce sujet, invoquons un exemple médiatisé de la mi-décembre 2013, quand lors de la conférence de presse annuelle Vladimir Poutine a dénoncé «la soi-disant tolérance, stérile, qui ne fait pas de

¹ „Societatea autohtonă continuă să fie neasigurată de expansiunea culturii de masă, rămânând impasibilă la tendința de neglijare a culturii tradiționale și substituirii ei cu elemente străine mentalității autohtone care sunt asimilate cu nonșalanță, deoarece sunt poziționate ca părți definitorii pentru imagine și prestigiu.” „Introducere”, In *Redimensionarea valorilor în contextul noii vecinătății cu Uniunea europeană*.

différence entre les sexes» et le fait qu'«on procède aujourd'hui dans de nombreux pays à une réévaluation des normes morales et on exige de la société qu'elle mette sur le même plan le bien et le mal»¹. Bien sûr qu'il y aurait de telles interprétations de la part des anciens et actuels opposants de l'Europe unie.

Un défi important dans les aspirations européennes de la République de Moldova est de résister aux tentatives de manipulation extérieures et aux faiblesses intérieures. La République de Moldova doit adopter des valeurs qui structurent les relations internationales: la fermeté de la position pro-européenne, la légitimité des élites gouvernementales et l'intégrité institutionnelle, des élites politiques et diplomatiques et des éléments du système politico-administratif et médiatique. Ici se pose encore le problème de l'intérêt national qui est une valeur démocratique par excellence. Lurie Pîntea estime que les intérêts nationaux sont basés «sur les valeurs et le patrimoine national, le potentiel moral et intellectuel de la société qui sont réalisés et garantis par l'activité de perspective dans les domaines économique, politique et militaire, social et démographique, informationnel et de l'environnement etc.»².

Dans le temps d'une nouvelle donne sociale et culturelle ("new social and cultural order"), les politiques doivent chercher à rétablir l'équilibre entre le patrimoine et les enjeux de la contemporanéité, entre l'utilisation de toutes les infrastructures communautaires et le bon sens de culturalisation de la communauté, entre la promotion de valeurs communautaires et la protection de la diversité des expressions culturelles, entre la fuite de cerveaux et le développement humain. La stabilisation de l'équation *la fuite des cerveaux, le gain de cerveaux et la mobilité* ("Brain

¹ Déclaration faite lors de la conférence de presse annuelle, 19 décembre 2013, à Moscou. *L'Orient le Jour*: «Poutine dénonce certaines valeurs occidentales». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: <http://www.lorientlejour.com/article/847406/poutine-denonce-certaines-pseudo-valeurs-de-loccident.html>; *Le Figaro*: «Poutine: les pseudo-valeurs occidentales». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: <http://www.lefigaro.fr/flash-actu/2013/12/19/97001-20131219FILWWW00399-poutine-les-pseudo-valeurs-occidentales.php>; *Le Point.fr*: «Poutine dénonce certaines «pseudo-valeurs» de l'Occident». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: http://www.lepoint.fr/monde/poutine-denonce-les-pseudo-valeurs-de-l-occident-19-12-2013-1771955_24.php; consulté le 7 février 2014.

² Pîntea Lurie. «Identificarea pericolelor existente și probabile pentru interesele naționale de bază ale Republicii Moldova». p.24.

drain” versus “Brain regain”) est un défi majeur pour notre pays, d’un point de vue démographique, économique, de la ressource humaine, mais elle est aussi une préoccupation grandissante à l’échelle mondiale. Bien que la mobilité et l’exode des cerveaux ne soient plus l’apanage des seuls pays du tiers monde, pour ces pays notamment il pose plus de difficultés et conditionne plus de précarités. Les états qui ont été déjà frappés par l’exode des cerveaux, tels que les ex-républiques soviétiques, la Corée de Sud, les pays de l’Afrique et du Moyen Orient, ont transformé l’approche «gain de cerveaux» dans une politique d’état. Nous considérons que cette urgence sociale doit se constituer dans une politique d’état prioritaire et faire partie du programme gouvernemental de la République de Moldova.

Fondements axiologiques de l’intégration. En termes d’intégration, la Moldavie fera l’objet des changements internes qualitatifs. Si la République de Moldova refuse le parcours européen ce sera une séparation artificielle d’un territoire à l’intérieur duquel le pays se trouve géographiquement et d’une civilisation à laquelle il appartient historiquement et culturellement. Les principes de l’intégration axiologique se basent sur le partage des traditions, d’une identité culturelle, des structures de sens moral, spirituel, religieux, des politiques et croyances libérales-démocratiques, des aspects sociétaux et des normes sociales communes. Les finalités des valeurs européennes se reflètent dans l’UE comme projet économique (vaste marché), démocratique et citoyen.

La citoyenneté (européenne) et la sécurité (politique, économique, culturelle) doivent arriver au centre des préoccupations de l’agenda moldave. Le projet citoyen comporte les enjeux de la société (libre circulation), de la science, de l’éducation (mobilité académique) et des domaines de la vie (recherche au service des citoyens – domaines de la santé, de la sécurité alimentaire et de l’environnement), des aspects éthiques, culturels et interculturels. La réforme politique, économique, éducationnelle, écologique (développement durable: la prise de conscience de la fragilité des équilibres naturels), etc. doivent graduellement créer de nouveaux espaces de la qualité. La fédéralisation des valeurs européennes se fait par la culture, les arts (la danse, la musique etc.), le sport en tant qu’exercice de communication internationale. La participation de la Moldavie à la vitalité de la francophonie est une preuve d’interculturalité assumée et un critère de l’européanisation.

Relancer la République de Moldova en suivant l'exemple de l'Europe veut dire accorder une place centrale, dans la reconsidération des valeurs, au patrimoine intellectuel. L'eupéanisation de l'éducation et de la science de la République de Moldova signifiera une nouvelle prise de conscience de la démarche éducationnelle, du secteur des sciences et technologies, de la mobilité et l'innovation dans l'éducation, de la recherche et de la coopération internationale.

L'élite intellectuelle, le patrimoine immatériel, la moralité. Une valeur inestimable est l'homme moral, qui par définition est l'intellectuel, l'homme de culture, le scientifique, l'artiste, le sage. Il ne s'agit pas là de l'homme idéal, mais de celui qui inspire; celui qui pense, ne reste pas indifférent, mobilise les autres et qui se trouve aux sources de l'agir juste. Son rôle est déterminant dans la promotion et protection de la démocratie, des libertés, du sens de la justice et de l'égalité. Idéalement, le développement et le progrès – ou bien pour actualiser les valeurs des deux notions dans un seul terme: la modernisation – de l'État commencent avec de nouvelles personnes, de nouvelles idées, une élite, des orientations claires, une attitude pertinente, un comportement approprié, une «politique juste»¹. L'élite intellectuelle fait figure de «catalyse et de moyen d'expression d'un destin commun»². L'élite intellectuelle plaide les droits et veille à la dignité et intégrité de sa communauté. Dans l'implicite, l'élite intellectuelle éduque la société et cultive ses attachements aux valeurs, étant à la fois la seule force motrice capable de sauvegarder la souveraineté de l'esprit en tant que «bien suprême du monde occidentale»³.

Il faut valoriser le potentiel de la République de Moldova sur l'arène internationale par ses atouts. Un des premiers atouts est l'agriculture, qui se présente comme un secteur stratégique pour une Europe majoritairement industrialisée. Un atout incontestable pour tout pays, et pour le nôtre aussi, relèvent des ressources humaines et du patrimoine intellectuel (hommes de talents, artistes, scientifiques). Puis, c'est le développement rural, le développement du tourisme vert et le développement des secteurs clés,

¹ Cf. Renaut Alain. *Qu'est-ce qu'une politique juste?*

² Morin Edgar. *Penser l'Europe*. p.215.

³ „Cultura pusă în serviciul întregii ființe a omului și a întregii omeniri va salva binele suprem al lumii occidentale: suveranitatea spiritului”, Ciorănescu George. *Europa unită. De la idee la întemeiere*. p.383.

comme le domaine du textile spécialisé dans le luxe. Dernièrement, la Moldavie est devenue «l'atelier du textile de l'Europe»: les produits issus des fabriques moldaves sont très demandés en Europe. Une autre priorité stratégique c'est le mode d'alimentation: les traditions d'une alimentation assez bio et les traditions culinaires, enracinées dans l'institution de la famille. N'oublions pas les valeurs culturelles spécifiques du patrimoine immatériel, telles que la culture ethnique et folklorique. Un trait inédit de la culture ethno-folklorique est comporté par la danse populaire, si riche, diverse et représentative pour l'esprit de l'identité nationale. Citons ici : a) la troupe musicale-chorégraphique de danses populaires moldaves «Joc»; b) la danse nommée «căluș»/ «Les Călușari», qui est une danse traditionnelle de l'homme-cheval. Le chant populaire est une autre valeur du patrimoine immatériel avec l'incomparable Doïna, qui est un chant traditionnel roumain d'expression nostalgique, du sentiment d'amertume du destin du peuple ou d'un individu, du fardeau des privations de tout type, des frustrations etc. La série est complétée avec les ballades, qui sont des chansons traditionnelles lyriques de cri contre toute forme d'injustice ou expression de tout sentiment, d'habitude de mélancolie ou de tristesse. Décidément ce qui a déjà apporté la reconnaissance de l'UNESCO à notre culture c'est l'art du chant populaire polyphonique: «Colindatul de ceată bărbătească» de la République de Moldova. Ce chant collectif à la veille des fêtes d'hiver est inscrit dans le patrimoine culturel immatériel de l'humanité UNESCO depuis 2013. Le patrimoine intellectuel comme la science, les produits intellectuels, les personnalités, les élites etc. sont bien sûr les valeurs générales à cultiver. Les autres atouts inhérents seraient: la compétence interculturelle (qui englobe les compétences linguistique et ethno-linguistique), le culte du travail (qui devrait être accompagné du culte de la performance), le sens de pacification et conciliation etc.

Culture politique et haute moralité. La personnalité du pays fera avancer la volonté d'une gouvernance juste. Disons, en définitive, que l'eupéanisation axiologique pose une question de révision morale de l'ensemble de l'activité humaine – matérielle, sociopolitique et spirituelle –, une reconsidération du statut des valeurs en question dans le cadre local. Dans le cas de la société moldave, les trois grandes sphères qui sont mises à l'épreuve par l'élément oligarchique sont: la ségrégation politique, le clivage social, la désorientation morale. Ces trois atrocités «feignent le

développement du socium»¹. La pauvreté, la corruption et la dualité des valeurs sont les conséquences et à la fois les causes d'une transition prolongée vers une démocratie fragile dans une société fragilisée.

Pour sortir du cercle vicieux, le pouvoir politique doit impérativement consolider les valeurs de la société démocratique par quelques enjeux majeurs:

- 1) développer une culture politique,
- 2) dépolitiser la morale,
- 3) cultiver la moralité.

La haute moralité est en crise non seulement locale, mais globale, ici et ailleurs. Il est urgent de (re)créer l'homme moral, «la priorité de l'homme moral»². Les autres urgences du contexte axiologique sont d'ordre matériel: réglementer l'économie de marché selon le code éthique (pour la qualité et légalité des produits, la sécurité alimentaire et la santé publique etc.), mettre en œuvre la déontologie des marchés bancaires et financiers et de la production et circulation des biens et des services, sensibiliser la conscience sociale collective (envers l'individu) et la conscience civique (de chaque individu).

Algorithmes d'adoption des valeurs européennes : multilatéralisme du dialogue, citoyenneté, réintégration, démocratie providentielle. Une valeur incontestable est le multilatéralisme du dialogue. En parlant de cette priorité que les Européens reconnaissent au multilatéralisme, Derruine mentionne que «le continent a été décheté par tellement de conflits régionaux et de guerres totales qu'ils savent les vertus du dialogue. D'où leur soutien à l'ONU. Le Traité ainsi que le projet de Constitution ne disent-ils pas que l'action extérieure de l'Union se fonde sur la Charte des Droits de l'Homme des Nations Unies?»³. La République de Moldova doit faire preuve d'un parcours en concertation avec tous ses partenaires politiques, sociaux,

¹ *Puterea politică și coeziunea socială în Republica Moldova din perspectiva integrării europene*. p.180.

² „Despre morală, prioritar în reflectarea ei negativă, se amintește doar în cazul confruntărilor politice. Aprecierile morale sunt solicitate doar în contextul luptei politice (în majoritatea cazurilor, în lupta pentru electorat) și se utilizează pentru defăimarea concurenților politici. Doar în aceste împrejurări populație i se vorbește despre „păcatele” reprezentanților elitei politice”. *Ibidem*, p.181.

³ Derruine Olivier. «Donner corps aux symboles de l'identité Européenne». p.79.

de la société civile. Les compétences et options du dialogue politique, économique, diplomatique, culturel, académique, professionnel, ouvrent des opportunités inestimables pour l'intégrité de notre pays. La République de Moldova dépend de l'action et de la réaction européenne et elle compte sur une réponse coordonnée. Les avantages de l'eupéanisation de la République de Moldova commencent à se présenter par les Traités signés, traités qui matérialisent des valeurs réelles. Parmi ces valeurs, notons la libéralisation du régime de visas et le traitement préférentiel de la République de Moldova (vu le fait que la République de Moldova présente un intérêt géopolitique, le pays bénéficie d'un traitement préférentiel qui stipule: accélération de la signature des traités, fonds de collaboration pour le développement des infrastructures, pour le développement régional et pour la réforme de la justice etc.). La Politique européenne de voisinage (PEV) formalise l'appartenance commune aux valeurs européennes. L'Accord de l'Association est un élément du cadre de cette politique. Nous connaissons les problèmes de l'UE et les précarités de l'organisation interne de l'Europe. Malgré le fait que la crise actuelle dénonce la faible intégration politique, (et non seulement politique) des états membres, les avantages de l'intégration sont indiscutables. Pour prendre une comparaison générale avec les états d'orientation pro-occidentale, nous constatons que leur avancée socioculturelle est évidente. Tout en gardant l'optimisme du parcours européen, il est raisonnable de ne pas chercher de mesures messianiques, de ne pas adopter d'attitudes fétichistes envers les réformes proposées par la gouvernance et de se donner le temps de construire des trajectoires politiques, sociales et institutionnelles. La vision réaliste de la réalité européenne et des réalités politiques et sociales autochtones, une connaissance suffisante de la personnalité de l'UE et une prise de conscience citoyenne constitueront les prémisses internes d'une eupéanisation réelle.

L'eupéanisation pour la République de Moldova sera un processus volontairement accepté d'auto-transformation. Les étapes de l'eupéanisation axiologique de la République de Moldova peuvent être identifiées aux mécanismes essentiels d'adoption des valeurs européennes: citoyenneté, intégration et réintégration, démocratie providentielle. Les objectifs spécifiques à suivre ici sont à titre interrogatif: Quelles sont les relations entre les rôles et les fonctions de l'eupéanisation dans la

République de Moldova? pour ce qui tient de l'organisation et de la mobilisation de la modernisation. Rappelons donc là que les priorités stratégiques développées (ou au moins déclarées et fixées sur l'agenda) par le gouvernement de la République de Moldova sont: 1. L'intégration européenne est une prérogative fondamentale de la politique interne et étrangère de la République de Moldova; 2. La réintégration de la République de Moldova est un des objectifs fondamentaux du Gouvernement (il s'agit bien sûr de la solution du conflit transnistrien); 3. La suprématie de la loi. Une dimension importante de la République de Moldova c'est la définition cohérente de la politique externe et interne sur deux piliers d'action: a) Valorisation de la priorité stratégique de la mise en place de l'intégration européenne et la promotion des réformes politiques et sociales – deux processus qui se complètent; b) Adoption du modèle européen axiologique et adaptation aux contextes locaux (en matière de valeurs, normes, règles communautaires dans la politique intérieure).

Citoyenneté et intégration sont les deux valeurs pratiques de l'ensemble européen où la démocratie providentielle est un mode de vie. Si la démocratie traditionnelle prévoit l'égalité formelle de la citoyenneté, qui garantit l'équité devant la loi, alors la démocratie providentielle est l'égalité réelle des conditions sociales, qui cherche à assurer l'égalité et l'équité effectives de la loi envers le citoyen. La pratique de la démocratie moderne prévoit une compréhension complexe et comporte: la citoyenneté active, l'implication des communautés, la rationalisation (scientifique, le cas échéant) des décisions sociales, la modernisation administrative.

La modernisation efficace commence par l'institutionnalisation des valeurs dans l'ensemble des espaces (social, politique, juridique, culturel etc.), la mise en place des codes éthiques par domaines, la déontologie par sphères et les bonnes pratiques par secteurs d'activité. Si dans le cas de l'europanisation nous parlons de l'élite intellectuelle comme catalyse, pour la modernisation ce sera le culte de la personnalité. Certes, les distinctions sont trop fines et sans ambitions de clivage. La priorité de l'homme moral, de l'élite intellectuelle ou de la personnalité servent de force motrice pour le développement humain et l'évolution du pays. Comme l'atteste à juste titre Kohn, la modernisation se ressource dans le patrimoine intellectuel: "The modernization of the Orient is not confined to things political or economic, it originated with the intelligentsia and some of its most important

manifestations are cultural and religious”¹. La modernisation ainsi que l’eupéanisation se font par l’institutionnalisation des modèles, y inclus le modèle humain: de bonne conduite, d’initiative, de compétitivité. Dans cette logique, la compétence se présente comme une valeur réelle et un objectif central de la modernisation de l’état. La priorité de la moralité, de la compétence et de la personnalité peut développer des réseaux interprofessionnels avec des alliés extérieurs et intérieurs pour mobiliser les ressources humaines et valoriser les ressources sociales, patrimoniales.

L’état ne peut pas se moderniser sans l’appui d’une élite, de nouvelles visions pertinentes et des valeurs démocratiques réelles. Formellement, la modernisation de l’état se fait par des réformes, procédures et développements locaux, alors qu’effectivement et en termes de fonctionnalité, elle se fait par la mise en place des mesures systémiques et complexes. Un processus de modernisation sociale ou sociétale accéléré ne comportera pas un caractère profond et durable. Les actions de la modernisation sont attachées directement ou indirectement aux valeurs et la mise en place des codes éthiques et le recours à la déontologie seront les premières étapes du redressement de la situation économique. A titre illustratif, une des prémisses aux modalités de modernisation c’est la transparence et l’informatisation des flux financiers qui permettent une administration fiscale juste et qui neutralisent l’économie souterraine.

La dynamique de la modernisation dépend de la dynamique axiologique du socium et du politique (la culture politique, le culte du politique, la politique, les politiques). Parmi les valeurs primordiales de la modernisation c’est la gouvernance comme management performant et la bonne gouvernance comme composante essentielle du cadre national, c’est la stabilité, car un pays plus stable, veut dire un système politique plus prévisible. Les mesures qui peuvent garantir une dynamique positive seraient:

- a) prioriser les valeurs selon les urgences sociétales;
- b) immuniser l’état, les élites, les citoyens aux tentations du facteur russe, aux manipulations des éléments oligarchiques et aux autres influences nocives et atroces socialement et culturellement;

¹ Kohn Hans. “The Europeanization of the Orient”. In *Political Science Quarterly*, Vol. 52, No. 2, Juin, Ed. The Academy of Political Science, 1937 (pp. 259-70), p.267.

- c) moderniser l'infrastructure des systèmes publics d'éducation et diversifier les services éducatifs;
- d) stimuler le développement qualitatif du capital humain et de la couche dynamique de la culture (le monde académique, les institutions);
- e) stabiliser et humaniser le socium: donner la possibilité de répondre aux questions sociales ardentes, solutionner des inquiétudes intra-sociétales et diminuer l'incertitude citoyenne;
- f) contribuer au renforcement de la prospérité régionale et nationale.

L'intégration européenne sera la finalité des transformations internes qualitatives de l'eupéanisation. Dans ce contexte, l'eupéanisation signifie la transformation de «la structure traditionnelle de la société» (à laquelle faisait référence encore en 1937 l'historien Hans Kohn) par le biais de l'intégration d'un modèle de société, des enjeux civilisationnels, des politiques de transformation des aspects de la vie sociale et politique. Les dialogues politique, social et culturel se prêtent très bien à une activité implicite de concertation pour une approche proactive d'une modernisation qualitative. Le rôle du dialogue social, interculturel, professionnel et académique dans la dynamique de la modernisation de la République de Moldova sera déterminant.

Pour identifier les grands axes stratégiques du parcours européen de la République de Moldova, nous avons fait recours au modèle de diagnostic, connu sous le nom de l'analyse AFOM (SWOT). Nous avons classé les données internes et externes (dans un contexte international) en Menaces et Opportunités et les données internes, du cadre national, en Forces et Faiblesses. En nous appuyant sur les données qui ont le plus d'impact sur la démarche européenne, nous allons prendre en compte, dans une brève synthèse, les facteurs d'un vrai impact. Nous proposons cette grille analytique, adaptée à notre sujet, afin de prioriser les avantages (consolider les Forces), faire attention aux désavantages (prendre acte des faiblesses et des menaces) et valoriser les opportunités.

Atouts - les points forts ou «les forces» du cadre national (dans un contexte international):	Faiblesses - les points faibles du cadre national :
1. l'agriculture - secteur stratégique	9. le culte du travail qui devrait

<p>pour une Europe majoritairement industrialisée;</p> <p>2. les ressources humaines et le patrimoine intellectuel (hommes de talents, artistes, scientifiques);</p> <p>3. le développement rural et le tourisme vert;</p> <p>4. le domaine du textile spécialisé dans le luxe – la Moldavie est devenue «l’atelier du textile de l’Europe»¹, les produits issus des usines moldaves);</p> <p>5. les valeurs culturelles spécifiques du patrimoine culturel immatériel;</p> <p>6. les traditions d’une alimentation saine, traditions culinaires enracinées dans l’institution de la famille (le fait maison/la cuisine fait maison);</p> <p>7. la participation de la Moldavie à la vitalité de la francophonie comme preuve d’interculturalité assumée et critère préliminaire d’européanisation;</p> <p>8. les (pluri)compétences linguistiques, ethno-linguistique et interculturelles qui sont des atouts principaux pour nous rendre compétitifs au plan européen et mondial;</p>	<p>être accompagné du culte de la performance;</p> <p>10. le sens de pacification et conciliation du peuple moldave;</p> <p>11. l’inefficience des gouvernances moldaves;</p> <p>12. les réalités politiques moldaves;</p> <p>13. la dynamique négative de la pauvreté et des vulnérabilités sociales ;</p> <p>14. la dualité de la société comme ambivalence axiologique dans l’espace spirituel de la Moldavie – la morale de la civilisation libérale versus la morale (le Code moral et éthique) de type soviétique-socialiste;</p> <p>15. la précarité dans le secteur de l’emploi moldave – le cercle vicieux: le niveau d’éducation faible conditionne des couches sociales mal intégrées dans certains secteurs et la désintégration sociale à cause d’une formation précaire (gens peu instruits – travailleurs précaires);</p> <p>16. les attitudes fétichistes envers les réformes promises par la classe politique;</p>
--	---

¹ «La Moldavie, l’atelier du textile de l’Europe» est le titre d’un reportage de «France 2» sur la fabrication des produits de luxe en textile issus des usines moldaves. Voir: «La Moldavie, l’atelier du textile de l’Europe». In: *Francetv info*. Mis à jour le 09/06/2015 | 22:09, publié le 09/06/2015 | 22:09. Disponible en ligne. URL. <http://www.francetvinfo.fr/monde/europe/la-moldavie-l-atelier-du-textile-de-l-europe_944051.html> Consulté le 11 juin 2015, 18:50.

Opportunités (des données internes et externes) :	Menaces (des données internes et externes):
<p>17. la valeur proactive de la diplomatie et de la gouvernance de la RM ;</p> <p>18. la promotion de l'image positive du pays;</p> <p>19. les moyens de l'éducation nouvelle;</p> <p>20. les medias comme facteur de pouvoir dans la politique et le journalisme d'opinion indépendante, le journalisme d'investigation (qui puisse illustrer correctement les états d'esprit, les attitudes, positions, etc. de la société et de la gouvernance);</p> <p>21. le renforcement de la vocation européenne – la gouvernance et les élites intellectuelles, médiatiques doivent incorporer dans la logique du discours publique et dans les politiques publiques l'impératif européen pour débattre et construire la connaissance de l'UE ;</p> <p>22. la valorisation de la «compétence civique»¹ du dialogue social, politique, (inter)culturel. Sensibiliser la conscience sociale collective (envers l'individu) et la conscience civique (de chaque individu);</p> <p>23. le revirement de mentalité,</p>	<p>26. réviser la valeur que nous accordons au mode de vie et de penser : réviser la valeur du travail, des vacances, des traditions authentiques, de l'histoire, des rites etc.;</p> <p>27. l'oligarchisation de la politique et de l'économie d'état – le potentiel économique comme motivations économiques de clivage – pomme de discorde des éléments de l'élite politique et du monde interlope;</p> <p>28. le facteur russe – l'intérêt de la Fédération de Russie de maintenir le contrôle des ex-républiques soviétiques et son influence dans la zone postsoviétique per ensemble ;</p> <p>29. les conflits (les rivalités) politiques sur la dimension intérieure et extérieure et l'incohérence des politiques intérieures et extérieures (géopolitiques) ;</p> <p>30. les clivages sociaux, sociétaux, civiques ;</p> <p>31. le conflit transnistrien - le ressentiment dans le discours politique transnistrien et les divergences internes plus prononcées entre les acteurs</p>

¹ Le syntagme de R. Aron.

<p>d'attitude, de position et la valorisation (=valorisation-récupération) du sens de la dignité nationale, de la confiance et de l'autorité des institutions étatiques;</p> <p>24. bénéficiaire de l'existence transnationale de la diaspora; le rôle de la diaspora en tant que lobbies ethniques (associations ethnoculturelle) sur l'arène politique nationale et internationale afin de promouvoir l'image du pays à l'extérieur et partager les bonnes pratiques européennes dans son pays, contribuer à l'impact identitaire culturel sur la scène internationale.</p> <p>25. transformer l'approche «gain de cerveaux» dans une politique d'état. Œuvrer à la stabilisation de l'équation <i>la fuite des cerveaux, le gain de cerveaux et la mobilité</i>.</p>	<p>politiques internes et externes au sujet du rapprochement de la RM de l'UE;</p> <p>32. l'exode de la ressource humaine: la fuite des cerveaux vers l'étranger;</p> <p>33. les convulsions linguistiques, ethniques et identitaires – la dichotomie des valeurs collectives dénonce une ségrégation entre des attitudes parallèles: favorable à l'UE ou à l'Union douanière, où la dernière peut se prononcer en opposition avec le vecteur européen;</p> <p>34. implication KGB-iste dans le système diplomatique, économique (réminiscences du système économique bolchéviste inefficace).</p>
---	--

Notons que cette grille analytique, axée sur la dimension axiologique de l'eupéanisation de la République de Moldova, regroupe les critères susmentionnés d'une manière globale et sans ambition taxonomique ou d'homogénéité (car cela se prête à une étude séparée!).

En guise de synthèse, soulignons que les opportunités de l'eupéanisation de la République de Moldova dans le contexte international seraient: a) meilleure résolution des conflits internes et externes; b) accès aux libertés de circulation; c) possibilité d'utilisation des fonds communautaires; d) changement d'attitude en termes d'investissement, risque, profit.

Conclusion

Les principes de l'intégration européenne sont forcément d'ordre axiologique, basés sur le partage des traditions, des structures de sens moral, spirituel, religieux. Le multilatéralisme du dialogue est une valeur à

cultiver avec les partenaires politiques, sociaux, de la société civile. Les multi-compétences de ce dialogue politique, économique, diplomatique, culturel, académique, professionnel se présentent comme des opportunités réelles de l'européanisation de la République de Moldova.

Malheureusement, les attitudes des élites politico-administratives dictent le parcours d'un pays fractionné politiquement, fragile économiquement vers un avenir dédoublé et incertain. Les élites doivent s'accorder à reconnaître que l'européanisation et l'intégration sont les outils de la politique juste. Une valeur incontestable c'est l'intégrité de chacun et la volonté d'être unis.

Comme nous l'avons déjà dit, tout en gardant l'optimisme du parcours européen, il est raisonnable de ne pas chercher de mesures messianiques, de ne pas adopter d'attitudes fétichistes envers les réformes. Par contre, il est essentiel de se donner le temps de construire des trajectoires politiques dépolitisées, des trajectoires sociales et institutionnelles réelles et judicieuses.

Nous devons encore beaucoup œuvrer au culte de la performance où chaque itinéraire et trajectoire individuel, chaque accomplissement débouche sur un parcours de performance collective, nationale.

Pour clôturer, notons que le statut de l'Union européenne consacre le statut des valeurs générales humaines dans la société occidentale contemporaine. L'UE se veut un pôle de prospérité et de stabilité: pour le développement économique dans un espace commun dynamique et privilégié (les politiques économiques communautaires) et une politique extérieure commune. L'UE a la vocation d'un pôle de solidarité et mobilité: pour la citoyenneté européenne et le sentiment d'appartenance à une communauté des citoyens partageant une histoire, des racines culturelles et religieuses; le patrimoine européen commun et la mise en marche des fondements de la recherche européenne. Réitérons que les prémisses internes d'une européanisation réelle s'appuient sur une vision réaliste de la réalité européenne, une analyse objective des réalités politiques et sociales autochtones, une connaissance suffisante de la personnalité de l'UE et une prise de conscience citoyenne. Pour ponctuer de manière pragmatique la démarche scientifique, notons qu'à l'heure actuelle le parcours européen de la République de Moldova s'accompagne malheureusement d'une situation interne déconcertante et une situation régionale tendue. Or c'est un motif

de plus de bien penser les politiques et repenser le cadre des valeurs du développement de la République de Moldova.

Bibliographie:

1. Ciorănescu George. *Europa unită. De la idee la întemeiere*. București: Editura Paideia, 2004, 448 p.
2. Déclaration faite lors de la conférence de presse annuelle, 19 décembre 2013, à Moscou. *L'Orient le Jour*: «Poutine dénonce certaines valeurs occidentales». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: <http://www.lorientlejour.com/article/847406/poutine-denonce-certaines-pseudo-valeurs-de-loccident.html>; *Le Figaro*: «Poutine: les pseudo-valeurs occidentales». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: <http://www.lefigaro.fr/flash-actu/2013/12/19/97001-20131219FILWWW00399-poutine-les-pseudo-valeurs-occidentales.php>; *Le Point.fr*: «Poutine dénonce certaines «pseudo-valeurs» de l'Occident». [Disponible en-ligne] URL: http://www.lepoint.fr/monde/poutine-denonce-les-pseudo-valeurs-de-l-occident-19-12-2013-1771955_24.php; consulté le 7 février 2014.
3. Derruine Olivier. «Donner corps aux symboles de l'identité Européenne». In *Les cahiers de politique et d'histoire européennes. L'Europe: une œuvre inachevée. 1947-2007*. Gianni Copetti (éd.). 50e anniversaire de la signature 13 du Traité de Rome. Numéro spécial du 7^e Congrès du M.S.E.U.E. Vol. 1, Nr. 15, juillet-août, 1954, pp. 69-81.
4. Kohn Hans. "The Europeanization of the Orient". In *Political Science Quarterly*, Vol. 52, No. 2, Juin, Ed. The Academy of Political Science, 1937, pp. 259-70.
5. Morin Edgar. *Penser l'Europe*. Paris: Gallimard, 1987.
6. Pîntea Iurie. «Identificarea pericolelor existente și probabile pentru interesele naționale de bază ale Republicii Moldova» În: *Evaluarea strategică a securității și apărării naționale a Republicii Moldova*. Chișinău: IPP, 2001. p.18-37
7. *Puterea politică și coeziunea socială în Republica Moldova din perspectiva integrării europene*. Col. de red. Moraru Victor, Roșca Alexandru, Panteleimon Varzari, Victor Juc. Chișinău: Institutul de Integrare Europeană și Științe Politice, Academia de Științe a Moldovei, Tipografia „Print-Caro”, 2010, 222 p.

8. *Redimensionarea valorilor în contextul noii vecinătății cu Uniunea europeană*. Chișinău: Tipografia Sirius, AȘM, 2011, 144 p.
9. Renaut Alain. *Qu'est-ce qu'une politique juste?* Paris: Editeur d'origine Grasset, Coll. Biblio Essais. Livre de poche. Date de parution: 26/10/2005, 288 pages.
10. Roșca Ludmila. *Filosofia. Ghidul afacerii de succes*. Institutul de Relații Internationale din Moldova. Chișinău: Tipografia „Print-Caro”, 2013, 324 p.
11. Vianu Tudor. *Studii de filosofia culturii*. București: Editura Eminescu, 1982, 472 p.

Copyright©Carolina DODU-SAVCA

Le Cosmopolitisme européen de Rousseau

MCF. Dr. Snezana PETROVA

snezanapetrov@me.com

Université «Saints Cyrille et Méthode» de Skopje, Macédoine

Abstract: No writer of his time was by his Genevan origins as well prepared to create a union between Latin Europe and Germanic Europe. In fact “Geneva has always been a land of predilection for Anglomaniacs and without crediting this fact as a direct influence to the formation of the genius of Jean-Jacques, one can still note - as he has aligned himself so highly with his Genevan origin - that his country owed much to the English genius itself. However, whatever Geneva owes to the English genius, it is not but a small part of what it owes to the Germanic genius”. For this Northern Europe and that of the South - as they were identified in many writings of that time, Rousseau was a European channeler with his art and his genius. Rousseau used to say: “nowadays, there are no more French, Germans, Spaniards, even English, whatever people may say; there are only Europeans”. Is there any assertion more real than this one, when it has been said in the 18th century? Did Rousseau predict with these words, the creation of the European Union?

Key-words: Rousseau, cosmopolitanism, Europe, European, state, union, national genius.

Le génie national et européen

Nul écrivain de son époque n’a été, par ses origines genevoises, aussi bien préparé à faire l’union entre l’Europe latine et l’Europe germanique. En fait «Genève a donc toujours été, pour les anglomanes, une terre de prédilection, et, sans attribuer à ce fait une influence directe sur la formation du génie de Jean-Jacques, on peut noter cependant - puisqu’il s’est réclamé si haut de son origine genevoise – ce que sa patrie devait elle-même au génie anglais. Mais ce que Genève doit au génie anglais n’est qu’une part de ce qu’elle doit au génie germanique»¹. Pour cette Europe du Nord et celle du Midi - telles qu’elles étaient identifiées dans bien des écrits de cette époque, Rousseau a été un canalisateur européen par son art et par son génie. Rousseau disait: «il n’y a plus aujourd'hui de Français, d’Allemands, d’Espagnols, d’Anglais même, quoi qu’on en dise; il n’y a que

¹ Texte Joseph, *Jean-Jacques Rousseau et les origines du cosmopolitisme littéraire*, p. 108.

des Européens. Quoi de plus réelles affirmations que celles-ci alors qu'elles ont été dites au XVIIIe siècle? Est-ce que Rousseau prédisait par ces dires la formation de l'Union européenne?

Jean-Jacques Rousseau est un écrivain-philosophe observateur, contemplatif, un rêveur, qui fut en son temps désabusé par les questions politiques et sociales. La pensée de Rousseau est obsédante, révoltée et révoltante; une de celles qui ont vu le jour au XVIIIe siècle français; au siècle des Lumières. Cependant, il n'est peut être pas un auteur qui a laissé pour les temps à venir autant d'impressions qu'un Voltaire ou un Montesquieu dans le domaine politique, domaine qui au cours du XVIIIe siècle était indissociable de la littérature dite «militante», mais il est loin d'avoir été absent de la vie littéraire et de la recherche. Il est un penseur politique des plus complexes et des plus ambigus de l'histoire de la philosophie et des nations occidentales. D'ailleurs si nous abordons la question de l'histoire de la nature et du monde, combien ses propres propos sont véridiques, actuels et pénétrants: «Toute la terre est couverte de nations dont nous ne connaissons que les noms, et nous nous mêlons de juger le genre humain! Supposons un Montesquieu, un Buffon, un Diderot, un d'Alembert, un Condillac, ou des hommes de cette trempe, voyageant pour instruire leurs compatriotes, observant et décrivant comme ils savent le faire, la Turquie, l'Égypte, la Barbarie, l'Empire du Maroc, la Guinée, le pays des Caffres, l'intérieur de l'Afrique et ses côtes orientales, les Malabares, le Mogol, les rives du Gange, les royaumes de Siam, de Pégu et d'Ava, la Chine, la Tartarie et surtout le Japon; puis dans l'autre hémisphère le Mexique, le Pérou, le Chili, les terres Magellaniques, sans oublier les Patagons vrais ou faux, le Tucuman, le Paraguay, s'il était possible le Brésil, enfin les Caraïbes, la Floride et toutes les contrées sauvages; voyage le plus important de tous et qu'il faudrait faire avec le plus de soin. Supposons que ces nouveaux Hercules, de retour de ces courses mémorables, fissent ensuite à loisir l'histoire naturelle, morale et politique de ce qu'ils auraient vu, nous verrions nous-mêmes sortir un monde nouveau de dessous leur plume, et nous apprendrions ainsi à connaître le nôtre»¹.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau a autant contribué que ses contemporains à

¹ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *Œuvres complètes*, Tome huitième, *Discours sur l'inégalité*. p. 284.

ce brassage d'idées et de points de vue qui caractérise son époque; lesquels d'ailleurs sont toujours aussi actuels au sein de notre société «mondialisante» du XXI siècle. Nous nous confrontons toujours et encore à des problèmes et des questionnements similaires sinon identiques et nous essayons encore et toujours de trouver la solution idéale et unitaire.

L'Europe d'antan formait déjà une unité, sous le nom d'Empire romain, de religion chrétienne, mais depuis le XVIII siècle cette unité est bouleversée. Ainsi, sur d'autres bases, d'unique elle devient plurielle mais constitutive d'un tout commun. Cela entend que nous avons donc certaines distinctions, certaines mœurs qui persistent et qui nous qualifient, des coutumes et des habitudes qui nous identifient et qui font que nous soyons quelque peu différents au sein même de cette union qu'est l'Europe. D'ailleurs Rousseau ajoute: «Ce sont les institutions nationales qui forment le génie, le caractère, les goûts et les mœurs d'un peuple, qui le font être lui et non pas un autre, qui lui inspirent cet ardent amour de la patrie fondé sur des habitudes impossibles à déraciner, qui le font mourir d'ennui chez les autres peuples au sein des délices dont il est privé dans le sien»¹.

«L'Europe est le plus morcelé des continents», disait Hume; «c'est en cela que réside sa nouvelle unité et c'est pour cela qu'elle a pu engendrer les Lumières».

Si l'on réfléchit bien, l'Europe d'antan a créé les Lumières mais c'est surtout grâce au cosmopolitisme des auteurs de ce siècle, de ces grands philosophes que l'Europe s'est «illuminée» de pareils feux. Le fait de parcourir différentes contrées, de rencontrer d'autres peuples, d'autres civilisations, d'apprendre et de parler leur langue, de séjourner dans différents pays par choix ou par nécessités, a bouleversé l'état d'esprit et de pensées de bien d'hommes. Ainsi, par ces migrations, des écrivains et philosophes français se sont fait connaître non seulement dans leur terroir, en France, mais plus loin encore, ce qui les a fait bénéficier d'une renommée européenne si ce n'est plus. Cette communion de différents esprits et savoirs, de différentes confrontations et réflexions, a constitué les fondations de l'Europe occidentale. Ainsi, les unités constituées par chaque pays – la France, l'Allemagne, le catholicisme, etc. – devenaient un tout mais avec les différences de chacun. C'est cette unité que les Lumières ont réussi

¹ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *Œuvres complètes*, Volume 1, p.706.

à construire et en analysant et observant d'autres pays ils ont réussi à mieux comprendre le leur, leurs institutions, leurs coutumes. «Quand on veut étudier les hommes, il faut regarder près de soi, mais pour étudier l'homme, il faut apprendre à porter sa vue au loin; il faut d'abord observer les différences pour découvrir les propriétés»¹.

«Sans l'Europe, pas de Lumières; mais sans les Lumières, pas d'Europe».

Cependant, Jean-Jacques Rousseau porte un regard probant mais toutefois désabusé sur le côté idéaliste de l'union des États d'Europe. Sa pensée pointe la complexité de la construction européenne voyant avant tous les autres, avant tous les philosophes, grands penseurs et gouvernements, les obstacles et les dangers du système politique où les pensées seraient unifiées. L'Union politique porte cette complexité «idéalisante» d'un peuple libre, mais qui, sur le terrain est partagé et mis à parti entre des gouvernants qui eux-mêmes sont écartelés entre européisme et souverainisme.

Rousseau a compris bien avant l'heure la complexité de la tâche de formation de cette Europe des nations. Ses écrits sur l'Abbé de Saint Pierre comme ses *Considérations sur le gouvernement de Pologne*, canalisent ses réflexions à ce sujet et montre son regard désabusé sur la création de cette Europe. L'union de différents peuples en une même entité européenne, selon Rousseau, doit avant tout être précédée de l'obtention de la liberté du peuple laquelle sera garantie par son législateur, mais aussi par l'émancipation de l'homme de ses passions car selon Rousseau ce sont justement les passions qui ont rapproché les hommes les uns des autres et qui ont constitué la société.

Le modèle européen élaboré par Rousseau n'a malheureusement pas été compris de la même façon par Robespierre, Fouquier ou autres révolutionnaires français qui d'éducateurs du peuple comme ils devaient l'être en tant que fondateurs de cette union, sont devenus de vrais dictateurs sanglants au nom de la vertu et de la nation. C'est un fait logique mais purement révolutionnaire qui fait de Rousseau un homme moderne mais qui ne plaît aucunement aux soi-disant représentants de la démocratie. Ces derniers, tels Sieyès et Robespierre, sous la Révolution auraient

¹ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *Essai sur l'origine des langues*, Ch. 8.

certainement préféré substituer l'assemblée, le club, au peuple. Il est facile de comprendre pourquoi à cette époque on aurait voulu se défaire de Rousseau car non seulement il voulait donner la souveraineté au peuple mais aussi la légitimité. En proclamant l'identité de la souveraineté du peuple et de la volonté générale, J.-J. Rousseau sacralisait le pouvoir du peuple, qui n'est plus seulement un principe politique mais un principe moral. Déléguer son pouvoir de la volonté, c'est l'aliénation. Déléguer le pouvoir de la décision; c'est nécessairement différer la délibération et si nous suivons la réflexion de Rousseau, ce ne serait pas le peuple lui-même mais l'assemblée de ses représentants qui délibérerait. En fait, c'est dans la délibération que les volontés particulières se généralisent. En tenant les citoyens à l'écart de la délibération, on inhibe la formation d'une «raison publique». On la dégrade en opinion. Inversement, la participation des citoyens au processus délibératif est le principal vecteur de formation d'une opinion publique éclairée, donc informée.

Entre autre, Rousseau témoigne aussi du fait que tout est affaire de passion. Ce sont les passions humaines qui sont corrompues dans une société. Selon lui, une union pourrait exister si elle répond à un traité, à un «contrat social» lequel garantirait la souveraineté nationale. A ce propos, l'Abbé de Saint-Pierre voyait les choses autrement et estimait que les pays sont beaucoup plus enclin à faire la guerre que la paix et que cette dernière ne peut persister que dans la création d'un droit public de l'Europe. Tout conflit serait réglé ou du moins discuté par voie d'arbitrage ou de jugement lors d'un congrès ou d'une assemblée permanente des États qui serait présidé par les souverains eux-mêmes mais à tour de rôle. Rousseau ne voit pas les choses de cet œil estimant que cela ne garantit en rien la liberté du peuple et la paix de l'Etat. Dans ses propos, l'Abbé de Saint Pierre avait même fixé les limites frontalières de cette union, où les Turcs en seraient exclus. Cette question frontalière de l'union est a fortiori d'actualité puisque la candidature de la Turquie à l'Union européenne se heurte aujourd'hui encore à des réticences en Europe occidentale pour différentes raisons avouées ou non avouées.

Cette vision d'une unité des Etats paraît idéale, mais au XVIII siècle elle n'est encore que trop fragile et même illusoire ce qu'a prouvé Rousseau en pointant du doigt le joug encore trop important de la féodalité, de l'honneur par l'épée et le sang au nom de la patrie et de la religion. Il avait

déjà pressenti la difficulté de la mise en œuvre d'une véritable citoyenneté européenne qui sous-entend une unité nationale mais aussi universelle. Lui qui s'imaginait un européisme en tant que pacifisme et universalisme s'est rapidement vu désenchanté.

Selon Rousseau, les gouvernants sont encore trop guidés par leurs passions, par leur intérêt personnel ou par les intérêts de leur nation et qu'ils ne peuvent atteindre l'universel. Pour faire une union politique des Etats d'Europe, le peuple européen doit être souverain avec des visions universelles ce qui n'est pas maintes affaires de par la personnalité de chacun et de son état social. Combat pipé de l'homme social sur l'homme civil. Le premier est enclin à la notion de propriété qui annihile son côté naturel. C'est pourquoi, Rousseau voit l'unité politique des États d'Europe telle une utopie qui n'est ni réalisable ni souhaitable. Le peuple ou le citoyen européen se laisserait bien plus guidé par ses passions que par ses devoirs. Pour lui, seul un projet raisonnable, impulsé par des hommes de raison pourrait peut-être donner forme à cet Etat-nations.

La construction de l'Europe ne s'est pas faite du jour au lendemain. L'idée a foisonné pendant des années, s'est couverte de différents manteaux plus ou moins adaptés et de différentes teintes. Il a fallu passer par la Révolution française, les différents moments politiques de l'histoire de France, par les guerres mondiales et l'impulsion des pères fondateurs ou dirigeants visionnaires, mais la question d'une finalité politique se pose depuis toujours et encore, des années même après la signature du fameux traité de Rome. Notre visionnaire de Rousseau en avait bien avant l'heure compris les enjeux et les obstacles. La portée universelle d'une unité politique contractuelle reste encore un but à atteindre où les hommes seraient les premiers à payer.

L'unité européenne et la littérature

La réflexion de l'unité européenne n'était pas seulement visible dans les grandes salles de réunion lors des assemblées, l'idée d'une unité européenne s'est aussi et surtout forgée par et dans les livres. De par les courants d'idées qui se développent dans un pays, de par les tendances qui se manifestent dans un autre, de par l'influence d'une nation sur une autre, en littérature, au XVIII siècle, nous avons dépassé le stade de simple imitation ou adaptation des œuvres des anciens. Ainsi, cette imitation des œuvres antiques (caractéristique théorique du classicisme), ne

correspondait-elle plus aux besoins du moment, aux réflexions, aux courants d'opinions, aux idées qui circulent d'auteur à auteurs, de peuple à peuples, d'un pays européen à un autre, si ce n'est plus loin encore. C'est ainsi qu'un bon nombre d'études analytiques, philosophiques, d'œuvres littéraires françaises ont traversé nos frontières et que d'autres sont entrées par les mêmes portes ou par des portes différentes. C'est aussi de cette façon que le roman anglais trouva sa place en Allemagne, en France, dans les pays du Nord comme dans ceux du Sud, répondant à la nouveauté par la nouveauté, une œuvre libre de toutes contraintes antiques ou traditionnelles; véritable épopée du monde moderne.

L'influence du cosmopolitisme, de l'exotisme qui était abordé un peu plus haut dans notre sujet, s'opposait en beaucoup de points à l'humanisme et au classicisme français. D'ailleurs ce cosmopolitisme peut être vu comme origine du nouveau mouvement littéraire qu'est le romantisme: «Il est vrai que les romantiques ont déchainé, si je puis dire, le cosmopolitisme en France, mais le maître de tous les romantiques – et celui de Mme de Staël, à celui dont ils n'ont fait que formuler les aspirations et développer l'influence, c'est Rousseau»¹. Rousseau faisait trembler l'hégémonie de la littérature française au profit de l'anglaise et de l'allemande par la science, la philosophie mais aussi par le théâtre et le roman. Unificateur et pacificateur des deux Europe, celle du Nord et celle du Midi, il nous a mené vers un nouveau mouvement littéraire; le romantisme. Ainsi, les nouveaux esprits français, ceux des Lumières, et particulièrement Rousseau, nous ont fait découvrir par leur cosmopolitisme le «génie du Nord» comme l'appelait Mme de Staël; cosmopolitisme qui avec les années et surtout avec cette écrivaine est devenu un point important de la théorie littéraire romantique. Cette ouverture d'esprit envers les littératures étrangères et particulièrement anglaises insuffla une tendance nouvelle, une protestation contre l'esprit classique contre tout ce qui est réglé pour laisser la place à la sensibilité et au sentiment. La question de la sensibilité et celle de la capacité à imaginer sont primordiales dans la réflexion de Rousseau. Elles sont des qualités générales qui fondent l'égalité par delà les distinctions sociales, et donc caractérisent l'homme. Ce dernier ne doit pas s'illusionner sur sa nature et faire un mauvais usage de la raison qui ne peut le rendre

¹ Introduction, p.X.

que malheureux. Donc l'homme se caractérise par une sensibilité à la fois physique et morale. Cette sensibilité est un amour de soi qui fait rechercher son bien-être et satisfaire ses besoins. L'homme n'étant pas uniquement un animal, il développe sa sensibilité morale dans les relations à autrui. Ainsi, l'amour de soi, non corrompu par l'inégalité, engendre naturellement l'amour d'autrui.

La migration intellectuelle qui s'est produite au XVIII^e siècle a fait que la «voix» littéraire française s'est entremêlée à celle de l'Angleterre, de l'Allemagne etc., et par cela il s'est forgé un nouveau génie national. La critique et cette évolution a mené la France vers d'autres «voies» plus cosmopolites; des voies «européennes». Rousseau a ainsi légué à la postérité l'individualisme, le «moi», la rêverie solitaire, le désir, l'esprit de révolte; en un mot le romantisme. Les auteurs tels que Chateaubriand, Mme de Staël, Senancour, Benjamin Constant mais encore Lamartine, Hugo, Musset, etc., n'ont eu qu'à s'accaparer et épanouir cette matrice. Qu'auront été ces auteurs sans la combativité, les réflexions et points de vue, sans les études et surtout sans les nouveautés fortement révolutionnaires de Rousseau?

L'influence de Rousseau ne s'est pas exercée uniquement sur des auteurs français mais au nom du cosmopolitisme sur des auteurs étrangers tels Goethe, Schiller, Byron, sur Kant, Jacobi, Schleiermacher et même sur Tolstoï. Aujourd'hui encore, ses écrits font mouche par sa vision du monde et surtout par sa sensibilité du cœur.

Conclusion

Le regard que Rousseau a porté sur son temps, sur ses connaissances et ses injustices, n'est peut être pas franchement le nôtre cependant les réflexions qu'il a mené sur l'homme naturel, sur l'homme civilisé et la corruption de celui-ci par la civilisation, la question relative au bien fondé de la société, sur l'Europe et l'universalisme sont encore d'actualité. Rousseau peut nous mener à réfléchir autrement, à nous ouvrir à d'autres manières de penser et de voir la nature de l'homme. D'ailleurs, il nous dit: «Tous dans les mêmes circonstances, feront les mêmes choses; tous se diront désintéressés et seront fripons; tous parleront du bien public et ne penseront qu'à eux-mêmes ; tous vanteront la médiocrité et voudront être des Crésus; ils n'ont d'ambition que pour le luxe, ils n'ont de passion que

celle de l'or»¹. Il continue de la sorte: «Que leur importe à quel maître ils obéissent, de quel État ils suivent les lois? Pourvu qu'ils trouvent de l'argent à voler et des femmes à corrompre, ils sont partout dans leur pays»². Qu'ajouter de plus à cela...

Bibliographie:

1. Brunetiere Ferdinand. *Etudes critiques sur l'histoire de la littérature française*, troisième série. Paris: Librairie Hachette et Cie, 1898.
2. Chuquet Arthur. *Les grands écrivains français; J.-J. Rousseau*, Paris: Librairie Hachette et Cie, 1919.
3. Cresson André. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau, sa vie, son œuvre avec un exposé de sa philosophie*. Paris: PUF, 1950
4. Gillouin René. *Une Nouvelle Philosophie de l'Histoire Moderne et Française*. Paris: Grasset, 1920.
5. Guéhennon Jean. *Jean-Jacques, en marge des «Confessions»*. Paris: Grasset, 1948.
6. Guéhennon Jean. *Jean-Jacques roman et vérité*. Paris: Grasset, 1950.
7. Rousseau Jean-Jacques. *Oeuvres complètes; Considérations sur le gouvernement de Pologne et sur sa réformation projetée*. Paris, 1836. [Ressource disponible en-ligne] URL: <https://books.google.mk/books?id=BuIFAAAIAAJ&pg=PA706&lpg=PA706&dq=Tous+dans+les+mêmes+circonstances+feront+les+mêmes+choses%3B+tous+se+diront+désintéressés+et+seront+fripons&source=bl&ots=8ZoLnrjof&sig=i3wTpDHNin0alm3h07UK7AUhTCA&hl=fr&sa=X&ei=5JErVazSD8bRywO6lYL4CA&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Tous%20dans%20les%20mêmes%20circonstances%20feront%20les%20mêmes%20choses%3B%20tous%20se%20diront%20désintéressés%20et%20seront%20fripons&f=false> [Consulté le 12 mars 2015].
8. Rousseau Jean-Jacques. *Essai sur l'origine des langues*, Ch. 8, 1761 (publié en 1781),
9. Rousseau Jean-Jacques. *Œuvres complètes*, Tome huitième, *Discours sur l'inégalité*. Paris, 1819; Notes, p.284. [Ressource disponible en-ligne]

¹ Jean-Jacques Rousseau. *Oeuvres complètes; Considérations sur le gouvernement de Pologne et sur sa réformation projetée*, p.706.

² *Ibidem*, p.706.

URL:

<<https://books.google.mk/books?id=KmnAlYqIvwcC&pg=PA321&dq=l%27histoire+naturelle,+morale+et+politique+de+ce+qu%27ils+auraient+vu,+nous+verrions+nous-mêmes+sortir+un+monde+nouveau+de+dessous+leur+plume,+et+nous+apprendrions+ainsi+à+connaître+le+nôtre&hl=fr&sa=X&ei=ZXgrVaapM4v8ywOLjoHACA&ved=0CCYQ6AEwAg#v=onepage&q=l%27histoire%20naturelle%2C%20morale%20et%20politique%20de%20ce%20qu%27ils%20auraient%20vu%2C%20nous%20verrions%20nous-mêmes%20sortir%20un%20monde%20nouveau%20de%20dessous%20leur%20plume%2C%20et%20nous%20apprendrions%20ainsi%20à%20connaître%20le%20nôtre&f=false>> [Consulté le 14 avril 2015].

10. Mornet Daniel. *Rousseau*. Paris: Hatier, 1950.
11. Howlett Marc-Vincent. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau; L'homme qui croyait en l'homme*. Paris: Découvertes, Gallimard littérature, 1989.
12. Lemaitre Jules. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau*. Paris: éditeurs Calmann-Lévy, 1905
13. Schinz Albert. *Etat présent des travaux sur J.-J. Rousseau*. Paris: Société d'édition les Belles Lettres, 1941.
14. Schinw Albert. *La pensée de Jean-Jacques Rousseau, essai d'interprétation nouvelle*. Paris: Librairie Félix Alcan, 1929.
15. Texte Joseph. *Jean-Jacques Rousseau et les origines du cosmopolitisme littéraire*. Paris: Hachette, 1895.
16. Tornesy A. *La légende des «Philosophes», Voltaire, Rousseau, Diderot peint par eux-mêmes*. Paris: Librairie académique Perrin et Cie, 1911.

Copyright©Snezana PETROVA

WHO'S WHO

Consiliul onorific

Președinte:

Dusan SIDJANSKI

Profesor emerit, Facultatea de Științe Economice și Sociale, Institutul European, Universitatea din Geneva, Geneva, Elveția

Președinte de onoare, Centrul Cultural European, Geneva, Elveția

Fondator, Departamentul de Științe Politice, Universitatea din Geneva, Geneva, Elveția

Membru, Consiliul Directorilor al Fundației Latsis, Geneva, Elveția

Vicepreședinte:

Ioan HORGA

Profesor universitar, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Decan, Facultatea de Istorie, Relații internaționale, Științe Politice și ale Comunicării, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Director, Institutul de Studii Euroregionale (ISER) Oradea-Debrecen – Centrul European de Excelență Jean Monnet, Oradea-Debrecen, România-Ungaria

Secretar General, Asociația Universitară a Regiunii Carpatice (ACRU), Cașovia, Slovacia

Expert, Agenția Română de Asigurare a Calității în Învățământul Superior, București, România

Vicepreședinte, ECSA-România, București, România

Președinte, Fundația Forum Oradea, Oradea, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Membri:

Francisco ALDECOA LUZÁRRAGA

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Științe Politice și Sociologie, Universitatea Complutense din Madrid, Madrid, Spania

Co-director, Centrul European de Excelență Jean Monnet „Antonio Truyol”, Universitatea Complutense din Madrid, Madrid, Spania

Director, Revista „Tiempo de Paz”, Madrid, Spania

Profesor Jean Monnet

Carlos Eduardo PACHECO AMARAL

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Istorie, Filosofie și Științe Sociale, Universitatea din Azore, Ponta Delgada, Portugalia

Președinte, Consiliul Academic, Universitatea din Azore, Ponta Delgada, Portugalia

Director, Programul de Studii Europene și Științe Politice Internaționale, Universitatea din Azore, Ponta Delgada, Portugalia

Coordonator, Centrul de Studii Europene, Universitatea din Azore, Ponta Delgada, Portugalia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Alexandru ARSENI

Legislator moldovean

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea de Stat din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Avocat, Baroul Chișinău, Chișinău, Moldova

Enrique Lorenzo BANÚS IRUSTA

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Studii Umaniste, Universitatea Internațională din Catalonia, Barcelona, Spania

Director, Institutul de Studii Europene „Charlemagne”, Universitatea Internațională din Catalonia, Barcelona, Spania

Președinte, ECSA-World, Damme, Belgia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Iordan Gheorghe BĂRBULESCU

Diplomat român

Profesor universitar, Școala Națională de Studii Politice și Administrative, București, România

Decan, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Integrare Europeană, Școala Națională de Studii Politice și Administrative, București, România

Președintele Senatului, Școala Națională de Studii Politice și Administrative, București, România

Coordonator științific, Colecția „Politici publice și integrare europeană”, Editura Polirom, Iași, România

Expert, Agenția Română de Asigurare a Calității în Învățământul Superior,
București, România
Președinte, ECSA-România, București, România
Profesor Jean Monnet

Georges CONTOGEOGRIS

Ministru grec
Rector grec
Profesor universitar, Universitatea Panteion din Atena, Atena, Grecia
Coordonator, Programul de Masterat în Studii Europene, Universitatea
Panteion din Atena, Atena, Grecia
Director științific, Centrul Național de Cercetări Științifice, Paris, Franța
Membru, Rețeaua Europeană de Științe Politice, Wicklow, Irlanda
Profesor Jean Monnet

Ioan DERȘIDAN

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Litere, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea,
România
Membru, Consiliul Departamentului de Limba și Literatura Română,
Facultatea de Litere, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Gaga GABRICHIDZE

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea Noua Viziune, Tbilisi,
Georgia
Decan, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea Noua Viziune, Tbilisi, Georgia
Președinte, ECSA-Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia
Profesor Jean Monnet

Nico GROENENDIJK

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Științe Sociale și Management,
Universitatea Twente, Enschede, Olanda
Co-director, Centrul de Studii Europene, Universitatea Twente, Enschede,
Olanda
Membru, Adunarea Regiunilor Europene, Strasbourg, Franța
Președinte, Curtea de Conturi, Hengelo, Olanda
Președinte, ECSA-Olanda, Enschede, Olanda

Profesor Jean Monnet

Wilfried HELLER

Profesor emerit, Institutul de Geografie, Universitatea din Potsdam, Potsdam, Germania

Membru, Centrul de Cercetări al Legăturilor Germane cu Noua Zeelandă și Țările Pacificului, Universitatea din Auckland, Noua Zeelandă

Victor JUC

Profesor cercetător, Institutul de Cercetări Juridice și Politice, Academia de Științe din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Director adjunct, Institutul de Cercetări Juridice și Politice, Academia de Științe din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Expert, Comisia de Evaluare, Academia de Științe din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Anatoliy KRUGLASHOV

Profesor universitar, Catedra de Științe Politice, Universitatea Națională „Juriy Fedkovych” din Cernăuți, Ucraina

Șef, Catedra de Științe Politice, Universitatea Națională „Juriy Fedkovych” din Cernăuți, Ucraina

Director, Institutul de Integrare Europeană și Studii Regionale, Universitatea Națională „Juriy Fedkovych” din Cernăuți, Ucraina

Profesor Jean Monnet

Ariane LANDUYT

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Științe Politice, Universitatea din Siena, Siena, Italia

Director, Centrul de Cercetări în domeniul Integrării Europene, Universitatea din Siena, Siena, Italia

Director, Programul de Masterat în Studii Europene, Universitatea din Siena, Siena, Italia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Ewa LATOSZEK

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Științe Socio-Umane, Școala de Economie din Varșovia, Varșovia, Polonia

Expert, H2020, Bruxelles, Belgia

Expert, PC7, Bruxelles, Belgia

Președinte, PECSA, Varșovia, Polonia

Vice-Președinte, ECSA-World, Damme, Belgia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Ani MATEI

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Administrație Publică, Școala Națională de Studii Politice și Administrative, București, România

Secretar General, Comisia Națională a României pentru UNESCO, București, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Elena PRUS

Director, Institutul de Cercetări Filologice și Interculturale, Chișinău, Moldova

Redactor-șef, Revista „Intertext”, Chișinău, Moldova

Expert, Biroul Europa Centrală și Orientală, Agenția Universitară a Francofoniei, București, România

Maria Manuela TAVARES RIBEIRO

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Litere, Universitatea din Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugalia

Profesor universitar, Centrul de Studii Interdisciplinare, Universitatea din Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugalia

Coordonator, Programul de Masterat în Studii Europene, Universitatea din Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugalia

Director, Programul de Doctorat în Studii Europene, Universitatea din Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugalia

Membu corespondent, Academia de Științe din Lisabona, Lisabona, Portugalia

Membu, ECSA-Portugalia, Lisabona, Portugalia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Grigore SILAȘI

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Științe Economice, Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, Timișoara, România

Director, Centrul European de Excelență Jean Monnet, Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, Timișoara, România

Expert, Agenția Română de Asigurare a Calității în Învățământul Superior, București, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

István SÜLI-ZAKAR

Profesor universitar, Departamentul de Geografie Socială și Dezvoltare Regională, Universitatea din Debrecen, Debrecen, Ungaria

Profesor Emeritus, Departamentul de Geografie Socială și Dezvoltare Regională, Universitatea din Debrecen, Debrecen, Ungaria

Membru, Academia Ungară de Științe, Budapesta, Ungaria

Mihai ȘLEAHIȚCHI

Profesor universitar, Institutul de Științe ale Educației, Chișinău, Moldova

Cercetător științific coordonator, Institutul de Științe ale Educației, Chișinău, Moldova

Consilier al Președintelui Moldovei pentru Educație, Cercetare și Cultură, Chișinău, Moldova

Comitetul științific

Președinte:

Tudorel TOADER

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași, Iași, România

Decan, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași, Iași, România

Director, Școala Doctorală, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași, Iași, România

Coordonator, Seria de publicații juridice JUS, Editura Junimea, Iași, România

Membru, Consiliul științific, Institutul Național al Magistraturii, București, România

Membru, Asociația Internațională de Drept Penal, Paris, Franța

Membru, Asociația Română de Drept Constituțional, Iași, România

Membru de onoare, Consiliul științific, Institutul de Cercetări Juridice „Acad. Andrei Rădulescu”, Academia Română, București, România

Judecător, Curtea Constituțională a României, București, România

Vicepreședinte:

Marta PACHOCKA

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Științe Socio-Umane, Școala de Economie din Varșovia, Varșovia, Polonia

Membru, Societatea Economică Poloneză, Varșovia, Polonia

Membru, Asociația Academică de Studii Europene Contemporane, Varșovia, Polonia

Secretar-General, PECSA, Varșovia, Polonia

Membri:

Mircea BRIE

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Istorie, Relații Internaționale, Științe Politice și ale Comunicării, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Director, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Redactor-șef, Analele Universității din Oradea, Seria Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene, Oradea, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Paulo Jorge TAVARES CANELAS DE CASTRO

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea din Macau, Macau, China

Coordonator general, Programul de Masterat și Studii Postuniversitare în Dreptul Uniunii Europene, Dreptul Internațional și Dreptul Comparat, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea din Macau, Macau, China

Membru, Asociația de Drept European și Economie, Coimbra, Portugalia

Membru, Asociația de Drept Internațional, Londra, Marea Britanie

Președinte, ECSA-Macau, Macau, China

Profesor Jean Monnet

Georgeta CISLARU

Conferențiar universitar, Centrul de Lingvistică Franceză, Universitatea Paris 3 Sorbonne Nouvelle, Paris, Franța

Membru, Comitetul de redacție „Les Carnets du Cediscor”, SYLED-CEDISCOR, Universitatea Paris 3 Sorbonne Nouvelle, Paris, Franța

Simion COSTEA

Conferențiar universitar, Departamentul de Istorie și Relații Internaționale, Universitatea „Petru Maior” din Târgu-Mureș, Târgu-Mureș, România

Redactor-șef, Revista „L’Europe unie”, Paris, Franța

Expert, Comisia Europeană, Bruxelles, Belgia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Dorin DOLGHI

Lector universitar, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Redactor-șef, „Romanian Journal of Security Studies”, Oradea, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Sedef EYLEMER

Conferențiar universitar, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale, Facultatea de Științe Economice și Administrative, Universitatea „Katip Celebi” din Izmir, Izmir, Turcia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Aurelian LAVRIC

Conferențiar universitar, Academia Militară „Alexandru cel Bun”, Chișinău, Moldova

Cercetător științific superior, Centrul de Studii Strategice de Apărare și Securitate, Academia Militară „Alexandru cel Bun”, Chișinău, Moldova

Cristina-Maria MATIUȚĂ

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Istorie, Relații Internaționale, Științe Politice și ale Comunicării, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Director, Departamentul de Științe Politice și ale Comunicării, Facultatea de Istorie, Relații Internaționale, Științe Politice și ale Comunicării, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Membru, Centrul de Studii pe Problemele Identității și Migrației, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Membru, Societatea Română de Științe Politice, București, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Giancarlo NICOLI

Director, Centrul Cultural Italian, Chișinău, Moldova

Redactor-șef, Revista „IL PONTE”, Chișinău, Moldova

Președinte, Moldova Film Commission, Chișinău, Moldova

Mihaela Narcisa NIEMCZIK-ARAMBAȘA

Cercetător, Institutul de Geografie, Universitatea din Potsdam, Potsdam, Germania

Expert, Consiliere Interculturală, Potsdam, Germania

Danielle OMER

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Litere, Limbi și Științe Umaniste, Universitatea din Maine, Le Mans, Franța

Cercetător, Școala Doctorală „Cognition, Education, Interactions”, Pôle Manceaux „Innovation en didactique”, Le Mans, Franța

Membru, Centrul de Cercetări în Științele Educației din Nantes, Nantes, Franța

Marco OROFINO

Conferențiar universitar, Departamentul de Studii Internaționale, Juridice, Istorice și Politice, Universitatea din Milano, Milano, Italia
Profesor Jean Monnet

Saverina PASHO

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Limbi Străine, Universitatea din Tirana, Tirana, Albania
Vicepreședinte, Alianța Franceză din Albania, Tirana, Albania
Membru, Comitetul Științific al Revistei „Travaux de didactique du FLE”,
Universitatea Paul Valery – Montpellier 3, Montpellier, Franța

Snezana PETROVA

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Filologie „Blaze Koneski”,
Universitatea „Sf. Chiril și Metodie”, Skopje, Macedonia
Coordonator ECTS, Facultatea de Filologie „Blaze Koneski”, Universitatea „Sf.
Chiril și Metodie”, Skopje, Macedonia
Președinte, Asociația Profesorilor de Limba Franceză din Macedonia, Skopje,
Macedonia

Vadim PISTRINCIUC

Legislator moldovean
Lector universitar, Facultatea de Sociologie și Asistență Socială,
Universitatea de Stat din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Galina POGONET

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Institutul de Relații
Internaționale din Moldova
Decan, Facultatea de Drept, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova
Avocat, Baroul Chișinău, Chișinău, Moldova

István József POLGÁR

Lector universitar, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Studii
Europene, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România
Profesor Jean Monnet

Ada-Iuliana POPESCU

Lector universitar, Facultatea de Economie și Administrarea Afacerilor,
Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași, Iași, România

Avocat, Baroul Iași, Iași, România

Membru, Uniunea Avocaților din România, București, România

Membru, American Bar Association, Chicago, Statele Unite ale Americii

Lehte ROOTS

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea Tehnică din
Tallinn, Tallinn, Estonia

Șef, Catedra de Drept Public, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea Tehnică din
Tallinn, Tallinn, Estonia

Membru, Asociația Avocaților din Estonia, Tallinn, Estonia

Membru, Consiliul pentru Refugiați din Estonia, Tallinn, Estonia

Vicepreședinte, ECSA-Estonia, Tallinn, Estonia

Profesor Jean Monnet

Alina STOICA

Lector universitar, Departamentul de Relații Internaționale și Studii
Europene, Universitatea din Oradea, Oradea, România

Profesor Jean Monnet

Aleksandra SZCZERBA-ZAWADA

Conferențiar universitar, Universitatea de Management din Varșovia,
Varșovia, Polonia

Membru, PECSA, Varșovia, Polonia

Zorina ȘIȘCAN

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Relații Economice Internaționale,
Academia de Studii Economice din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Expert, EUBAM, Chișinău, Moldova

Membru, Assorts Experts Team, Bruxelles, Belgia

Beatrice ȘTEFĂNESCU

Lector universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea „Mihail Kogălniceanu”,
Iași, România
Judecător, Judecătoria Iași, Iași, România

Alexis VAHLAS

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Științe Politice și
Management, Universitatea din Strasbourg, Franța
Director, Programul de Masterat în Studii de Securitate Externă și Internă a
Uniunii Europene, Institutul de Studii Politice din Strasbourg, Franța

Diego VARELA PEDREIRA

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Științe Economice și Business,
Universitatea din A Coruña, Spania
Editor executiv, „European Journal of Government and Economics”, A
Coruña, Spania
Profesor Jean Monnet

Khaydarali YUNUSOV

Lector superior, Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea de Economie Mondială și
Diplomație, Tașkent, Uzbekistan
Membru, Societatea Uzbekă de Drept Internațional, Tașkent, Uzbekistan
Membru, Asociația Americană de Drept Internațional, Washington, Statele
Unite ale Americii
Profesor Jean Monnet

Colegiul redacțional

Editor:

Vasile CUCERESCU

Președinte, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Profesor Jean Monnet

Redactor-șef:

Carolina DODU-SAVCA

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Limbi Străine, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Șef de catedră, Catedra de Filologie Franceză, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Moldova

Coordonator, Centrul European pentru Dialog Intercultural, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Membri, Alianța Franceză din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Redactor-șef adjunct:

Mihai HACHI

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Relații Economice Internaționale, Academia de Studii Economice din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Cercetător științific coordonator, Institutul de Ecologie și Geografie, Academia de Științe, Chișinău, Moldova

Coordonator, Centrul European de Studii Economice, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Membri:

Ion BURUIANĂ

Conferențiar universitar, Facultatea de Drept, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Cercetător, Institutul de Cercetări Juridice și Politice, Academia de Științe, Chișinău, Moldova

Coordonator, Centrul European pentru Drepturile Omului, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Avocat, Baroul Chișinău, Chișinău, Moldova

Profesor Jean Monnet

Violeta MELNIC

Conferențiar universitar, Catedra de Drept Internațional, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Șef, Catedra de Drept Internațional, Facultatea de drept, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Vicepreședinte, Consiliul Consultativ pentru Adopții Internaționale, Chișinău, Moldova

Șef adjunct, Direcția Generală Agent Guvernamental, Ministerul Justiției, Chișinău, Moldova

Șef, Direcția Reprezentare la CEDO, Ministerul Justiției, Chișinău, Moldova

Membru, Colegiul Disciplinar al Executorilor Judecătorești, Chișinău, Moldova

Coordonator, Centrul European de Studii Juridice, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Ludmila ROȘCA

Profesor universitar, Facultatea de Relații Internaționale și Științe Politice, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Prorector, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Redactor-șef, Revista „Relații internaționale Plus”, Institutul de Relații Internaționale din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Coordonator, Centrul European de Informare și Comunicare, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Coordonator academic Jean Monnet

Alexandru ZNAGOVAN

Conferențiar universitar, Universitatea de Medicină și Farmacie „Nicolae Testemițanu” din Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

Membru, Centrul European de Informare și Comunicare, ECSA-Moldova, Chișinău, Moldova

9772345104101

ISSN 2345-1041

ISSN-L 2345-1041